

PROCEEDINGS OF NATIONAL CONFERENCE ON RECENT INNOVATION IN ENGINEERING AND SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH (NC RIE SR'25)

EDITOR DETAILS

Prof.(Dr) Anshad A. S is the Principal of John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of Technology, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala. He has a doctoral degree in electronics engineering and significant academic and administrative experience in several Engineering Colleges in Kerala. He is passionate about teaching, research, believes in learning, and strives to enhance OBE skills. His research areas include Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs), Artificial Intelligence, Deep learning and Communication. He is an approved research supervisor at APJA KTU and has 16+ years of academic experience in teaching and managerial positions. His research findings have been published in SCIE, SCOPUS, and other Google-indexed journals. He has authored some books and patented some designs and utilities. He has attended and presented many research articles at international conferences. He is updating his knowledge by organizing and undergoing many FDPs, PDPs, workshops, seminars and MOOCs to comply with the current scenario. He has active membership in professional institutions like FIETE, MISTE, CSI, IAENG, ABCD Index, etc. He will be available @ <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-2012-5787> or www.dranshad.as.in

Dr. Lim J Seelan is a Professor in Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering at John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of Technology, with 14 years of academic experience. He holds a doctoral degree and has published his research findings in reputed journals which are indexed in SCIE, SCOPUS and Google. His researches focuses in the fields of Embedded Systems and Digital Image Processing. He is dedicated to academic excellence, research innovation, and mentoring students in emerging technologies within embedded and imaging systems.

Ms. Renjini Rani K. S is an Associate Professor in the Department of Computer Science and Engineering at John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of Technology. She has over 16 years of teaching experience and has played a vital role in shaping the academic growth of students in the field of computer science. She is currently pursuing her Ph.D. at Noorul Islam Centre for Higher Education, with her research focused on Intrusion Detection. Her areas of interest include Machine Learning, Deep Learning, and the Internet of Things (IoT). Ms. Renjini Rani is committed to academic excellence and is actively engaged in integrating emerging technologies into teaching and research.

PROCEEDINGS OF NATIONAL CONFERENCE ON Recent Innovation in Engineering and Scientific Research (NCRIESR'25) 24th March 2025

PUBLISHED BY
John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of Technology

Editor

Dr. Anshad A. S

Co-Editors

Dr. Lim J Seelan

Ms. Renjini Rani K. S

PROCEEDINGS OF NATIONAL CONFERENCE ON RECENT INNOVATION IN ENGINEERING AND SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH
PUBLISHER: JOHN COX MEMORIAL CSI INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY ISBN: 978-81-986828-6-4

ISBN: 978-81-986828-6-4

Proceedings of National Conference on Recent Innovation in Engineering and Scientific Research (NCRIESR'25)

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Sl. No.	Title	Authors	Page No.
1	AI Powered Video Conferencing App for Meeting Management by Using NLP Algorithm	Saaji S.J.	1-4
2	An IoT-Based Infusion Pump	Nibin Sabu	5-10
3	CLASSIFICATION & SEGMENTATION OF HUMAN LUNG NODULES ON COMPUTER TOMOGRAPHY IMAGES USING NOVEL OPTIMIZED COMPUTER-AIDED TECHNIQUES	Dr. Lim J Seelan	11-20
4	Cloud-Enhanced Ensemble Intelligence for IoT Attack Detection in Edge Computing: A Critical Review	Mrs. Renjini Rani K.S	21-26
5	Implementation of ANN controller to mitigate voltage fluctuations in Wind Energy ships	B P Beno Ben	27-33
6	AGRISENSE	Alan Anil Aleena Joseph Erin Biju Greeshma B.	34-35
7	AI AUTONOMOUS FIRE FIGHTING ROBOTIC VEHICLE	Sidharth S Keseya S A Jebin H A Julianne Joseph	36-37
8	AI DERMASCAN	Aiswarya S.M. Arsha S.T. Raji N.	38-42
9	Biometric Attendance System using Arduino	Anand A Saju R Vishnupriya Sujith Mrs. TINTU S S	43-45
10	CIPHER CLOUD	Allen Kuruvilla Arun T. Paulose A.S. Abhaya Jobin Mathew	46-49
11	Design and Development of Safety Pod for Rescue Operations During Natural Disasters	Sheba O S Dr. Lim J Seelan	50-53
12	DESIGN OF RAINWATER HARVESTING SYSTEM FOR JOHN COX MEMORIAL CSI INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY KANNAMMOOLA	Abiya A S Sneha S S Soorya S V Abhin J Nitya V Arnold	54-59
13	Evaluating the effectiveness of using geotextile and flyash in improving lateritic subgrade soil strength	Alex Binu Anusha SS Blessy S Prasad Murukan M	60-69

14	E-WASTE MANAGEMENT USING IMAGE SENSING	Anusree A B Arya R Jothi Krishna K S Rijin Mohan S	70-72
15	Inferno Rover - A Robotic Solution for Fire-Fighting	Abhishek R. S Ashin V. Praveen George Reshma S.	73-76
16	MALWARESHIELD AI USING DEEP LEARNING AND XAI	Abin S. Sam, Adithya R.J., Akshay M., A.J. Aswathy	77-80
17	MANUFACTURING OF PAVER BLOCK BY REPLACING COARSE AGGREGATE WITH REFRACTORY BRICK AGGREGATES AND SAND WITH RECYCLED GLASS	Abhishek J S Chrispin Raj W Hephzibah Mol R Varsha S Cheraman	81-91
18	Medicine Tracker	Abhiram S G Gautham Mahendran Angelene Rose Antony Sona S Raj	92-95
19	QUADRAPED SPIDER ROBOT FOR SURVEILLANCE	Anantha Krishnan K B Sibi S Jofna Joseph	96-99
20	REAL TME SIGN LANGUAGE CONVETER	Boby Shibu Thomas Sai Krishna U.S. Sidharth V. Jeslin B.S. Mrs. Sreelakshmi A.	100-106
21	Remote controlled lifejacket for drowning prevention	Devika V M Vaishnavi S K	107-114
22	Seashell-Infused Permeable Pavement With Polyester Fiber Strengthening	Adithyan.R Ahimdas.S.B Annie Johniya Gowri.R.Kutty	115-123
23	Smart Garbage Management System	Abhishek R Sen Anandu B Vijay Sivani Bhadra Mrs. TINI S RUSSEL	124-126
24	SMART MEDICINE BOX	Abhijay A. S. Aishwarya baburaj S. Nandana B. S. Vishnu Varma	127-130
25	Smart Vision: An AI-Based Assistive Device for Visually Impaired People	Alvina S Anjana S Anisha L.S Angel S	131-133
26	SMART WHEELCHAIR	Anurenjana Pradeep Gouri B S Joslien Jeromias Reshma S	134-137

27	Stabilization Of Marine Clay Using Banana Fibre And Alkaline Activators	Abin Raj.T.P Anto.P.R Roshni.S.S Saniya.S.M	138-145
28	STUDY OF EFFECTS OF PARTIAL REPLACEMENT OF COARSE AGGREGATE USING ALUMINIUM SCRAP	Aiswarya L Aswathy S Darshik S S L Sreelatha Cera Shalom	146-151
29	UNDER WATER IMAGE CORRECTION, ENHACEMENT AND RECOGNITION USING DEEP LEARNING	ABHIRAM V.M.	152-155
30	USAGE OF PHARMACEUTICAL WASTE FOR CLAY STABILIZATION	Manjima M G Neeraj S S Vishnu dath S Sreejith K M L Sreeletha	156-161

AI Powered Video Conferencing App for Meeting Management by Using NLP Algorithm

Saaji S.J.

Computer Science And Engineering Dept.,
John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of Technology,
Kannammoola, Kerala, India.

Saajisj83@gmail.com.

Abstract—The AI Video Conference App, developed on the Python Django framework, is a web-based solution designed to offer a sophisticated and intelligent video conferencing experience. This comprehensive documentation serves as a vital resource for developers, users, and administrators, guiding them through the installation, configuration, and utilization of the application. Key components include real-time video conferencing with a user-friendly interface, integration of artificial intelligence for advanced features such as automated transcription and sentiment analysis, secure user authentication and authorization mechanisms, real-time chat functionality during conferences, efficient file sharing among participants, and seamless screen sharing for collaborative efforts. The documentation provides a detailed walkthrough for getting started, encompassing prerequisites, installation procedures, configuration steps, and guidance on running the app locally. It delves into the intricate features of the application, exploring the nuances of video conferencing, AI integration, user authentication, chat functionality, file sharing, and screen sharing. Additionally, the architecture section offers a comprehensive overview, shedding light on how the various components harmonize to deliver a robust video conferencing solution. Whether you are a developer seeking to contribute or a user aiming to harness the power of intelligent video conferencing, this documentation serves as an indispensable guide, empowering individuals with the knowledge necessary to deploy, customize, and optimize the AI Video Conference App to its fullest potential.

Keywords—Python, artificial intelligence, Video Conference, NLP Algorithm.

I. INTRODUCTION

The AI Video Conference App stands at the forefront of technological advancement, merging the robust capabilities of the Python Django framework with innovative features that revolutionize the landscape of video conferencing. In an era where organizations and individuals increasingly rely on virtual communication, this application emerges as a transformative solution. Beyond facilitating real-time video conferencing, it seamlessly integrates artificial intelligence to elevate the overall user experience to unprecedented levels [1]. This documentation serves as a guiding beacon, illuminating the path for developers as they embark on the journey of comprehending, implementing, and tailoring the AI Video Conference App to meet diverse needs. Encompassing a vast array of topics, the scope of this documentation spans from the fundamental prerequisites necessary for seamless installation to the intricacies of AI integration, user authentication, and collaborative functionalities. From enabling chat functionalities to facilitating file sharing and screen sharing, every aspect is meticulously covered. The intended audience is diverse, encompassing developers contributing to the project and end-users seeking to optimize their video conferencing encounters. With a deliberate intent to bridge the chasm between technical intricacies and practical usability, this documentation aims to render itself accessible and indispensable to all readers. Acknowledging the swift evolution of virtual communication technologies is paramount. The AI Video Conference App

embodies dynamism, acknowledging the present needs while catering to the imminent future of intelligent and interactive online collaboration. Its adaptability and forward-thinking nature extend an open invitation to users and developers, urging them to explore and actively contribute to a platform meticulously designed not just for the present but with an astute eye on the future. This convergence of cutting-edge technologies is not merely a fusion of tools; it's a strategic synergy that redefines conventional paradigms of video conferencing. Python Django's robustness forms the backbone, ensuring stability, security, and scalability, while the infusion of artificial intelligence introduces a realm of possibilities. These possibilities manifest in various forms, enhancing user experiences through intuitive features that learn and adapt, catering to individual preferences and optimizing interactions. At the heart of this innovation lies the aim to transcend the limitations of traditional video conferencing. It's not just about connecting faces on screens; it's about creating an environment that fosters collaboration, sparks creativity, and facilitates seamless communication, irrespective of geographical boundaries. The documentation, meticulously curated, offers a roadmap towards achieving this aspiration, guiding developers to unlock the app's full potential and empowering end-users to harness its capabilities for enriched virtual interactions. The future of online collaboration is dynamic and multifaceted, constantly evolving to meet the burgeoning demands of an interconnected world. The AI Video Conference App stands as a testament to this evolution, inviting stakeholders to be part of a collective journey toward continuous innovation. By embracing this dynamic nature, users and developers alike can chart the course for a future where intelligent technologies harmoniously converge with human interaction, shaping an era of unparalleled connectivity and collaboration.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In this section a review of the existing features of various AI Video Conference App presented in each research. A system that allows users to modify their voice characteristics in real-time during video calls, introducing a new dimension to personal expression and communication. The methodology involves the utilization of Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), a cutting-edge machine learning approach. GANs are employed to facilitate voice conversion by learning and transforming the characteristic features of the user's voice. This enables real-time modification of the voice during video calls, offering users the ability to customize their voice in a dynamic and interactive manner. The benefits of real-time voice conversion system are evident in its performance. The system allows users to seamlessly modify their voice during video calls, contributing to a more engaging and expressive communication experience. However, the paper acknowledges a noteworthy drawback related to training data limitations. The quality of voice conversion is influenced by the diversity and quantity of the training data available. Insufficient or non-representative training data may lead to limitations in the system's ability to accurately convert voices, emphasizing the need for comprehensive and diverse datasets in training voice conversion [2]. The use of Temporal Convolutional Networks (TCNs) as a key component in achieving efficient neural impersonation. TCNs, a type of neural network architecture, are employed to capture temporal dependencies in the animation process, allowing for more realistic and natural movements. The emphasis on temporal convolutional networks signifies a

departure from traditional methods, highlighting the importance of considering temporal information for achieving photorealistic animations in real-time [3]. Recognizing the importance of precise pose information in understanding human movements to the pose estimation technology. The methodology adopts a CNN with multiple visual cues as input. This approach allows the model to capture intricate details of human poses by considering various visual cues simultaneously. By leveraging multiple cues, the system aims to enhance accuracy and robustness in pose estimation, particularly during dynamic gesturing [4]. In real-time face reconstruction, transforming 2D representations into high-fidelity 3D avatars. This not only enhances the realism of virtual characters but also finds applications in various fields, such as gaming, virtual reality, and digital communication. [5,6]. A powerful class of neural network architectures known for their effectiveness in image-related tasks. In this context, CNNs are trained on depth and 3D hand pose data, allowing the system to learn complex spatial relationships and variations in hand gestures. This approach enables the system to achieve real-time performance in recognizing and interpreting hand gestures accurately. The benefits of this hand gesture recognition system are evident in its high recognition accuracy and real-time responsiveness. The ability to recognize hand gestures swiftly contributes to a seamless and natural interaction between users and computing devices [7].

III. PROPOSED APPROACH

This proposal outlines the design and development of an innovative AI-based NLP (Natural Language Processing) video conferencing application. The aim is to create a platform that not only facilitates real-time communication but also leverages advanced AI technologies to enhance user interaction, understanding, and overall experience. This system lies in the integration of NLP, enabling the application to comprehend and respond to natural language commands. By implementing state-of-the-art NLP algorithms, the system will be capable of understanding the intent, context, and nuances of spoken and written language during video conferences. This goes beyond simple command recognition, focusing on creating a more natural and intuitive communication environment. The proposed system will embrace multimodal interaction by combining NLP with Computer Vision (CV). This integration will enable the application to interpret visual cues, gestures, and facial expressions. By leveraging CV, the system can enhance user engagement by recognizing non-verbal communication and incorporating it into the context of the conversation. This multimodal approach aims to create a more immersive and dynamic conferencing experience. The user interface of the application will be designed with intelligence in mind. Through NLP, the system will offer voice-controlled commands for initiating and managing video conferences.

A. MODULAR ARCHITECTURE

The proposed system will follow a modular architecture to accommodate the integration of various components seamlessly. The architecture comprises the following key modules: Responsible for processing natural language inputs, extracting intents, and understanding contextual information. This module will leverage pre-trained language models and advanced NLP algorithms to interpret user commands. Focused on visual processing, this module employs Computer Vision techniques to recognize gestures, facial expressions, and other visual cues. The output from this module will be integrated with the NLP module to create a comprehensive understanding of user interactions. The user interface module will be designed to facilitate easy and intuitive interactions. It will incorporate voice-controlled commands, visual feedback, and adaptive elements to create a user-centric experience. This module will serve as the primary point of interaction for users. Responsible for managing real-time communication during video conferences. This module will ensure the seamless integration of NLP and CV outputs, enabling the application to generate intelligent responses and adapt to user interactions in real-time. The proposed system will be implemented using modern programming languages and frameworks suitable for NLP and CV applications. Machine learning libraries, such as TensorFlow or PyTorch, will be employed for training and deploying deep learning models. Cloud-based services may be utilized for scalability, ensuring the application's performance during peak usage. The user experiences will be a focal point throughout the development process. The intelligent user interface, combined with real-time contextual understanding, aims to provide a natural and seamless interaction environment. User feedback will be actively collected and analyzed to refine the system continuously. Given the sensitive nature of video conferencing, robust security measures will be implemented to safeguard user data and communications. End-to-end encryption, secure authentication protocols, and adherence to privacy regulations will be integral components of the application's design. The proposed system is designed to evolve with advancements in AI and technology. Future enhancements may include the integration of emotion recognition, improved language models, and additional features to further enhance user engagement and overall satisfaction.

Fig 3.1 Architecture of AI Video conference App

B. The Role of NLP in Explanation-Driven Mode

The Role of NLP in Explanation-Driven Mode NLP is at the heart of the Explanation-Driven Mode, providing the system with the ability to not only comprehend user commands but also to articulate its responses. When a user issues a command or poses a question, the system utilizes NLP algorithms to interpret the linguistic input. What sets the Explanation-Driven Mode apart is its capacity to not only execute the command but also to generate human readable explanations regarding the rationale behind the system's actions. Enhancing User Understanding One of the primary objectives of an Explanation-Driven Mode is to enhance user understanding of the AI video conferencing system's decisions and operations. Through NLP, the system can generate explanations that elucidate the logic, data, or contextual information influencing a particular response. This transparency not only fosters user trust but also empowers individuals to make more informed decisions during virtual interaction.

C. Addressing Ambiguities and Misinterpretations NLP in Explanation-Driven Mode

Addressing Ambiguities and Misinterpretations NLP in Explanation-Driven Mode is equipped to handle linguistic ambiguities and potential misinterpretations effectively. Through advanced language models and contextual analysis, the system can discern the user's intent, allowing it to not only execute the command but also to clarify any uncertainties by providing detailed explanations. This feature is especially crucial in scenarios where a user's instructions may carry multiple meanings.

D. User-Centric Design in AI Video Conferencing

The Explanation-Driven Mode aligns seamlessly with the principles of user-centric design. By incorporating NLP to articulate the system's decision-making processes, the mode prioritizes the user's need for transparency and comprehension. The system engages in a dynamic and bidirectional communication with the user, fostering a more natural and intuitive virtual collaboration experience. Overcoming Challenges While the Explanation-Driven Mode enhances transparency, it also poses challenges in terms of system complexity and the need for robust NLP capabilities. Handling diverse linguistic inputs, maintaining real-time responsiveness, and ensuring the accuracy of generated explanations are challenges that necessitate continuous advancements in NLP algorithms and models.

E. Methodology for AI Powered Video App

The development of an AI-based NLP video conferencing app involves a systematic methodology encompassing data collection, pre-processing, model selection, training, and evaluation. This methodology aims to create a robust and intelligent system capable of understanding natural language commands and providing a seamless video conferencing experience. Data Collection The dataset for training the AI models is a critical component. In the context of a video conferencing app, data may include audio-visual recordings of various interactions, diverse natural language commands, and scenarios that represent real-world usage. Data can be collected from multiple sources, ensuring a diverse and representative dataset that captures various accents, languages, and communication styles. Pre-processing is essential to prepare the collected data for training. This involves cleaning and formatting audio-visual data, extracting relevant features, and synchronizing audio and video streams. Text data from spoken language must be transcribed and tokenized. Additionally, the integration of Computer Vision techniques may be required to process visual cues and gestures for a multimodal approach. Model Selection The choice of the AI model plays a crucial role

in the system's performance. For NLP tasks, pre-trained language models like BERT or GPT-3 may be considered. In the domain of Computer Vision, architectures like Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) can be employed for visual processing. The integration of both modalities requires a multimodal model that effectively captures correlations between audio-visual data.

Fig 3.2 Flow chart for AI powered Video App

The flowchart outlines a comprehensive process within a user application, encompassing data handling, machine learning algorithms, real-time video processing, and meeting-related functionalities. The incorporation of various technologies and algorithms suggests a multifaceted application catering to diverse user needs.

1. Start User App:

The flowchart begins with the initiation of the user application, indicating the launch of a software application designed to facilitate a specific purpose.

2. Data Collection, Cleaning (NumPy, Pandas):

Following the app start, the process involves collecting and cleaning data. NumPy and Pandas, popular Python libraries for numerical operations and data manipulation, respectively, are employed for efficient handling and preprocessing of data.

3. User Interface

The flow moves to the user interface, suggesting the incorporation of a graphical interface that users interact with. This interface likely provides controls and options for the user to navigate through different functionalities within the application.

4. KNN Algorithm Meeting Controls:

Within the user interface, the mention of the KNN (K-Nearest Neighbors) algorithm and meeting controls suggests the integration of a mechanism that utilizes KNN for some aspect of meeting-related functionalities. This may include features like participant recommendation or grouping based on proximity.

5. Preprocessing:

Hyperparameter Tuning Before employing machine learning algorithms, there's a stage for data preprocessing and hyperparameter tuning. This step ensures that the data is appropriately prepared for training, and the algorithm's parameters are optimized for better performance.

6. Real-Time Video Processing (Web-RTC):

The flowchart introduces real-time video processing using

Web-RTC (Web Real-Time Communication). This indicates that the application involves live video handling, possibly for video conferencing or other real-time visual data processing tasks.

7. *Sign Language Interpreter (Random Forest Algorithm):*

A notable feature in the flow is the inclusion of a sign language interpreter utilizing the Random Forest algorithm. This implies that the application has a capability to interpret sign language gestures, offering accessibility features.

8. *Meeting Control, Manage Meeting State:*

The flow includes a section for meeting controls and managing meeting state, suggesting that the application is equipped with functionalities related to orchestrating and overseeing virtual meetings.

9. *CNN Neural Network:*

The flow incorporates a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), indicating the utilization of deep learning for image-related tasks. This could be employed for tasks like image recognition or processing within the application.

10. *User Exist:*

The flowchart accounts for a decision point where it checks for the existence of a user, implying that the application manages user sessions or states.

11. *Closes the App:* The flow concludes with the option for the user to close the application, marking the end of the user interaction session.

IV. CONCLUSION

The development of an AI-based NLP video conferencing app is a multifaceted process that involves intricate experimental analyses and meticulous consideration of system requirements. The integration of AI, NLP, and Computer Vision technologies promises a dynamic and adaptive system capable of providing a seamless and intelligent video conferencing experience. Continuous refinement and user feedback will be crucial in ensuring that the application remains at the forefront of technological advancements, addressing evolving communication needs and contributing to the ever-expanding landscape of AI-driven applications. As the app progresses, it has the potential to reshape the way users engage with virtual collaboration tools, offering a glimpse into the future of interactive and intelligent communication platforms.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

To the bounty of the almighty, who made everything possible. To my parents, for believing in me, helping me all the way through, and supporting me with their love, care and encouragement. I would like to thank our Principal Dr. A. S. Anshad and Head of the Department Mr. Vishnu Kumar S. for rendering great encouragement. I would like to thank my family members for helping me all the way through and supporting me with their love, care and encouragement.

REFERENCES

- [1] Kwok-Fai Ng, Man-Yan Ching, Yang Liu, Tao Cai, Li Li, and Wu Chou, "A P2P-MCU Approach to Multi-Party Video Conference with WebRTC," International Journal of Future Computer and Communication, Vol. 3, No. 5, October 2014.
- [2] Dongming Tang, and Liqun Zhang "Audio and Video Mixing Method to Enhance WebRTC," IEEE Access, April 2020.
- [3] Zhiwen Liao, and Ling Zhang "Elastic Timeslot-based Advance Reservation Algorithm for Enterprise Video Conferencing Systems," systems. IEEE Access, vol. 4, pp 1-17 ,2019.
- [4] Zhiwen Liao, and Ling, "Scheduling Dynamic Multicast Requests in Advance Reservation Environment for Enterprise Video Conferencing Systems," IEEE Access, vol. 4, 2016.
- [5] Eymen Kurdoglu, Yong Liu, and Yao Wang, "Dealing With User Heterogeneity in P2P Multi-Party Video Conferencing: Page 4 of 161

Distribution Versus Partitioned Simulcast," IEEE Transactions on Multimedia, vol.18, No.1, pp 90-101, Jan 2016.

- [6] Richard G. Clegg, Raul Landa, David Griffin, Miguel Rio, Member, Peter Hughes, Ian Kegel, Tim Stevens, Peter Pietzuch, and Doug Williams, "Faces in the Clouds: Long-Duration, Multi-User, Cloud-Assisted Video Conferencing," IEEE Transactions on Cloud Computing, 2016.
- [7] Nabeel Siddiqui, and Rosa H. M. Chan, "Hand Gesture Recognition Using Multiple Acoustic Measurements at Wrist," IEEE Transactions on human-machine systems, vol. 51. No. 1, pp 56-62. Feb. 2021.

An IoT-Based Infusion Pump

Nibin Sabu

Biomedical Engineering

Noorul Islam Center For Higher Education

kumaracoil, Tamil Nadu, India

nibinn28@gmail.com

Abstract— A patient's circulatory system is controlled by an infusion pump to provide fluids and drugs in both large and tiny doses. Although rarely subcutaneous, arterial, and epidural infusions are employed, it is typically administered intravenously.

An infusion pump's primary function is to help maintain IV patency. The Internet of Things (IoT) is utilized in this study to communicate data between the control and the infusion pump. This saves the doctor time, and the patient will be dynamically monitored.

I. INTRODUCTION

An Infusion Pump is used for delivering fluids as well as medicines in large and small amounts into a patient's circulatory system in controlled amount. It is generally used intravenously, although subcutaneous (under the skin), arterial and epidural (spinal cord) infusions are occasionally used. The major necessity of infusion pump is to assist in maintaining IV patency.

In this paper, the physician can control the infusion pump from anyplace. For this Internet of Things (IoT) is used for transferring the data between the infusion pump and the control. This helps the physician to laborious time and the patient's monitoring will be dynamic.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Sakthivel Sankaran [14] et al., has solved several problems, including software problems, alarm faults, battery problems, sparks, and shocks. They and their team came up with a solution to address these issues. It can be lifted with one hand due to its weightlessness and the components of our project are durable, affordable, and easy to use.

Luiz E.G. Martins [9] et al., created a low-cost insulin infusion pump with the goal of helping Brazilians with type 1 diabetes. The creation of the prototype is the outcome of industrial and academic collaboration in Brazil. We discuss the creation of such a prototype as well as the lessons discovered as a result of it.

Isabella L. Grassetti [3] et al., has administered the chemical compounds for chemotherapy using infusion pumps. Radiation that unintentionally enters the infusion pumps during therapy could harm the internal solid state integrated circuit chips. Such flaws could lead to improper dosing. The usage of infusion pumps during chemoradiotherapy persists despite manufacturer instructions that caution against using the devices in radiological settings. Device malfunction risk could be reduced with proper shielding of the gadgets while they are exposed to radiation.

Jennifer Biltoft [4] et al., has implemented smart pump-EMR interoperability to measurable, data-based improvements in IV medication safety and improved accuracy, timeliness, and efficiency of IV infusion documentation. Revenue was increased due to improved charge capture for outpatient IV infusions. Non-lead composites for shielding. Micro particles of Bismuth (III) oxide (BO) were impregnated into two materials at various

percent weights: Polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) and Polyurethane Elastomer (PU). PDMS/BO samples attenuated X-rays of 52KVp at 4 mm thickness. PU/BO attenuated X-rays of 52KVp at 3 mm thickness.

Moret. E [11] et al., has examined the issue with infusion pumps at the hospital for continuous drug monitoring to lower medical errors. To increase precision, get rid of harmful pumps, and develop a staff-friendly pump formation. The medication mistakes were overcome, and the patients benefited greatly and were safer as a result.

Karen K Giuliano [6] et al., has launched large-volume secondary infusion In the acute care situation, IV smart pumps are widely utilized for intermittent or one-time administration of pharmaceuticals such antibiotics, electrolyte replacements, and several oncology treatments. The system and setup requirements must be fully understood in order to distribute secondary drugs consistently and accurately. Regrettably, it happens frequently for nurses to discover that a secondary drug has only been half administered while their programming called for a full infusion. The technical prerequisites for using an IV smart pump to provide secondary drugs are covered in this article for all nurses.

M. Deepa Lakshmi [10] et al., have suggested a compact and economical integrated infusion pump system that isn't yet readily available in the Indian market at a low price. It delivers the right amount of insulin and keeps blood sugar levels within a certain range.

They came to the conclusion that ongoing monitoring was necessary, which may be seen as a disadvantage of the system.

Frank Doesburg [2] et.al, have calculated the benefits of including a bedside central that manages all intravenous (IV) infusion pumps. The execution time is not longer, usability is excellent, and medication error is decreased. Controlling and keeping an eye on the numerous infusion pumps is simple. The correctness of the result, however, has not been disclosed.

Jeffrey M. Rothschild [5] et.al, have run a time-series trial, compared error rates, and discovered that employing smart pumps can eliminate errors and time delays. Serious drug incidents can also be found, as well. For enhancing and ensuring drug safety, it is necessary to understand technical and nursing behavioral variables. Before the use of smart pumps, they found significant mistakes.

Thorunn Oskarsdottir [15] et.al, have talked about using intravenous infusions in neonatal and pediatric hospitals. In the United Kingdom, traditional procedures are the only ones employed, so it is crucial to disclose the SCI, but standardizing also has little actual use. They came to the conclusion that study must be done to harmonize the SCI in order to increase acceptance.

Brian J. Anderson [1] et al., have talked about using complete IV anesthesia in conjunction with the pumps.

The use of propofol for very prolonged periods in sick or young

children is contraindicated due to the possibility of developing Propofol Infusion Syndrome. Complete intravenous (IV) sedation and anesthesia are utilized in intensive care (PRIS).

the introduction of pharmacokinetically-programmed pumps that may choose which infusion pump to use to maintain a specific concentration.

Linda J Murdoch [8] et al., have talked about the significant risk factors that are present in intensive care units. In order to prevent prescription errors, calculate drugs, and recognize and fix them, the smart infusion pump is employed. Especially for intensive care units, this smart pump technology establishes a minimum level of safety.

Karen Wilson [7] et al., has mostly concentrated on pinpointing the regions that damage patients and prevent drug errors. Keystroke error software is available, and infusion pump technology is used to prevent heparin-related mistakes as well as patient harm.

Pascale Carayon [13] et.al., have suggested the potential use of intelligent intravenous infusion pumps to cut down on medicine administration mistakes. Implementation, technical performance, usability, and user acceptance are among the three surveys that collect the data.

Mark H. Myers [12] et.al., In Complete Intravenous Anesthesia, it was discussed the use of an automated drug delivery system with computer-assisted control to dispense propofol (TIVA). In order to simulate how the medicine degrades, a dilution chamber is employed. Monitored and evaluated is the concentration. They proved the viability and did so.

III. EXISTING SYSTEM

A. POWER SUPPLY SYSTEM

An AC or DC supply can be used as the power source. Currently, rechargeable batteries predominate.

B. DETECTOR UNIT

Sensor unit consists of sensors such a thermopile array sensor, a liquid pressure sensor, a sound detection sensor, and a sensor for measuring liquid pressure.

C. SOUND DETECTION SENSOR

A sound sensor is a component that analyzes the intensity of sound waves to detect them and transforms them into electrical signals. The sound sensor includes an amplifier, peak detector, and capacitive microphone built-in.

D. LIQUID PRESSURE SENSOR

Pressure sensors for viscous liquids are transducers because they provide an electrical signal in proportion to the pressure they are measuring.

This makes it possible for electronic equipment like microprocessors, programmable controllers, or computers to monitor pressure.

E. AIR BUBBLE DETECTION SENSOR

Two piezoelectric ultrasonic transducers, one serving as a transmitter and the other as a receiver, are typically used in non-invasive ultrasonic bubble sensors. Based on the significant acoustic impedance differential between the fluid or tubing wall and air, the principle of air detection in flowing fluid is based.

F. TEMPERATURE SENSOR

Thermopile sensors are made to monitor temperature at a distance by spotting Infrared (IR) energy from an object. The amount of IR radiation released increases with temperature.

Little thermocouples mounted on a silicon chip make up the thermopile sensing element, which absorbs the energy and generates an output signal.

G. BOLUS

It enables you to schedule the delivery of a specified quantity of medicine or substance at a particular time.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

This proposed system is used for controlling the infusion pump from any place. It consists of Node MCU (ESP-32), Liquid pressure sensor, Air Bubble Detection Sensor, Door Alarm, Peristaltic Pump, OLED, Occlusion Alarm. All the sensor details are sent to the NODE-MCU microcontroller after detecting fall. Based on the sensor output, the alarm will be triggered and the physician will be notified. In addition to this, immediate notification will be sent through wirelessly to the respective person to take further actions. As a result, all the patient parameters that are being tracked may be readily managed.

B. ADVANTAGES

- The proposed system is under the control of IoT, so that anyone can control it from anywhere.
- In the system advanced and secured program is used in which the spark from the circuit and most of the other errors will be removed.
- Occlusion alarm is used for quality alarm ringing.
- Peristaltic pump is used for obtaining the specific flow rate of the fluid.
- Thermopile sensor is used for detecting any other person's arrival.

C. DISADVANTAGES

- The notification's arrival could be delayed
- Battery issues could result in significant damage.

D. APPLICATIONS

- It is simple for everyone to maintain and control.
- Also included are the problems' fixes.

Fig.1 BLOCK DIAGRAM

V. COMPONENTS DESCRIPTION

A. CIRCUIT DIAGRAM

Fig.2 CIRCUIT DIAGRAM

The circuit diagram consists of Node MCU ESP-32 in the middle, 12V battery, Power Regulator L298 on the right corner, Peristaltic pump in the top right corner of the Figure 5.1, temperature and humidity sensor in the bottom right corner for detecting external sources, Buzzer, OLED in the top left corner for viewing the values, Turbidity sensor for bubble detection in the left corner and Sound detection sensor with Mic for reporting noise in the left bottom corner.

B. MICRO CONTROLLER UNIT (MCU)

A processing unit, memory modules, communication interfaces, and peripherals make up this intelligent semiconductor Integrated Circuit (IC). A wide variety of devices, such as washing machines, robotics, drones, radios, and game controllers, utilise MCUs, as shown in figure 5.2.

The development of Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor-Field-Effect-Transistor (MOSFET) technology is credited with giving rise to MCU. The MCU used to be a simple semiconductor IC with a CPU and memory module in its early stages. MCUs often use the Harvard architecture as their foundation.

Popular companies like Intel, Motorola, Microchip, and Atmel advanced the invention over the years. These firms mostly produce 8-bit MCUs with proprietary architecture. The ARM-based MCU is the exception, which uses the ARM architecture.

Fig.3 MICRO CONTROLLER UNIT

C. ORGANIC LIGHT EMITTING DIODE (OLED)

It is a film formed of organic compounds that, in reaction to an electric current, emits light. Between two electrodes, one of which is transparent, is this layer. OLEDs are used to create digital displays for gadgets like televisions, computer monitors, and portable systems like smartphones, among other things. A layer of organic materials is typically sandwiched between two electrodes—the cathode and anode—and placed on a substrate to form the OLED, as shown in. Because of the pi electrons' subsequent delocalization as a result of conjugation over the molecules, organic molecules are conductive.

Fig.4 ORGANIC LIGHT EMITTING DIODE

D. SOUND DETECTION SENSOR

Andrew S. Tanenbaum created the MIC-1 processor design as a straightforward yet comprehensive model for his instructional book Structured Computer Organization.

A very basic control unit that executes microcode from a 512-word storage makes up the system. The Java Virtual Machine (JVM) interpreter source code may be obtained in the book. The Micro-Assembly Language (MAL) is designed to make developing a JVM interpreter simple.

Fig.5 SOUND DETECTION SENSOR

E. TEMPERATURE AND HUMIDITY SENSOR

A composite sensor, the DHT11 digital temperature and humidity sensor generates calibrated digital signals for both temperature and humidity. The technology of a dedicated digital modules collecting as well as the temperature and humidity sensor technology gives the device excellent dependability and superb long-term stability. The sensor comprises a resistive feel of wet component, a Negative Temperature component, and is connected to a high-performance 8-bit microcontroller.

Fig.6 TEMPERATURE AND HUMIDITY SENSOR

F. PERISTALTIC PUMP

The term "peristaltic pump," sometimes known as a "roller pump," refers to a positive displacement pump that is used to pump a range of fluids. The fluid is housed in a flexible tube that is placed around the outside of the pump casing. Despite the development of linear peristaltic pumps, the majority of peristaltic pumps work in a circular motion. The flexible tube is compressed while the rotor rotates by several "wipers" or "rollers" that are attached to its outside circumference. When the compressed portion of the tube closes, the fluid must pass through the tube. Moreover, extra fluid

is sucked into the tube when it returns to its original state after the rollers pass. Peristalsis is a process that occurs in many biological systems, including the gastrointestinal tract. The tube will often be compressed by two or more rollers, trapping a body of fluid in the space between them. The fluid is moved through the tube and out of the pump through the outlet. Peristaltic pumps can be indexed through partial revolutions to deliver lesser volumes of fluid or they can run continuously. Positive displacement pumps are capable of moving a range of fluids. This pump costs less to repair because it lacks valves, seals, and glands. Every peristaltic pump has a flexible hose or tube that creates an open flow path with a high resistance to abrasion and allows the movement of solids and viscous materials with ease.

The three-roller liquid peristaltic pump shown in Figure 5.11 uses this Kamoer 12V 540ml/min Silicon Tube brush motor. When pumping liquids when no direct contact with the liquid is necessary, the brand-new series of peristaltic pumps from Kamoer offers an easy option. Unlike other pumps, the KHM series pumps have a choice between a stepper motor and a 12 v DC brushed motor as their base motor. Instead of immediately impelling a silicone tube, these motors crush it, avoiding direct contact with the liquid in the process. A 12 V DC input is required for this pump, which has a maximum flow rate of 540 ml per minute.

Fig.7 PERISTALTIC PUMP

G. L298 INTEGRATED CIRCUIT

The 15-lead Milliwatt and PowerSO20 packages for the L298 are integrated monolithic circuits. It is a twin full-bridge driver with a high voltage and high current rating that can drive inductive loads including relays, solenoids, DC motors, and stepping motors and accept conventional TTL logic levels. A high-power motor driver module, the L298N Motor Driver Module can be used to operate both DC and stepper motors. A 78M05 5V regulator and an L298 motor driver IC make up this module. Up to 4 DC motors or 2 DC motors with directional and speed control can be controlled by the L298N Module..

Fig.8 L298 INTEGRATED CIRCUIT

H. BUZZER

As seen in Figure 5.15, an auditory signaling device like a buzzer or beeper could be electromechanical, piezoelectric, or mechanical. The signal is converted from audio to sound as its primary function. It is often powered by DC voltage and used in timers, alarm clocks, printers, computers, and other electronic devices. It can produce a variety of sounds, including alarm, music, bell, and siren, according on the varied designs.

Fig.8 BUZZER

I. TURBIDITY SENSOR

The bubbles which are formed in the flow of IV are detected easily through this way in the sensor ,it works under the phenomena of turbidity in which it can be easily discovered and the result is shown in Binary forms (0,1). When the number is 0 then the flow is not interrupted when the value turns to 0 then the bubbles are detected. Turbidity is defined as the reduction of transparency of a liquid caused by the presence of undissolved suspended matter [1]. The origin of the particles found in seawater can be mineral (such as clay and silts) or organic (such as particulate organic matter or living organisms like plankton). Turbidity is not, however, a direct measure of suspended particles in water, but a measure of the scattering effect such particles have on light.

Fig.9 TURBIDITY SENSOR

Open-source prototyping platform Arduino is built on simple hardware and software. It is made up of a circuit board that can be programmed (known as a microcontroller) and ready-made software called the Arduino IDE that is used to develop and upload computer code to the actual board. The micro-features controller's are separated into a more usable container by Arduino's standard form factor. Arduino boards have the ability to read analog or digital input signals from a variety of sensors and convert them into an output, such as starting or stopping a motor, turning an LED on or off, connecting to the cloud, and many more operations. Via the Arduino IDE, you can use a series of instructions to direct the actions of your board's microcontroller (referred to as uploading software). Arduino does not require an additional piece of hardware (referred to as a programmer) in order to load fresh code onto the board, in contrast to earlier programmable circuit boards. Only a USB cable will do. Moreover, the Arduino IDE employs a condensed form of C++, which makes learning to program simpler. The functions of the micro-controller are finally broken down into a more approachable packaging by Arduino's standard physical factor. According to the different microcontrollers utilized, various types of Arduino boards are available. Although they are all programmed using the Arduino IDE, Arduino boards all share a similar trait. The distinctions are based on the quantity of inputs and outputs (the number of sensors, Lights, and buttons you may utilize on a single board), speed, operating voltage, form factor, etc. Some boards have no hardware programming interfaces because they are intended to be embedded, thus you would need to purchase them separately. A 3.7V battery can power some while a 5V power source is required for others.

Fig.12 Turbidity Sensor or Bubble Detecting Sensor

Fig.13 IoT based Infusion Pump

VII. RESULTS

Fig.10 Front panel of the system

REFERENCES

[1] Brian J. Anderson, James D. Morse, Luis Ignacio Cortinez, "The total intravenous anesthesia to implement along with the pumps", *Pediatric Anesthesia*, Wiley Online Library, Volume 20, Pages 223-232, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-9592.2009.03072.x>

[2] Frank Doesburg, Maarten. W. Nilsen "Estimated the advantages of adding the bedside central that controls all the IV infusion pumps", *PMC Article*, National library of medicine, Volume 18, Pages 132-141,2020,10.1371/journal.pone.0183104

[3] Isabella. L. Grasseti, Isabella. L. Curran, Anita. M. Petrilli, James O'Brien "Discussed that infusion Pumps exposed to radiation must be protected from the x-rays", *International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology (IJEAT)* , Volume-9 Issue-1S4, 2018, 10.35940/ijeat.A1137.1291S419

[4] Jenifer Biltoft, Lonnie Finneman. "Discussed about implementing A smart electronic pump that health condition of the patient Around the particular region", *AMJ Health-System Pharmaceutical*, volume 75 Page 14 ,2019, 10.2146/ajhp161058

[5] Jeffrey M. Rothschild, Noah syroid, "Performed a time-series trial and compared the rate of error and found that, the errors and the time delay can be solved by using smart pumps", *PMC Article*, volume 21, page 160-179,2007, 10.1097/01.ccm.0000155912.73313.cd

[6] Karen. K. Giuliano, Daleen Penoyer, Rebecca. S. Mahuren, Melody Bennett "Discussed that before the Introduction of the infusion pumps the rate of infusion were Calculated manually", *PMC Article*, Volume 16, pages 56-64, 2006, 10.1097/01.NAJ.0000767808.75464.c3

[7] Karen Wilson, Mark Sullivan "Focused in identifying the areas that causes harmful to the patients and prevent the medication errors", *PMC Article*, Volume 15, Pages 112-122, 2017, 10.1093/ajhp/61.2.177

[8] Linda J Murdouch, and Victoria. L. Cameron "Discussed about the serious risk factors being faced in the intensive care units", *PMC Article*, Volume 13, Pages 141-156, 2007, 10.12968/bjon.2006.17.10.29476

[9] Luiz Eduardo Galvao Martins, Hanniere de Faria, Lucas Vechete, Tatiana sousa Cunha "Develop a low-cost insulin infusion pump for the treatment of diabetes", *PMC Article*,

Fig.11 The hardware portion

- [10] M. Deepalakshmi and Dr.R.Jayaparvathy “Proposed small size and cost-efficient integrated infusion pump system”, AMJ Health-System Pharmaceutical, volume 22 Page 64 ,2015, 10.2146/ajhp161058
- [11] Moret. E,Muntane. E, Ricart. P,Andreu. “Analyzed the situation of infusion Pumps at the hospital for continuous monitoring of drug to Reduce the medical errors”, AMJ Health-System Pharmaceutical, volume 7 Page 34 ,2016, 10.2146/ajhp161058
- [12] Mark H. Myers , Yaqin Li, Francine kivlehan “Discussed about the automatic drug delivery method with a computer-aided control for propofol delivery in total intravenous anesthesia”, PMC Article, Volume 19, Pages 67-81, 2014, 10.12968/bjon.2014.17.10.29476
- [13] Pascale Carayon, Ann scoofs Hundt “Discussed about implementation of smart intravenous infusion pump to reduce the medication administration errors”, PMC Article, Volume 34, Pages 129-142, 2014, 10.12968/bjon.2014.17.10.29476
- [14] Sakthivel Sankaran, J. Deny, M. Pallikonda Rajasekaran “ Designed and Developed a Low Cost, Smart Infusion Pump to Deliver IV for Patients using LabVIEW Interface with Arduino”, PMC Article, Volume 27, Pages 54-67, 2004, 10.12968/bjon.2004.17.10.29476
- [15] Thorunn Oskarsdottir, David Harris, Adam Sutherland, “Discussed about the usage of intravenous infusions paediatric and neonatal units”, AMJ Health-System Pharmaceutical, volume 14, Page 168-177 ,2021, 10.2146/ajhp

CLASSIFICATION & SEGMENTATION OF HUMAN LUNG NODULES ON COMPUTER TOMOGRAPHY IMAGES USING NOVEL OPTIMIZED COMPUTER-AIDED TECHNIQUES

Dr. Lim J Seelan
Professor, Department of ECE,
John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of Technology,
Thiruvananthapuram.

ABSTRACT

Now a day the lung cancer is considered as one of the deadliest diseases among the lung disorders. Detecting the tumor cells present in the lung area at an early stages helps to reduce the mortality rate of the patients. This early detection is one of the challenging tasks carried out by the radiologists so far. There are numerous techniques proposed by the researchers to identify and classify the tumor cells in the lungs. But it does not provide better accuracy. This method is mainly focused on detecting the cancerous region and classifying the lung cancer CT images. This proposed work plays a significant role in detecting the types of cancerous region in the lung CT images and helps radiologists to enhance the diagnosis in medical care of patients. It's also a less time consuming process in classifying the lung CT images. Here Fundamental medical image processing steps with different techniques are implemented. The major drawbacks of existing CAD systems are the accuracy in segmenting the nodule and staging the lung cancer. The most important intention of this suggested work is to segment the lung nodule from CT image and classifies as cancerous or non-cancerous to detect the location of the cancer with better sensitivity, specificity and accuracy compared to those of the other techniques.

Keywords: *Histogram equalization, fuzzy Thresholding, optimized chan-veese algorithm, Optimized BoVW.*

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the major cause's deaths through cancer is Lung cancer. It's hard to identify since in the final stage it occurs and exhibits symptoms. Moreover, through initial identification and treatment of the disease, mortality rate and risk can be decreasing. Best CT imaging technique is effective for the diagnosis because it can show both normal and

abnormal nodules of lung cancer [1]. Although, inconsistency in brightness of CT scanning images and mis-judgment of anatomical structure by physician and radiologist can cause difficulties in labelling the cancer cell[2]. Recently, computer Aided Diagnosis has become a complementary and effective tool for helping radiologists and doctors to detect cancer correctly [3]. Many systems have been developed and research has been under way to detect lung cancer. On the other hand certain models do not have sufficient detection accuracy and certain model still need to be developed in order to achieve the maximum accuracy of 100%. Numerous scientists have suggested and introduced lung cancer identification models using various imaging and machine learning methods.

Bhuvanewari et al. (2014)[4] established an effective diagnostic tool for the computer-aided diagnostic process using Computer Tomography (CT) images here classifiers namely decision tree, K nearest neighbor (KNN), Multi-layer perceptron Neural Networks (MLP-NN) have been used in the final stage to perform lung disease classification. Ajin M & Mredhula Lb (2017)[5] studied the different methods used in the extraction, selection and classification of features. Here methods such as Linear Ternary Co-occurrence pattern, histogram selection function, and SVM classifier hybrid kernel are used ANN is initially used to identify the ILD pattern Roy, Sirohi, and Patle (2015)[6] designed a system for detecting nodule of lung using a fuzzy interference system and an active contour model. Ignatious and Joseph (2015)[7] have established a watershed segmentation scheme. This result is compared with the model of neural fuzzy and the region growing. Gonzalez and Ponomaryvo (2016)[8] have proposed a system for classifying tumor. This method utilizes the priori data and the Housefield Unit (HU) to measure the Region of Interest (ROI). A support vector system is utilized to evaluate whether the nodule is normal or severe. Bhuvanewari and Brintha Therese (2015)[9] are focusing on early detection of lung cancer. Genetic K-Nearest Neighbor (GKNN) is proposed as a non-parametric approach

for detection. This optimization method helps doctors to classify the nodules in the early stage Sachi et al. (2018)[10] explained approach to recover a patient's possibility of survival using Optimal Deep Neural Network (ODNN) and Linear Discriminate Analysis. Jeovane et al. (2018)[11] Study of lung malignancy and other diseases, such as interstitial lung diseases (ILDs), utilizing Fully Convolution Networks (FCNs) coupled with Fully Connected Conditional Random Fields (CRFs). Ezhil & Kumar 2016[12] developed an region based active contour model based as well as a Fuzzy C-Means (FCM) technique for lung nodule segmentation. Another analysis by Ezhil & Kumar 2019[13] for lung segmentation is an variation level set function and region based active contour model There are various segmentation concepts[14] involved in detecting cancer cells from normal cells. Region based Segmentation [15], Edge based technique [16], thresholding technique [17]. The various classification method based on Neural Network Classifier [18], Decision Classifier [19].

Research Gap Identified

In current situation, lung disease, is measured as one of the real reason for death, would be help in decrease by beginning period identification. To identify the nodules in the chest wall is one of the difficult undertakings completed by the radiologist up until this point. Here the Identification of lung nodules in juxtapleural and juxtavascular tissue is difficult, the shapes and sizes of tissues is different, so minute (small) nodules identification is difficult. Over Segmentation and under Segmentation problem arises while segmenting the tumor region. There are some procedures proposed by the analysts to recognize and characterize the tumor locale. In any case, it doesn't give better precision like characterization method utilized by the proposed framework.

The major importance of the research is to establish an Auto-Detective Computed Aided Diagnostic (AD-CAD) model to discover the lung nodules in CT images in the following ways:

- To identify and classifying lung cancer lesion using novel optimization and classification techniques.
- Developing the algorithm, the region of interest is separated from parameters like mean standard error and variance are extracted which is compared with the existing technique
- Using a feature extraction technique the features are separated from the segmented image
- To obtain better accuracy the novel classification is proposed, hereby reduce time consumption problem

- To evade severe phases in earlier and to decrease lung malignancy proportion distribution

The work is described as follows: Introduction part is portrays in section 1 as well as the studies of several research papers portrayed, part 2 highlights the suggested method and defines the performance metrics in part 3. Part 4 describes the results of the research and the work is completed in part 5.

2. PROPOSED WORK

The proposed work flow diagram is shown in Figure. 1. The outline illustrates the block diagram for the proposed work, follows in different steps. This work's primary role is defined as follows (i) for denoising and edge sharpening of lung image the curvelet transform and histogram equalization models are used. (ii) The lung image binarization and lung border corrections are performed using various algorithms such as Fuzzy, canny edge detector, morphological operation, adaptive concave hull. (iii) Segmentation is performed by using novel optimized Chan-Vese algorithm. (iv) By using novel optimized Bag of Visual Word Classifier (BOVW) the different stages of lung nodules such as benign and malignant are identified.

2.1 Image Acquisition

In medical image acquisition process the computer Tomography (CT) is used. Comparing other modality images it has little commotion and good clearness. The images are collected from NIH / NCI Lung Image Database Consortium (LIDC), an online dataset of CT images accessible in the "Cancer Imaging Archive." Here the image format is DICOM, using the converters to convert these images to JPEG format. The image size is typically 512×512 and then translated to 256×256 for a superior function. There are 150 images used for diagnosis in this proposed method, consisting of tumor and non-tumor images.

2.2 Image Preprocessing

The image enhancement stage is mainly used for enhancing and to make the image better from noising. The major plan of this processing is to obtain the correct information from the image for human visual perception. When the pixel value changes it helps to gives the orthogonal transformed image or it gives improved handling procedures dependent on rate of recurrence domain strategy it performs.

The alteration of color (shade) image into grayscale image is a complex procedure and it is important for obtaining the wanted highlights. The changed grayscale image may drop contrasts, sharpness, shadow, and structure of the color image.

The curvelet transform is a novel multi-scale transform follow on wavelet transform. The main use is detecting edge and image de-noising.

A curvelet coefficient $t(j, l, k)$ is given by,

$$t(a, b, c) = \langle f, \varphi_{a,b,c} \rangle \quad (1)$$

Where,

$a = 0, 1, \dots$ - Scale limit; $b = 0, 1, \dots$ - orientation limit; $c = (c_1, c_2), c_1, c_2 \in Z$ - translation limit.

Histogram equalization is a method used to adjust the intensity values of the images which enhances the contrast. The histogram equalization is

$$r_k = \frac{n_k}{N} \quad (2)$$

Where, n_k is the intensity level, N is the sum of pixels in image

Figure 1: Overall View of Proposed Work

2.3 Image Binarization

The Binarization technique changes over the gray scale image (0 up to 256 dim levels) in to highly contrasting image (0 or 1). The fantastic binarized image can give more precision in character response as looked at unique image since noise is available in the first image. Binarization is made by fuzzy C-means clustering algorithm.

FCM clustering is mainly utilized for dividing N items into C classes. The FCM calculation is utilized for iterative optimization of an objective

function dependent on a weighted similarity evaluate between the pixels in the image and all the c -group focuses. A neighborhood pixel of objective function shows a best possible grouping of the input data. The minimization of objective function is given by

2.4 Lung Extraction

The morphological operations and canny edge detector are used to show the outlines plus limits of the apparatus associated with them. To

achieve specific initial lung masks, a innovative adaptive concave hull algorithm is used.

Morphological based spatial segmentation is performed by applying dilation and erosion operations of morphological filters on lung images. This method improves the quality of images by shrinking and expanding the boundaries of desired area of images.

Edge location is an essential device utilized in image handling, fundamentally for highlight identification and extraction, which plan to recognize focuses in an advanced image where intensity of image changes pointedly and discover discontinuities. It is an ideal edge location method as give great identification, clear reaction and great confinement. It is generally utilized in current image handling procedures with further upgrades.

For a various field the Convex and concave hulls are broadly used and helpful for various research. Compared to the convex hull model the concave hull model provides superior performance. The concave hull calculation is performed by the known value of the convex hull algorithm and to create a concave hull with suitable profundity the dig is to perform.

2.5 Segmentation

In the recent times, segmentation plays an indispensable task in medical image analysis for image investigation and interpretation. Lung tumor segmentation of computer tomography images is a significant task. Here k-means clustering and Region based active contour models are designed for implementation. These techniques perform well but have some limitations. To avoid this optimized chan- vese algorithms is used. This technique correctly marks the minute nodules.

Optimized Chan-Vese Algorithm is one of the prominent division procedures. This calculation depends on region based active contour model, this active contour model don't utilize image inclination rather utilizes accurate data for calculating the shape within the object limit all through the progress. Region based models are fewer delicate to frail edges, noise, in-homogeneity, poor contrast and so on. To avoid these problems a novel technique is proposed. It accurately identifies the object boundaries. It allows the outline to deform so as to reduce a known energy function in turn to generate the accurate segmentation. The classical optimization methods are valuable in finding the optimum solution. Here combine two optimization algorithms [20 and 21] to obtain better results. This hybrid method gives optimum value accurate. There are three major changes have been made into the classical BFO which is emerged as proposed Hybrid BFO-GWO algorithm. The detailed explanation of proposed optimized chan- vese algorithm is described below.

2.6 Feature Extraction

Feature extraction is the procedure engaged with analyzing image texture. The outcomes gives a superior understanding of texture and object shape determination. Feature extraction is related to reduction of dimension. The algorithm has too large input data to be processed and it is suspected to be smaller sets. The feature extraction is important thing to powerful model construction. The feature extraction stage is portrayed by means of feature vector, a pixel portrayal regarding some quantifiable estimation which can be effectively utilized in the classification stages. Here run length features technique is useful for extract the image features

Algorithm 1

Input: computed tomography (CT) lung image

Output: Segmented tumor region and its parameter values such as area, perimeter, centroid, diameter.

Step 1: establish the procedure

Step 2: Set $\varphi = \varphi_1$

Step 3: for $k=1$:no.of outside contour procedure

Step 4: work out c_0 and c_1 for the current φ

Step 5: for $l=1$:no.of inside contour procedure

Step 6: renew φ

Step 7: reinitialize φ to signed distance function

Step 8: find the local best (pbest) using BFO

Step 9: find the global best (gbest) using GWO

Step 10: calculate Step size $c(i) = \alpha (rand - 1/2)$ The values lies in between $[0, 1]$, α is the randomization variable

Step 11: update optimized result, segmented image, labeled image

Step 12: calculate performance parameter like area, perimeter, centroid, diameter for an obtained result.

Step 13: stop the procedure.

2.7 Classification

Image classification is the way toward grouping images into various classes. Image classification is a significant procedure in the field of medical image processing. In an image classification technique the feature extraction outcome is significant. The techniques like naïve bayes classifier, bag of visual word classifier and optimized bag of visual word classifier is used for classification.

Depending on the feature value the BOVW (Bag of Visual Word) classifier gives superior accuracy, but some optimization problem occur. To avoid this optimized BOVW classifier is used. The optimized bag of visual classifier consists of BOVW

classifier followed by ABC (Artificial Bee Colony) algorithm. The Artificial Bee Colony algorithm [22] is very popular and simple algorithm to solve complex optimization problems. There are lots of complex real world problem that are not solvable by conventional methods. In order to solve this type of problem population base techniques are very helpful. The use of intelligence appeared from collective actions of a swarm that is by and large used to crack multifaceted problems when an individual is not able to find solution of a meticulous problem. The block diagram of the optimized BOVW classifier is shown in Figure 2 and the algorithm is described as follows.

Figure 2: Flow Diagram of Optimized Bag of Visual Classifier

Algorithm 2

- 1) *Load Image Sets: Cancer image dataset contains two categories: benign and malignant, which can be loaded for classification.*
- 2) *Set up Training and Validation Image Sets: To equalize the images in each and every category.*
- 3) *Generate a Visual Vocabulary:*
- 4) *Extracts SURF features from all images in all image class.*
- 5) *Finding best cost of each image sets.*
- 6) *Constructs the visual vocabulary by decreasing the quantity of highlights through quantization of highlight space utilizing K-means Clustering.*
- 7) *Evaluate Classifier Performance: First test it with the preparation set, which should create close flawless*

- perplexity grid, i.e., ones on the slanting.*
- 8) *Adopting ABC to optimize the BOVW model*
 - 9) *Is optimized parameter obtained?*
 - 10) *If: Yes*
 - 11) *Optimized Trained BOVW*
 - 12) *apply the recently prepared classifier to sort new images.*
 - 13) *Finally display the accuracy of the classifier and predict the stages.*
 - 14) *else*
 - 15) *continues the Adopting ABC to optimize the BOVW model*
 - 16) *Stop procedure*

3. PERFORMANCE MEASURES

The statistical methods are calculated for the classification process.

$$Sensitivity = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \times 100\% \quad (3)$$

$$Specificity = \frac{TN}{TN+FP} \times 100\% \quad (4)$$

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+FP+FN+TN} \times 100\% \quad (5)$$

$$Border Error = \frac{FP+FN}{TP+FN} \times 100\% \quad (6)$$

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \times 100 \quad (7)$$

Where, TN & TP is True Negative and positive, FP & FN is False Positive.

4. Experimental Results & Discussion

In this proposed work the benign and malignant samples of lung cancer images which are taken from the publically available LIDC databases. These lung CT images are considered for the classification use on finding the stage of the disease. 75 samples of each category are taken but here 3 samples of each category outputs are shown in this chapter. These images are processed in the MATLAB software version 2016a. In this work to identify and categorize the lung cancer images the Optimized BoVW classifier is applied. This helps in enhancing the classification technique and to provide 97.3% accuracy.

Figure: 3. (a) Input image (b) Gray scale image, (c) preprocessed image (d) Equalized histogram image

Figure 4: (a) Fuzzy thresholding result (b) erosion result, (c) dilated result, (d) Result of canny detector, (e) result of image without border (f) result of adaptive concave hull

The figures 3 show the preprocessing stages of lung images. Here the unrelated components

eliminated and the image features will be improved. The result of image binarization and lung extraction is depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 5: result of segmentation (a) K-means clustering (b) region based active contour (c & d) final result of proposed optimized cahn-vee and labeled image

Following the extraction process the segmentation is performed using some novel algorithms. This novel segmentation technique gives better performance compared with the other technique such as k-means clustering and region based active contour model.

The performance of these two techniques is good but it has some drawback, it missed the minute nodules from the image and over segmentation problem occurred. To overcome these problems the optimization model is used. This suggested optimized technique correctly isolates the image with unclear boundaries and clearly marks the shapes, labels the nodule efficiently.

This proposed segmentation technique includes any size of the nodules and exactly smooth's the pulmonary vessels. It does not require any user interaction and reduces over segmentation and under segmentation. Figure 5 shows the result of segmentation. Based on the results the optimized Chan-vee techniques gives best outcomes compared to other technique. The GLRM technique is applied to the segmented images and the features are extracted for the following SVM naïve bayes classifier. The feature values are shown in table 1.

Table 1: GLRM feature extraction

Features		GLRM			
Images	SRHGE	SRLGE	LRLGE	LRHGE	
1	2170	321.0111	12.10332	2170	
2	2474.04	851.4939	9.647325	2345	
3	2474	561.4939	8.196796	2474	
4	2474	851.4939	21.13615	2474.78	
5	2344.09	851.4939	6.904325	2474	

Figure 6: confusion matrix Result: (a)SVM Naive Bayes (b) BoVW (c) Optimized BoVW

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 7: accuracy plot and Error Plot, sensitivity, appecificity and Precision Plot

The obtained accuracy of SVM naïve bayes classifier and BOVW is 92% and 94.6%. Further improving the performance the optimized BoVW is used, here optimization is performed by ABC algorithm. The obtained accuracy after optimization is 97.3%. The resultant accuracy of SVM naïve bayes

classifier, BOVW and optimized BOVW is shown in Figure 6.(a), (b) and (c). The diagonal area of the confusion matrix shows the perfect identification of benign and malignant images. Figure 7 shows the various plots of proposed SVM, naïve bayes, Bag of Visual Words and optimized BoVW classifiers. The various performance values are described in Table 2.

Table 2: Performance Comparison

Classifier	Naive – Bayes	BoVW	Optimized BoVW
Accuracy	92%	94.6%	97.3%
Error	8%	5.4%	2.7%
Sensitivity	93.3%	98.5%	98.6%
Specificity	84%	91.35%	96.1%
Precision	93.15%	90.66%	96%

5. Conclusion

People who have been affected by the lung tumor need screening to prevent the mortality. Medical image processing methods and advanced detection algorithms are used to detect the abnormalities present in the Lung. In the proposed system, various types of image processing techniques and classification algorithms are applied for automatic detection of lung tumor. The various stages of lung cancer are classified in the proposed system. In general, the process is carried out in three stages. First, various preprocessing methods applied in the lung images and the results are presented. Then, segmentation is carried out. Finally, the lung tumor stages like benign and malignant are classified using the proposed classifiers. Significantly better results are obtained with the proposed technique. The sensitivity, specificity and accuracy values are calculated from the confusion matrix. Finally, the Optimized Bag of visual words classifier is used to detect the lung cancer stages and its sensitivity, specificity and accuracy are measured or calculated and compared with other proposed methods. Better results are obtained compared with other proposed methods. The obtained accuracy is 97.3% by the proposed classifier. The proposed method is supportive to detect the lung tumor at initial stages. An obtained sensitivity of 98.6% and specificity of 96.1% was achieved by the proposed classifier. The results proved that it is possible to use the developed algorithms for assisting a radiologist to classify lung images into various stages, thus supporting the radiologist in decision making.

REFERENCES

1. Bray, Freddie, Jacques Ferlay, Isabelle Soerjomataram, Lindsey A. Torre, Rebecca L. Siegel, Ahmedin Jemal. "World cancer statistics 2018: GLOBOCAN reports the prevalence and mortality of 36 cancers globally in 185 countries." *CA: Clinician Cancer Journal* 68, No. 6 (2018): 394-424.
2. Ramaswamy Govindan, Morgensztern, Daniel, Shean Huey Ng, Feng Gao. "Trends in the stage distribution of non-small cell lung cancer patients: a National Cancer Database Survey." *Thoracic Oncology Journal* 5, No. 1 (2010): 29-33.
3. Weinberg, Robert A. *Cancer Biology: Second Student Edition International*. WW Company & Norton, 2013.
4. Bhuvaneswari, C., P. Aruna, and D. Loganathan. "A new fusion model for classification of the lung diseases using genetic algorithm." *Egyptian Informatics Journal* 15, no. 2 (2014): 69-77.
5. Ajin, M., and L. Mredhula. "Diagnosis of Interstitial Lung Disease by Pattern Classification." *Procedia computer science* 115 (2017): 195-208.
6. Roy, Tanushree Sinha, Neeraj Sirohi, and Arti Patle. "Classification of lung image and nodule detection using fuzzy inference system." In *International Conference on Computing, Communication & Automation*, pp. 1204-1207. IEEE, 2015.
7. Ignatious, Sruthi, and Robin Joseph. "Computer aided lung cancer detection system." In *2015 Global Conference on Communication Technologies (GCCT)*, pp. 555-558. IEEE, 2015.
8. Rendon-Gonzalez, Elmar, and Volodymyr Ponomaryov. "Automatic Lung nodule segmentation and classification in CT images based on SVM." In *2016 9th International Kharkiv Symposium on Physics and Engineering of Microwaves, Millimeter and Submillimeter Waves (MSMW)*, pp. 1-4. IEEE, 2016.
9. Bhuvaneswari, P., and A. Brintha Therese. "Detection of cancer in lung with k-nn classification using genetic algorithm." *Procedia Materials Science* 10 (2015): 433-440.
10. Lakshmanprabu, S. K., Sachi Nandan Mohanty, K. Shankar, N. Arunkumar, and Gustavo Ramirez. "Optimal deep learning model for classification of lung cancer on CT images." *Future Generation Computer Systems* 92 (2019): 374-382.
11. Alves, Jeovane H., Pedro M. Moreira Neto, and Lucas F. Oliveira. "Extracting Lungs from CT Images using Fully Convolutional Networks." In *2018 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*, pp. 1-8. IEEE, 2018.
12. Nithila, Ezhil E., and S. S. Kumar. "Segmentation of lung nodule in CT data using active contour model and Fuzzy C-mean clustering." *Alexandria Engineering Journal* 55, no. 3 (2016): 2583-2588.
13. Nithila, Ezhil E., and S. S. Kumar. "Segmentation of lung from CT using various active contour models." *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control* 47 (2019): 57-62.
14. Lee, Howard, and Yi-Ping Phoebe Chen. "Image based computer aided diagnosis system for cancer detection." *Expert Systems*

- with Applications* 42, no. 12 (2015): 5356-5365.
15. Rendon-Gonzalez, Elmar, and Volodymyr Ponomaryov. "Automatic Lung nodule segmentation and classification in CT images based on SVM." In 2016 9th International Kharkiv Symposium on Physics and Engineering of Microwaves, Millimeter and Submillimeter Waves (MSMW), pp. 1-4. IEEE, 2016.
 16. Bhuvaneswari, P., and A. Brintha Therese. "Detection of cancer in lung with k-nn classification using genetic algorithm." *Procedia Materials Science* 10 (2015): 433-440.
 17. Lakshmanaprabu, S. K., Sachi Nandan Mohanty, K. Shankar, N. Arunkumar, and Gustavo Ramirez. "Optimal deep learning model for classification of lung cancer on CT images." *Future Generation Computer Systems* 92 (2019): 374-382.
 18. Alves, Jeovane H., Pedro M. Moreira Neto, and Lucas F. Oliveira. "Extracting Lungs from CT Images using Fully Convolutional Networks." In 2018 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN), pp. 1-8. IEEE, 2018.
 19. Nithila, Ezhil E., and S. S. Kumar. "Segmentation of lung nodule in CT data using active contour model and Fuzzy C-mean clustering." *Alexandria Engineering Journal* 55, no. 3 (2016): 2583-2588.
 20. Nithila, Ezhil E., and S. S. Kumar. "Segmentation of lung from CT using various active contour models." *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control* 47 (2019): 57-62.
 21. Lee, Howard, and Yi-Ping Phoebe Chen. "Image based computer aided diagnosis system for cancer detection." *Expert Systems with Applications* 42, no. 12 (2015): 5356-5365.
 22. Taher, Fatma, and Rachid Sammouda. "Lung cancer detection by using artificial neural network and fuzzy clustering methods." In 2011 IEEE GCC Conference and Exhibition (GCC), pp. 295-298. IEEE, 2011.

Cloud-Enhanced Ensemble Intelligence for IoT Attack Detection in Edge Computing: A Critical Review

Mrs. Renjini Rani K.S

Computer Science and Engineering, John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of
Technology, India ranirenjini23@gmail.com

Abstract

With the rapid proliferation of the Internet of Things (IoT), the need for strong and adaptive security measures against cyber threats has become more pressing than ever. This literature review investigates recent progress in the convergence of cloud and edge computing as a means to strengthen IoT security. It focuses particularly on the application of ensemble machine learning techniques for identifying and preventing malicious attacks. The review presents an organized analysis of contemporary methods that utilize both cloud capabilities and edge-level intelligence to overcome IoT-specific security challenges. One of the key developments discussed is the transition from fully centralized cloud architectures to distributed edge computing, where processing and storage are offloaded to nearby devices like smartphones and routers. This shift enhances the system's ability to detect threats in real-time and respond with minimal latency. In addition to reviewing existing solutions, the paper also outlines innovative trends in attack detection strategies and suggests potential avenues for future research aimed at building resilient, intelligent, and scalable IoT security frameworks.

Keywords: Edge Defender, Edge computing, Cloud Resource, IoT

I. INTRODUCTION

Edge computing represents a significant evolution in cloud computing, designed to meet the demands of a digital landscape with billions of interconnected devices around the world. By moving computational tasks and networking closer to the end-user devices, edge computing enhances real-time responsiveness and reduce the load on centralized cloud systems. This distributed architecture introduces an edge layer that offers essential network storage, and processing capabilities adapted to specific user needs. The edge layer, comprising localized data centres provides benefits such as improved energy efficiency reduced latency and lower bandwidth consumption, it is well-suited for various applications. In the IoT architecture, which includes the thing layer, fog layer, and cloud layer, edge computing that incorporates with IoT devices to manage data more effectively. The thing layer consists of various IoT devices that collect data from

different resource constraints. The fog layer, positioned closer to these devices, facilitates real-time processing and decision-making but faces limitations in load balancing, computing power, and device reliability. These challenges must be managed to optimize edge-based applications. Security solutions for IoT systems, including detection, authentication and prevention, are evolving with the integration of machine learning (ML) algorithms. The effectiveness of these algorithms depends on their execution layer—whether in the cloud, fog, or thing layer—which influences decision-making fast. While cloud-based ML models can offer high performance, they may introduce latency that effect real-time decisions. Conversely, executing ML algorithms in the fog or thing layer can be bounded by limited resources.

Studies show that traditional ML techniques, like support vector machines (SVM), can be effective when combined with various algorithms but may struggle with the resource limitations of lower-tier layers. Algorithms such as decision trees, naïve Bayes, and K-nearest neighbours (KNN) are generally robust for offline predictions but may fall short in real-time scenarios. Recent research suggests that ensemble models could be particularly effective for IoT environments with limited resources, especially in the edge layer. The approach involves selecting an optimal ensemble model in the cloud and deploying it in the edge layer to achieve real-time detection with reduced latency. Securing IoT systems is challenging due to several factors, including insufficient security design and severe resource constraints. Many existing security mechanisms, attribute-based access control [1], group-signature-based authentication [2], homomorphic encryption [3], and public-key solutions, demand high levels of computational power and memory. These requirements often exceed the capabilities of many IoT end devices, such as smart meters, smart lockers, and smart cameras. Although cloud computing typically offers

nearly unlimited resources, its distance from IoT devices can impede effective service delivery. Edge computing, which moves extensive computing and storage resources closer to the IoT devices, addresses this issue by offloading resource-heavy tasks from the constrained end devices to the more capable edge layer [4]. This paradigm not only mitigates the resource limitations of IoT devices [5 - 8] but also improves overall system performance [9] and opens up new possibilities for designing IoT security solutions. Initial research has explored various edge-based security approaches, including edge-based security architectures [5–8], firewalls [10], intrusion detection systems [11,12], authentication and authorization protocols [13], and privacy-preserving mechanisms.[14–17].

2.BACKGROUND

This section presents an overview of intrusion detection, the time characteristics of data, edge computing, as well as the key requirements and the applications of edge computing.

2.1. Operational Needs of Edge Computing

The successful deployment and operation of edge computing depend on four fundamental requirements. Each of these plays a vital role, and in practice, achieving an optimal balance among them is essential, as the relative importance of each requirement may vary depending on the specific application scenario.

Firstly, real-time interaction is fundamental to edge computing and distinguishes it from traditional cloud computing. This requirement ensures low latency, which is critical for delay-sensitive applications and services, such as remote surgery, tactile internet, ultra-reliable low-latency communication (URLLC), unmanned vehicles [18], [19], and vehicle accident prevention. By supporting real-time decision-making and data analysis, edge computing enhances the quality of service (QoS).

Another essential requirement is local processing, enabled by edge servers that handle data and user requests directly at the network edge, rather than forwarding them to centralized cloud data centres. This localized approach significantly reduces the volume of data transmitted between small cells and the core network, resulting in two major advantages: enhanced bandwidth availability, which helps to prevent network bottlenecks, and a decreased traffic load on the core infrastructure, improving overall system efficiency and responsiveness.

High data rates are crucial to manage the enormous volumes of data generated by bandwidth-intensive applications like virtual reality, remote surgery, and other real-time services.[20] Edge servers, often integrated directly into base stations (BSs), play a

key role by enabling access to edge clouds without relying on the core network. This localized approach not only reduces latency but also improves data transfer speeds. Additionally, the use of millimetre wave (mmWave) frequency bands in small cells significantly enhances the transmission capacity, supporting the high data rates necessary for these advanced applications. Lastly, high availability ensures that cloud services remain accessible at the edge. With edge computing shifting data and application logic to edge clouds, maintaining the availability of these edge clouds is critical to ensure uninterrupted service.

3. COMPUTATIONAL FRAMEWORK

Different computational platforms provide a range of computing capabilities, with each offering distinct advantages depending on the application. These platforms vary in terms of processing power, availability, proximity to user equipment (UEs), and the complexity of the underlying network infrastructure. For example, edge servers, located closer to end users, can provide low-latency, high-performance computing for applications requiring quick data processing. On the other hand, cloud computing platforms offer more substantial processing power but come with higher latency due to the greater distance data must travel. The choice of platform depends on factors such as the specific service requirements, data processing needs, and the desired quality of service (QoS). These platforms can be deployed either individually or in combination, allowing for greater flexibility in addressing diverse network scenarios and application needs.

In practical terms, the selection of computational platforms is often driven by the nature of the application or service in question. For instance, services with strict QoS demands—such as autonomous driving or industrial automation—are more likely to rely on edge servers for real-time data processing to ensure rapid response times. In contrast, applications that require both real-time and non-real-time processing, like healthcare services, may adopt a hybrid model. In this case, edge servers would handle time-sensitive, lightweight data processing—such as monitoring vital signs—while more complex, data-intensive tasks, such as storing and analyzing patient histories, would be offloaded to cloud computing resources. This combination of edge and cloud resources enables a balance of efficiency and scalability, optimizing both the speed of response and the ability to handle large-scale data processing.

Cloud computing manages and processes a vast amount of network-wide data and information from user equipment (UEs) across the network. It then sends data, information, or decisions back to the

UEs. While cloud computing can support UEs with limited computational and storage capabilities, it is not well-suited for real-time services due to potential latency introduced by the distance between the cloud and the UEs.

Edge computing, in contrast, handles and processes a substantial amount of local data and information from UEs within a specific area. It operates closer to the UEs, reducing latency compared to cloud computing, which may be situated far from the UEs.

Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) enhances edge computing by providing storage and computational resources at the edge of the network, such as within radio access networks (RANs) and base stations (BSs). This setup improves context awareness and minimizes latency. MEC servers, often located alongside multiple hosts (e.g., BSs), use a virtualized interface to access storage and computational resources. A MEC orchestrator oversees the MEC hosts by collecting and providing real-time information on the services offered by each host, available resources (e.g., network capacity and load), network topology (e.g., UEs connected to the servers, including their locations and networking details), and managing MEC applications.

4. TYPE OF IDS FOR IOT

Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) are vital components of network security, designed to detect intrusions, attacks, and malicious activities within Internet of Things (IoT) environments. These systems play a crucial role in safeguarding IoT networks by monitoring device behavior or the network as a whole. Given the diverse nature of IoT applications and the potential for various types of threats, IDSs are often employed to ensure early detection and prompt mitigation of security risks.

IDSs for IoT can be classified in two main ways: based on their deployment position and the detection techniques they use. When classified by deployment position, IDSs can be either **Network-Based** or **Host-Based**. Network-Based IDSs monitor traffic across the entire network, looking for suspicious patterns or activity that may indicate an intrusion. In contrast, Host-Based IDSs focus on individual devices, tracking their activities and analyzing the behavior on each device to detect any malicious actions or compromises.

In terms of detection techniques, IDSs can utilize several approaches to identify potential threats. **Signature-Based** methods rely on pattern matching, comparing network traffic or device behavior

against a predefined database of attack signatures to detect known threats. **Anomaly-Based** IDSs, on the other hand, establish a baseline of normal system behavior and flag any deviations from this pattern, helping to identify new or unknown threats. Additionally, **Hybrid IDSs** combine both signature-based and anomaly-based techniques, enhancing detection accuracy and coverage by leveraging the strengths of both methods.

4.1 IDS Types Based on its Position in the Network

Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) in IoT can be deployed in various ways based on network requirements, with options including border routers, selected nodes, or across the entire network. These systems are typically categorized into three types: **Distributed IDS**, where detection occurs at multiple points across the network; **Centralized IDS**, where data from various nodes is sent to a central system for analysis; and **Hybrid IDS**, which combines both approaches by using distributed sensors for detection and centralizing the analysis. Each deployment type offers unique benefits depending on the scale, complexity, and security needs of the IoT environment.

4.1.1. Distributed IDS (Host-Based IDS)

In a distributed deployment, each node in the IoT network is responsible for monitoring and detecting attacks, leading to the installation of IDSs on nearly all nodes. This decentralized approach allows for attack detection across the network. However, given the resource constraints of IoT devices, optimizing the deployment of IDSs is crucial. Several strategies have been proposed to address these constraints: Oh et al. [21] developed a lightweight approach that identifies attacks by comparing packet payloads and attack patterns. Their method uses techniques such as auxiliary shifting and early decision-making to reduce the number of comparisons needed, effectively lowering memory usage and computational costs. While this approach reduces memory requirements, it may also impact detection accuracy.

Lee et al. [22] introduced a lightweight distributed IDS aimed at detecting Denial of Service (DoS) attacks in 6LowPAN networks. This method identifies malicious nodes by analysing the battery power consumption of IoT devices, though their study focused on a single node.

Mehmood et al. created a multi-agent IDS using a Naïve Bayesian algorithm to detect Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks within IoT layered

architectures. Their system incorporates various types of agents (system monitoring, communicating, collector, and actuator) distributed across IoT devices, which share the task of intrusion detection and reduce the workload on individual nodes. Although the approach uses sensors to gather and analyse data, its applicability to low-capacity systems is not fully explored, and the results are limited to simulations in Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN) and Mobile Ad-hoc Networks (MANET).

Cervantes et al. proposed a distributed Intrusion Detection System (IDS) called "Intrusion Detection of Sinkhole Assaults on 6LoWPAN for Internet of Things (INTI)." This system combines trust and status concepts with watchdogs within a hierarchical structure involving associated, leader, and member nodes. These nodes dynamically adjust their roles in response to network changes or attacks, enabling them to track and isolate attackers. While the effectiveness of this system for low-capacity nodes is not thoroughly discussed, the hierarchical nature of the IDS suggests it functions as a Hierarchical Intrusion Detection System.

In a different approach, Sforzin and Conti developed a distributed IDS called RpiIDS, deploying the Snort tool on Raspberry Pi devices within a smart home environment. Although RpiIDS is capable of hosting Snort, the limited resources of the Raspberry Pi pose challenges for monitoring and managing attacks on a larger scale. This constrained environment makes it difficult to achieve optimal scalability and effectiveness in large or complex networks.

4.1.2 Centralized IDS (Network IDS)

In this approach, intrusion detection systems (IDS) are installed on a centralized router or dedicated server. The border router, serving as the centralized edge node

connecting the IoT network to the Internet, simplifies the implementation of centralized IDS in IoT environments. This setup allows the IDS to quickly identify external attackers, as data packets from the outside enter through the border router. Consequently, the IDS can efficiently monitor, analyse, and filter out malicious data packets when attacks are detected. However, detecting internal attacks is more challenging with this method, as it requires comprehensive monitoring and analysis of all internal nodes connected to the border router. centralized IDS known as the "Knowledge-driven Adaptable Lightweight Intrusion Detection System (KALIS)." This system can be deployed on specialized external devices or integrated into a central router. KALIS autonomously learns about

network entities and dynamically generates detection algorithms. Compared to traditional IDS, KALIS performs better in identifying Denial of Service (DoS), routing, and other conventional attacks. However, it demands more memory than traditional IDS systems.

4.1.3. Hybrid IDS

By assessing the advantages and limitations of both centralized and distributed placement strategies, the hybrid placement strategy was developed to leverage the strengths of each approach while minimizing their respective drawbacks..

Using this hybrid approach, a hybrid intrusion detection system was introduced. In this design, selected nodes act as watchdogs (Distributed IDS), detecting intrusions by monitoring neighboring nodes for suspicious activity. These watchdogs apply specific rule sets to identify potential attacks, with each node using different rules based on observed network behavior. The centralized component of the IDS analyzes patterns in the monitored messages, according to these predefined rules. This hybrid method offers flexibility with rule sets, allowing for customization, but it requires frequent updates to remain effective against new and evolving threats.

A key limitation of the system is its inability to dynamically detect attacks, as it depends heavily on predefined rules for detection. Another hybrid attack detection system focused on identifying internal anomalous activities. This system monitors and evaluates neighbouring nodes within a one-hop distance and reports anomalies to its parent node. Upon detecting an intrusion, the system isolates the affected node and discards data packets at the link layer to minimize network overhead. Additionally, it features a fingerprinting function that helps the border router detect network changes and pinpoint the source of threats.

4.2 IDS Types Based Techniques

4.2.1 Signature-Based IDS

Also known as "misuse-based IDS," this type of system relies on a database of known attack patterns. The IDS scans the generated data to check for matches with these pre-stored signatures. Signature-based IDSs are highly effective at identifying known attacks and provide a high true positive rate. However, they require regular updates to remain effective, as their performance depends on the attack signatures in the database. They are not capable of detecting new or unknown attack patterns.

For instance, a Unified IDS (UIDS) was proposed to detect various types of attacks, including Denial of Service (DoS), probe, generic, and exploit attacks.

The system utilized a decision tree algorithm on the UNSW-NB15 dataset and incorporated multiple rule sets to improve detection accuracy. While the signature-based IDS outperformed previous models, it still faced challenges in identifying new, previously unseen attacks. Furthermore, the dataset used was not tailored to IoT environments, limiting the system's ability to effectively address emerging or unknown threats specific to IoT networks.

4.2.2. Anomaly-Based IDS

Anomaly-based Intrusion Detection Systems (IDSs) classify system behaviour as either normal or anomalous based on predefined rules or heuristics, rather than using attack signatures. These systems require an initial training phase to establish what constitutes normal behaviour. Any deviation from this baseline is flagged as a potential attack. While anomaly-based IDSs are particularly effective at detecting unknown or novel attacks, they often suffer from higher false positive rates, as not all deviations from normal behaviour indicate an actual threat.

Machine learning algorithms are commonly used to train these systems to recognize normal behaviour patterns. However, deploying machine learning models on resource-constrained IoT nodes presents substantial challenges. The lightweight nature of these algorithms must be carefully considered to ensure they can be effectively implemented without overburdening the limited resources of IoT devices.

4.2.3 Specification-Based IDS

Specification based IDS known as "rule-based IDS," this type of intrusion detection system relies on a set of predefined rules and thresholds defined by experts. These rules specify what constitutes normal and abnormal behaviour for nodes and protocols within the network. Specification-based IDSs monitor network activity and detect attacks by comparing it against these predefined rules and thresholds.

Unlike anomaly-based IDSs, which require training to establish normal behaviour patterns, specification-based IDSs operate with predefined rules set by human experts. This manual specification generally results in a lower false-positive rate compared to anomaly-based system. However, because the rules are manually defined, these systems can be less flexible and more prone to errors. They require periodic updates to ensure they remain effective against evolving threats.

4.2.4. Hybrid IDS

Hybrid IDSs combine elements from various detection methods to leverage their strengths and mitigate their weaknesses. By integrating signature-based, anomaly-based, specification-based, or other

detection techniques, hybrid IDSs aim to improve detection accuracy and overall system performance. One such hybrid IDS, developed using the Map Reduce approach, combines the unsupervised Optimum-Path Forest (OPF) algorithm with both anomaly-based and specification-based techniques. Experimental results show that this hybrid system effectively reduced false positives and increased true positives, making it suitable for detecting sinkhole and selective forwarding attacks in IoT networks.

However, the system's reliance on unsupervised learning and the Map Reduce approach introduces certain limitations. Furthermore, the dataset used for this research, sourced from simulated Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs), is not specifically designed for IoT environments, which may limit its relevance and applicability to real-world IoT scenarios.

5. CONCLUSION

This study proposes an approach to offload the ensemble machine learning model selection task to the cloud and the real-time prediction task to edge nodes. Using this technique, the cloud can handle more resource-intensive tasks and the fog nodes can handle real-time computations to simplify and reduce real-time attack detection. The proposed approach has been tested on the NSL-KDD dataset. The research also shows that the ensemble method with voting takes less time to execute than stacking.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

To the bounty of the all mighty who made everything possible. I would. I would like to thank my family members for helping me all the way through and supporting me with their love, care and encouragement

REFERENCES

- [1] Osanaiye, O., Chen, S., Yan, Z., Lu, R., Choo, K.K.R., Dlodlo, M.: From Cloud to Fog Computing: A Review and a Conceptual Live VM Migration Framework. *IEEE Access*. 5, 8284–8300 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2017.2692960>
- [2] Mutlag, A.A., Abd Ghani, M.K., Arunkumar, N., Mohammed, M.A., Mohd, O.: Enabling technologies for fog computing in healthcare IoT systems. *Futur. Gener. Comput. Syst.* 90, 62–78 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2018.07.049>
- [3] Pereira, J., Ricardo, L., Luís, M., Senna, C., Sargento, S.: Assessing the reliability of fog computing for smart mobility applications in VANETs. *Futur. Gener. Comput. Syst.* 94, 317–332

(2019).<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future>. 2018.11.043

[4] Ning, Z., Huang, J., Wang, X.: Vehicular fog computing: Enabling real-time traffic management for smart cities. *IEEE Wirel. Commun.* 26, 87–93 (2019)<https://doi.org/10.1109/MWC.2019.1700441>

[5] Verba, N., Chao, K.M., Lewandowski, J., Shah, N., James, A., Tian, F.: Modeling industry 4.0 based fog computing environments for application analysis and deployment. *Futur. Gener. Comput. Syst.* 91, 48–60 (2019).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future>. 2018.08.043

[6] Yousefpour, A., Fung, C., Nguyen, T., Kadiyala, K., Jalali, F., Niakanlahiji, A., Kong, J., Jue, J.P.: All one needs to know about fog computing and related edge computing paradigms: A complete survey. *J. Syst. Archit.* 98, 289–330
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sysarc.2019.02.009> (2019).

[7] Giacinto, G.; Roli, F.; Bruzzone, L. Combination of neural and statistical algorithms for supervised classification of remote-sensing images. *Pattern Recognit. Lett.* 2000, 21, 385–397. *Future Internet* 2022, 14, 102 16 of 17

[8] Bansal, A.; Mahapatra, S. A Comparative Analysis of Machine Learning Techniques for Botnet Detection. In *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Security of Information and Networks SIN '17*, New York, NY, USA, 13–15 October 2017; Association for Computing Machinery: New York, NY, USA, 2017; pp. 91–98. [CrossRef]

[9] Jaber, A.N.; Rehman, S.U. FCM–SVM based intrusion detection system for cloud computing environment. *Clust. Comput.* 2020, 23, 3221–3231.

[10] Zhang, Y.; Ren, Y.; Wang, J.; Fang, L. Network forensic computing based on ANN-PCA. In *Proceedings of the 2007 International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Security Workshops (CISW 2007)*, Harbin, China, 15–19 December 2007; pp. 942–945.

[11] Hemavathi, D.; Srimathi, H. Effective feature selection technique in an integrated environment using enhanced principal component analysis. *J. Ambient. Intell. Humaniz. Comput.* 2021, 12, 3679–3688.

[12] Salo, F.; Nassif, A.B.; Essex, A. Dimensionality reduction with IG-PCA and ensemble classifier for network intrusion detection. *Comput. Netw.* 2019, 148, 164–175

[13] Abu Al-Haija, Q.; Al-Badawi, A. Attack-

Aware IoT Network Traffic Routing Leveraging Ensemble Learning. *Sensors* 2022, 22, 241. [CrossRef]

[14] Wang, J.; Pan, J.; Esposito, F.; Calyam, P.; Yang, Z.; Mohapatra, P. Edge cloud offloading algorithms: Issues, methods, and perspectives. *ACM Comput. Surv. (CSUR)* 2019, 52, 1–23.

[15] Tariq, N.; Asim, M.; Al-Obeidat, F.; Zubair Farooqi, M.; Baker, T.; Hammoudeh, M.; Ghafir, I. The Security of Big Data in Fog-Enabled IoT Applications Including Blockchain: A Survey. *Sensors* 2019, 19, 1788. [CrossRef]

[16] Alrawais, A.; Alhothaily, A.; Hu, C.; Xing, X.; Cheng, X. An attribute-based encryption scheme to secure fog communications. *IEEE Access* 2017, 5, 9131–9138.

[17] Hu, P.; Ning, H.; Qiu, T.; Song, H.; Wang, Y.; Yao, X. Security and privacy preservation scheme of face identification and resolution framework using fog computing in internet of things. *IEEE Int. Things J.* 2017, 4, 1143–1155.

[18] Li, Z.; Zhou, X.; Liu, Y.; Xu, H.; Miao, L. A non cooperative differential game-based security model in fog computing. *China Commun.* 2017, 14, 180–189.

[19] Shi, Y., Abhilash, S., Hwang, K.: Cloudlet mesh for securing mobile clouds from intrusions and network attacks. *Proc. - 2015 3rd IEEE Int. Conf. Mob. Cloud Comput. Serv. Eng. MobileCloud 2015*. 109–118 (2015)
<https://doi.org/10.1109/MobileCloud.2015.15>

[20] Zhang, Y., Zhao, J., Zheng, D., Deng, K., Ren, F., Zheng, X., Shu, J.: Privacy-Preserving Data Aggregation against False Data Injection Attacks in Fog Computing. *Sensors*. 18, 2659 (2018).
<https://doi.org/10.3390/s18082659>

[21] Xun, P., Zhu, P., Zhang, Z., Cui, P., Xiong, Y.: Detectors on edge nodes against false data injection on transmission lines of smart grid. *Electron.* 7, 1–12 (2018).
<https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics7060089>

[22] Liu, D., Shen, J., Vijayakumar, P., Wang, A., Zhou, T.: Efficient data integrity auditing with corrupted data recovery for edge computing in enterprise multimedia security. *Multimed. Tools Appl.* 79, 10851–10870
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-019-08558-1> (2020).

Implementation of ANN controller to mitigate voltage fluctuations in Wind Energy ships

B P Beno Ben

Electrical and Electronics Engineering, John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of Technology,
Trivandrum.

Abstract

The shipping business must deal with two main constraints: new restrictions rules on pollution and CO₂ emissions and increasing of fuel oil. To this end fuel consumption shall be reduced and global ship energy efficiency shall be enhanced. Therefore, the shipping industry is constraint to find new solutions for designing and efficiently operating the ship. In this study, an example of a practical solution is presented to enhance the energy efficiency of tanker by fitting a wind turbine for generating the electric power which is usually produced by diesel generator burning fuel

Oil and emitting GHG. The sample vessel used for this study is small size tanker operating in regular between Moroccan ports. It has been demonstrated that for the case understudy, the fuel oil consumption necessary for the shipboard electric needs may be reduced by 23%. The global ship energy efficiency will be improved accordingly, it has also proven that wind turbine will not impair the ship stability and resistance.

This paper also proposes the concepts of ANN based Thyristor Switched Capacitor and Static Compensator and STATCOM. And also, the results are compared for these cases. Thus, with such a control, a balanced load currents are obtained even in the presence of non-linear load.

Introduction

The shipping sector is under considerable pressure to improve energy efficiency, while CO₂ emissions are decreasing in many other activities, transport emissions are expected to increase in the future. Shipping currently accounts for about 3% of global CO₂ emissions, but its share is expected to increase due to increased transportation activities, combined with challenges in implementing effective energy efficiency measures and replacing fossil fuels. [1].

In 2011, IMO adopted mandatory technical and operational energy efficiency measures which are expected to significantly reduce the amount of CO₂ emissions from international shipping [2]. All ships built after 2013 with 400 gross tonnages and

above must meet the minimum standard of energy efficiency, and the ships must achieve 20% more efficient by 2020 and 30% more efficient from 2025. Therefore, ship designers and builders must innovate and develop new energy and new solutions for energy saving, in order to enable new ships to meet higher energy efficiency standards in the future.

Many papers related to the ship energy efficiency improvement can be found in the literature [3-7] and are to the study of the optimization of the machinery cooling system, loading conditions, ship's routine, waste heat recovery systems etc.

The combination of conventional generation sources and local renewable resources will increase efficiency gains and energy savings. So, a hybrid energy system

will provide a more economic, environment friendly and make energy availability to end-use with affordable cost. In this way, this paper attempts to develop a hybrid Diesel-Wind energy system for energy saving and greenhouse gas emissions reducing. In contrast, there are some considerations for wind turbine installing on ships like:

- Different route of ship voyage has different wind parameters. Therefore, the wind power potential also varies according to that.
- Air draft limitation: Wind turbines onboard ships will increase the air draft of the ship and may outpace the limits on air drafts of some canal or bridges, thereby restricting the ship's operation.
- Air drag: The turbine tower and blades reference area will contribute to the drag force of the ship and increase the ship resistance.
- Ship stability: Once fitted onboard, both the height and weight of the wind turbine would affect the ship's stability condition. As the gravity center of the ship is shifted, the overall ship stability shall be reviewed.
- Safety of and operations: Turbine motion constitutes a safety hazard on board, the turbine should not restrict the normal ship's operations such mooring, cargo handling, maintenance and crew movements.
- Turbine structure should withstand the ship movements (rolling, pitching etc.) and should resist to the generated accelerations.
- Turbine should not disturb the ship's radio and navigation equipment. The overshadowing influence of wind turbine on the ship's radar performance may be a problem.

In the following sections, these constraints will be widely discussed in order to successfully set up our wind system.

1. Wind Turbine

In order to improve the energy efficiency of ships and reduce emissions from marine activities, the use of renewable energy is considered as promising solution. In particular, wind energy has a great advantage in navigation activities as it is always available on the high seas compared to other renewable energies. [3]. In [4] fuel oil economy achieved through the application of three wind-assisted vessel propulsion technologies was discussed and The results show that these three solutions generate fuel savings of between 5.6% and 8.9%. In [4], the authors presented a study on the potential fuel savings achieved with a kite installed on a cargo ship. According to the study, potential fuel savings of 1% to 21% are achieved at the speed of 15 knots and 4% to 36% at 13 knots. As a result, wind aid vessel (WASP) propulsion is one of the rare solutions that offers promising fuel and emission savings and is admitted as a serious source of renewable energy for the future shipping industry.

So far wind energy is mainly studied as auxiliary power for ship propulsion and despite the performances demonstrated there's no successful prototype of its application. The wind energy for electric power generation is mainly used on small sailing boats but not in cargo ships. In this paper we will discuss the potential of fuel saving by using wind turbine for electric power generation on sample ship trading in regular line where wind potential is proven. From turbine technology for electricity generation, it is likely there are important lessons to be transferred now to the shipping sector.

1.1 Vertical axis wind turbine

Wind turbines are the primary devices to convert the wind's momentum into rotor rotation, they can be classified into two main categories according to their axis alignment: horizontal axis wind turbines (HAWTs) and vertical axis wind turbines (VAWTs) as presented in Figures 1&2.

The mathematical model used to convert wind speed to electrical power by a wind turbine is given by equation (1).

$$P_e = \frac{1}{2} C_p \cdot \rho \cdot A \cdot V^3 \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where, P_e is the Electrical power watts [W]

C_p the wind turbine power coefficient

ρ the air density kg/m^3

The wind turbine rotor swept area m^2

V is the wind velocity at hub height m/s

Referred to figures 1 and 2, the wind turbine swept area is calculated as per equations (2) and (3), depending on the geometry of the rotor.

$$A = \pi r^2 \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

$$A = D H \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

1.2 Wind energy potential assessment

To evaluate the energy production of a wind turbine, it is not sufficient to know the average wind speed at a given site, It is also necessary that data showing, for a defined period of time, the histogram of the duration as a percentage of the different wind speed, is available. From this histogram, it is possible to draw the histogram of the statistical frequency of the occurrence of wind speed. The temporal distribution of wind speed for a given site is usually expressed using Weibull's statistical distribution function as it is close to the frequency of distribution of average wind speeds. [4].

Figure 1: HAWT Turbine

Figure 2: VAWT Turbine

The annual electrical energy expressed in [kWh] can theoretically be described and calculated using Weibull's distribution taking into account the wind speed at the installation site and the curve of the electrical energy produced by the wind turbine as a function of the instantaneous wind speed.

Consequently, referring to (4), the annual producibility can be expressed as:

$$E = d \cdot \int_0^\alpha P(v) \cdot f(v) \cdot dv \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

Where:

$f(v)$: represents the probability of wind speed,

v : the wind velocity,

k and c are the shape and scale parameters.

'k' has no dimensional units whereas the 'c' parameter is expressed in (m/s).

From the integrating the Weibull probability distribution,

1.3 Influence of ship speed:

When moving, apparent wind is the speed and direction of wind measured on board as depicted in Figure 3. It is composed of the combined speeds and directions of the ship and wind observed by a stationary wind instrument (the true wind). A true wind coming from the bow increases the apparent wind induced by the speed of the ship, coming from the stern it decreases apparent wind.

Figure 3: Ship speed Vs Wind speed

The apparent (Relative) wind speed \$V_R\$ is given by equation (5).

$$V_R = \sqrt{V_s^2 + V_w^2 + 2V_s V_w \cos \alpha} \quad \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

Where

\$V_s\$: Ship seed over the ground

\$V_w\$: True wind seed

\$\alpha\$: True pointing angle

1.4 Disadvantage

The main disadvantage of wind power generation is that fluctuations in wind speed may prevent production of stable power.

2. About Controller

the concepts of ANN based Thyristor Switched Capacitor and Static Compensator and STATCOM. And also, the results are compared for these cases. Thus, with such a control, a balanced load currents are obtained even in the presence of non-linear load. The experimental setup is done in Matlab and verified the simulation results [6].

A new PWM-based control scheme has been implemented to control the electronic valves in the DSTATCOM. The D-STATCOM has additional capability to sustain reactive current at low voltage, and can be developed as a voltage and frequency support by replacing capacitors with batteries as energy storage. In this paper, the configuration and design of the DSTATCOM with LCL Passive Filter are analyzed. It is connected in shunt or parallel to the 11 kV test distribution system. It also is design to enhance the power quality such as voltage sags, harmonic distortion and low power factor in distribution system.

3. Wind turbine

Wind turbines square measure classified into 2 general types: Horizontal axis wind turbine and Vertical axis wind turbine. A vertical axis wind machine has its blades rotating on axis perpendicular to the bottom. The square measure variety of obtainable styles for each and every kind has bound benefits and downsides [7].

Figure 3: Basic Wind Turbine System

The wind turbines with a squirrel cage generator are equipped with a soft starter mechanism for reactive power compensation as coop generators consume reactive power. This generator and also the turbine rotor area unit coupled through a shell, because the best rotor and generator speed ranges are totally different.

3.1 STATCOM and its Control Technique

A STATCOM is a one of the compensated device which is obtained from the FACTS family [11] and is a combination of power electronic converter along with reactor. Mostly, the converter is constructed by the use of fully controlled devices such as GTO, IGBT or MOSFET. The main purpose of this STATCOM converter control technique is used to compensate the deviations in power system for improving power quality. In this paper grid interfaced wind turbine based STATCOM control scheme is proposed for improving the reliability of electrical power [12]. • The Dc voltage obtained for STATCOM is generated from Solar Cells. The schematic diagram of Static compensator is given in figure5.

Figure 5: Basic Block diagram for Static Compensator

The utilization of different types of electrical loads in three phase system, produces an unbalances in current, which causes the unreliable power [7]. Thereby for maintaining the electrical reliability the statcom controller plays a key role. In this statcom control technique, the reference voltage and dc link capacitor voltages are compared and the result obtained from this is converted to two phase coordinators called as orthogonal vectors.

3.2 Control for Reactive Power Compensation

The aim of the control scheme is to maintain constant voltage magnitude at the point where a sensitive load under system disturbances is cFconnected. The control system only measures the root mean square (r.m.s) voltage at the load point, i.e., no reactive power measurements are required. The VSC switching strategy is based on a sinusoidal PWM technique which offers simplicity and good response. Since custom power is a relatively lowpower application, PWM methods offer a more flexible option than the fundamental frequency switching methods favored in FACTS applications. [6]Apart from this, high switching frequencies can be used to improve on the efficiency of the converter, without incurring significant switching losses.

Figure 5: PI control scheme

The controller input is an error signal obtained from the reference voltage and the r.m.s terminal voltage measured. Such error is processed by a PI controller; the output is the angle δ , which is provided to the PWM signal generator. It is important to note that in this case, of indirectly controlled converter, there is active and reactive power exchange with the network simultaneously. The PI controller processes the error signal and generates the required angle to drive the error to zero, i.e. the load r.m.s voltage is brought back to the reference voltage.

4. Artificial Neural Networks

Figure 6 shows the basic architecture of artificial neural network, in which an hidden layer is indicated by circle, an adaptive node is represented by square [8]. In this structure hidden layers are presented in between input and output layer, these nodes are functioning as membership functions and the rules obtained based on the if-then statements is eliminated. For simplicity, we considering the examined ANN have two inputs and one output. In this network, each neuron and each element of the input vector p are connected with weight matrix W .

Figure 6: ANN architecture for a two input multi-layer network

SIMULATION RESULTS

The simulation results for the proposed grid interfaced wind energy system with D-STATCOM is shown in below figures.

Figure 7: Simulation Result for Three Phase Output Voltage from wind System

Figure 8: Simulation result for Power generated from Wind System

Figure 9: Simulation Result for Line voltage under RMS with DSTATCOM and ANN

CONCLUSION

The wind turbine mainly the vertical axis type may be one of the practical solutions for reduction of greenhouse gas emissions by vessels and improving the global energy efficiency of ships. In this study it was demonstrated that by fitting the wind turbine on board a coastal tanker operating between Moroccan port, the reduction of fuel oil consumption and CO2 emission by 23% for electrical generation. This is a novel concept of integration of STATCOM with grid inter faced wind energy system for power quality improvement. The paper also presents effects of power quality on

consumer and power utility systems. The shunt devices proposed here, while reducing the distortions in currents, improved the power factor thus reducing the reactive power demand from the wind generator and the load at point of common coupling. Thus, the integration of FACTS devices maintains the desired power quality requirements. The operation of STATCOM and their control strategies are simulated in MATLAB/SIMULINK.

REFERENCES

- [1] Third IMO Green House Emission Study. Executive Summary and Final Report. Published in 2015 by the international maritime organization. 4 albert embankment, London Se1 7Sr www.imo.org
- [2] IMO, Resolution MEPC.203(62): Amendments to the annex of the protocol of 1997 to amend the international convention for the prevention of pollution from ships, 2011. Available online: [http://www.imo.org/en/KnowledgeCentre/IndexofIMOResolutions/Marine-Environment-Protection-Committee-\(MEPC\)/Documents/MEPC.203\(62\).pdf](http://www.imo.org/en/KnowledgeCentre/IndexofIMOResolutions/Marine-Environment-Protection-Committee-(MEPC)/Documents/MEPC.203(62).pdf)
- [3] G. Theotokatos, K. Sfakianakis and D. Vassalos. Investigation of ship cooling system operation for improving energy efficiency. *Journal of Marine Science and Technology* 22, 38–50 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00773-016-0395-9>
- [4] E. G. Pariotis, T. C. Zannis and J. S. Katsanis. An Integrated Approach for the Assessment of Central Cooling Retrofit Using Variable Speed Drive Pump in Marine Applications. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*. 2019; 7(8):253. <https://www.mdpi.com/2077-1312/7/8/253>
- [5] A.Q.Huang, M Baran, S.Bhattacharya “STATCOM importance on the integration of a large wind farm into a weak loop power system,” *IEEE Trans. Energy Conv.*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 226–232, Mar. 2008.
- [6] Hook, Y. Liu, presents a paper on “Mitigation of the wind generation integration related power quality problems by energy storage,” at EPQU J., vol. XII, no. 2, in 2006.
- [7] Wind Turbine Generating System—Part 21, International standard-IEC 61400-21, 2001.
- [8] J.Manel, “Power electronic system for grid integration of renewable energy source: A survey,” *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 53, no. 4, pp. 1002–1014, 2006, Carrasco.
- [9] S. Ezhilarasan, P. Palanivel, S. Sambath “Design and Development of Energy Management System for DG Source Allocation in a Micro Grid with Energy Storage System” Volume 8, Issue 13, July 2015.

AGRISENSE

Alan Anil, Aleena Joseph, Erin Biju,
Greeshma B. Department of Computer
Science and Engineering, John Cox
Memorial CSI Institute of Technology,
Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala

Abstract— Agricultural productivity is often hindered by plant diseases and inefficient water and nutrient management. This paper presents AGRISENSE, an IoT-based smart agriculture system that leverages deep learning and real-time environmental monitoring to enhance crop health and yield. A Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model analyzes leaf images for accurate plant disease detection, providing timely treatment recommendations. A smart irrigation system utilizing soil moisture sensors and real-time weather data optimizes water distribution. Furthermore, NPK sensors continuously monitor soil nutrient levels, offering precise fertilizer recommendations. Farmers can access real-time disease reports, weather conditions, and nutrient insights through a user-friendly web application. By integrating IoT and AI technologies, AGRISENSE enhances precision farming, minimizes waste, and contributes to sustainable agricultural practices.

Keywords— *IoT, Smart Irrigation, Plant Disease Detection, CNN, Precision Agriculture*

I. INTRODUCTION

The global agricultural sector faces challenges such as declining soil fertility, plant diseases, and inefficient water usage. Conventional methods of disease detection and irrigation management are often manual, leading to delays in response time and inefficient resource utilization. The rapid advancements in IoT and artificial intelligence (AI) have paved the way for smart farming solutions. AGRISENSE addresses these challenges by integrating cutting-edge deep learning techniques and real-time environmental monitoring. This system helps farmers make data-driven decisions, ensuring optimal crop health and resource efficiency.

AGRISENSE is designed to be scalable and adaptable for different farming environments, including small-scale farms, greenhouses, and large agricultural enterprises. This paper outlines the system's architecture, implementation, and performance evaluation to demonstrate its effectiveness in improving farming practices.

II. OBJECTIVES

The primary objectives of AGRISENSE are:

Automate Plant Disease Detection: Utilize Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to accurately detect plant diseases by analyzing leaf images, reducing dependency on manual inspection.

Optimize Water Usage: Implement a smart irrigation system that leverages real-time soil moisture data and weather forecasts to reduce water wastage and improve irrigation efficiency.

Enhance Soil Nutrient Management: Deploy NPK sensors to monitor essential soil nutrients and provide farmers with precise fertilizer recommendations to improve crop health and yield.

Enable Real-Time Monitoring and Control: Provide a web-based dashboard for farmers to monitor plant health, irrigation status, and nutrient levels remotely.

Improve Sustainability in Agriculture: Minimize excessive use of water, fertilizers, and pesticides, thereby promoting environmentally friendly and sustainable farming practices.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

A. Plant Disease Detection Using Deep Learning

Existing research highlights the effectiveness of CNNs in identifying plant diseases through image-based analysis. CNN models extract key features such as color, texture, and lesion patterns to classify diseases with high accuracy. However, most studies lack integration with real-time farm monitoring systems. Some models require high computational power, limiting their deployment on low-resource devices like mobile phones or embedded systems. AGRISENSE aims to overcome these challenges by optimizing deep learning models for real-time, low-power applications.

B. IoT-Based Smart Irrigation Systems

IoT-based irrigation systems automate water distribution using soil moisture sensors. Advanced solutions integrate weather forecasting to prevent unnecessary watering. However, existing models rarely incorporate manual control options for farmers, which AGRISENSE provides. Additionally, studies show that over-reliance on automation without human oversight can sometimes lead to inefficient water use. Our system balances automation with farmer intervention to maximize efficiency.

C. Nutrient Monitoring with NPK Sensors

Precision agriculture techniques emphasize monitoring soil nutrient levels to optimize fertilizer application. IoT-enabled NPK sensors measure nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and potassium (K) levels, reducing excess chemical usage and improving crop yield. Despite advancements, many existing solutions fail to provide actionable recommendations for fertilizer application. AGRISENSE addresses this by integrating AI-powered suggestions based on real-time sensor data.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

A. System Architecture

AGRISENSE integrates three core modules: (i) plant disease detection via CNN, (ii) smart irrigation control using soil moisture sensors and weather API, and (iii) soil nutrient monitoring with NPK sensors. The system architecture includes a microcontroller unit (NodeMCU), sensors for data collection, a machine learning model for disease

identification, and a cloud-based platform for real-time monitoring. The architecture is designed for modularity, allowing seamless integration of additional features such as pest detection, climate prediction, and automated crop growth analysis. The IoT-enabled sensors continuously transmit data to a central server, where machine learning models analyze the information and generate actionable insights for farmers.

B. Plant Disease Detection

Image Acquisition & Preprocessing: Farmers upload leaf images to the system, where preprocessing techniques such as normalization and edge detection enhance image quality. **CNN Model for Classification:** A trained CNN model classifies diseases based on extracted features, ensuring accurate diagnosis. The model is trained on a diverse dataset of plant leaf images to improve its robustness. **Treatment Recommendations:** The system provides customized recommendations for disease treatment, integrating an agricultural database for precision guidance. These recommendations include organic and chemical treatment options to suit different farming preferences.

C. Smart Irrigation System

Soil Moisture Sensors: Continuously measure soil moisture levels to determine optimal watering schedules.

Weather API Integration: Fetches real-time weather conditions to prevent overwatering and optimize irrigation schedules.

Automated and Manual Control: Farmers can override automation through a web application, ensuring flexibility in irrigation management. This feature allows farmers to take proactive measures during extreme weather conditions.

D. NPK-Based Nutrient Monitoring

Real-Time Soil Nutrient Analysis: Monitors soil health and detects deficiencies in nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium.

Fertilizer Recommendations: Based on NPK readings, the system suggests appropriate fertilizers, promoting balanced soil nutrition. The recommendations take into account crop type, soil composition, and historical nutrient trends.

Long-Term Soil Health Monitoring: Aggregates data over time to analyze trends in soil fertility, aiding in sustainable farming practices.

V. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

To evaluate AGRISENSE, a prototype was deployed in a controlled agricultural setting. Key performance metrics included:

CNN Model Accuracy: Achieved an 89% accuracy rate in detecting plant diseases. Further training and data augmentation techniques can enhance performance.

Water Conservation: Reduced water usage by 30% through optimized irrigation scheduling. This reduction was achieved by intelligently predicting irrigation needs based on soil moisture and weather conditions.

Nutrient Utilization Efficiency: Optimized fertilizer application, reducing chemical overuse by 25% and preventing soil degradation.

System Latency: Average response time for disease detection and irrigation control was under 2 seconds, ensuring real-time responsiveness for farmers.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

AGRISENSE presents an innovative approach to smart farming by integrating IoT, machine learning, and real-time data monitoring. The system successfully automates disease detection, irrigation, and nutrient management, contributing to sustainable agriculture.

Future enhancements include expanding the CNN model to detect a wider range of diseases, integrating pest detection features, deploying AI-driven yield prediction algorithms, and incorporating blockchain technology for secure agricultural data management. Additionally, a mobile application for farmers will be developed to provide on-the-go access to system insights.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We express our sincere gratitude to the faculty and staff of the Department of Computer Science and Engineering at John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of Technology for their valuable guidance and support throughout this research. We also extend our appreciation to APJ Abdul Kalam Technological University for providing the academic framework that enabled this study. Furthermore, we acknowledge the contributions of our peers and faculty whose work has laid the foundation for advancements in IoT-based smart agriculture. Lastly, we thank our families and friends for their encouragement and unwavering support during this research.

REFERENCES

- [1] Suresh Manic Kesavan Department of Electrical and Communication Engineering, College of Engineering, National University of Science and Technology, Muscat, Oman
INetCache/IE/2EFDC0R0/IoT_Based_Smart_Wheelchair_for_Disabled_People[1].pdf
- [2]<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/8703354> Institute of Instrument Science and Engineering, Southeast University, Nanjing 210096, China
- [3]<https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/22/22/8716> Finger-Gesture Controlled Wheelchair with Enabling IoT by Muhammad Sheikh Sadi Mohammed Alotaibi ,Md. Repon Islam Md. Saiful Islam ,Tareq Alhmiedat Zaid Bassfar
- [4]<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9319822/>

AI AUTONOMOUS FIRE FIGHTING ROBOTIC VEHICLE

Sidharth S , Keseya S A

Dept. of Electronics & Communication Engineering

John Cox Memorial Csi Institute of Technology Kannammola

Trivandrum kerala India

(sidharthsatheesh65@gmail.com)

(Keseyasa61@gmail.com)

Jebin H A, Julianne Joseph

Dept. of Electronics & Communication Engineering

John Cox Memorial Csi Institute of Technology Kannammola

Trivandrum Kerala India

(jebincrik@gmail.com)

(Juliannejoseph03@gmail.com)

Abstract— AI autonomous firefighting robot focuses on developing a fire detection system that integrates flame detection with human detection using an ESP32-CAM module for live video streaming. The system is designed to monitor environments in real-time, utilizing a flame sensor to detect the presence of fire and the ESP32-CAM module to capture and stream live video. The video stream is processed using a computer vision model, which identifies the presence of humans in the area. This combination of flame detection and human recognition ensures that the system can accurately detect fires while simultaneously identifying any individuals who may be in danger. Upon detecting fire or human presence, the system can trigger alarms, send notifications to emergency services, or initiate other safety protocols. The integration of the ESP32-CAM for live video streaming adds an additional layer of situational awareness, making this system a robust and reliable solution for fire safety in various environments, including residential, commercial, and industrial settings.

I. INTRODUCTION

Now-a-days, Fire accidents are becoming more and more in society that maybe building fires, motor vehicle fires, etc. These accidents cause many hazards to people and also pollute and damage to environment. Fire accident leads to number of people deaths. Basically, the firefighter's works hard to protect the people from the fire and to save human and animals life. But they cannot protect the more number of people from the fire and it also somewhat time taken to fire fighters. So we came with application of firefighting robot based on artificial intelligence. As the technology has finally bridged the gap between firefighting and machines allowing for a more efficient and effective method of firefighting [1]. We create an automated system for early detection and extinguished of fire thereby making the work of fireman easy and reduce loss of human life. The importance of the proposed thesis is to make a reliable, safe, and smart system to reduce limitations and faults like false alarms, which cause panic among the people and even the loss of money with the use of new technology and make the places safe from the hazardous fire. Additionally, having a compact size and automatic small and narrow spaces with hazardous environments such as tunnels or nuclear power plants [6]. Furthermore, this robot can increase productivity, safe, efficiency and quality of the task given [2]. A human operator can monitor the robot by using camera which connects to a smart phone or remote devices. Finally robots can be used in situations where human access is not possible, such as in collapsed buildings or in remote locations. The paper aims to motivate the robotics community to develop a real-world application based on what it can accomplish. In addition to being able to be installed in homes, laboratories, stores, shops etc., fire fighting robot is easily portable and can be used once installed [3].

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

A. Fire Detection Module

- Uses infrared sensors for fire identification.
- Employs a deep learning model trained on fire datasets for real-time detection

B. Navigation and Obstacle Avoidance

- The Incorporates ultrasonic sensors for autonomous path planning and obstacle avoidance.

C. Human Detection Module

- ESP32-CAM module is used to capture images
- Using image sensing the Human presence will be detected

III. TECHNOLOGY USED

A. Arduino IDE

The Arduino IDE is a software platform for writing, compiling, and uploading code to microcontrollers. The Arduino IDE provides a user-friendly interface for the user.

This community is vast and active, providing a wealth of resources, libraries and example code.

B. Anaconda

Anaconda provide a comprehensive platform for data science and machine learning tasks. Anaconda's libraries like pandas and NumPy can be used for data cleaning and preprocessing.

C. Jupyter notebook

Jupyter Notebook is web-based interactive computing environment that allows users to create and Share documents that contain live code, equations, visualizations, and narrative text. For human detection image and video processing, feature detection, and object recognition.

IV. WORKING

The firefighting robot equipped with a flame sensor, ESP32 microcontroller, water pump, motor driver, motor, and relay operates through a series of coordinated components to detect and extinguish fires autonomously. The flame sensor continuously monitors the environment. This sensor detects the presence of fire by sensing infrared light emitted by flames. It generates a signal indicating whether a flame is detected. And this signal is send to the ESP32, a powerful microcontroller that processes input from the flame sensor and controls other components like motors and the water pump. Relay is used to control high-power components like the water pump. The ESP32 activates the relay to turn the pump on or off based on the flame sensor's readings. Water pump draws water from a reservoir and sprays it to extinguish the fire. It is activated when a flame is detected. Here motor driver controls the direction and speed of the motors that drive the robot. It receives signals from the ESP32 to activate the motors based on sensor inputs. While motor provides movement to the robot, allowing it to navigate towards the detected fire. Another unit of this firefighting robot act as a monitoring system which is done by the use of ESP32-CAM module. The ESP32-CAM is a compact module that integrates a camera with the ESP32 microcontroller, allowing for video streaming and image capture. In a firefighting robot, the ESP32- CAM can enhance functionality by providing real-time video feedback. While extinguishing the fire, the ESP32-CAM continues to provide video feedback, allowing for assessment of the situation and confirmation of fire suppression. After the fire is extinguished, the robot can send a status update or video confirmation, ensuring that the task has been completed. This ESP32-CAM module also enables to detect the presence of human who may be got trapped in the fire accident and further can provide further rescue operation.

FIG 1 BLOCK DIAGRAM

FIG 2 FLOW CHART

V. FUTURE SCOPE

The paper has been motivated by the desire to design a system that can detect fires and take appropriate action, without any human intervention. The development of sensor networks and the maturity of robotics suggest that we can use mobile agents for tasks that involve perception of an external stimulus and reacting to the stimulus, even when the reaction involves a significant amount of mechanical actions[4]. This provides us the opportunity to pass on to robots tasks that traditionally humans had to do but were inherently life- threatening. Fire-fighting is an obvious candidate for such automation. Given the number of lives lost regularly in fire- fighting, the system we envision is crying for adoption. Our experience suggests that designing a firefighting system with sensors and robots is within the reach of the current sensor network and mobile agent technologies. Furthermore, we believe that the techniques developed in this work will carry over to other areas involving sensing and reacting to stimulus, where we desire to replace the human with an automated mobile agent[5]

CONCLUSION

The automated fire fighting robot is capable of detecting fire and extinguishes the fire source successfully. The prototype of the fire fighter robot was efficiently designed. This prototype has facilities to be integrated with many sensors making it move forward. The toolkit detects the infrared light emitted by the fire with photo diode and sends signal to controller. The system works on real time, as it provides continuous monitoring. For detecting the fire in the peripheral region of robot, fire sensors are used, which helps in efficient working of the robot and to avoid damage to the robot.

REFERENCES

- [1] Jeelani, S., et al., Robotics and medicine: A scientific rainbow in hospital. Journal of Pharmacy & Bioallied Sciences, 2015. 7(Suppl 2): p.S381-S383.
- [2] Bugatha Ram Vara prasad, "Solar Powered BLDC Motor with HCC Fed Water Pumping System for Irrigation," Int. J. Res. Appl. Sci. Eng. Technol., vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 788-796, 2019,doi: 10.22214/ijraset.2019.3137.
- [3] Aliff, M., S. Dohata, and T. Akagi, Simple Trajectory Control Method of Robot Arm Using Flexible Pneumatic Cylinders. Journal of Robotics and Mechatronics, 2015. 27(6): p. 698-705.
- [4] Aliff M, D.S., and Akagi T, Control and analysis of simple-structured robot arm using flexible pneumatic cylinders. International Journal of Advanced and Applied Sciences, 2017. 4(12): p. 151-157.
- [5] Aliff, M., S. Dohata, and T. Akagi, Control and analysis of robot arm using flexible pneumatic cylinder. Mechanical Engineering Journal, 2014. 1(5): p. DR0051-DR0051.
- [6] Bugatha Ram Vara prasad, "HIGHWAY MONITORING SYSTEM AND POWER SAVING," vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 2270-2274, 2020.
- [7] M. Aliff, S. Dohata and T. Akagi, Trajectory controls and its analysis for robot arm using flexible pneumatic cylinders," IEEE International Symposium on Robotics and Intelligent Sensors (IRIS), 2015, pp. 48-54.
- [8] M. Aliff, S. Dohata and T. Akagi, Trajectory control of robot arm using flexible pneumatic cylinders and embedded controller, IEEE International Conference on Advanced Intelligent Mechatronics (AIM), 2015, pp. 1120-1125.
- [9] C. Xin, D. Qiao, S. Hongjie, L. Chunhe and Z. Haikuan, Design and Implementation of Debris Search and Rescue Robot System Based on Internet of Things, International Conference on Smart Grid and electrical Automation (ICSGEA), 2018, pp. 303-307.

AI DERMASCAN

¹Aiswarya S.M.

Department of Computer Science
and Engineering,
John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of
Technology Kannammoola,
Thiruvananthapuram, India.
aiswaryastephen2021@gmail.com

²Arsha S.T.

Department of Computer Science
and Engineering,
John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of
Technology Kannammoola,
Thiruvananthapuram, India.
arshast26@gmail.com

³Raji N.

Department of Computer Science
and Engineering,
John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of
Technology Kannammoola,
Thiruvananthapuram, India.
rajitn222@gmail.com

Abstract: Skin diseases affect millions worldwide, necessitating early detection and proper treatment to prevent complications. This project, "AI DermaScan," leverages deep learning techniques to assist in diagnosing skin conditions and recommending suitable treatments. A Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model is trained on a dataset of dermatological images to classify various skin diseases accurately. The system is integrated into a web-based platform with separate portals for patients, doctors, and administrators. Patients can upload images of skin conditions for analysis, while doctors can review diagnostic results, access patient data, and prescribe treatments. The admin portal manages system users and data. The backend is developed using Django with PostgreSQL for database management, ensuring secure and efficient data handling. The proposed system aims to enhance dermatological diagnosis accessibility, reduce misdiagnosis, and provide quick treatment recommendations. Experimental results demonstrate the model's effectiveness in identifying skin diseases, showcasing the potential of AI in dermatology.

Keywords— Skin disease prediction, Skin Disease Detection, Deep Learning, Convolutional Neural Network, AI in Healthcare, Django, Dermatology, Treatment Recommendation, HAM10000.

I. INTRODUCTION

Skin diseases affect millions of people worldwide, with conditions ranging from mild infections to severe dermatological disorders. Early and accurate diagnosis is essential for effective treatment, but access to dermatologists is often limited, especially in remote areas. Traditional diagnosis relies on manual examination, which can be time-consuming and prone to human errors. With advancements in artificial intelligence and machine learning, automated skin disease detection has gained significant attention. A machine learning-based approach can assist in early diagnosis, improve accuracy, and provide timely treatment recommendations.

This project aims to develop a web-based platform that leverages Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for automated skin disease prediction and treatment recommendations. The system will feature three separate portals for patients, doctors, and administrators. Patients can upload images of affected skin areas, and the AI model will analyze them to predict possible diseases. Doctors will have

access to a dedicated portal where they can review AI-generated results, validate the diagnosis, and prescribe appropriate medications. An admin portal will manage users and system operations. The project will utilize Python, Django, HTML, CSS, and a PostgreSQL database for efficient data storage and retrieval.

The proposed system enhances accessibility and accuracy in diagnosing skin conditions, offering a valuable AI-driven decision support system for dermatologists. By integrating deep learning with web technologies, the platform aims to reduce diagnosis time, assist healthcare professionals, and improve remote healthcare services. This project is particularly beneficial in regions with limited access to dermatologists, ensuring that patients receive timely and effective medical attention. Fig 1 represents the sample images of various skin types

Fig 1: Sample Skin Disease images

Notwithstanding, skin tainting with typical skin ought to be estimated in one line, as skin opposition might change in various lines. Skin calming and mitigating measures are unique, so it is feasible to analyze skin illnesses. An inaccurate electronic framework utilizing the above strategy comprises of two cathodes dependent on an earthenware plate. The wellspring of the cathode gives a little wellspring of skin, and the sink terminal gives input to the microcontroller. The length of the external terminal is 10 mm. Skin calming estimations can be utilized for sorrow, uneasiness, cerebral paralysis, and muscle harm.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

R.Sumithra et.al gives a better approach to quickly recognize and sort skin injuries. [1] The skin picture is first sifted to eliminate undesirable hair and clamor, then, at that point, decreased to isolating the harmed regions. Mahamad et.al gives the technique for expanding the region is utilized to begin the seed [2] right away. Division execution is estimated by an assortment of known techniques, and the outcomes are self-evident.

Mohammad Melanoma is one of the most well-known types of malignant growth. Notwithstanding [3], can mend a ton when it shows up in the beginning phases. Shadrokh Samavi describes It is vital to shield the shell from suspected harm. Identification should be possible with standard accounts, [4] which is fantastic as a result of its minimal expense and accessibility.

One of the main strides in examining a skin sore on a PC is to recognize the space of the injury, that is, to partition the picture into two sections, like a typical skin sore. Karimi record requires a profound way to deal with appropriately mining the region. [5] The embedded picture is handled and its parts are taken care of into a proper cylinder. Fathima explains the skin disease is a genuine medical condition that influences most of the populace, paying little heed to skin tone [6]. These impacts can be determined to have a dermo scope to decide whether apparent skin sores are harmless or threatening ,In spite of the fact that specialists are capable it is hard to list skin sores, so PC framework are intended to further develop malignant growth.

This framework assists with distinguishing skin malignant growth by creating advanced pictures to recognize clinically characterized tumors. Manishkumar describes the essentially founded on different useful medicines. [7] Two of the most widely recognized techniques for wound assessment are the ABCD and the 7-point list. Notwithstanding, the remarkable and broad limits. Jeffrey Glaister describes Melanoma is a strategy for killing skin disease when left untreated. Melanoma is on the ascent, particularly among youngsters, [8] yet its endurance rate is high when it is distinguished early.

Luckily, long haul care experts have a significant expense of diagnosing all patients with melanoma. Rakesh discusses extraordinary or costly gear. [9] One of the difficulties in executing the framework is distinguishing skin sores in advanced pictures. Sajitha expline the majority of the skin of the piece of the calculation is intended for imaging utilizing an extraordinary dermatoscope [10]. Advanced pictures, similar to shadows, have light changes that make it hard to decide the harm.

The purpose of this review was to foster a framework for swift remediation. Satish discusses Melanoma is a strategy for killing skin disease when left untreated [11]. Melanoma is on the ascent, particularly among youngsters, yet its endurance rate is high when it is distinguished early. Luckily, long haul care experts have a significant expense of diagnosing all patients with melanoma. Raorane explains the initial segment of the examination is to configuration light changes utilizing the projected enlightenment calculation [12], and afterward alter the main picture utilizing a model, Our review depended on pictures from the ISIC data set.

Ramesh kumar explains Dermatology assessment is one of the main issues in the field of finding [13]. Different skin illnesses, like dry skin, organisms, and sensitivity manifestations, affect human wellbeing. The motivation behind this paper is to investigate skin illnesses utilizing skin examination. Nadhal states reviews fostered a technique for diagnosing skin sicknesses. [14] The framework was utilized to analyze psoriasis.This review depends on skin tone and surface (qualities from GLCM) for a superior and more precise conclusion of skin sickness. Jafari,Ebrahim Nasr-Esfahani, Nader Karimi, S.M. states the neural organization to make an image [15] that could communicate irresistible psoriasis or non-irresistible psoriasis. This framework has yielded extremely intriguing outcomes with regards to the preparation of the overall organization of muscles and eyes.

III Materials and methodology

3.1 Architecture

The System Architecture represents a Machine Learning-Based Skin Disease Detection and Treatment Recommendation System, involving three main user roles: Patients, Doctors, and Admins. Patients interact with the system through a visual interface, where they upload an input image of the affected skin area. The system stores their medical records and treatment history for reference. The uploaded image undergoes pre-processing, including image resizing and normalization, followed by segmentation to isolate the affected region. Important features such as texture and color are extracted for classification. These features are then processed by a CNN-based classifier, where a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), such as VGG16, predicts the skin disease. The diagnosis is sent to the Doctor's Portal, where doctors can review the AI-generated results and prescribe appropriate treatments. The Admin manages the database, which securely stores patient and doctor information. The system also maintains a training model, which continuously updates to improve classification accuracy.

Fig 2: Architecture Diagram

3.2 CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK (CNN) ALGORITHM

STEP 1: Preprocessing

Dropping the duplicate images by using the lesion ids and resizing of images by a factor of 0.25.

STEP 2: Data splitting

Splitting the dataset in to 80:20(training: testing)

STEP 3: Feature extraction

1. *Convolutional Layer: Extract the image features by applying convolutions of different sizes.*
2. *Pooling Layer: Perform Pooling to reduce the high-dimensional feature map.*
3. *Flatten Layer: Flatten the feature map into a single-dimensional vector to pass it to the classification*

STEP 4: Data augmentation

Every individual image will be augmented in every epoch to reduce the overfitting.

STEP 5: Classification

3.4 Data Collection

Our dataset comprises of about 3000 images that we gathered from numerous websites that are devoted to skin illnesses and their treatment in order to be as accurate and realistic as possible, including Beni-Suef University Hospital, Cairo University Hospital, and others. The information has been divided into 2 elements, coaching set and taking a look at sets. The coaching set information is used to coach our model, therefore looking at the set is used to determine whether or not our model is operating wisely.

The categories of diseases to be trained for in each of them are then used to classify our dataset into a variety of elements. Fig 3 shows the However within future updates add several alternative diseases solutions that are growing. Fig 3 shows the dataset on the different skin diseases.

Disease	Sample Image	No. of Images
Cellulitis		136
Impetigo		80
Athlete-foot		124
Nail-fungus		129
Ringworm		90
Cutaneous-larva-migrans		100
Chickenpox		136
Shingles		130

Fig 3 Skin disease dataset

3.4 MODULES OF THE APPLICATION

- Machine Learning Module
- Admin Module
- Doctor Module
- Patient Module

a) Machine Learning Module

The trained Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model will predict the type of skin disease based on the input image. The prediction will be a classification output indicating the type of skin disease (e.g., acne, eczema, melanoma, etc.).

Fig 3.4.1 Input symptoms

b) Admin Module

Manage user accounts, monitor system performance and data analytics, update machine learning models as needed.

c) Doctor Module

Doctors can access patient data, review the AI-generated diagnosis, and provide additional medical advice or modify treatment recommendations. They can prescribe medicines based on the model's predictions and their expertise.

Fig 3.4.2 Doctor page

d) Patient Module

Patients can register, log in, and upload images of their skin conditions. The trained CNN model processes these images and provides an initial diagnosis along with recommended treatments. Patients can also view their diagnosis history and receive prescriptions from doctors.

Fig 3.4.3 Consultation page

IV. RESULT

The Machine Learning-Based Skin Disease Detection System using VGG16 CNN achieved over 90% accuracy, ensuring reliable classification. Preprocessing techniques like resizing, normalization, and augmentation improved performance. Integrated into Doctor and Patient Portals, the system enables real-time diagnosis and treatment

recommendations. While challenges like misclassification of similar diseases exist

V. Conclusion

The Machine Learning-Based Skin Disease Detection and Treatment Recommendation System successfully integrates deep learning and web-based healthcare solutions to enhance dermatological diagnosis. The system leverages CNN (VGG16) for accurate disease classification and provides separate portals for Patients, Doctors, and Admins, ensuring a seamless workflow. The model achieved over 90% classification accuracy, demonstrating its reliability in identifying various skin diseases. Key preprocessing techniques, including image resizing, normalization, segmentation, and augmentation, significantly improved model performance.

The system's real-world impact is evident through its ability to assist doctors in reviewing AI-generated diagnoses and prescribing appropriate treatments, improving patient accessibility to dermatological healthcare. By providing real-time disease detection, the platform enables early diagnosis and reduces the risk of misclassification. However, some challenges remain, such as the difficulty in distinguishing between visually similar skin diseases and the need for a more diverse dataset to improve model generalization.

REFERENCES

- [1] Sumithra Ra, MahamadSuhilb, D.S.Guruc, " Segmentation and Classification of Skin Lesions for Disease Diagnosis", doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2015.03.090, 2015.
- [2] Mohammad H. Jafari, Ebrahim Nasr-Esfahani, Nader Karimi, S.M. Reza Soroushmehr, ShadrokhSamavi, KayvanNajarian, " Extraction of Skin Lesions from Non-Dermoscopic Images Using Deep Learning", ResearchGate, September 2016.
- [3] Manish Kumar and Rajiv Kumar, " AN INTELLIGENT SYSTEM TO DIAGNOSIS THE SKIN DISEASE", VOL. 11, NO. 19, OCTOBER 2016.
- [4] JerreyGlaister, " Automatic segmentation of skin lesions from dermatological photograph", Waterloo, Ontario, Canada, 2013.
- [5] K.Indupriya, Dr. G. P. Ramesh Kumar, " A Survey On Skin Texture Analysis For Medical Diagnosis Using Image Processing Techniques", K. Indupriya Et Al. Volume 3 Issue 5, 2015.
- [6] MdNafiulAlam, TamannaTabassum Khan Munia, KouhyarTavakolian, Vasefi, Nick MacKinnon, Reza Fazel-Rezai, "Automatic Detection and Severity Measurement of Eczema Using Image Processing", IEEE, 2016

[7] R. Yasir, M. S. I. Nibir, and N. Ahmed, "A skin disease detection system for financially unstable people in developing countries," *Global Science and Technology Journal*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 77–93, 2015.

[8] Kumar, V., Kumar, S., & Saboo, V. (2016) "Dermatological Disease Detection Using Image Processing and Machine Learning." IEEE.

[9] S. Kumar and A. Singh, "Image processing for recognition of skin diseases," *International Journal of Computer Applications*, vol. 149, no. 3, pp. 37–40, 2016.

[10] Dawid Połap,* Alicja Winnicka, Kalina Serwata, Karolina Kęsik, and Marcin Woźniak et al. An Intelligent System for Monitoring Skin diseases. Published online 4 August 2018, DOI: 10.3390/s18082552

[11] Z. Hu and C. S. Yu, "Functional research and development of skin barrier", *Chinese Journal of clinicians*, vol. 7, no. 7, pp. 3101- 3103, 2013

[12] Nidhal K. Al Abbadi, Nizar Saadi Dahir, Muhsin A. AL-Dhalimi and Hind Restom, "Psoriasis Detection Using Skin Colour and Texture Features", *Journal of Computer Science* 6 (6): 626- 630, 2010, ISSN 1549-3636, © 2010 Science Publications

[13] Megha D. Tijare, Dr. V. T. Gaikwad et al. "Detecting skin disease by accurate skin segmentation using various color spaces" Published 2018 in *Journal of Engineering Research and application*.

[14] Ekta Singhal, Skin Cancer Detection using Artificial Neural Network, *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science* Volume 6, No. 1, Jan-Feb 2015.

[15] Manish Kumar and Rajiv Kumar, An intelligent system to diagnosis the skin disease, *ARPJ Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences* VOL. 11, NO. 19, OCTOBER 2016 ISSN 1819 -6608.

Biometric Attendance System using Arduino

Anand A , Saju R, Vishnupriya Sujith

Mrs. TINTU S S (ASST. PROFESSOR ECE)

Department of Electronic And Communication Engineering, JCMCSIT, Kannammoola

Abstract— A fingerprint attendance system automates attendance tracking in educational institutions using biometric technology, eliminating manual roll calls and human errors. A handheld device allows students to mark their presence by scanning their fingerprints, ensuring accurate and fraud-proof attendance logging. The system uses an Arduino UNO as the central controller, interfacing with a DS3231 RTC module for time display, a 16×2 I2C LCD for feedback, LEDs, a buzzer, and four push buttons for control. The IoT-based design ensures efficiency, security, and ease of use by directly storing attendance data without manual input. Biometric verification prevents proxy attendance and enhances security. The system is versatile for both students and employees, providing reliability across institutions. It records fingerprint identification accuracy and processing time to improve performance. Testing confirms high accuracy and fast recognition speeds. The system enhances time efficiency and user satisfaction. It provides a secure, foolproof, and automated solution for attendance management, saving time and reducing errors.

Keywords — *Arduino Uno, ESP8266, R307 Fingerprint module, 16X2 I2C LCD Display, Push Button*

I. INTRODUCTION

A secure identity management system is essential for an effective attendance system. Traditional methods like manual registers, passwords, or ID cards are prone to fraud and inefficiency. Biometric authentication, using fingerprints, facial recognition, or iris scans, provides a unique and tamper-proof way to verify identities. Unlike passwords or ID cards, biometric identifiers cannot be forgotten, stolen, or duplicated, ensuring higher security. This project develops a fingerprint-based attendance system using Arduino for faster and more reliable user verification. A fingerprint sensor integrated with an Arduino microcontroller ensures accurate identification before marking attendance. This prevents proxy attendance, buddy punching, and unauthorized access. The system enhances data accuracy, security, and efficiency in attendance tracking. It is suitable for workplaces, educational institutions, and secure areas. The system automates attendance management, reducing fraud and improving reliability.

II. EXISTING SYSTEM

The previous attendance system relied on traditional methods such as manual registers, passwords, or ID cards. These

methods were prone to fraud, manipulation, and inefficiency. Manual registers required significant time and effort, often leading to human errors and inaccurate records. ID cards and passwords could be lost, forgotten, or shared, making it easy for students or employees to engage in proxy attendance. Additionally, these systems lacked real-time authentication, it difficult to ensure genuine attendance. These disadvantages led to the development of our fingerprint-based attendance system, which enhances security, accuracy, and efficiency through biometric authentication.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The system proposed a secure and automated method for recording attendance via fingerprint authentication. The fingerprint module scans and verifies the user's fingerprint against stored templates, granting or denying access accordingly. A 16×2 LCD displays real-time feedback, while LEDs and a buzzer indicate authentication success or failure. The system includes four push buttons for enrolling, deleting, and navigating stored fingerprints. An ESP8266 Wi-Fi module enables real-time data logging to web page for remote monitoring. Serial communication allows debugging and live attendance tracking via a PC. It eliminates manual attendance errors, prevents fraud, ensures real-time monitoring, and enhances record-keeping accuracy.

IV. HARDWARE

Arduino Uno, ESP8266, R307 Fingerprint module, DS3231 RTC module, 16x2 I2C LCD Display, Push button

A. *Arduino Uno*

The ATmega328 Controller is an open-source controller board based on the Arduino.cc ATmega328 microchip controller. The board is equipped with sets of digital and analog input / output (I/O) pins that can be interfaced with different boards (shields) for expansion and other circuits. The board has 14 digital pins, 6 analog pins and is programmable via a type B USB cable with the Arduino IDE (Integrated Development Environment). It can be powered by a USB cable or by an external 9 Volt battery, but it accepts voltages between 7 and 20 volts. It's similar with Arduino Nano and Leonardo, too. Distributed under a Creative Common Attribution Share-Alike 2.5 license, the hardware reference design is available on the Arduino website. The ATmega328 comes pre-programmed with a boot loader that enables new code to be uploaded to it without using an external hardware programmer

The ESP8266 is a low-cost Wi-Fi module that enables wireless communication between the Arduino Uno and cloud services. In this biometric attendance system, it transmits attendance data in real time, allowing remote monitoring and management. Upon successful fingerprint authentication, the Arduino sends user details to the ESP8266 via serial communication, which then connects to Wi-Fi and updates Google Sheets via HTTP requests. This eliminates the need for physical storage, ensures real-time synchronization, and enhances system automation, efficiency, and reliability in attendance tracking.

C. R307 Fingerprint module

The R307 is an optical fingerprint sensor module designed for biometric authentication, offering reliable and accurate recognition. It features an optical sensor, DSP processor, and advanced algorithms for fingerprint enrollment, image processing, and matching (1:1 and 1:N). Capturing high-resolution images (500 DPI), it stores up to 1,000 fingerprint templates. With low power consumption (50mA), it suits battery-powered devices. Commonly used in access control, attendance tracking, and security systems, the R307 ensures efficient and secure biometric authentication.

D. DS3231 RTC Module

The DS3231 is a precise I²C real-time clock (RTC) module with a built-in temperature-compensated crystal oscillator (TCXO) for high accuracy. It maintains consistent timekeeping by adjusting for temperature variations and includes a battery backup to retain time during power loss. Widely used in data logging, clocks, and embedded systems, its reliability and precision make it ideal for applications requiring continuous and accurate timekeeping.

F. 16x2 I2C LCD Display

The 16x2 I2C LCD is a compact display used in the biometric attendance system to show real-time messages like "Place Finger" and "Access Granted." Unlike standard LCDs, it reduces wiring complexity by using only two pins (SDA & SCL) via the PCF8574 I2C expander. This enhances system efficiency, simplifies circuit design, and improves user interaction by providing instant authentication feedback.

G. Push Button

Push-buttons are simple switches used for system control. The **Register/Back Button** enrolls new fingerprints and navigates back or cancels actions. The **Delete/OK Button** removes stored fingerprints and confirms selections. The **Forward Button** moves through memory slots in ascending order, while the **Reverse Button** navigates in descending order.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

The biometric attendance system using Arduino Uno is designed to provide a secure and automated method for recording attendance using fingerprint authentication. The process begins with the fingerprint module, which captures and scans the user's fingerprint. The scanned fingerprint is then compared against pre-stored templates in the module's memory. If a match is found, the Arduino Uno processes the authentication result and proceeds with attendance marking; otherwise, access is denied. Upon successful authentication, the 16x2 LCD display provides real-time feedback to the user by displaying messages such as "Access Granted" or "Attendance Marked." If the fingerprint is not recognized, it shows "Access Denied," indicating an unsuccessful attempt. To enhance user interaction, the system includes keys/buttons that allow for additional functionalities like manual attendance input, resetting, or switching operational modes. For a better user experience, LEDs and a buzzer act as feedback indicators. A green LED turning on or a buzzer sound signifies a successful authentication, whereas a red LED and a different buzzer pattern indicate an unsuccessful attempt. The system further integrates the ESP8266 Wi-Fi module, which enables internet connectivity. This module transmits attendance records to web page, ensuring real-time data logging and remote monitoring. This feature is particularly useful for centralized attendance tracking in workplaces, schools, or organizations. Additionally, the system supports serial communication with a PC for debugging and monitoring purposes. Using the Serial Monitor, administrators can track attendance logs in real time and troubleshoot any issues. This biometric attendance system is a robust, reliable, and efficient solution that eliminates traditional manual attendance methods, reduces fraud, and enhances record-keeping accuracy. We have used 4 push buttons. The functions of each button are: Register/Back Button: Used for enrolling new fingerprint as well as reversing the back process or going back Delete/OK Button: This Button is used for deleting the earlier stored fingerprint system as well as granting access as an OK selection. Forward Button: Used for moving forward while selecting the memory location for storing or deleting fingerprints. Reverse Button: Used for moving backward while selecting memory location for storing or deleting fingerprints

VI. BLOCK DIAGRAM

VII. FLOW CHART

VIII. CONCLUSION

The development of a Biometric Attendance System using Arduino has effectively addressed the limitations of traditional attendance tracking methods by introducing a secure, efficient, and user-friendly solution. By leveraging fingerprint recognition technology, the system ensures accurate identification of individuals, thereby eliminating issues such as buddy punching and unauthorized access. The integration of the fingerprint sensor with the Arduino microcontroller facilitates real-time authentication, while the use of EEPROM ensures reliable data storage. The addition of the ESP8266 module enables seamless data transmission to platforms allowing attendance records to be viewed in web page. This integration not only streamlines the attendance management process but also enhances data accessibility and analysis. The successful implementation of this system demonstrates the potential of combining biometric technology with microcontroller-based platforms to create cost effective and scalable solutions for attendance management. Such systems can be widely adopted in educational institutions, corporate environments, and other organizations requiring precise attendance monitoring. Future enhancements could include integrating additional biometric modalities, such as facial recognition, to further improve security and user convenience. Moreover, expanding the system's capabilities to include real-time notifications and integration with existing organizational databases could provide a more comprehensive attendance management solution. In conclusion, the Biometric Attendance System using Arduino represents a significant advancement over manual attendance methods, offering a reliable, secure, and efficient alternative that aligns with modern technological trends.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We are grateful to the Department of electronics and communication, JCMCSIT, Kannammoola for inspiring the project.

REFERENCES

- [1] EPIC-Electronic Privacy Information Centre (2002): "National ID Cards, accessed January, 2012.
- [2] Kadry S. and Smaili M. (2010): Wireless Attendance Management System based on Iris Recognition. Scientific Research and Essays. Vol. 5(12), pp. 1428-1435, 18 June, 2010. [
- [3] Khan B., Khan M. K. and Alghathbar K. S. (2010): Biometrics and identity management for homeland security applications in Saudi Arabia. African Journal of Business Management Vol. 4(15), pp. 3296-3306, 4 November, 2010.
- [4] Bevan S and Hayday S. (1998): Attendance Management: a Review of Good Practice Report 353, Institute for Employment Studies.
- [5] McKeehan D.A. (2002): Attendance Management Program, The City of Pleasanton, Human Resources

CIPHER CLOUD

Allen Kuruvilla, Arun T. Paulose,
A.S. Abhaya, Jobin Mathew

from John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of Technology
Affiliated to APJ Abdul Kalam Technological University

Abstract— This paper presents that in the era of cloud computing, dynamic access control and efficient user revocation mechanisms are essential for ensuring data security and integrity. Existing systems for Revocable Attribute-Based Encryption (RABE) often struggle with maintaining data integrity after user revocation and cause increased computational overhead. We propose an Efficient Revocable Fully Attribute-Based Message Encryption (RFAME) scheme, which ensures secure access control, robust user revocation, and data integrity. Security is validated through semantic security analysis, and experimental results demonstrate improved efficiency. The scheme integrates a secure public key infrastructure (PKI), cryptographic hashing, fingerprint authentication, and backward secrecy for secure data management in cloud environments.

Keywords— Cloud security, Attribute-Based Encryption, Revocation, Data Integrity, Cryptography, IOT Devices

I. INTRODUCTION

Cloud computing offers scalable storage solutions but raises security concerns regarding data integrity, access control, and user revocation. As organizations and individuals increasingly rely on cloud services, ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of data has become a crucial challenge. Data breaches, unauthorized access, and inefficient revocation mechanisms expose sensitive information to potential threats. To address these issues, encryption-based security solutions have been widely adopted. However, conventional encryption models struggle with dynamic user access, requiring re-encryption upon revocation, leading to inefficiencies and computational overhead.

Attribute-Based Encryption (ABE) has emerged as a promising approach for fine-grained access control, allowing users to be granted access based on defined attributes rather than static keys. Despite its advantages, existing ABE-based schemes face limitations in handling user revocation efficiently, often requiring the re-encryption of large datasets when access rights change. This process can be time-consuming and resource-intensive, particularly in large-scale cloud environments.

Our proposed RFAME scheme enhances security while reducing computational overhead, making cloud storage more resilient to unauthorized access and revocation issues. By integrating cryptographic techniques such as secure hashing, public key infrastructure (PKI), and biometric authentication, RFAME provides an efficient and scalable encryption model. Furthermore, it ensures that revoked users cannot regain access while maintaining the

integrity of stored data. This paper discusses the challenges of cloud security, the limitations of existing encryption schemes, and how RFAME addresses these issues through an optimized revocation and access control framework.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Our RFAME scheme introduces improvements in:

- **Efficient Access Control:** Uses an advanced attribute-based encryption model to control access dynamically.
- **Revocation Mechanism:** Delegates revocation to the cloud, reducing computational load on data owners.
- **Data Integrity Verification:** Uses SHA-256 cryptographic hashing to verify data authenticity after revocation.
- **Authentication Enhancement:** Incorporates biometric fingerprint authentication for secure user access.

The proposed system consists of:

- 1) **Authority Center (AC):** Generates master keys and public parameters.
- 2) **Data Owner (DO):** Encrypts data using access control policies.
- 3) **Cloud Server (CS):** Stores encrypted data and manages revocation.
- 4) **Data User (DU):** Decrypts data based on valid attribute-based credentials.

Backward secrecy ensure that revoked users cannot access previously stored data, and new users can be seamlessly integrated without re-encryption.

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology of the RFAME system involves the following phases:

1. Key Generation and Distribution

The Authority Center generates cryptographic key pairs and distributes public keys to authorized users. The key generation process is based on attribute-based encryption principles, ensuring that keys align with access control policies. A combination of symmetric and asymmetric cryptographic techniques is employed to optimize key management and ensure secure distribution.

2. Data Encryption and Storage

Before uploading data to the cloud, the Data Owner encrypts it using attribute-based encryption. The encryption policy defines which users can access the data based on their attributes. The encrypted data is then stored in the cloud server along with cryptographic hashes for integrity verification. The encryption process follows an efficient

hybrid model, combining symmetric encryption (for data security) and asymmetric encryption (for key distribution).

3. User Authentication and Access Control

When a user attempts to access data, they must authenticate themselves using biometric fingerprint verification. Once authenticated, the system checks the user's attributes against the encryption policy. If the attributes match, the user is granted access and can proceed with decryption. Multi-factor authentication mechanisms, including OTP-based verification, are incorporated to further enhance security.

4. User Revocation Mechanism

User revocation is handled by updating the cloud's revocation list. Once a user is revoked, they lose access to previously accessible files without affecting other users. The revocation process is optimized to prevent unnecessary re-encryption of large datasets. The system dynamically updates attribute policies and generates new revocation tokens to ensure seamless access control enforcement.

5. Data Integrity Verification

To ensure that stored data remains unaltered, cryptographic hash functions (SHA-256) are used. Each file's hash value is computed at the time of upload and compared with the hash upon retrieval. If any tampering is detected, access is denied, and an alert is generated. The system integrates blockchain-based verification to maintain an immutable log of data integrity checks, ensuring transparency and security.

6. Performance Optimization

To reduce computational overhead, the RFAME system employs optimization techniques such as batch encryption, parallel processing, and cloud-based computation offloading. These techniques improve efficiency by reducing encryption and decryption time while ensuring secure data processing in real-time cloud environments.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

Our scheme is tested against existing models based on:

- **Encryption/Decryption Time:** Demonstrates reduced computational overhead compared to traditional RABE schemes.
- **Revocation Efficiency:** Revocation is handled without requiring extensive re-encryption.
- **Integrity Verification:** Hashing mechanisms ensure data remains untampered post-revocation.

Experimental results indicate that our RFAME scheme achieves higher efficiency and security than existing RABE models.

V. LITERATURE REVIEW

Various encryption models have been studied for secure cloud access. Attribute-Based Encryption (ABE) has been widely used for fine-grained access control. Hierarchical Identity-Based Encryption (HIBE) allows flexible key delegation. However, these schemes do not efficiently handle dynamic user revocation. The use of PKI for secure key management and cryptographic hashing for data integrity has been explored in, forming the basis of our proposed scheme.

1. Attribute-Based Encryption for Secure Cloud Storage

The concept of Attribute-Based Encryption (ABE) has been widely explored in cloud computing for ensuring fine-grained access control. Goyal et al. introduced a foundational ABE model that allows access control policies to be defined over attributes rather than individual users [1]. The study highlighted the advantages of ABE in securing cloud data but also noted limitations in handling user revocation efficiently.

2. Revocable Attribute-Based Encryption (RABE)

Yu et al. proposed a Revocable Attribute-Based Encryption (RABE) scheme that integrates attribute revocation mechanisms [2]. Their work improved upon traditional ABE by introducing dynamic key updates for revoked users, ensuring that users who lose access cannot retrieve previously available data. However, their approach introduced significant computational overhead due to frequent re-encryption.

3. Hierarchical Identity-Based Encryption (HIBE)

Hierarchical Identity-Based Encryption (HIBE) was introduced by Boneh and Franklin as an alternative approach for managing encryption keys efficiently [3]. HIBE allows hierarchical delegation of decryption rights, making it useful in large-scale enterprise environments. However, its applicability to cloud-based access control is limited due to the complexity of key management and security vulnerabilities in dynamic cloud environments.

4. Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) and Cloud Security

A study by Rivest et al. explored the integration of Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) in cloud-based encryption frameworks [4]. PKI ensures secure key distribution and authentication, addressing issues related to identity verification in cloud environments. However, PKI alone does not offer efficient attribute-based access control, necessitating the combination of ABE with PKI for enhanced security.

5. Cryptographic Hashing for Data Integrity

To maintain data integrity, various cryptographic hashing techniques have been explored. Menezes et al. proposed SHA-based hashing mechanisms that ensure data integrity in cloud storage systems [5]. Their study demonstrated that secure hashing can detect unauthorized modifications to cloud data, but it does not provide access control, requiring integration with encryption schemes for comprehensive security.

6. Biometric Authentication for Secure Cloud Access

Recent research by Jain et al. highlighted the advantages of biometric authentication in cloud security [6]. Fingerprint and facial recognition technologies provide enhanced security by ensuring that only authorized users can access cloud data. However, biometric authentication must be combined with cryptographic encryption techniques to prevent unauthorized decryption in case of compromised biometric data.

VI. CONCLUSION

CIPHER CLOUD provides a comprehensive and efficient solution to the challenges of secure cloud storage, access control, and data integrity. As organizations

increasingly rely on cloud-based services, ensuring secure and scalable access to sensitive data has become a priority. The Efficient Revocable Fully Attribute-Based Message Encryption (RFAME) scheme enhances security, flexibility, and efficiency, overcoming the limitations of traditional encryption models, which often suffer from high computational costs and complex revocation processes.

Unlike conventional schemes that require re-encryption when revoking user access, CIPHER CLOUD delegates revocation management to the cloud server, ensuring immediate access removal without disrupting authorized users. This reduces operational complexity and minimizes performance overhead, making access control more scalable and efficient. To further enhance data security, CIPHER CLOUD integrates cryptographic hashing techniques to verify data integrity, ensuring that any unauthorized modifications or corruption are promptly detected.

Additionally, Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) is used for secure key management, preventing unauthorized access to encryption keys. These security measures fortify cloud-based access control, protecting sensitive information from cyber threats. A key feature of the RFAME scheme is its backward secrecy, which allows new users to access previously encrypted data without requiring re-encryption. This significantly enhances scalability and efficiency, reducing computational overhead while allowing seamless user onboarding. Moreover, biometric authentication, such as fingerprint recognition, is integrated to provide enhanced security against unauthorized access, offering a more secure alternative to password-based authentication.

Through extensive testing, CIPHER CLOUD has demonstrated superior encryption, decryption, and revocation performance, outperforming traditional models in execution speed, security, and scalability. Future enhancements will focus on fine-grained revocation mechanisms and advanced cryptographic techniques, ensuring even greater security, flexibility, and efficiency for cloud-based access control systems.

VII. FUTUREWORK

One of the key areas for future development is the introduction of dynamic attribute updates, which would allow users to modify their attribute sets or permissions in real-time without requiring the re-encryption of existing data. This enhancement would significantly improve the flexibility of access control, ensuring that any changes in user roles or permissions are immediately reflected without disrupting system operations. More importantly, this feature would not compromise the security of stored data, nor would it introduce the overhead of time-consuming re-encryption processes. By enabling real-time updates to user attributes, the system would become more adaptable to evolving organizational structures and security requirements.

Another promising direction for improvement involves the integration of privacy preserving techniques for attribute-based policies. In existing attribute-based encryption schemes, user attributes—such as roles or organizational hierarchies—can sometimes be exposed to the cloud provider, creating potential privacy concerns. By

incorporating privacy-preserving methods, future iterations of the system could ensure that these attributes remain confidential, even from the cloud service itself. This would prevent unauthorized access to sensitive attribute information and further strengthen user privacy. Enhancing attribute confidentiality would add an additional layer of security, ensuring that even cloud administrators cannot infer details about user roles or access privileges.

Furthermore, extending the system to support cross-cloud interoperability would be a crucial advancement. Many organizations rely on multiple cloud service providers for data storage and management, making it essential to establish a secure and unified access control mechanism across different cloud environments. By implementing cross-cloud compatibility, users would be able to securely store, share, and manage data across multiple cloud platforms while maintaining consistent security policies. This feature would be particularly beneficial for enterprises that utilize hybrid or multi-cloud infrastructures, ensuring seamless and secure data exchange across diverse cloud services without compromising security or performance. These enhancements would collectively contribute to making the RABE-DI system more efficient, scalable, and privacy centric, addressing existing limitations while paving the way for future advancements in cloud-based encryption and access control.

VIII. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to express their gratitude to the faculty and staff of John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of Technology for their guidance. Special thanks to our project advisor, Mrs. Saaji S. J., for her invaluable support.

REFERENCES

- [1] Teles, A., Cagy, M., & Silva, F. (2017). "Using Brain- Computer Interface and IoT for Smart Wheelchair Control." *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems & Rehabilitation Engineering*.
- [2] Kumar, R., & Singh, M. (2018). "Gesture Recognition for Smart Wheelchair Navigation." *IEEE Sensors Journal*.
- [3] D'Souza, D. J., Srivastava, S., & Prithika, R. (2019). "IoT-Based Smart Wheelchair for Health Monitoring." *International Conference on Biomedical Engineering*.
- [4] Pawar, S., Kanade, Y., & Singh, H. (2021). "Autonomous Wheelchair with AI-Based Navigation." *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*.
- [5] Pushpa, D., & Vijayalakshmi, K. (2022). "Voice-Controlled Wheelchair: IoT Integration and Safety Features." *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*.
- [6] Sri, D., & Kanuri, R. K. (2023). "Fall Detection and Emergency Alert System for Smart Wheelchairs." *IEEE Transactions on Mechatronics*.
- [7] Chen, Y., & Wu, X. (2023). "Deep Learning-Based Smart Wheelchair for Healthcare Applications." *Journal of Medical Internet Research*.

- [8] Gupta, A., & Raman, S. (2024). "Sensor-Based Mobility Aids: A Review of Assistive Technologies." IEEE Access.
- [9] H.Cui,R.H.Deng,G.Wu, andJ.Lai, "Anefficient andexpressive ciphertext-policyattribute basedencryptionschemewithpartiallyhid denaccessstructures,"inInternationalConferenceonProvableSecurity.Springer,2016,
- [10] Nik-U, "Pbcpackage," <https://github.com/Nik-U/pbc>,2015.
- [11] B. Lynn et al., "Pbc library,"Online: <http://crypto.stanford.edu/pbc>, 2006.
- [12] S.Hohenberger andB.Waters, "Attribute-based encryptionwith fast decryption," in InternationalWorkshoponPublicKeyCryptography. Springer,2013, pp.
- [13] B.Waters,"Ciphertext-policyattribute-basedencryption:Anexpressive, efficient, andprovablysecure realization,"LectureNotes inComputer Science,vol.2008,pp, 2011.

Design and Development of Safety Pod for Rescue Operations During Natural Disasters

Sheba O S
Dept. of Electrical & Electronics Engineering
JCMCSIIT, Kannammoola, TVM
TVM, INDIA
Email: - shebakjm1234@gmail.com

Dr. Lim J Seelan
Associate Professor
Dept. of Electrical & Electronics Engineering
JCMCSIIT, Kannammoola, TVM
Email: - limseelan@gmail.com

Abstract—This project presents the development of a Smart Sleeping Pod designed to enhance personal safety during natural calamities such as earthquakes. The pod integrates advanced technologies, including an ESP32 CAM, GSM, GPS modules, ESP8266 and ATmega 328P microcontrollers, an earthquake sensor, and a load cell. These components work together to monitor the environment and ensure occupant safety in emergency situations. In the event of a detected threat, such as seismic activity or hazardous air quality, the pod automatically seals its door to provide a protective enclosure. The system also checks whether the user is inside the pod; if not, an alert is sent to their phone, urging them to return for safety. The pod is equipped with food and water storage, calibrated based on its size, ensuring that occupants can remain inside for extended periods. For realtime emergency responses, the pod sends GPS coordinates and live images to rescue teams, ensuring the prompt location of the user. Powered by a battery system optimized for the pod's size, the sleeping pod is designed to be self-sustaining during critical times. This innovative approach combines comfort, technology, and safety to provide a comprehensive solution for survival during natural disasters.

Keywords— safety pod; rescue operations; natural disasters; structural design; communication systems; emergency shelter.

I. INTRODUCTION

Smart Sleeping Pods provide personal safety during natural disasters, like earthquakes, with innovative technologies. Equipped with earthquake sensors, pods automatically seal doors and create protective enclosures during seismic activity. Pods monitor occupancy and alert users via mobile devices if they're outside during a crisis. Built-in food and water storage sustains occupants for extended periods. GPS coordinates and live images are sent to rescue teams for prompt location and risk assessment. Self-sustaining battery system ensures uninterrupted operation during emergencies. Pods provide comprehensive survival solutions, combining comfort, technology, and safety. Advanced monitoring systems and alerts enhance user safety and rescue response times.

Smart Sleeping Pods exemplify human ingenuity in developing safety technologies for natural disaster resilience. These pods are typically designed to be compact, durable, and easily deployable in high-risk areas. The materials used in constructing these safety enclosures are selected for their strength and resistance to impact, pressure, and moisture, ensuring that they can withstand the destructive forces of natural disasters. In addition to structural resilience, the design must also incorporate essential life-support features, such as air filtration, water purification systems, and emergency supplies like food, first aid kits, and communication devices. Furthermore, safety pods can be equipped with GPS tracking systems to allow rescuers to locate them swiftly, even when communication networks are down.

Innovative approaches in safety pod development also consider the need for modular and scalable solutions. Pods can be designed in various sizes to accommodate individuals, families, or groups of people, and they can be stacked or linked together to form larger survival shelters. The incorporation of renewable energy sources like solar panels can ensure that the pods remain functional over extended periods in the absence of conventional power sources. Additionally, ergonomic and user-friendly designs ensure that individuals with no prior training can operate and take refuge within them quickly during emergencies. A well individuals caught in these perilous situations. In summary, the development of safety pods offers a vital tool in enhancing disaster preparedness and response strategies.

II. DESIGN PARAMETERS AND REQUIREMENTS

A. Structural Integrity

The safety pod must be able to withstand extreme environmental conditions such as heavy winds, flooding, and debris. The design incorporates high-strength, lightweight materials that can provide adequate protection against impact, thermal extremes, and water penetration. Composite materials such as carbon fiber and reinforced polymers have

been considered for their excellent strength-to-weight ratios and durability.

B. Mobility and Ease of Deployment

Given the unpredictable nature of natural disasters, the safety pod should be easily portable by rescue teams and can be deployed rapidly in a variety of environments. This includes incorporating a foldable design for easy transportation and a quick setup mechanism that minimizes the time required for deployment. The use of pneumatic inflation systems for quick assembly has been explored.

C. Self-Sustaining Capabilities

The safety pod is designed to provide essential services to its occupants for a period of 72 hours or more. This includes:

1. Food and Water Storage
2. Temperature and Humidity Sensor

D. Communication Systems

The safety pod will feature an integrated communication system that allows survivors to send distress signals and receive updates from rescue teams. This system may include satellite phones, GPS locators, and emergency beacon transmitters.

III. DEVELOPMENT AND PROTOTYPING

A. Materials selection

The initial phase of development focused on selecting the appropriate materials for the safety pod's construction. The chosen materials must balance durability, weight, and cost. A combination of 4X Sheet and Aluminium for structural parts offers a strong and lightweight solution and foam sheet for bed inside the pod. The main components are ESP32 CAM, GSM, GPS modules, ESP8266 and ATmega 328P microcontrollers, an earthquake sensor, Temperature and humidity sensor and a load cell.

B. Testing and Evaluation

In the final stages of development, a fully functional prototype was subjected to real-world conditions to evaluate its usability and performance. This testing involved setting up the pod in disaster scenarios and assessing how well it provides shelter, protection, and communication for users.

Figure 1 Prototype

IV. BLOCK DIAGRAM

Figure 2 Block diagram

The microcontroller serves as the central processing unit that manages data flow between all connected sensors, modules, and actuators. It reads data from sensors, processes it, and makes decisions about system behaviour. Based on the input it receives, the microcontroller can trigger alarms, send information to remote servers, or control other devices such as the air purifier or communication modules. A load cell is a sensor used to measure force or weight. In this system, the load cell likely sends its data to the microcontroller, which could be used for monitoring loads on a structure, pressure on certain components, or weight-based measurements.

This sensor detects seismic activity or vibrations. When an earthquake occurs, the sensor captures the intensity and sends the data to the microcontroller, which can trigger safety measures. For example, upon receiving earthquake data, the microcontroller might sound an alarm (via the buzzer and alerts system) or initiate evacuation protocols. A temperature sensor measures ambient temperature and relays this data to the microcontroller. In critical situations, such as when temperature exceeds safe limits, the system can be programmed to trigger an alarm or activate cooling mechanisms.

The buzzer and alert system is responsible for providing immediate notifications to users when the system detects critical conditions. For example, when the earthquake sensor detects significant vibrations, the microcontroller can activate the buzzer to warn inhabitants. This feature enhances safety by providing real-time feedback based on sensor data.

This module combines GPS location data and imaging (camera) capabilities. The GPS allows the system to track its location or provide geolocation data in case of an emergency, which is particularly useful in disaster scenarios such as earthquakes, where precise location information is critical. The microcontroller processes this data and can either store it locally or send it via a network for further analysis. The network module, possibly a Wi-Fi hotspot or other wireless network, provides connectivity to the system.

The microcontroller might use this network to send sensor data to a remote monitoring center, allowing users or authorities to track humidity, temperature, or seismic activity in real-time.

The overall architecture of the system is designed for environmental monitoring, safety, and automation. Each sensor feeds data into the microcontroller, which then uses this information to make decisions, trigger alerts, or take corrective action. The diagram represents an intelligent, connected system capable of both local decision-making and remote monitoring, providing a comprehensive solution for environmental and safety management.

V. DISCUSSION

The design and development of the safety pod represent a significant advancement in disaster response technology. The pod's integration of advanced materials, self-sustaining systems, and communication technology ensures its effectiveness in critical situations. However, further testing is necessary to refine the usability and ensure the long-term reliability of the components under various disaster conditions.

VI. RESULTS

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure 8

Figure 9

Figure 10

Figure 3 shows a blue earthquake-resistant sleeping pod with an open entrance, designed to protect a person during an earthquake.

Figure 4 shows an electronic control system consisting of an Arduino board, sensors, a GSM module, a GPS module, a battery pack, and other connected components, which likely monitor environmental conditions and send alerts.

Figure 5 shows the interior of the sleeping pod, revealing a storage compartment containing a bottle, likely for emergency supplies.

Figure 6 displays an alert message stating, "Get inside your sleeping pod! Earthquake detected!" which suggests that the system has detected seismic activity and is warning the user.

Figure 7 is the same blue and black structure is now open, revealing a black interior with a soft surface. A pink and yellow plush toy is placed inside, possibly representing a child or an object for testing purposes. A tablet or small screen is placed on the side, likely controlling or monitoring the system. The design suggests this could be a safety pod or an emergency shelter activated during an earthquake.

Figure 8 shows a blue and black structure is placed on a table in what appears to be a workshop or lab environment. The structure seems to be a prototype or a protective enclosure, possibly designed for emergency situations like earthquakes. There are tools and equipment in the background, indicating an ongoing development or testing process.

Figure 9 is a text-based emergency alert indicating an earthquake has been detected. It includes GPS coordinates (8.506314, 76.932395), which likely point to the earthquake's

location. The alert also provides environmental conditions: a temperature of 32.6°C and humidity of 71.00%.

Figure 10 is a digital interface is displayed, showing a camera feed of the toy inside the box. Camera settings such as brightness, contrast, saturation, and other parameters are adjustable. This suggests that the box is equipped with an internal camera, likely for monitoring the occupant's status during an emergency. The ability to stream video indicates it may be part of a smart disaster response system.

VI. CONCLUSION

The design and development of a Safety Pod for rescue operations during natural disasters, particularly earthquakes, represents a significant advancement in emergency response technology. Utilizing lightweight materials, the pod is designed to protect occupants from debris and aftershocks, which are common during and following an earthquake. Additionally, it is equipped with safety harnesses and protective padding to safeguard occupants from injuries during the chaotic aftermath of an earthquake. Recognizing that rescue teams often operate in environments with obstructed access, the pod is designed to be compact and portable. It includes a user-friendly interface for communication, allowing trapped individuals to contact rescue teams. The pod is equipped with essential supplies, such as water, food to sustain occupants until help arrives. Furthermore, the interior is designed to be comfortable, with adequate ventilation and lighting, promoting a sense of security and calm during distressing situations. The effectiveness of the pod relies not only on its physical design but also on the ability of rescuers to deploy it effectively. By incorporating simulations and practical exercises, rescue teams can enhance their preparedness, ultimately improving response times and outcomes in real disaster scenarios.

In conclusion, the Safety Pod represents a comprehensive approach to enhancing rescue operations during natural disasters, particularly earthquakes. By focusing on durability, mobility, and user-friendliness, the pod addresses the critical needs of both rescuers and those in danger. Its advanced design not only protects occupants from immediate threats but also facilitates effective communication with rescue teams, ensuring timely assistance. Through ongoing research and development, the Safety Pod can evolve to meet the changing demands of emergency response, ultimately contributing to a safer and more resilient society in the face of natural disasters.

b.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. El-Rabbany, "Introduction to GPS: the global positioning system," Norwood: Artech house, 2002.
- [2] A. Kaur, A. Jadli, A. Sadhu, S. Goyal, A. Mehra, and Rahul, "Cloud Based Surveillance using ESP32 CAM," International

Conference on Intelligent Technology, System and Service for Internet of Everything (ITSS-IoE), 2021, pp. 1–5.

[3] A. Khanum and V. Rekha, "An enhanced security alert system for smart home using IOT," Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science, volume 13, number 1, pp. 27–34, 2019.

[4] J. Du, M. Chan, S. Deng, "An experimental study on the performances of a radiation-based task/ambient air conditioning system applied to sleeping environments," Energy Build. 139 (2017) 291–301.

DESIGN OF RAINWATER HARVESTING SYSTEM FOR JOHN COX MEMORIAL CSI INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY KANNAMMOOLA

Abiya A S, Sneha S S, Soorya S V, Abhin J, Nitya V Arnold
UG Students – Final Year and Assistant Professor
Department of Civil Engineering JCM Institute of Technology, Kannammoola, Trivandrum,
India

Abstract: - Rainwater harvesting system is mainly the process or a phenomenon of collection and conservation of rainwater from various techniques where the rainwater is the main source for the process of harvesting. As the scarcity of water is rapidly increasing everyday particularly during the summer season, the demand for water also substantially increases. Previously around thirty to forty years back, the major part of the earth is unpaved and the amount of infrastructure built on the earth were also very low, hence during the monsoon season the rainwater easily percolates into the earth through the soil and the ground water level increases. But now the scenario is completely different, most of the areas have been paved and the chance of percolation of water is completely reduced. Hence to replenish the ground water table and also to re-utilize the rainwater for domestic and agricultural purposes, the rainwater harvesting method is adopted. Here in our project, we are going to adopt the roof-top rainwater harvesting method and implement it in college itself, without allowing the water to be wasted through the gutters. In this project main focus is to design the collecting tank and design of collection procedure to store the rainwater from rooftop of all buildings of John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of Technology, Kannammoola.

Keywords: Roof top rainwater harvesting, Gutter.

1. INTRODUCTION

Rooftop rainwater harvesting system is nothing but the process or the technique of collection of the rainwater from the rooftop or catchment surface of the building and intern transferring this water into the storage tank through pipes from the gutters that are attached at the ends of the roof catchment .Also by the adoption of the rain water harvesting system techniques, the recharge of groundwater could also be take intensively done, that is by the method of groundwater recharge technique .The water scarcity could be mainly avoided and also the demands could be easily fulfilled by the adoption of this technique of rainwater harvesting especially in the college campus and in the school building for the required construction works and gardening maintenance. The amount of required supply of water could be easily provided or demands of water could be fulfilled. For this process of installation of rooftop rainwater

harvesting system we mainly required the area of catchment and also the necessary data of rainfall that maybe annual rainfall data and also the area of JIT campus that we are going to deal with, for this process of installation of rainwater harvesting systems.

A rainwater harvesting system (RWHs) collects, concentrates, stores and treats rainwater from rooftops for on-site use. The storage tank can be either in the form of rain barrels for small-scale applications or cisterns in a large building. Once captured, collected rainwater can undergo treatment on physical and biological parameters through processes, including filtration, disinfection and other treatment strategies. The level of treatment required depends upon the type of use and local policies. Normally, a method for backup supply with municipal drinking water is present for periods of deficit, ensuring the water demand from users.

OBJECTIVES:

To calculate the catchment area for the design of rainwater harvesting system using total station.

To calculate the total amount of runoff in catchment area.

To design a filtration tank.

To design a rain water harvesting collecting tank.

To estimate the cost of installation of RWHs.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Following are the research works conducted on concrete with various alternatives as partial to full replacement for coarse aggregate.

Akash et al. (2020) This journal presents a comprehensive study on the implementation of a rooftop rainwater harvesting system at the Rajarajeswari College of Engineering (RRCE) in Bengaluru, Karnataka. The research addresses the critical issue of water scarcity faced by the campus, which serves approximately 2,425 students across its extensive area of 36,855.425 square meters. By adopting this sustainable practice, the RRCE campus aims to significantly increase its water resources, thereby ensuring a reliable supply for various needs, including construction and gardening.

Adnan et al. (2022) This journal explains the design parameters essential for the effective implementation and evaluation of rainwater harvesting systems. The authors emphasize the significance of specific design parameters, such as rainfall, catchment area, water demand, storage capacity, and runoff coefficient. The authors suggest that future research should delve into sensitivity analyses of these design parameters to better understand their interrelationships and impacts on RWHS performance. This article serves as a valuable resource for engineers and researchers, providing insights into the critical factors that influence the design and effectiveness of rainwater harvesting systems, particularly in the context of Malaysia's unique environmental and regulatory landscape.

Becciu et al. (2023) This journal presents a comprehensive examination of the design considerations for storage tanks used in rainwater harvesting systems. The authors utilize a continuous simulation of 47 years of rainfall data to derive statistical parameters that inform the design process, particularly focusing on the volumetric reliability index. The findings are particularly relevant in the context of evolving stormwater management policies that advocate for sustainable practices, including the integration of storage and infiltration systems. The research is open access, allowing for broader dissemination and application of its findings within the field of hydrology and environmental engineering.

Gibbered et al. (2023) This study explores various methodologies for designing rainwater harvesting systems, particularly in the context of schools. It also explains the importance of rainwater harvesting as a sustainable water supply alternative, particularly for schools, which often have suitable roof areas for collection and space for storage tanks. It discusses the Rainwater Use Model (RUM) utilized in the case study, which analyzes water consumption patterns, rainfall data, and the effectiveness of rainwater harvesting systems.

Natarajan et al. (2021) It provides a comprehensive analysis of the potential for implementing rainwater harvesting (RWH) systems in residential areas across Tamil Nadu. The study explores both the technical and economic feasibility of these systems, considering factors like the region's rainfall patterns, water scarcity issues, and urbanization trends. By analyzing case studies, existing infrastructure, and the capacity of local communities to adopt such systems, the journal highlights the key challenges and benefits. The study concludes by outlining strategies for scaling up RWH practices in Tamil Nadu, emphasizing the importance of community engagement, policy support, and continuous technological innovation for sustainable water management in the region.

Mondal et al. (2024) It focuses on sustainable water management, addressing both water scarcity and conservation in an arid or semi-arid region. The plan

includes collecting rainwater from the extensive rooftop areas of various buildings within the establishment, which are likely spread across a vast area. The harvested rainwater would be channeled through a system of gutters, downspouts, and pipes, leading to storage tanks or underground reservoirs. These systems are designed to accommodate heavy rainfall during the monsoon season, ensuring maximum collection efficiency. The stored water can be treated and utilized for non-potable purposes, such as irrigation, vehicle washing, and landscaping, while also being a potential backup for potable use after filtration.

Sunil Kumar et al. (2024) This research addresses the critical challenges of water scarcity and flooding that many regions in India face, particularly during the monsoon season. The study emphasizes the importance of efficient water resource management through the implementation of economical rainwater harvesting structures, such as drystone masonry and cement masonry, which are designed to capture and store rainwater effectively. The author also discusses various traditional water harvesting techniques employed across different regions of India, highlighting their cultural significance and practical applications.

3. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

3.1 MATERIALS

3.1.1 MULTIBOARD

A multiboard is a versatile tool often used in creating still models, especially in large-scale projects such as architectural models, dioramas, and prototypes. Typically made from a lightweight, durable material, multiboard is prized for its ability to be easily cut, shaped, and painted, making it ideal for intricate detailing and achieving precise, realistic finishes. The board's smooth surface allows for a high degree of accuracy in design, and it can be used to create everything from structural components to intricate textures. Its flexibility in terms of material manipulation allows model makers to adapt the board for different scales and types of models, making it an essential part of the toolkit for professionals and hobbyists alike in the field of model making. The material's strength also ensures that models remain stable and robust, even when used for larger, more complex designs.

3.1.2 TOTAL STATION

A total station is a sophisticated electronic instrument used in modern surveying and construction projects to measure angles, distances, and elevations with high precision. It combines the functionalities of an electronic theodolite for measuring angles and an electronic distance measuring (EDM) device to calculate distances, making it a highly versatile tool for surveying professionals. The total station operates by emitting a laser beam or infrared light towards a target, which is then reflected back to the instrument, allowing for the calculation of accurate distance and angle measurements.

These readings are then processed by the instrument's onboard computer, providing real-time data that can be used to create detailed maps, topographic surveys, or building layouts.

Fig 1: Total Station

Fig 3: CAD Plan generated from total station

3.2 METHODOLOGY

3.2.1 MEASUREMENT OF COLLEGE BUILDING

We have taken the dimensions of four block (A or Seminar block, B block, Main block and Lab block) of our college using a measuring tape, with all dimensions recorded in meters. This was done carefully to record the length and width of each building precisely. Once we collected the measurement, we started to make the still model of our college. This step is crucial for ensuring that the model will be a true-to-scale representation of the actual college. To translate these real-world measurements into a workable scale model, we chose to use a 1:100 ratio. This means that every 1 meter of actual length, width, or height will be represented as 1 centimeter in the model. The 1:100 scale is ideal for large structures like buildings, as it allows the model to retain realistic proportions.

3.2.2 CATCHMENT AREA CALCUATION

The catchment area was calculated using a total station, a highly accurate surveying instrument that measures distances, angles, and elevations. This allowed for precise data collection across the terrain, ensuring that the boundaries of the catchment area were defined with great accuracy. Once the measurements were gathered, a detailed CAD (Computer-Aided Design) plan was generated, providing a digital representation of the catchment area. The CAD plan enables easy visualization of the terrain's features, such as slopes, contours, and water flow patterns, facilitating further analysis and decision-making. This method not only enhances the precision of the catchment area calculation but also allows for efficient sharing and modification of data in a digital format.

Fig 2: Measuring catchment area using total station

Total Catchment area = **3055.29 m²**

3.2.3 MAKING OF MINIATURE MODEL OF COLLEGE

We have created a miniature model of our college using a 1:100 scale, where every 1 unit in the model represents 100 units in the actual structure. This scale allows us to maintain proportional accuracy while showcasing the college's key features in a compact form. To construct the model, we used a material called Woodfill, a type of filament commonly used in 3D printing. The use of Woodfill not only ensured strong adhesion between the pieces but also added a textured finish that mimics the appearance of wood, contributing to the model's aesthetic appeal. This technique allowed us to represent the layout, architectural design, and significant details of the college, all while keeping the construction process manageable and precise. The final result is a detailed and visually striking miniature representation of the college that serves as both a model and a creative way to showcase its architectural features.

Fig4: Cutting of Multiboard

Fig 5: Miniature of block B

Fig 6: Miniature of block A

3.2.4 COLLECTION OF RAINFALL DATA

Rainfall data is a key factor in the successful design of a rainwater harvesting system, as it directly influences the calculations for water collection capacity, storage, and distribution. To obtain this critical data, we reached out to both the Meteorological Center and the IDRIB in Trivandrum. In response, they requested certain formalities be completed before they could provide us with the information. Specifically, they asked for an ID proof bearing the college seal to verify our institutional credentials. Furthermore, they instructed us to make a cash payment at the sub-treasury, which is a standard procedure for acquiring official data. Once these steps are fulfilled, they will release the necessary rainfall data, which will be pivotal in designing an optimized rainwater harvesting system tailored to the specific rainfall patterns of our region. This data will not only help in ensuring that the system is efficient but also allow us to make accurate predictions regarding water availability throughout the year, ensuring sustainability and effective water management for the college.

Table 1: Daily Rainfall Data

YEAR	RAINFALL INTENSITY (mm)
2018	5.88 mm
2019	5.48 mm
2020	6.29 mm
2021	9.46mm
2022	5.54 mm
2023	6.54 mm
2024	6.64 mm

Daily rainfall = 6.55mm

3.2.5 CALCULATION OF RUNOFF

Runoff refers to the flow of water, typically from precipitation, that moves across the land surface and eventually enters water bodies such as rivers, lakes, and oceans. The Rational Method is a commonly used technique for estimating peak runoff from a drainage area based on land use, rainfall intensity, and watershed characteristics. It is particularly effective for small, urban catchments. The method uses the equation:

$$Q=CiA$$

Coefficient of runoff for urban area is **0.5**.

$$\text{Runoff} = 0.5 \times \text{Total intensity of rainfall} \times \text{Catchment area}$$

$$\text{Total rate of runoff} = 9.98 \text{ m}^3$$

3.2.6 DESIGN OF STORAGE TANK

Storage tanks designed to collect and store rainwater are built using durable materials to ensure strength and longevity. The side should be constructed with second-class bricks, bound together with a 1:5 cement mortar, which provides a solid, stable structure. The base should be made of concrete using an M 20 mix. These materials and construction methods significantly enhance the tank's overall strength, durability, and ability to withstand environmental factors.

$$\text{Capacity of rainwater storage tank} = \text{Rate of runoff} \times \text{Coefficient of runoff for water removed from first flush filter}$$

Coefficient of runoff for water removed from first flush filter is 0.8.

$$\text{Capacity of rainwater storage tank} = 7.984 \text{ m}^3$$

Assume the depth of the storage tank = 2m

$$\text{Area} = \frac{\text{Volume}}{\text{Depth}}$$

$$\text{Area} = 3.99 \text{ m}^2$$

$$\text{Area} = \pi r^2$$

Radius, r = 1.12m

Diameter, d = 2.24m

3.2.7 DESIGN OF FILTRATION TANK

Filters play a crucial role in rainwater harvesting systems by ensuring that the collected rainwater is free from harmful suspended pollutants. One of the most commonly used types of filters in such systems is the sand filter, which is both efficient and cost-effective. Sand filters work by using commonly available sand as the primary filtering media.

Filter media specification for sand filters [6]

Gravel bed

Table 2: Size and Thickness of gravel

Layer no: from top	Size of gravel (mm)	Thickness of layer (cm)
1	2-5	7.5-10
2	5-12	7.5-10
3	15-20	10
4	20-38	10
5	38-65	10

The quality of gravel should conform to 4.1 of IS: 8419 (part I) – 1977. Gravel should be free from clay, dust, organic materials etc. Naturally available rounded gravels are more preferred.

Sand layer

Over a gravel bed a coarse sand layer of 50 to 75 cm thick is provided. The quality of sand shall be conformed to 3.1 of IS: 8419 (part I) – 1977. Filter sand shall consist of hard, durable grains of silica. Sand should be free from dust, roots, organic materials etc.

Design of Sand Filter

Filter bed area

Normally the rate of filtration of bed is considered 4 to 5 m^3/m^2 /hour.

Peak runoff rate = Peak rainfall intensity × Catchment area × Runoff Coefficient × Coefficient of runoff for water removed from first flush diverter

Peak runoff rate = $11.56m^3$

Area of filter bed = $\frac{\text{Peak runoff rate}}{\text{Rate of filtration}}$

Area of filter bed = $2.89 m^2$

$$\frac{L}{B} = 1.25$$

Provide a filter bed of $1.9m \times 1.52m$

Height or Depth of filter unit

Depth of filter sand = 75 cm

Depth of filter gravel = 50 cm

The depth of tank is kept one foot above the top of filter media to provide the required hydro-static for filtration.

3.2.8 COST ESTIMATION

Cost estimation is the process of forecasting the financial resources needed to complete a project, encompassing all direct and indirect costs, and is crucial for project budgeting and feasibility assessment. Cost of rainwater storage tank and filtration tank is estimated using Microsoft excel. In Microsoft Excel, cost estimation involves using formulas and functions to calculate and project the costs associated with a project, product, or service, often based on historical data, estimated quantities, and unit costs.

Table 3: Cost estimation of storage tank

SL NO	DESCRIPTION OF WORK	HEIGHT	RADIUS	QUANTITY	UNIT	RATE	AMOUNT
1	Earth work excavation	2m	1.12m	7.88	CUM	125.95	992.49
2	PCC 1:1.5:3	0.20m	1.12m	0.79	CUM	5000	3950
3	RCC (Base, Roof)	0.2m	1.12m	0.79	CUM	3500	2765
4	RCC(Roof)	0.15m	1.12m	0.59	CUM	3500	2065
5	Formwork (shuttering) for RCC	0.35m	1.12m	1.38	CUM	500	690
6	Plastering 15mm thick	2m	1.12m	7.88	CUM	250	1970
7	Water profiling for entire surface	2m	1.12m	7.88	CUM	300	2364
8	Miscellaneous(Pipes,valves)						2000
9	Labour charges						5000
10	Contingencies(5% of total cost)						1090
11	Total estimated cost						22886

Table 4: Cost estimation of filtration tank

SL NO	DESCRIPTION OF WORK	LENGTH	WIDTH	HEIGHT	QUANTITY	UNIT	RATE	AMOUNT
1	Excavation of earthwork	1.9m	1.52m	1.55m	4.47	CUM	200	894
2	PCC 1:1.5:3	1.9m	1.52m	0.10m	0.28	CUM	6000	1680
3	RCC (Base)	1.9m	1.52m	0.2m	0.58	CUM	3500	2030
4	RCC(Roof)	1.9m	1.52m	0.15m	0.43	CUM	3500	1505
5	Formwork for RCC	1.9m	1.52m	0.35m	1.01	CUM	900	909
6	Plastering 15mm thick	1.9m	1.52m	1.55m	4.47	CUM	250	1117
7	Water profile for entire structure	1.9m	1.52m	1.55m	4.47	CUM	300	1341
8	Sand filter(75 cm thick)	1.9m	1.52m	0.75m	2.17	CUM	800	1736
9	Gravel layer(50cm thick)	1.9m	1.52m	0.5m	1.44	CUM	1000	1440
10	Miscellaneous (Pipes,valves)							15000
11	Labour charges							5000
12	Contingencies(5% of total cost)							1632
13	Total estimated cost							34,284

4. RESULTS

Total catchment area for the design of rainwater harvesting system = $3055.29 m^2$

The total amount of runoff in catchment area at 1hr = $9.98 m^3$

Design of storage tank

Volume of the storage tank = $7.984m^3$

Depth of the storage tank = 2m

Diameter of the storage tank = 2.24m

Area of the storage tank = $3.99 m^2$

Therefore, Storage tank has a depth of 2m and a diameter of 2.24m.

Design of filtration tank

Length of filtration tank = 1.9m

Width of filtration tank = 1.52m

Area of filter bed = $2.31 m^2$

Total cost for the installation of rainwater harvesting system = Rs 57170/-

5.CONCLUSION

Hence, conclusion can be made saying that this study mainly aimed on the designing of the rainwater harvesting system for John Cox Memorial CSI institute of Technology. By the adoption of this system the water source of the campus could be increase. The design of rainwater harvesting system is been carried or its adoption are been done since ancient times. The technique is simple but it very much fulfills the water demand.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] Adnan A. B., Ahmad A. B. C., and Teriman S. B (2022). "Design Parameter of Rainwater Harvesting System (RWHS): A Systematic Literature Review", *Journal of Water Supply: Research and Technology-Aqua*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/367218065_Design_Parameter_of_Rainwater_Harvesting_System_RWHS_A_Systematic_Literature_Review
- [2] Becciu G., Chiana M. G. D., Marchioni M., Raimondi A. and Sanfilippo U (2023). "Probabilistic Approach to Tank Design in Rainwater Harvesting Systems", *Journal of Hydrology*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/hydrology10030059>
- [3] Gibbered J. (2023). "Rainwater Harvesting Design Approaches", *Journal of Hydrology*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/368222379_Rainwater_Harvesting_Design_Approaches
- [4] Natarajan N., and Vasudevan M. (2021). "An investigation on the adaptability of residential rainwater harvesting system in Tamil Nadu – technoeconomic considerations and the way

forward”, *Journal of Water supply*, Vol.21.

<https://doi.org/10.2166/ws.2020.249>

[5] Mondal K. C., Naik P. K., Naik P. K. and Prasad G. (2024). “A design plan for rooftop rainwater harvesting in a large defence establishment in central India”, *Journal of Desalination and Water Treatment*, Vol.317.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dwt.2024.100252>

[6] Marve S. R., Wankar M. S., (2020). “Design of Harvesting Filter Unit”, *Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and technology*, Vol.4.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/342802375_Design_of_Harvestine_Filter_Unit

[7] Prasad S. H. C., Sanjith S. A., (2021). “Feasibility of roof top rainwater harvesting potential - A case study of South Indian University”, *Journal of Cleaner Engineering and Technology*.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clet.2021.100206>

[8] Sunil Kumar (2024). “Design of Rain Water Harvesting System for Efficient Water Scarcity and Flood Management in India”, *International Journal of Environment and Climate change*, Vol.14, pp.295-303.

<https://doi.org/10.9734/ijecc/2024/v14i64229>

Evaluating the effectiveness of using geotextile and flyash in improving lateritic subgrade soil strength

Alex Binu, Anusha SS, Blessy S Prasad, Murukan M,

Civil Engineering dept.

John Cox Memorial C.S.I Institute Of Technology

Trivandrum, India

Abstract- This study investigates the effectiveness of using geotextiles and flyash to improve the strength of lateritic subgrade soil. Lateritic soils are commonly found in tropical regions and are known for their poor engineering properties, making them a challenge for construction projects. The use of geotextiles and flyash as soil reinforcement materials has shown promise in improving soil strength. In this study, a series of laboratory tests were conducted to evaluate the effect of geotextiles and flyash on the compressive strength, California Bearing Ratio (CBR), and shear strength of lateritic subgrade soil. The results show that the addition of geotextiles and flyash significantly improves the soil's strength, with increases in compressive strength, CBR, and shear strength. The study concludes that the use of geotextiles and flyash is an effective method for improving the strength of lateritic subgrade soil, making it a viable option for construction projects in tropical regions. The article explores the possibility of a ternary blend, i.e., geotextile and flyash on effectively stabilizing pavement subgrade. Limited literature was available to address the issue of utilizing the industrial wastes that otherwise pose disposal issues.

Keywords- Lateritic soil; Flyash; Geotextile; UCS; CBR.

I. INTRODUCTION

Soil is the basic foundation for any civil engineering structures. It is required to bear the loads without failure. In some places, soil may be weak which cannot resist the incoming

loads for which soil stabilization is needed. Stabilization of weak soils with fly ash not only improves engineering properties of soil, but also provides answers to issues of fly ash disposal. Geotextile is a newly emerging material in construction fields, offer great potential in varied areas of application globally. It plays a significant part in modern pavement design and maintenance techniques. Fly ash acquired from power stations causes removal challenges and environmental concerns. Disposal concerns can be solved by employing these waste materials as a raw source to improve soil stability. Stability of soil refers to the improvement of soil behaviour due to the enhancement of the soil's geotechnical properties. Water content, strength, plasticity, and density are the most often adjusted properties. Extensive studies have focused on the influence of fly ash on soil stability. Therefore, this investigation discussed some of these studies, drawing a critical review to find out the effect of fly ash additive on soil characteristics. Also, this study focused on the impact of fly ash (FA) mixed with clay soil. Generally, it can be said that fly ash improved the soil stability, especially in terms of CBR values, the permeability of the soil and decreased the potential of volumetric soil changes through a series of experimental tests. This is due to the size and shape of particles; in addition to the treated period, volumetric dilation of the ground is reduced. Considering that the additives are not biodegradable, the behavioural adjustment of the hardened soil does not disappear.

Fig 1: Non-Woven Geotextile Membrane

The integration of geotextiles and fly ash in enhancing the strength of lateritic subgrade soils represents a significant advancement in geotechnical engineering, particularly in tropical regions where such soils are abundant. Lateritic soils, formed through the weathering of parent rock in warm, humid climates, are often characterized by their high clay content, variability in strength, and tendency to undergo significant changes in moisture content. These characteristics pose challenges for construction projects, leading to issues such as foundation failures, increased maintenance costs, and difficulties in achieving adequate compaction. Geotextiles, which are synthetic fabrics designed to reinforce soil, offer several advantages in this context. They improve load distribution, enhance drainage, and prevent soil erosion, thereby increasing the overall stability of the subgrade.

Fig 2: Lateritic Soil

When geotextiles are combined with fly ash a lightweight byproduct of coal combustion with excellent pozzolanic properties, the benefits are further amplified. Fly ash contributes to the reduction of the plasticity index of lateritic soils, making them less susceptible to changes

in moisture content and improving their workability. The pozzolanic reactions that occur when fly ash is mixed with water and lime result in the formation of additional cementitious compounds, which bind soil particles together and enhance shear strength. This dual approach not only strengthens the soil but also promotes sustainable construction practices by recycling industrial waste, thereby reducing landfill use and minimizing environmental impact.

Fig 3: Flyash

Moreover, the combined use of geotextiles and fly ash has been shown to produce synergistic effects that significantly enhance the performance of lateritic subgrade soils. For instance, studies have demonstrated substantial increases in load-bearing capacity and durability, with reductions in pavement distress and extended service life in road construction applications. This method has also proven effective in stabilizing embankments, reducing the risk of erosion and slope failure. The cost-effectiveness of using these materials is evident as they allow for improved soil properties while reducing the need for additional or more expensive construction materials.

As infrastructure development continues to expand in developing regions, the adoption of innovative solutions like the integration of geotextiles and fly ash will be crucial in overcoming the challenges posed by local soil conditions. Future research efforts should aim to optimize the ratios and configurations of these materials, as well as explore their long-term performance under varying environmental conditions. By doing so, engineers can ensure the construction of safer, more resilient infrastructure that meets the growing demands of society while protecting the environment. Ultimately, the effective use of geotextiles and fly ash not only addresses

immediate engineering challenges but also contributes to the sustainability of construction practices in the face of increasing urbanization and climate change.

The main objectives are:-

- To determine the optimal dosage of fly ash required to improve the strength of lateritic subgrade soils.
- To evaluate the effect of geotextiles on the CBR of lateritic subgrade soils.
- To investigate the effect of fly ash and geotextile on the UCS of lateritic subgrade soils.
- To study the effect of geotextile layers on UCS value.

II. SPECIMEN PREPARATION AND TESTING

A. Materials

1. Lateritic subgrade soil

Lateritic subgrade soil is a type of soil formed through the weathering of rocks in tropical and subtropical regions, characterized by a high concentration of iron and aluminum oxides.

Fig 4: Lateritic subgrade soil

2. Flyash

Soil Stabilization, Fly ash can improve the strength and stability of lateritic soil, making it more suitable for construction purposes. It can help bind soil particles together, reducing plasticity and improving load-bearing capacity. Increased Durability, When mixed with fly ash, lateritic soil exhibits improved durability and resistance to weathering, which is crucial for road and foundation applications.

Fig 5: Flyash

3. Geotextile

Geotextiles are flat, permeable sheets constructed of polyester or polypropylene resin with yarns that have been knitted, needle-punched, woven, thermally or chemically bonded, or bonded with a thermal agent. They belong to a class of geosynthetic materials that are frequently employed in civil engineering projects to stabilize the soil. In comparison to conventional stabilization methods, geotextiles offer a variety of benefits, including simplicity of installation, lower cost, and enhanced performance.

Geotextiles have many advantages to stabilizing soil. First, because geotextiles may be laid with local resources, less expensive earth materials need to be carried to the construction site. This lowers expenses while simultaneously lowering the project's negative environmental impact.

Fig 6: Jute geotextile

B. Preparation of Specimens

1. Lateritic soil with Fly Ash:

The mixing process involves combining lateritic soil and fly ash to create a homogeneous blend that enhances soil strength. First, the dry lateritic soil and fly ash are measured and added to a clean container in

predetermined proportions, typically ranging from 5% to 30% fly ash by weight. Using a shovel or a mechanical mixer, the two materials are thoroughly mixed until uniformity is achieved. Next, water is gradually added to the mixture to reach the optimum moisture content, determined from prior compaction tests. The mixture is stirred continuously to ensure even moisture distribution, creating a workable consistency suitable for compaction into molds. This careful blending is crucial for achieving the desired engineering properties in the final soil-fly ash specimens.

➤ Material Preparation

- Selection of Materials
 - Lateritic Soil: The soil has been collected from the college ground. The ground is mainly covered with lateritic soil, which is rich in iron and aluminum oxides.
 - Fly Ash: Class C fly ash has been selected for the test as it contains pozzolans that can initiate chemical reactions which could potentially increase the strength of soils for geotechnical applications.
- Equipment and Tools
 - Mixing Equipment: The equipments include shovels, buckets, mixing pans, measuring jars and many more equipments has been used for the purpose of mixing , collection of soil. And also specific machines has also been used.
 - Measuring Instruments: Accurate weighing scales and measuring containers are essential for ensuring the correct proportions of lateritic soil and fly ash, as well as water.

C. Proportioning Fly Ash

- The optimal proportion of fly ash typically ranges from 5% to 30% of the total dry weight of the lateritic soil. The exact ratio may depend on the specific engineering requirements, desired strength characteristics, and environmental factors.

- A preliminary trial mix can be conducted to establish an initial baseline. This involves creating small batches with varying fly ash contents to determine which ratio yields the best results in terms of strength and workability.

D. Water Content Adjustment

The amount of water added is critical for achieving the optimum moisture content. This is based on prior tests that indicate the ideal moisture level for compaction. The goal is to achieve a workable consistency that allows for easy compaction without excess water that could lead to weak specimens.

E. Mixing Procedure

➤ Dry Mixing

Begin by adding the measured quantities of dry lateritic soil and fly ash into a clean mixing container. It's essential to add the materials in a manner that prevents segregation; typically, the soil is added first, followed by the fly ash.

Use a shovel to blend the materials thoroughly. This step is crucial as it ensures that the fly ash is evenly distributed throughout the lateritic soil, preventing clumps and ensuring uniformity. The mixing should continue until there are no visible segregated patches of either material, typically taking about 5–10 minutes.

➤ Adding Water

After achieving a uniform dry mix, gradually introduce water into the mixture. It's advisable to add water in increments, mixing thoroughly between additions to prevent over-saturation.

The mixing continues until the moisture content reaches the optimum level determined earlier. The consistency should be such that the mixture holds together without crumbling when compacted, resembling a damp sand-like texture.

➤ Final Mixing

Once the optimum moisture content is achieved, a final round of mixing is performed to ensure that the water is evenly distributed throughout the entire mixture. This step is vital to avoid weak spots in the final specimens, which could lead to inconsistent test results.

F. Quality Control

➤ Consistency Checks

During the mixing process, it is important to perform periodic checks for consistency. A simple field test can involve taking a handful of the mixture and observing its texture and moisture retention.

If the mixture appears too dry or too wet, adjustments can be made by adding more water or soil, respectively, to achieve the desired consistency.

➤ Sample Testing

Before proceeding to the molding stage, it may be beneficial to conduct preliminary tests on small samples of the mixture. For example, compact a small batch into a mold and perform a quick unconfined compressive strength test to gauge the mixture's performance. This allows for any necessary adjustments before the final specimen preparation.

G. Transition to Molding

➤ Preparing for Molding

Once the mixing process is complete and quality checks have been satisfied, the mixed material should be transported promptly to the molding area to prevent any moisture loss.

Use clean molds that have been adequately prepared to ensure that the specimens do not stick during the curing phase.

➤ Final Adjustments

Before molding, give the mixed material a final stir to ensure uniform consistency. This is particularly important as some moisture may have settled or evaporated during the mixing process.

After ensuring the mixture is ready, it can be transferred into molds for compaction.

H. Compaction of Specimen

➤ Proctor Test

Standard or Modified Proctor Test: Conduct this test to find the maximum optimal moisture content. This involves compacting soil in a mold with a specific number of blows from a hammer of a known weight.

➤ Compaction Process

Layering: Place the soil sample in a mold or compaction device in layers, typically about 4 to 6 inches thick for field applications.

➤ Compaction Techniques:

Static Compaction: Use a manual tamper to compress the soil.

➤ Monitoring

Ensure that the compaction is uniform and meets the required density. This can be checked using a nuclear density gauge or sand cone method.

➤ Testing Compacted Sample

After compaction, test the sample for properties like moisture content, density, and strength (e.g., Unconfined Compressive Strength).

➤ Testing for Performance

Unconfined compressive strength tests to assess strength improvements.

Measure maximum strength using California Bearing Ratio (CBR) of lateritic subgrade soil.

Determining the weight of soil using specific gravity.

I. Preparation of Sample (Lateritic soil, Fly Ash and Geotextile)

The stabilization of lateritic soil, particularly in regions where it serves as a foundation material, is crucial for ensuring structural integrity and longevity in construction projects. Lateritic soils, characterized by their high clay content and poor load-bearing capacity, often require enhancement to improve their physical and mechanical properties. One effective method of stabilization involves the incorporation of fly ash, a byproduct of coal combustion, alongside the application of geotextiles for reinforcement. This approach not only improves the soil's engineering characteristics but also promotes sustainable practices by utilizing industrial waste materials.

The first step in the stabilization process is the collection and characterization of the lateritic soil. This involves obtaining representative samples from the construction site and

performing a series of laboratory tests to assess properties such as grain size distribution, Atterberg limits, and compaction characteristics. Understanding these properties is essential as they inform the selection of the appropriate mix design for stabilization. Class C fly ash has been used due to its pozzolanic properties and fineness, which are critical for determining its effectiveness as a stabilizing agent. The ideal pozzolanic material should enhance the soil's strength and reduce plasticity, thus improving its overall performance.

Once the soil and fly ash properties are well understood, the next phase is to establish a suitable mix design. This typically involves determining the optimal proportion of fly ash to be mixed with the lateritic soil, which can range from 5% to 30% by weight. The specific ratio will depend on the desired engineering properties, including increased strength, reduced plasticity, and improved durability. Preliminary trials are conducted to evaluate the effects of different fly ash percentages on the soil's characteristics, ensuring the selected mix will achieve the required performance standards.

The mixing process is critical for achieving a homogeneous blend of soil and fly ash. In a designated area, the two materials are combined according to the predetermined ratios, with thorough mixing to ensure an even distribution of the fly ash throughout the lateritic soil. Following this, water is added to the mixture to attain the optimal moisture content, which is typically around 12-15% for effective compaction. The moisture content is vital, as it influences the workability and compaction behavior of the soil-fly ash blend. Proper mixing ensures that the components are well integrated, leading to enhanced pozzolanic reactions that contribute to improved strength.

The application of jute geotextiles is another significant aspect of this stabilization procedure. Geotextiles are synthetic fabrics that provide additional reinforcement to the soil, enhancing its load-bearing capacity and minimizing potential deformation under stress. After preparing the soil-fly ash mix, the geotextile is laid over the prepared subgrade or integrated within the soil layers. Care is taken to position the fabric without wrinkles or

overlaps, ensuring that it covers the entire area intended for stabilization. This reinforcement not only supports the soil but also improves drainage, reducing the risk of water retention that could compromise the integrity of the structure.

Once the geotextile is in place, the next step is compaction. The soil-fly ash mixture is compacted in layers, typically 15-20 cm thick, using a plate compactor or roller. This process is crucial for achieving the desired density and strength of the stabilized layer. Adequate compaction enhances the soil's load-bearing capacity and minimizes the likelihood of settlement or failure under applied loads. It is essential to monitor the moisture content during this stage, as excessive moisture can lead to inadequate compaction and compromised performance.

J. TEST CONDUCTED ON SOIL SAMPLE:

➤ UNCONFINED COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH (UCS) TEST

The Unconfined Compressive Strength (UCS) test is a critical laboratory procedure designed to evaluate the compressive strength of Lateritic soils and certain rock types. It provides valuable insights into the material's behavior under axial load, specifically measuring the maximum stress a cylindrical specimen can endure without any lateral confining pressure. The process begins with obtaining an undisturbed soil sample, which is then carefully prepared and positioned vertically in a compression testing machine. As axial load is applied at a controlled rate, the specimen is monitored until it ultimately fails, at which point the maximum load is recorded.

The UCS is calculated using the formula $UCS = P/A$ where P represents the maximum load and A is the cross-sectional area of the sample. The resulting UCS value is crucial for geotechnical engineers as it reflects the soil's load-bearing capacity, influencing decisions related to foundation design, slope stability, and the overall suitability of the soil for construction projects. Additionally, the UCS test is particularly useful in characterizing soil for projects involving earthworks and embankments.

However, the test has its limitations; the accuracy of results can be affected by factors such as sample disturbance during collection, variations in moisture content, and the inherent heterogeneity of soil materials. Therefore, careful sample handling and testing procedures are essential to obtain reliable data. Ultimately, understanding UCS helps engineers predict soil behavior under load, ensuring safe and effective construction practices.

Fig 7: Unconfined Compression Testing machine

➤ CALIFORNIA BEARING RATIO (CBR)

The California Bearing Ratio (CBR) test is a widely recognized method used in geotechnical engineering to assess the strength and load-bearing capacity of soil and aggregate materials, particularly in the context of road and pavement construction. Developed in the 1920s in California, this test has become a standard practice for evaluating subgrade materials, helping engineers design safe and efficient roadways. The CBR test measures the resistance of a soil or aggregate sample to penetration by a standardized piston, providing a quantitative assessment of its ability to support loads. This test is especially important in the design of flexible pavements, where the ability of the subgrade to bear traffic loads directly influences the pavement's performance and longevity.

Fig 8: CBR Apparatus

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. OPTIMAL DOSAGE OF FLY ASH

Table 1

Percentage of fly ash	q_u (kg/cm ²)
5%	0.106
10%	0.25
15%	0.29
20%	0.38
25%	0.4
30%	0.37
35%	0.48

Fig 9 : Optimal dosage of fly ash

- Fly ash can improve the compressive strength of lateritic soil when mixed in optimal proportions.
- The ideal dosage is usually in the range of 5% to 25% by weight of the soil.
- Beyond this range, the strength improvement may plateau or even decrease, depending on the specific characteristics of the lateritic soil and the fly ash.
- It is found that addition of fly ash improves the UCS value and the optimal dosage of fly ash is obtained as 25%.
- However, 5-25% fly ash by weight is commonly used for improving strength and workability.

Table 2

SOIL WITH ADDITIVES	CBR VALUE(%)
Geotextile and Fly ash	84.32
Lateritic soil and Fly ash	43.66
Lateritic soil	33.56

Fig 10: CBR value of lateritic soil with additives.

- From the graph it is found that addition of geotextile and flyash improves the subgrade soil strength.

- The California Bearing Ratio (CBR) is a standard test used to evaluate the strength and load-bearing capacity of soils, especially for use in pavement design.
- When additives like geotextile and fly ash are used to stabilize lateritic soils, the CBR value generally improves due to the enhanced properties of the soil.

Table 3

Deflection (mm)	Lateritic soil+Fly ash	Lateritic soil+Geotextile	Lateritic soil+Geotextile+Fly ash	Plain Lateritic soil
0	0	0	0	0
0.5	0.59	0.039	4.191	0.28
1	0.72	1.96	7.09	0.42
1.5	1.7	2.75	9.824	0.59
2	1.79	4.32	13.62	1.3
2.5	1.89	5.23	15.19	1.3
3	1.97	7.46	15.71	1.3

Fig 11: UCS value of lateritic soil with additives.

- The above graph depicts the UCS values of plain lateritic soil, geotextile and lateritic soil, fly ash and lateritic soil, and fly ash , geotextile and lateritic soil.
- Addition of fly ash and geotextile with lateritic soil increases the UCS value.

- Addition of geotextile improves the UCS value than fly ash.

Table 4

Layers of geotextile	qu(kg/cm ²)
1	0.1
2	0.106
3	0.118
4	0.123

Fig 12: Effect of geotextile layers in UCS value.

- By increasing number of layers of geotextile, the unconfined compressive strength of lateritic soil increases.
- Adding layers of jute geotextile to lateritic soil can have notable positive effects, particularly in terms of soil stabilization, reinforcement, and improvement of engineering properties like strength, drainage, and compaction.
- Jute geotextiles are natural and eco-friendly alternatives to synthetic geotextiles, made from plant fibers, and they are gaining popularity due to their biodegradability, strength, and cost-effectiveness.

IV CONCLUSION

- ❑ The optimal dosage of fly ash required to improve the strength of lateritic sub grade soil is 25%.
- ❑ The addition of geotextile to the lateritic soil improves the CBR value.
- ❑ The UCS of lateritic sub grade soil is increased by the addition of fly ash and geotextile. Compared to fly ash, lateritic soil with geotextile shows better compressive strength
- ❑ As the number of layers of geotextile increases CBR value is further improved. It is found that geotextile is a better additive for improving the strength of lateritic soil.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We express our sincere gratitude to Mrs.Amritha varsha TS, Assistant Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, for her invaluable guidance and support. We also extend our thanks to Mrs. Cera Shalom and Mrs. L. Sreeletha for their assistance, and to Dr. Anshad A.S for permitting us to carry out our project at John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of Technology. Finally, we are grateful to our faculty, parents, friends, and everyone who contributed to the successful completion of our project.

REFERENCES

1. Duddu S., Kommanamanchi V., Chennarapu H. and Balunaini U.(2024). "Field Evaluation of Deformation Modulus of Geogrid and Geocell Stabilized Subgrade Soil", *KSCE Journal of civil engineering*, Vol 28, pages 4944-4960, <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s12205-024-2322-7>.
2. Hamdanu Y. and Eisazadeh A.(2024). "Performance evaluation of laterite soil embankment stabilized with bottom ash, coir fiber, and lime" , *Journal of mountain science*, Vol 21, pages 2334-2351, <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11629-023-8571-y>.
3. Hamdanu Y., Sani E. and Eisazadeh A.(2023). "Influence of Coir Fiber on the Strength and Permeability Characteristics of Bottom Ash- and Lime-Stabilized Laterite Soil", *International journal of geosynthetic and ground engineering*, Vol 9,

- article number 63,
<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s40891-023-00483-6> .
4. Vimal H., Kaushik N. and Jaysawa D. (2023). "Stabilization of Soil Using Geotextile", *International Journal of Research in Civil Engineering and Technology*, Vol 4(1): 24-29, <http://www.civilengineeringjournals.com/ijrcet>.
 5. Pallavi A., Padalkar S., Tejashri A., Kulkarni and Chetan G. Joshi. (2017). "Study on properties of Lateritic Soil using Flyash and Coir Fibre", *International Journal Of Advance Research in Science and Engineering*, Vol 6, Issue No.3, <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348704563>
 6. Tamassoki S., Kusin M., Rashid A. and Jakami F.(2022). "Performance evaluation of lateritic subgrade soil treated with Lime and Coir Fibre- Activated Carbon", *MDPI Applied science*, Vol 12,(16)8279, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12168279>.

E-WASTE MANAGEMENT USING IMAGE SENSING

Anusree A B, Arya R

Dept. of Electronics & Communication Engineering
JCMCSIIT, Kannammoola
Trivandrum, Kerala, India

Jothi Krishna K S, Rijin Mohan S

Dept. of Electronics & Communication Engineering
JCMCSIIT, Kannammoola
Trivandrum, Kerala, India

Abstract— Effective waste management is crucial for environmental sustainability, particularly the segregation of e-waste and non-e-waste. E-waste management using image sensing presents an automated waste separation system utilizing a conveyor belt and YOLOv8(You Only Look Once version 8) object detection model to distinguish between e-waste and non-e-waste in real time. This model is trained on an extensive dataset of labelled waste images to ensure accurate detection and classification. The proposed system demonstrates significant potential in improving waste segregation processes, contributing to more effective recycling and waste management strategies. Initial results indicate the system's high accuracy and real-time processing capability, offering a scalable solution for various waste management applications. This automation reduces human intervention, minimizes sorting errors and enhances the throughput and efficiency of waste management facilities.

Keywords— E-waste, Image Sensing, YOLOv8, Automated Sorting, Waste Management

I. INTRODUCTION

Electronic waste, or e-waste, refers to discarded electrical and electronic devices, including a wide range of products such as computers, smartphones, televisions, and various appliances that are no longer wanted or functional. The rapid advancement of technology has accelerated the generation of e-waste, with millions of tons produced globally each year. According to the Global E-Waste Monitor, approximately 53.6 million metric tons of e-waste were generated in 2019, a figure that is expected to grow significantly as technology continues to evolve. It poses significant environmental and health risks, as many electronic devices contain hazardous substances such as lead, mercury, cadmium, and brominated flame retardants. When improperly disposed of, these materials can leach into the environment, leading to soil and water contamination that can harm wildlife and potentially affect human health through the food chain. Effective e-waste management is therefore crucial for protecting the environment, recovering valuable resources, ensuring regulatory compliance, and creating economic opportunities. E-waste contains valuable materials that can be recovered and reused, which reduces the need for virgin materials and conserves natural resources. Additionally, many countries have established regulations governing e-waste management, making

compliance essential for organizations and individuals to avoid legal penalties. The recycling industry associated with e-waste also has the potential to create jobs and stimulate economic growth by investing in recycling technologies and infrastructure.

II. RELATED WORK

Several studies have explored automated waste classification using machine learning techniques. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have been widely applied in general waste detection, demonstrating high accuracy in classifying organic, plastic, and metallic waste. However, research specifically targeting e-waste classification is still limited. Some existing methods use infrared sensors, X-ray fluorescence, and hyperspectral imaging for material identification, but these approaches are often expensive and require complex hardware setups. In contrast, our system leverages cost-effective image processing techniques combined with deep learning algorithms to classify e-waste into categories such as plastic, metal, and glass with high precision.

The main innovation of this work lies in integrating affordable hardware components (Arduino Nano, camera module, servo motors, and GSM module) with a deep learning-based classification system to create an effective, scalable, and sustainable solution for e-waste management..

III. METHODOLOGY

The proposed system consists of the following stages:

A. Image Capture

The camera module is positioned strategically to capture clear and high-resolution images of incoming e-waste items. These images serve as the primary input for the system, ensuring that the object is accurately identified. The module operates in real-time, continuously scanning items placed on the conveyor belt. Proper lighting and image stabilization

techniques are used to improve image quality and reduce errors caused by motion blur or low visibility.

B. Image Processing

The Arduino Nano, integrated with a machine learning model, processes the captured images to classify the e-waste items. Pre-trained neural networks analyze features such as shape, texture, and color to distinguish between materials like plastic, metal, and glass. To enhance classification accuracy, image preprocessing techniques such as noise reduction, edge detection, and contrast enhancement are applied. The identified category is then sent to the sorting mechanism for appropriate action.

C. Sorting

Once the type of e-waste is identified, the servo motor is activated to direct the item into the correct category bin. The sorting mechanism ensures precise placement of waste materials, reducing contamination between different categories. The servo motor's movement is controlled based on predefined angles corresponding to each category, ensuring efficiency and accuracy in waste segregation.

D. Conveyor Belt Simulation

A DC motor and a dummy motor work together to simulate the movement of a conveyor belt, allowing continuous and automated processing of e-waste items. The conveyor belt ensures a steady flow of materials to the camera module and sorting mechanism, preventing bottlenecks in the system. Speed control mechanisms are implemented to synchronize the image processing time with waste movement, ensuring accurate identification and sorting without disruptions.

E. Notification

After sorting, the system utilizes a GSM module to send real-time notifications to relevant authorities or recycling centers. These alerts include details about the type and quantity of e-waste collected, helping streamline waste collection and disposal logistics. The system can also generate periodic reports on waste processing activities, assisting in data-driven decision-making for recycling operations.

F. Power Management

The entire system operates on a rechargeable battery, optimized with a buck converter to regulate voltage and prevent energy wastage. The power management unit ensures a stable power supply to all components, maintaining efficiency even in cases of fluctuating energy demands. The system is designed to be energy-efficient, maximizing battery life while ensuring continuous operation, making it suitable for remote or off-grid locations.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The system was tested on a dataset containing images of different e-waste categories. The CNN model achieved an accuracy of 92%, outperforming traditional machine learning

methods. The automated sorting system successfully identified and categorized e-waste, reducing manual labor and processing time.

Key Observations:

The image preprocessing techniques significantly improved classification accuracy by eliminating background noise. The system successfully classified and sorted 95% of plastic items, 90% of metallic items, and 88% of glass components.

Real-time performance analysis showed that the system could process one e-waste item in approximately 2-3 seconds, making it feasible for industrial-scale applications.

The servo motor-based sorting mechanism achieved 85% sorting accuracy, with occasional misclassifications due to partial occlusion of objects.

The results indicate that this approach is highly efficient and scalable, but further optimizations are needed to increase sorting speed and reduce misclassification errors.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

E-waste management system using image sensing and YOLOv8 showcases a highly efficient and automated approach to tackling the pressing issue of electronic waste. The system's ability to accurately detect and classify various types of e-waste in real time addresses a major bottleneck in current waste management systems, where manual sorting often leads to inefficiencies and mismanagement. By using AI for object recognition, this project not only streamlines the sorting process but also reduces human error, leading to faster and more reliable recycling workflows.

Key Contributions:

Developed a cost-effective image sensing-based classification system for e-waste management.

Implemented a CNN-based deep learning model to achieve high classification accuracy.

Designed an automated sorting mechanism using servo motors and Arduino Nano.

Future Enhancements:

1. Integration with IoT: Real-time monitoring and tracking of sorted e-waste items.

2. Larger Dataset: Expanding the training dataset to include more diverse e-waste components.

3. Improved Sorting Accuracy: Enhancing the servo motor system for better object placement.

REFERENCES

- [1] Abadleh A, Al-Hawari E, Alkafaween E, Al-Sawalqah H (2017) Step detection algorithm for accurate distance estimation using dynamic step length. In: Proceedings of the 18th IEEE International Conference on Mobile Data Management, Daejeon.
- [2] Alam KM, El Saddik A (2017) C2PS: a digital twin architecture reference model for the cloud-based cyber-physical systems. IEEE
- [3] Albertos P, Goodwin GC (2002) Virtual sensors for control applications. *Annu Rev Control* 26:101–112
- [4] Baier L, Ku“hl N, Satzger G (2019) How to cope with change? Preserving validity of predictive services over time. In: Proceedings of the 52nd Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences, Maui.
- [5] Beverungen D, Kundisch D, Wu“nderlich N (2020) Transforming into a platform provider: strategic options for industrial smart service providers. *J Serv Manag.* Blanchard BS, Verma DC, Peterson EL (1995) Maintainability: a key to effective serviceability and maintenance management. Wiley, Hoboken
- [6] Bo“hmann T, Leimeister JM, Mo“slein K (2014) Service systems engineering: a field for future information systems research. *Bus Inf Syst Eng* 6:73–79.
- [7] Bose S, Sarkar D, Mukherjee N (2019) A framework for heterogeneous resource allocation in sensor-cloud environment. *Wirel Pers Commun* 108:19–36.
- [8] Brooks RR, Iyengar SS (1998) Multi-sensor fusion: fundamentals and applications with software. Prentice-Hall, New Jersey Chanson M, Bogner A, Bilgeri D et al (2019) Privacy preserving data certification in the internet of things: leveraging blockchain technology to protect sensor data. *J Assoc Inf Syst.* <https://doi.org/10.3929/ethz-b-000331556>
- [9] Chiu S, Morley D, Martin J (1986) Sensor data fusion on a parallel processor. In: Proceedings of the 1986 IEEE international conference on robotics and automation, San Francisco.

Inferno Rover

A Robotic Solution for Fire-Fighting

Abhishek R. S

Department of Computer Science and Engineering, John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of Technology Kannammoola, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, India.
Email: abhishekr412@gmail.com

Praveen George

Department of Computer Science and Engineering, John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of Technology Kannammoola, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, India.
Email: iampraveengeorge06@gmail.com

Ashin V.

Department of Computer Science and Engineering, John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of Technology Kannammoola, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, India.
Email: ashinv02@gmail.com

Reshma S.

Department of Computer Science and Engineering, John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of Technology Kannammoola, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, India.
Email: reshmas14tvm@gmail.com

Abstract—Fire emergencies pose a significant threat to lives and property, necessitating rapid and efficient response systems. This paper presents the development of an autonomous fire-fighting robot designed to enhance emergency response by quickly addressing fire hazards. Equipped with a water-based suppression system and a line-following navigation algorithm, the robot independently detects and extinguishes fires. Advanced sensors, including thermal imaging, enable it to identify the presence of trapped individuals, adding a life-saving component. Real-time communication ensures constant updates on fire status, supporting coordinated efforts in large-scale emergencies. Future enhancements may include AI-driven fire spread prediction, improved navigation algorithms, multi-robot teamwork, and integration with smart building infrastructure.

Keywords—Autonomous robot, fire-fighting, emergency response, navigation, suppression system.

I. INTRODUCTION

Fire incidents pose a significant risk in various environments, requiring immediate intervention. Traditional fire-fighting methods rely on human firefighters, exposing them to hazardous conditions. Although modern fire detection systems are in place, they lack real-time decision-making capabilities and require human intervention for action. This project introduces Inferno Rover, an autonomous fire-fighting robot capable of navigating through predefined paths to detect, report, and respond to fire outbreaks. Using a line-following algorithm and a water-based suppression system, the robot ensures rapid fire management while reducing human risk.

II. OBJECTIVES

Autonomous Navigation: The robot employs a line-following algorithm using infrared (IR) sensors to

autonomously navigate predefined paths. This ensures systematic movement through buildings or industrial sites without requiring manual intervention. By adhering to structured routes, the robot can reach fire-affected zones efficiently, reducing response time.

Fire Detection & Suppression: The robot is equipped with flame sensors that continuously monitor the environment for fire hazards. Once a fire is detected, the fire suppression module is activated, which includes a water-based system for extinguishing flames. This automated approach minimizes human risk and allows for quick containment of small fires before they spread.

Human Detection Module: A critical feature of the Inferno Rover is its ability to detect trapped individuals in fire-affected areas. Using thermal imaging and object recognition algorithms (YOLOv8), the robot can distinguish between humans, animals, and fire sources. This data is then relayed to emergency response teams for prioritizing rescue efforts.

Real-Time Communication: The robot is integrated with wireless communication modules, enabling real-time data transmission to external control units. This feature ensures continuous monitoring of fire incidents, allowing emergency personnel to receive updates on fire intensity, location, and the presence of survivors.

Scalability & Adaptability: Designed to function in multiple environments, including residential buildings, commercial spaces, industrial sites, and warehouses, the

system is scalable and can be upgraded with AI-based fire spread prediction, enhanced path planning algorithms, and multi-robot collaboration. This adaptability makes the Inferno Rover a versatile and future-proof fire management solution.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Several studies have explored autonomous fire-fighting robots and related technologies:

- **Autonomous Fire-Fighting Robot System**

Design^[1]: This research highlights the development of robots with line-following navigation and fire detection using flame sensors. While effective in controlled environments, these robots struggle in complex, real-world fire scenarios due to obstacles, unpredictable fire patterns, and environmental factors such as smoke and heat.

- **Multi-Robot Collaboration in Firefighting**^[2]:

Studies on swarm intelligence suggest that coordinating multiple robots improves firefighting efficiency. Swarm robotics allows multiple units to distribute tasks such as fire suppression and human rescue, reducing response time. However, real-time communication between robots remains a challenge, particularly in environments where wireless signals may be disrupted.

- **Human Detection in Fire Emergencies Using**

Thermal Imaging^[3]: Research demonstrates the potential of thermal cameras for identifying trapped individuals in smoke-filled environments. Thermal imaging is useful in detecting body heat signatures, but accuracy decreases when victims are unconscious, hidden behind objects, or in extreme heat conditions that obscure their heat patterns.

- **Smart Fire-Fighting Systems for Smart**

Buildings^[4]: IoT-integrated robots show promise in enhancing fire response by linking with building automation systems. These robots receive real-time updates on fire location and conditions from smart sensors, improving response accuracy. However, their effectiveness is limited by network reliability, as connectivity failures may hinder data transmission.

- **AI-Powered Fire Spread Prediction**^[6]: Machine-learning models help predict fire spread based on environmental factors such as temperature, wind direction, and material flammability. AI-powered robots can proactively plan suppression strategies, optimizing resource allocation. However, high computational requirements pose scalability challenges, making real-time decision-making difficult in large-scale fire incidents.

These studies provide valuable insights for designing an efficient and autonomous fire-fighting system, addressing key challenges in fire suppression, human rescue, and environmental adaptation.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The **Inferno Rover** is designed as an autonomous robotic system equipped with various modules to efficiently detect, suppress, and report fire incidents while ensuring human safety. The system consists of the following key components:

A. System Architecture

The **Inferno Rover** operates using an ESP32 microcontroller, which processes sensor inputs and autonomously executes navigation and suppression tasks. The robot communicates real-time data using Wi-Fi to ensure constant monitoring and efficient control. The primary hardware components include.

- 1) **Infrared (IR) sensors** for detecting predefined navigation paths.
- 2) **Flame sensors** to identify fire sources and determine fire intensity.
- 3) **ESP32-CAM** for human and animal detection via YOLOv8-based object recognition.
- 4) **L298N motor driver** for precise movement control.
- 5) **Water pump relay system** for automated fire suppression.

B. Functional Modules

1. Line Following Module

- The robot follows a predefined path using IR sensors.
- The ESP32 processes IR sensor data to ensure precise navigation.
- The motor driver adjusts speed and direction for smooth movement.
- This system allows the robot to autonomously move between rooms and high-risk areas.

2. Fire Detection and Reporting Module

- The flame sensors detect heat and fire anomalies.
- Once fire is identified, the ESP32 controller sends alerts to the control unit via Wi-Fi.
- Real-time reporting ensures immediate intervention and fire management.

3. Multi-Class Detection Module

- The ESP32-CAM module captures images for human and animal detection.
- The images are processed using a YOLOv8 model to identify trapped individuals.
- The system can classify humans, pets, or other life forms in fire zones.
- Alerts are transmitted to emergency responders to prioritize rescue operations.

4. Fire Suppression Module

- Upon fire detection, the ESP32 triggers the relay-controlled water pump.
- The pump activates a water-based suppression system to extinguish flames.

- This module ensures that the fire is controlled before spreading further.

C. Communication and Remote Monitoring

- The Inferno Rover integrates real-time Wi-Fi communication to send updates on fire detection and suppression status.
- Data logs are transmitted to a central control system, where responders can track fire incidents.
- The system supports remote monitoring, enabling manual intervention if necessary.

V. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

1. Flame Sensor

The flame sensors used in the system detect infrared (IR) radiation emitted by fire sources. The experimental testing involved:

- **Range Testing:** The sensors were tested at different distances (10 cm, 20 cm, 30 cm, 50 cm) to determine the maximum range at which fire could be accurately detected.
- **False Positive Evaluation:** The sensor was exposed to external light sources such as sunlight, incandescent bulbs, and LED lights to observe any erroneous fire detection.
- **Response Time:** The time taken for the sensor to trigger an alert after fire detection was measured using a stopwatch.

Test Distance (cm)	Number of Trials	True Positives (TP)	False Positives (FP)	Accuracy (%)
10 cm	25	25	0	100%
20 cm	25	24	1	96%
30 cm	25	22	3	88%
50 cm	25	19	6	76%

Findings

- The flame sensor provided accurate readings up to 30 cm.
- At angles greater than 60°, the detection accuracy dropped by 20%.
- Some false positives were recorded under intense sunlight, requiring calibration.
- Average response time was 20 to 30 seconds.

2. Infra-Red Sensor

The infrared sensors are used for detecting the black line on the ground, guiding the rover along a predefined path. The experiments conducted were:

- **Lighting Condition Impact:** The sensors were tested under bright indoor lighting, dim conditions, and complete darkness to determine their adaptability.

- **Detection Accuracy:** The percentage of successful path detections was recorded by running the rover over different line patterns (straight, curved, and intersecting).

Test Scenario	Number of Trials	True Positives (TP)	False Positives (FP)	Accuracy (%)
Straight Path	25	24	1	96%
Curved Path	25	21	4	84%
Intersections	25	18	7	72%

Findings

- Performance was optimal on smooth surfaces but reduced on reflective tiles.
- Bright ambient lighting slightly affected IR sensor readings.
- The detection accuracy was 96% on straight lines, 84% on curves, and 72% on intersections.
- i. **Path Following Efficiency:** The line-following module was tested with:
 - **Straight and Curved Paths:** Measuring accuracy in following predefined routes.
 - **Time to Destination:** Measuring the time taken for the rover to reach the fire location.

Navigation Scenario	Number of Trials	Successful Navigation (TP)	Failed Navigation (FP)	Success Rate (%)
Straight Line	50	49	1	98%
Curved Path	50	42	8	84%
Intersection Handling	50	38	12	76%

Findings

- Accuracy on straight paths: 98%, curved paths: 84%.
- Average time to reach the fire source was 20-30 seconds.

The Rover successfully detected fires, navigated to the source, and extinguished flames with high accuracy. The line-following module functioned efficiently, though obstacles occasionally disrupted navigation. Additionally, the flame sensors required calibration to minimize false positives in bright lighting conditions.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

The Inferno Rover marks significant progress in fire-fighting technology by integrating autonomous navigation, fire suppression^[5], and human detection to minimize human risk and improve response efficiency. Future enhancements will focus on AI-powered fire spread prediction^[6], allowing for proactive response strategies, as well as multi-robot collaboration^[2], improving large-scale fire management. Additional developments include advanced navigation algorithms for handling dynamic environments^[15], enhanced wireless communication for reliable data transmission in high-interference zones, and integration with IoT-based smart buildings^[4] to provide a fully automated fire-fighting solution.

These advancements will enhance the adaptability and effectiveness of the system, making it a robust and scalable tool for modern fire-fighting applications.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We express our sincere gratitude to the faculty and staff of the Department of Computer Science and Engineering at John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of Technology for their valuable guidance and support throughout this research. We also extend our appreciation to APJ Abdul Kalam Technological University for providing the academic framework that enabled this study. Furthermore, we acknowledge the contributions of our peers and researchers whose work has laid the foundation for advancements in IoT-based smart agriculture. Lastly, we thank our families and friends for their encouragement and unwavering support during this research.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Ahmadi; P. Stone ; Tushar Nandkishor Satbhai. Autonomous Fire-Fighting Robot System Design. 2018, [Research Gate]
- [2] Mauro S. Innocente; Paolo Grasso. Multi-Robot Collaboration in Firefighting, 2019, [Research Gate]
- [3] Z. Ren; Q Saffir ; Swati ; Human Detection in Fire Emergencies Using Thermal Imaging (2020), [Google scholar] [CrossRef]
- [4] L. Wang; M. Zhou. Smart Fire-Fighting Systems for Smart Buildings. 2021.[MDPI]
- [5] R. K. Gupta; S. Bhatia; Swati A. Deshmukh. Water-Based vs. Chemical Fire Suppression in Autonomous Robots. 2022.[Research Gate]
- [6] A. Patel; Saffir; J. Li. AI-Powered Fire Spread Prediction for Autonomous Robots.2023.[MDPI]
- [7] B. Chen; U. Jyostna; Sai Prasanna; R. Singh. Obstacle Detection and Avoidance in Fire- Fighting Robots. 2022.[IEEE] [CrossRef]
- [8] Sahil S.; Shah; D. Martinez; F. Wang; Robust Fire-Fighting in Harsh Environments. 2023.
- [9] Aliff, M.; Samsiah, N.; Yusof, M.; Zainal, A. Development of Fire Fighting Robot (QRob). Int. J. Adv. Comput. Sci. Appl. 2019, 10, 142 147. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef]
- [10] Bogue, R. The role of robots in firefighting. Ind. Robot. Int. J. Robot. Res. Appl. 2021, 48, 174–178. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef]
- [11] Ch. Bhawana; Venkatesh Thota; Srinivas Bachu. Artificial Intelligence based Wheeled Fire Fighting Robot with A Fire Extinguishing, Ball-Shooting Turret for Forest Areas. DOI: 10.1109/EICEEAI60672.2023.10590289[IEEE]
- [12] Ayman Yahya; Arbad Sarhan; Lewaa Omar;. Remotely Controlled Firefighting Robo with ESP32-CAM Module . DOI: 10.1109/EICEEAI60672.2023.10590289 [IEEE]
- [13] Ando, H.; Ambe, Y.; Ishii, A.; Konyo, M.; Tadakuma, K.; Maruyama, S.; Tadokoro, S. Aerial Hose Type Robot by Water Jet for Fire Fighting. IEEE Robot. Autom. Lett. 2018, 3, 1128–1135
- [14] Li, S.; Feng, C.; Niu, Y.; Shi, L.; Wu, Z.; Song, H. A Fire Reconnaissance Robot Based on SLAM Position, Thermal Imaging Technologies, and AR Display. Sensors 2019, 19, 5036. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef]
- [15] Jing Yuanquan, Wang Yuehui, Han Wei, et al. Overview of SLAM methods for driverless vehicles and mobile robots [J] Electronic World,2021 (13): 4-5

MALWARESHIELD AI USING DEEP LEARNING AND XAI

Abin S. Sam, Adithya R.J., Akshay M., A.J. Aswathy Department of Computer Science and Engineering John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of Technology, Kerala, India

Abstract—In the realm of cybersecurity, the detection and resolution of malware are critical to safeguarding digital infrastructure. The existing systems predominantly rely on artificial intelligence (AI) technologies to identify and mitigate threats. These systems scan binary information from the system, comparing it against known malicious code signatures. Upon detection, the software is flagged as malicious, preventing its execution. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) are the primary technologies employed for code fetching and analysis in these systems. Our proposed system, Malware Shield AI, advances this approach by integrating deep learning and Explainable AI (XAI) to enhance both detection and resolution capabilities. Unlike traditional methods, Malware Shield AI analyses both binary datasets and behavioural patterns exhibited by the device to identify potential threats. The inclusion of XAI provides users with transparent explanations for why a particular software is flagged or restricted, fostering greater trust and understanding. Additionally, a dynamic analysis module is incorporated to detect and respond to malicious behaviours in real-time, ensuring comprehensive protection against evolving threats. Malware Shield AI represents a significant leap forward in malware detection and resolution, combining the strengths of deep learning and XAI to deliver a robust, user-friendly solution for modern cybersecurity challenges.

Keywords— *Malware detection, artificial intelligence, machine learning, dynamic analysis, static analysis, cybersecurity*

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's digital landscape, the increasing sophistication of malware, including zero-day exploits and polymorphic viruses, has rendered traditional antivirus methods less effective. To address this, AI-powered malware detection systems are emerging as a robust solution by integrating static and dynamic analysis with machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) algorithms. These systems not only detect known threats but also identify emerging malware through behavior monitoring and pattern recognition. By combining both static and dynamic analysis, the system enhances its ability to detect various types of malicious software more effectively. This project aims to design an AI-based malware detection and removal system that enhances security through real-time notifications, explainable AI (XAI), and a continuously updated malware signature database. The system will provide comprehensive

protection by analyzing malware characteristics, developing DL-based detection algorithms, and offering customizable security solutions. Through rigorous testing and validation, the project seeks to deliver an efficient and user-friendly system that mitigates security risks and promotes awareness about evolving cyber threats.

II. Literature Survey

In recent years, several approaches have been explored to enhance malware detection using artificial intelligence. Traditional antivirus solutions primarily relied on signature-based techniques, which involve identifying known patterns of malware code. However, as cyber threats evolved, heuristic and behavior-based methods emerged to detect previously unknown threats. Static analysis techniques, such as opcode frequency analysis and control flow analysis, have been widely used to analyze the structure and behavior of executable files. Dynamic analysis techniques, including sandboxing and system call monitoring, offer a complementary approach by observing program behavior in a controlled environment. Recent advancements have seen the integration of ML and DL algorithms to improve malware detection accuracy. Supervised learning techniques, such as Support Vector Machines (SVMs) and Random Forests, have demonstrated notable success in classifying malware based on extracted features. Deep learning models, including Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), have further enhanced detection by identifying complex patterns within large datasets. Studies have also highlighted the effectiveness of hybrid models that combine static and dynamic analysis to improve overall detection efficiency. Moreover, the application of explainable AI (XAI) has gained attention, providing insights into model decisions and improving user trust. However, despite these advancements, challenges such as high false-positive rates and evolving malware tactics necessitate continuous improvement and adaptation of AI-based detection systems.

III. OBJECTIVES

The primary objectives of this research include evaluating the current malware threat environment and identifying the limitations of conventional detection techniques, with an emphasis on emerging threats such as zero-day exploits and polymorphic malware. The study also aims to integrate AI technologies, including ML, DL, and other AI models, to enhance malware detection and remediation strategies by adapting to new malware patterns and reducing response times. A deep learning algorithm will be developed to accurately classify and detect malicious software by extracting meaningful features. The algorithm will continuously evolve by learning from new data, improving its predictive accuracy. Enhancing detection efficiency is another key objective, ensuring that the system remains reliable and effective in real-time environments by minimizing false positives through statistical analysis and performance evaluation. The study also seeks to develop user-friendly malware detection tools that facilitate effective malware identification and removal. These tools will be designed to ensure ease of use for enterprises and individual users while promoting awareness among users and organizations about malware threats and encouraging proactive security measures.

IV. SCOPE

This study investigates the use of AI technologies, particularly ML and DL, to enhance malware detection techniques. The research encompasses the analysis of malware evolution, from simple pranks to sophisticated attacks orchestrated by organized cybercrime. It aims to develop an efficient and scalable detection algorithm capable of identifying malware on various platforms, including Windows and Android. Statistical analyses will be conducted to identify malware characteristics, which will inform the development of detection tools. Additionally, the study will explore the effectiveness of combining static and dynamic analysis to enhance the accuracy of malware detection. AI-based detection models will be assessed for their ability to adapt to evolving threat landscapes and their robustness in detecting polymorphic and metamorphic malware. Moreover, the study will involve the development of user-friendly interfaces and tools that enable seamless deployment of the proposed system across diverse platforms, ensuring accessibility and usability for enterprises and individuals alike.

V. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed system is designed to provide a comprehensive solution for detecting and removing malware using AI-based technologies. It integrates both static and dynamic analysis techniques to identify malicious files and abnormal behaviors effectively. Static analysis examines the code structure, file attributes, and metadata without executing the file, while dynamic analysis monitors the runtime behavior of a program in a controlled environment to detect anomalies and suspicious activities. The system utilizes a hybrid approach

that combines these techniques with machine learning models to enhance detection accuracy.

A key feature of the proposed system is the implementation of a deep learning (DL)-based detection algorithm that analyzes and classifies malware using a large dataset of known and unknown malware samples. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) are employed to identify intricate patterns within the data, improving the system's predictive performance. To ensure high detection accuracy, feature extraction techniques such as opcode frequency, API call patterns, and system call sequences are applied.

The system is also equipped with real-time monitoring capabilities, enabling it to detect and respond to threats immediately. Automated incident response mechanisms can isolate and neutralize detected threats, reducing the risk of further compromise. The integration of explainable AI (XAI) ensures transparency in the decision-making process by providing users with a clear understanding of why a file or behavior was classified as malicious. Furthermore, the system maintains an updated malware signature database, enabling it to stay current with evolving threats. The proposed system's architecture is designed to be scalable and adaptable, ensuring its applicability across different platforms and environments, including corporate networks, cloud infrastructures, and endpoint devices.

VI. METHODOLOGY

A. Static Analysis

Static analysis involves examining the code and structure of a file without executing it. This method identifies known malware patterns using signature-based detection techniques, allowing for the identification of threats before execution. Static analysis provides insights into the structure, metadata, and characteristics of a file, enabling early detection of malicious activity.

B. Dynamic Analysis

Dynamic analysis monitors the behavior of programs during execution, identifying anomalies indicative of malicious activity. By executing the program in a controlled environment, dynamic analysis detects threats that may evade static analysis. This approach is effective against polymorphic and

metamorphic malware, which modify their code structure dynamically to avoid detection.

C. Machine Learning Models

The proposed system employs supervised and unsupervised ML models for feature extraction and classification. Supervised learning models, trained on labelled data, identify known malware patterns, while unsupervised models detect unknown patterns and anomalies. These models continuously improve through learning and adapting to new threats.

D. Deep Learning Techniques

Deep learning models, including convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and recurrent neural networks (RNNs), enhance detection accuracy by capturing complex patterns and behaviors in large datasets. CNNs excel at analyzing visual and structural features, while RNNs are effective in identifying sequential patterns in malware behavior.

E. Feature Extraction

Feature extraction techniques such as opcode frequency analysis, system call monitoring, and API usage patterns enable the system to identify distinguishing characteristics of different types of malwares. This improves the classification accuracy and reduces false positives.

F. Continuous Learning and Adaptation

The system dynamically adapts by incorporating feedback from previously detected threats, improving its overall performance. Continuous learning ensures that the system remains effective against evolving malware patterns and enhances its ability to detect zero-day threats.

VII. RESULTS

The proposed system has been rigorously tested against existing malware detection frameworks to evaluate its performance. The results demonstrate improved detection rates, reduced false positives, and enhanced operational efficiency. Statistical analysis highlights the effectiveness of integrating AI techniques with traditional detection methods, offering a more reliable and adaptive solution. The system was evaluated using benchmark malware datasets, and the proposed DL algorithm outperformed conventional methods in identifying both known and unknown threats. Moreover, the system's ability to reduce false positives significantly improves its practical applicability in real-world scenarios. Through rigorous testing in simulated environments, the proposed model demonstrated its capability to identify and classify various malware types accurately, while maintaining high detection efficiency. The incorporation of XAI ensures transparency and trust in the decision-making process, providing users with detailed insights into detection outcomes.

Metric	MalwareShield AI Score	Traditional AV Software
Detection Accuracy	96.5%	~ 85%
False Positive Rate	3.2%	~ 10%
False Negative Rate	2.8%	~ 12%
Detection Speed	0.5s per file	~ 1.2s per file
Explainability	Yes (XAI Module)	No

VIII. CONCLUSION

This research introduces an AI-based malware detection and removal system that effectively combines static and dynamic analysis with ML and DL technologies. The proposed solution enhances detection efficiency, reduces security risks, and provides real-time notifications to keep users informed. Furthermore, the integration of explainable AI (XAI) ensures transparency in decision-making, promoting trust in the system. The system's adaptability to new malware patterns and its ability to learn from emerging threats make it a valuable tool in combating evolving cyber threats. Future research will focus on improving the scalability and adaptability of the system to address the ever-evolving cyber threat landscape. This includes exploring federated learning approaches to enhance model training across decentralized data sources and ensuring continuous improvement in detection efficiency.

REFERENCES

- [1] Kotenko I, Vitkova L, Saenko I, et al. The intelligent system for detection and counteraction of malicious and inappropriate information on the Internet. *Ai Communications*, vol. 33, no. 1, pp. 1- 13, 2020.
- [2] Lyamin N, Kleyko D, Delooz Q, et al. AI-Based Malicious Network Traffic Detection in VANETs. *IEEE Network*, vol. 32, no. 6, pp. 15- 21, 2018.
- [3] Al-Zewairi M, Almajali S, Ayyash M. Unknown Security Attack Detection Using Shallow and Deep ANN Classifiers. *Electronics*, vol. 9, no. 12, pp. 2006, 2020.
- [4] Hussain B, Du Q, Sun B, et al. Deep Learning-Based DDoS-Attack Detection for Cyber-Physical System over 5G network. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 17, no. 2, pp. 860-870, 2021.
- [5] Gupta S, Nguyen D, Rana S, et al. Verification of integrity of deployed deep learning models using Bayesian Optimization. *Knowledge-based systems*, vol. 2022, no. 6, pp. 241, 2022.

[6] Alejandro G. Martín, Alberto Fernández-Isabel, César González- Fernández, et al. Suspicious news detection through semantic and sentiment measures. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 101, no. 2, pp. 104230, 2021.

[7] Nancy P, Muthurajkumar S, Ganapathy S, et al. Intrusion detection using dynamic feature selection and fuzzy temporal decision tree classification for wireless sensor networks. *IET Communications*, vol. 14, no. 5, pp. 888-895, 2020.

[8] Li L, Yu Y, Bai S, et al. An Effective Two-Step Intrusion Detection Approach Based on Binary Classification and k-NN. *IEEE ACCESS*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 12060-12073, 2018.

[9] Zhang H, Xiao Z, Gu J, et al. A network anomaly detection algorithm based on semi-supervised learning and adaptive multiclass balancing. *Journal of supercomputing*, vol. 2023, no. 18, pp. 79, 2023.

[10] Iadarola G, Martinelli F, Mercaldo F, et al. Towards an Interpretable Deep Learning Model for Mobile Malware Detection and Family Identification. *Computers & Security*, vol. 105, no. 2, pp. 102198, 2021.

[11] Shi F, Zhu P, Zhou X, et al. Network attack detection and visual payload labeling technology based on Seq2Seq architecture with attention mechanism. *International Journal of Distributed Sensor Networks*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 155014772091701, 2020.

[12] Choi S, Bae J, Lee C, et al. Attention-Based Automated Feature Extraction for Malware Analysis. *Sensors*, vol. 20, no. 10, pp. 2893, 2020.

[13] Jerbi M, Dagdia Z C, Bechikh S, et al. On the use of artificial malicious patterns for android malware detection. *Computers & Security*, vol. 92, no. 5, pp. 101743.1-101743.22, 2020.

MANUFACTURING OF PAVER BLOCK BY REPLACING COARSE AGGREGATE WITH REFRACTORY BRICK AGGREGATES AND SAND WITH RECYCLED GLASS

Abhishek J S, Chrispin Raj W, Hephzibah Mol R, Varsha S Cheraman

Civil Engineering dept.

John Cox Memorial C.S.I Institute Of Technology

Trivandrum, India

Abstract- The construction industry is continuously seeking sustainable alternatives to traditional materials to minimize environmental impact and reduce resource depletion. This study focuses on the manufacturing of paver blocks by replacing conventional coarse aggregates with crushed refractory brick aggregates and substituting natural sand with recycled glass. Refractory bricks, known for their high heat resistance and durability, are often discarded after industrial use, making them a potential replacement for coarse aggregates in concrete. Similarly, glass waste, which poses disposal challenges, can be finely crushed and used as a partial or complete replacement for sand. This research aims to assess the feasibility of these replacements in terms of strength, durability, and overall performance of the paver blocks. The experimental methodology involves preparing different mix proportions of paver blocks incorporating varying percentages of refractory brick aggregates and recycled glass. These blocks will undergo mechanical testing, including compressive strength, water absorption, split tensile strength and flexural strength to compare their performance with conventional paver blocks. The expectation is that refractory brick aggregates will contribute to improved thermal stability and load-bearing capacity, while recycled glass will enhance the surface finish and reduce water absorption. The study will also analyze the economic and environmental advantages of these alternative materials, emphasizing waste reduction and resource conservation. The anticipated outcomes of this research could pave the way for sustainable construction practices by promoting the use of industrial and domestic waste materials

in building applications **Keywords-** Refractory brick; Recycled glass; Compressive Strength; Flexural Strength; Tensile Strength; Split Tensile ; Water Bsrption.

I. INTRODUCTION

Paver blocks are versatile, durable, and aesthetically appealing paving materials commonly used for walkways, driveways, patios, and other outdoor spaces. They are typically made from concrete, clay, or a combination of aggregates, providing a strong and long-lasting surface that can withstand various environmental conditions. Paver blocks are precast concrete or clay units designed for various paving applications. They come in a variety of shapes, sizes, colours, and textures, allowing for creative design and practical solutions in both residential and commercial settings. Paver blocks are engineered to withstand heavy traffic and harsh weather conditions, making them ideal for driveways, walkways, and public spaces. With numerous design options, paver blocks can enhance the visual appeal of any area. They can be arranged in countless patterns, contributing to unique landscaping designs. Many paver blocks are now made using recycled materials, promoting eco-friendly construction practices. They also facilitate water drainage, reducing runoff and supporting environmental sustainability. Paver blocks can be installed quickly and efficiently. If any block is damaged, it can be replaced individually without disturbing the surrounding area, making maintenance straight forward. Suitable for various applications, paver blocks are commonly used in residential driveways, pedestrian walkways, plazas, and even industrial sites.

Paver blocks represent a perfect blend of functionality, aesthetics, and sustainability. Their adaptability and durability make them a favoured choice in today's construction practices. As we delve deeper into this topic, we will explore their manufacturing processes, applications, and the latest innovations in paver block technology. The exact number of paver blocks manufactured in India can vary significantly each year based on factors such as demand, construction activity, and market conditions. However, the paver block industry in India is substantial, with millions of units produced annually to meet the needs of urban development, infrastructure projects, and landscaping. As of recent estimates, the Indian paver block market is valued at several billion dollars, and production can easily reach several hundred million blocks per year. The industry has been growing, driven by increasing urbanization, government infrastructure projects, and a rising focus on sustainable building materials. For the most accurate and current statistics, industry reports or publications from construction and materials organizations would provide detailed insights

II. SPECIMEN PREPARATION AND TESTING

A. Materials

1. REFRACTORY BRICK

Refractory brick, also known as firebrick, is a specialized type of brick designed to withstand high temperatures and harsh environments without deforming or melting. These bricks are used in various applications where resistance to heat and thermal shock is crucial. Refractory bricks can typically withstand temperatures exceeding 1,000 °C (1,832 °F) without losing their structural integrity. They provide excellent insulation, which helps to retain heat in high-temperature applications while protecting surrounding structures from heat damage. Many refractory bricks are resistant to chemical attacks, making them suitable for use in environments where corrosive materials are present. They exhibit good mechanical strength and stability, ensuring longevity in demanding applications.

Refractory bricks are highly resistant to wear and thermal shock, leading to a longer service life compared to standard materials. This reduces the frequency and costs associated

with repairs and replacements. Their excellent insulating properties help maintain temperature stability, which can lower energy costs in heating or cooling applications. This is particularly beneficial in industrial settings where maintaining high temperatures is essential. Due to their resilience against harsh conditions, refractory bricks require less maintenance over time, translating to lower operational costs. Their high strength can lead to thinner walls or smaller structures while still meeting safety and performance standards, reducing material usage and overall construction costs. In high-temperature environments (like kilns and furnaces), using refractory bricks can minimize downtime and maintenance costs associated with frequent replacements of other materials. Many refractory bricks can be made from recycled materials, which can lower material costs and support sustainable construction practices. Their use in various applications (e.g., furnaces, kilns, and chimneys) allows for integration into multiple projects, potentially reducing the need for different materials and simplifying procurement processes. The initial investment in refractory bricks can lead to significant long-term savings in construction projects. Their durability, energy efficiency, and low maintenance needs make them a cost-effective choice, particularly in high-temperature and industrial applications

Fig. 1 Refractory Brick

2. RECYCLED GLASS

Recycled glass refers to glass materials that have been collected, processed, and repurposed for use in new products. This sustainable material is increasingly being utilized in various industries, including construction, packaging, and manufacturing.

Fig 2. Glass Pellets

3. Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC):

Ordinary Portland Cement is the most commonly used type of cement for general construction purposes. It is made by finely grinding clinker, which is produced by heating a mixture of limestone and clay in a kiln. It reacts with water to form a solid mass, gaining strength over time. This makes it suitable for use in wet conditions. High early strength allows for faster construction. OPC typically achieves significant strength within the first 28 days. It provides good resistance to environmental conditions, making it suitable for a variety of structures. It has good workability, allowing it to be mixed with aggregates and moulded into various shapes. It has a relatively quick setting time, which can be adjusted by using retarders or accelerators. It is the most commonly used cement globally, making it a standard material in construction. It provides the necessary strength and stability for structural applications, including buildings, bridges, and roads

4. COARSE AGGREGATES

In the construction of paver blocks, several types of coarse aggregates can be used such as Crushed Stone Aggregates each with specific properties that contribute to the strength, durability, and aesthetics of the blocks. The aggregates should be clean and free from impurities, such as clay or organic matter, which can weaken the bond. The size of coarse aggregates used in paver blocks range from 4.75 mm to 20 mm.

5. FINE AGGREGATE

M Sand, or manufactured sand, is a fine aggregate that is typically cubical in shape, which improves the workability and strength of concrete. Its particle size range is finer than river sand, ranging from 0.15-4.75 mm, with a specific gravity of 2.6-2.8 and a density of 1600-1700 kg/m³. M Sand has a lower porosity than river sand, reducing the amount of water

required in concrete. Chemically, M Sand is composed of silicates, aluminosilicates, and iron oxides, with a pH value of 7-8 and lower alkalinity than river sand. Mechanically, M Sand can improve the compressive strength of concrete, with values ranging from 20-50 MPa, as well as its tensile and flexural strength. In terms of durability, M Sand can improve the resistance of concrete to chloride ion penetration, sulfate attack, and freeze-thaw cycles. The advantages of M-Sand include improved workability, increased strength, reduced water demand, and improved durability. However, M-Sand is typically more expensive than river sand, may not be widely available, and requires specialized equipment for production and processing.

6. **Admixtures** are chemical additives incorporated into concrete to enhance its properties and overall performance, making it more durable, workable, and structurally efficient. These additives play a crucial role in modern construction by improving various characteristics of concrete, such as workability, strength, shrinkage control, and durability. Admixtures are classified into different types based on their function, including air-entraining admixtures, retarding admixtures, accelerating admixtures, water-reducing admixtures, and super plasticizers. Air-entraining admixtures introduce tiny air bubbles into the concrete mix, improving its workability and increasing resistance to freeze-thaw cycles, making it ideal for structures exposed to harsh weather conditions. Retarding admixtures slow down the setting time of concrete, allowing for extended working periods, which is particularly beneficial in large-scale construction projects or hot weather conditions where rapid setting could be problematic. On the other hand, accelerating admixtures speed up the setting process, helping to achieve early strength development, which is advantageous for fast-track construction projects and repairs. Water-reducing admixtures help lower the amount of water required in the concrete mix without compromising its workability, which enhances its overall strength and durability by reducing the water-cement ratio. Super plasticizers, also known as high-range water reducers, can significantly decrease the water content in the concrete by up to 30% while maintaining excellent workability, resulting in high-

strength, high-performance concrete that is more durable and resistant to environmental factors. The use of admixtures in concrete construction provides numerous advantages, such as increased efficiency, improved structural integrity, and better adaptability to varying site conditions. By modifying concrete properties to suit specific project requirements, admixtures contribute to the production of high performance concrete that meets modern construction standards, ensuring long-lasting and resilient structures.

Fig 3. Sikament340

7. White cement

White cement can be as strong as normal cement, but it's often used for aesthetic purposes. White cement is finer than normal cement, which gives it a smoother finish. White cement is made with less iron oxide and manganese oxide than normal cement, which makes it finer. Normal cement contains more of these elements, which makes it denser. White cement is often used for interior and exterior aesthetic purposes, such as plastering, base layers, and ornate floorings. Normal cement is often used for construction projects, such as building bridges and other large structures.

SAMPLE PREPARATION

Combine the cement, fine aggregate, and coarse aggregate in a concrete mixer until the mixture is uniform in colour and consistency. Gradually add the calculated amount of water to the mix while mixing continuously to achieve a workable consistency. The mix should be cohesive and easily mouldable without excessive water separation. The sample preparation process began with the crushing of refractory bricks into aggregate form using a jaw crusher. The crushed aggregate was then sieved into using a sieve shaker. The sieved aggregate was subsequently

cleaned to remove any dust or debris. In parallel, glass was crushed into powder. The crushed glass powder was then sieved into 0.5mm, using a sieve shaker. The sieved glass powder was also cleaned to remove any dust or debris. The refractory brick aggregate, glass powder, fine aggregate, cement, water, and super plasticizer were then mixed together in a laboratory mixer, following a predetermined mix design methodology. The proportions of the ingredients were carefully controlled to ensure optimal workability and performance. The mixed concrete was then poured into a rubber mould and compacted using a vibration. The paver blocks were subsequently cured in a controlled environment, maintained at a temperature of 20°C and humidity of 80%, for a period of 24 hours. After curing, the paver blocks were subjected to various tests, including compressive strength, split tensile strength, and water absorption to evaluate their performance and suitability for practical applications.

B. Tests Procedure

1 Compressive Strength Test

A compression test on paver blocks is conducted to evaluate their load-bearing capacity and durability. The main purpose for the test is to determine the compressive strength of paver blocks, which ensures they can withstand the expected loads without failure. The main tools are compression testing machines, which are capable of applying load until failure. Measuring tools like callipers and measuring taps were used for marking dimensions. Select a representative sample of paver blocks. Measure and record the dimensions (length, width, height). For this test paver block of 304.8 mm × 177.8 mm × 63.5 mm are used. Ensure the samples are cured properly (usually for 28 days) before testing. Place the paver block in the compression testing machine. Ensure it is centred and aligned properly to avoid uneven stress distribution. Gradually apply load at a uniform rate. Monitor the machine and the block during loading. Record the maximum load the block can withstand before failure. Note any deformation or cracking during the test. Calculate Compressive Strength and compare

the results of normal manufactured paver block with blocks made by replacing. This test is crucial for ensuring that paver blocks can handle the stresses from vehicles and environmental factors over time.

Compressive strength (MPa) =

$$\frac{\text{Maximum load applied (N)}}{\text{Area of specimen (mm}^2\text{)}}$$

Fig 4 Compressive strength Test

2. Flexural Strength Test

The flexural test for paver blocks evaluates their ability to withstand bending loads, which is crucial for assessing their durability and structural integrity in paving applications. It is determine the flexural strength of paver blocks, which helps ensure they can support loads without cracking or breaking under normal usage conditions.

For this test paver block of 304.8 mm × 177.8 mm × 63.5 mm are used. Collect the specimen and clean in properly. Mark the midpoint of the specimen and 5 cm from both the sides. Place the specimen in the machine and align it carefully to ensure that the loading nose applies force at the midpoint or according to the specified loading configuration. Gradually apply the load to the specimen without shock, increasing it at a nominal and constant rate until failure. The load is applied until the specimen fails, and the maximum load is recorded.

$$\text{Flexural strength} = \frac{Pl}{bd^2}$$

P = Maximum load applied to the beam

l = Support length

b = width of the beam

d = failure point depth

Fig 5 Flexural Strength Test

3. Splitting Tensile Strength Test

The split tensile test is used to determine the tensile strength of concrete paver blocks, which helps evaluate their performance under tension. This test is conducted using a universal testing machine. Select a representative sample of paver blocks. Measure and record dimensions (length, width, height). For this test paver block of 304.8 mm × 177.8 mm × 63.5 mm are used. Ensure the samples are properly cured (typically 28 days) to achieve the desired strength. Position the paver block horizontally in the testing apparatus. Align the load application plates to ensure even distribution of stress. Apply a compressive load at a uniform rate until the block fails. The load is applied along the diameter of the block, creating tensile stresses. Record the maximum load at which the paver block fails. Observe any visible signs of cracking or splitting of the specimen (mm). Compare the results with industry standards for paver blocks.

$$\text{Split Tensile Strength} = \frac{2P}{\pi dl}$$

P = Load applied

d= diameter of specimen

l = length of specimen

Fig 6 Split Tensile Strength Test

4. WATER ABSORPTION

A water absorption test on paver blocks is essential to assess their durability and performance. For this test paver block of 304.8 mm × 177.8 mm × 63.5 mm are used. Ensure Weigh each dry paver block using a weighing scale and record the weight as W_1 (dry weight). use the paver blocks are clean and free from dust or debris. Fully submerge the paver blocks in water for 24 hours, ensuring they are completely covered. After 24 hours, remove the blocks from the water and allow any excess water to drip off for a few minutes. Weigh the wet paver blocks and record the weight as W_2 (wet weight). Use these values to calculate the water absorption percentage of the paver blocks.

$$\text{Water Absorption (\%)} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{W_1} \times 100$$

W_1 = Dry weight of the paver block.

W_2 = Wet weight of the paver block after 24hrs immersion in water.

Fig 7 Permeability Test

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH

Table 4.1 Compressive strength

Percentage Replacement	Compressive strength after 7 days of curing (MPa)	Compressive strength after 28 days of curing (MPa)
Normal	14.3	18.74
25% Glass 25% Brick	15.6	19.18
50% Glass 25% Brick	15	18.23
50% Glass 50% Brick	10.14	13.41
25% Glass 50% Brick	14.1	17.8

The table 4.1 presents the compressive strength of paver blocks with different levels of glass and brick replacements after 7 days and 28 days of curing. Normal paver blocks exhibit a

compressive strength of 14.3 MPa at 7 days and 18.74 MPa at 28 days. When 25% glass and 25% brick are incorporated, the compressive strength slightly increases to 15.6 MPa at 7 days and 19.18 MPa at 28 days, suggesting that a balanced proportion of glass and brick enhances early and long-term strength. Similarly, the 50% Glass + 25% Brick mix achieves 15 MPa at 7 days and 18.23 MPa at 28 days, showing that a higher proportion of glass can still maintain compressive strength close to normal paver blocks. However, when both glass and brick replacements reach 50% each, the compressive strength significantly drops to 10.14 MPa at 7 days and 13.41 MPa at 28 days, indicating that excessive replacement negatively impacts the structural integrity of the paver block. The 25% Glass + 50% Brick mix, while slightly weaker than normal paver blocks, still maintains 14.1 MPa at 7 days and 17.8 MPa at 28 days, suggesting that a higher brick content reduces strength more noticeably than glass.

Fig 8 Compressive strength after 7 and 28 days after curing

The test shows that compressive strength generally improves over time, with all paver block mixes gaining strength between 7 days and 28 days, which is a natural characteristic of cement-based materials as hydration progresses. The optimal replacement ratio appears to be 25% Glass + 25% Brick, as it provides a slight improvement in compressive strength over normal paver blocks, making it a viable eco-friendly alternative. However, the 50% Glass + 50% Brick mix shows a drastic reduction in strength, likely due to increased porosity and weaker bonding between materials. These findings highlight the importance of balancing replacement ratios to ensure that sustainable materials can be

effectively used in paver blocks without compromising their structural performance. Future research could focus on optimizing curing conditions, adjusting the particle size of glass and brick, or incorporating admixtures to enhance the bonding and durability of paver blocks made with recycled materials

SPLIT TENSILE STRENGTH

Table 4.2 Split tensile strength

Percentage Replacement	Split tensile strength after 7 days of curing (MPa)	Split tensile strength after 28 days of curing (MPa)
Normal	0.41	0.42
25% Glass 25% Brick	0.45	0.48
50% Glass 25% Brick	0.34	0.36
50% Glass 50% Brick	0.39	0.4
25% Glass 50% Brick	0.28	0.39

The split tensile strength of paver blocks varies depending on the percentage replacement of conventional materials with glass and brick. The normal paver block, without any replacement, exhibits a split tensile strength of 0.41 MPa after 7 days of curing, which slightly increases to 0.42 MPa after 28 days. When 25% glass and 25% brick are incorporated, the strength improves to 0.45 MPa after 7 days and 0.48 MPa after 28 days, indicating that this combination enhances the tensile performance of the paver block. However, with an increased replacement of 50% glass and 25% brick, the strength drops significantly to 0.34 MPa at 7 days and 0.36 MPa at 28 days, showing that higher glass content might negatively impact the tensile strength. Similarly, when 50% glass and 50% brick are used, the strength is slightly

higher than the 50% glass and 25% brick mix, measuring 0.39 MPa after 7 days and 0.40 MPa after 28 days, which is still lower than the normal mix and the 25% glass and 25% brick combination.

On the other hand, when 25% glass and 50% brick are used together, the 7-day split tensile strength is the lowest among all mixes, at 0.28 MPa. However, the 28-day strength significantly increases to 0.39 MPa, showing better long-term strength gain compared to its 7-day performance. This suggests that while initial curing might not favor this mix, it develops better tensile properties over time.

Fig 9 Split tensile strength after 7 and 28 days of curing

The results indicate that a balanced replacement of 25% glass and 25% brick yields the highest split tensile strength, making it the most effective mix among those tested. The trends also highlight that excessive glass replacement negatively affects early and long-term strength, while brick replacement alone, despite an initial weakness, can enhance tensile performance over time. Therefore, an optimized mix design considering both early and long-term performance is essential for durable paver blocks.

2 FLEXURAL STRENGTH

The Flexural strength of the concrete was measured at 7 days and 28 days. In this project we discuss about the comparison between normal paver block and blocks made by the

replacement of 25%, 50% of both glass and refractory bricks.

Table 4.3 Test result of flexural strength

Percentage Replacement	Flexural strength after 7 days of curing (MPa)	Flexural strength after 28 days of curing (MPa)
Normal	6.76	8.13
25% Glass 25% Brick	7.97	9.4
50% Glass 25% Brick	7.65	8.02
50% Glass 50% Brick	5.23	6.85
25% Glass 50% Brick	5.58	6.4

The table 4.3 presents the flexural strength of a material, likely concrete or a similar composite, after 7 and 28 days of curing, with varying percentages of glass and brick as replacement materials. The normal sample, presumably without replacement materials, shows a flexural strength of 6.76 MPa after 7 days and 8.13 MPa after 28 days. The sample with 25% glass and 25% brick exhibits increased strength, measuring 7.97 MPa at 7 days and 9.4 MPa at 28 days. However, when the glass content is increased to 50% with 25% brick, the strength decreases slightly to 7.63 MPa at 7 days and 8.02 MPa at 28 days. Further adjustments to the mixture, such as 50% glass and 50% brick result in lower flexural strengths compared to the 25% glass and 25% brick mixture, with values ranging from 5.21 MPa to 5.38 MPa at 7 days and 6.4 MPa to 6.83 MPa at 28 days. This data suggests that a 25% glass and 25% brick replacement yields the highest flexural strength within the tested combinations. The provided table presents the flexural strength of

a material, likely concrete or a similar composite, under different percentage replacements of its constituents and after varying curing periods. Flexural strength, measured in megapascals (MPa), indicates the material's resistance to bending forces. The table compares the flexural strength after 7 days and 28 days of curing for different mixes, including a normal mix and mixes with varying percentages of glass and brick as replacements. The data reveals that the normal mix has a flexural strength of 6.76 MPa after 7 days and 8.13 MPa after 28 days. Replacing 25% of the material with glass and 25% with brick results in a higher flexural strength of 7.97 MPa after 7 days and 9.4 MPa after 28 days. However, increasing the glass content to 50% while keeping the brick content at 25% yields a slightly lower strength of 7.63 MPa at 7 days and 8.02 MPa at 28 days. Further changes in the mix, such as 50% glass and 30% brick or 20% glass and 30% brick, lead to significantly lower flexural strengths, both at 7 and 28 days. This suggests that while some replacement ratios can enhance flexural strength, exceeding certain thresholds or altering the balance can have detrimental effects on the material's performance. The increase in strength from 7 to 28 days across all mixes is expected, as the curing process strengthens the material over time.

Fig 10 Flexural strength after 7 and 28 days of curing

3. WATER ABSORPTION

Table 4.4 Water absorption

Percentage Replacement	Water Absorption (%)
Normal	0.25
25% Glass 25% Brick	0.58
50% Glass 25% Brick	0.36
50% Glass 50% Brick	0.72
25% Glass 50% Brick	0.43

Water absorption is an important property in construction materials as it affects the durability and strength of the material. The table 4.4 presents the water absorption percentages of paver block with different levels of glass and brick replacements after 28 days of curing. The first row of the table represents the standard or "normal" material composition, meaning that no part of the material has been replaced with either glass or brick. In this standard composition, the water absorption percentage is recorded as 0.25%, serving as the baseline for comparison with other compositions that incorporate material replacements. When 25% of the material is replaced with glass and another 25% is replaced with brick, the water absorption percentage increases to 0.58%, indicating that the introduction of these replacement materials enhances the material's ability to absorb water. This increase in water absorption suggests that incorporating glass and brick raises the overall porosity of the material, creating more tiny spaces or voids within the structure that allow water to be retained. As a result, the composition becomes more susceptible to moisture penetration compared to the normal material. In the next case, the glass replacement percentage is increased to 50%, while the brick replacement remains at 25%, resulting in a recorded water absorption percentage of 0.36%. This percentage is noticeably lower than the 0.58% observed in the previous composition, suggesting that increasing the proportion of glass while

keeping the brick content relatively lower helps to reduce the amount of water absorbed. One possible explanation for this reduction in water absorption is that glass, being a non-porous material, contributes to a denser and less absorbent structure when its proportion is increased, thereby counteracting the porosity introduced by the brick replacement. When both glass and brick replacements are increased to 50% each, meaning that half of the original material is substituted with glass and the other half with brick, the water absorption percentage rises significantly to 0.72%, the highest value recorded in the entire table. This substantial increase suggests that as the proportion of replacement materials increases, particularly brick, the material's ability to absorb water also increases, possibly due to a greater presence of pores and voids. Since brick generally has a higher porosity than glass, replacing a significant portion of the material with brick contributes to an overall increase in the structure's ability to retain moisture, leading to the highest water absorption percentage observed in this dataset. In another case, where 25% of the material is replaced with glass and 50% is replaced with brick, the water absorption percentage is recorded as 0.43%. This value is lower than the 0.72% observed in the previous composition, where both materials were replaced at 50%, but it remains higher than the normal composition's 0.25% water absorption. This suggests that increasing the brick content leads to a greater tendency for water absorption, while glass, due to its non-porous nature, helps reduce the effect to some extent. However, since the proportion of brick in this composition is still significant at 50%, the water absorption remains relatively high compared to the normal material composition.

Fig 11 Water absorption at different mix proportions

IV CONCLUSION

Refractory bricks, and recycled glass each contribute to sustainable and efficient construction practices. Paver blocks offer durability, design flexibility, and easy maintenance, making them ideal for various applications. Refractory bricks provide excellent heat resistance and longevity in high temperature environments, reducing operational costs. Recycled glass supports eco-friendly construction by minimizing waste and energy consumption while enhancing aesthetics. Together, these materials reflect the growing emphasis on sustainability, innovation, and cost-effective solutions in modern construction.

- The values of compressive strength, flexural strength and tensile splitting strength were determined and it was noted that the paver block made by 25% glass and 25% refractory brick showed higher strength.
- As the paver block made by replacing fine and coarse aggregate by 25% glass and 25% brick showed higher strength in most of the tests, it is taken as the optimum percentage of replacement.
- The effect of change in the properties of selected paver block from normal paver block are;
 - i. 2.35% increase in compressive strength.
 - ii. 15.62% increase in flexural strength. 14.28% increase in split tensile strength.
 - iii. 14.28% increase in split tensile strength.

REFERENCES

1. Alaneme G.U. Naik B.G. and Nakkeeran, Roy D. (2024), "Investigating the Potential of Waste Glass in Paver Block Production Using RSM", Scientific Reports, Vol. 14 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-72789-y>
2. Bolívar J.P., González J.G., Pérez M.R. and Raya M.C.L. (2023), "Construction and Demolition Waste as Recycled Aggregate for Environmentally Friendly Concrete Paving", Environmental Science and Pollution Research, Vol. 29 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-021-15849-4>

3. Carong M. A., Pertiwi V. D and Tjaronge (2024), "Producing Eco-friendly concrete paving block using waste refractory brick aggregates", International Journal of Pavement Research and Technology, Vol. 17
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s42947-024-00425-z>
4. Chin C. S, Wang X, and Xia J (2023), "Study on the properties variation of recycled concrete paving block containing multiple waste materials", Journal of Case Studies in Construction Materials, Vol. 18
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cscm.2022.e01803>
5. Farooq M.U., Hameed R., Shahzad S., Sohail M.G. and Tahir M. (2023), "Mechanical and Durability Performance of 100% Recycled Aggregate Concrete Pavers Made by Compression Casting", Journal of Building Engineering, Vol. 73
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2023.106729>
6. Gaur A. S (2022), "A Brief Review of Experimental Studies of Paver Blocks Manufactured With Concrete Demolition Waste", Engineering and Technology Journal for Research and Innovation (ETJRI), Vol. 5
<https://doi.org/10.3390/ma115072365>
7. Gebremichael, Jadidi K., Karakouzian M. and Negasi (2023), "Waste glass recycling: The combined effect of particle size and proportion in concrete manufactured with waste recycled glass" Construction And Building Materials, Vol. 392
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2023.132044>
8. Wattanasiriwech D, Wattanasiriwech S and Punyasurb J (2023), "Permeable Blocks with Waste Glass as Coarse Aggregate", School of Science, Vol. 50
<https://doi.org/10.12982/CMJS.2023.062>

Medicine Tracker

Abhiram S G
Dept. of CSE

John Cox Memorial CSI institute of technology
Thiruvananthapuram, India

Angelene Rose Antony
Dept. of CSE

John Cox Memorial CSI institute of technology
Thiruvananthapuram, India

Gautham Mahendran
Dept. of CSE

John Cox Memorial CSI institute of technology
Thiruvananthapuram, India

Sona S Raj
Dept. of CSE

John Cox Memorial CSI institute of technology
Thiruvananthapuram, India

Abstract-- The Medicine Tracker is a mini project designed to help Suppliers, Pharmacist, Doctors and Patients manage and track their medical needs which in turn can help them in maintaining a better health care system. The primary objective of this mini project is to help Suppliers and Pharmacist efficiently monitor and manage their medicine inventory and help doctors to manage their patients and help patients to locate the nearest doctor and manage their health. The site allows the Suppliers to input the medicine details such as name, expiry date, manufacturing date, and quantity while displaying a well-organized list with visual indicators for expired and soon-to-expire medicines. The Pharmacist can make a contract with the Suppliers for the medicines. The website allows the doctors to manage their time efficiently and help the users make appointment with them. It allows the doctors to recommend alternative medicines efficiently thereby ensuring the uninterrupted treatment to patients. The site is developed using HTML, CSS, JavaScript, JSON with a simple command-lines for user friendly interaction. The back-end utilizes a Node.js and Supabase as database to store user data, ensuring data persistence and security. The mini project utilizes a dictionary-based data structure to store user data, allowing for easy handling of information. The interface includes an easy-to-use form for adding medicines, a table to display inventory, and color-coded alerts for better visibility. The application provides a practical solution to a common problem, enhancing health and time management. By integrating technology into healthcare management, this project enhances medicine safety, public well-being, and overall healthcare efficiency in society.

Keywords—Medicine Tracker, Chatbot, NLP, Database, Web Security, Deployment, Healthcare

I. INTRODUCTION

The medical industry plays a crucial role in ensuring the health and well-being of individuals by providing essential healthcare services. It consists of hospitals, pharmacies, research institutions, and pharmaceutical companies working together to deliver life-saving treatments, preventive care, and innovative medical solutions. Over the years, advancements in medicine, biotechnology, and digital health technologies have significantly improved healthcare accessibility and efficiency. The integration of telemedicine, automated healthcare systems, and artificial intelligence has further enhanced patient care by optimizing treatment plans, reducing human errors, and improving medication management. Effective communication

and well-organized medical resources contribute to faster diagnoses, better treatment outcomes, and an overall well-structured healthcare system.

The industry faces significant challenges in medicine inventory management and supply chain efficiency. Many pharmacies, hospitals, and suppliers still rely on traditional, manual tracking systems, leading to errors, delays, shortages, and the unintentional distribution of expired drugs. These inefficiencies can prevent patients from receiving the right medicines at the right time, which is critical for those with chronic illnesses or life-threatening conditions. Additionally, limited access to healthcare facilities in rural and underdeveloped areas further worsens the problem, making it difficult for patients to obtain essential medicines when needed.

Another major issue is inefficient time management and lack of coordination between healthcare professionals. Outdated systems slow down prescription processing, delay medicine distribution, and create confusion in patient treatment plans. In emergency situations, the availability of critical medicines is crucial for saving lives, making efficient inventory management a necessity. Technology-driven solutions such as automated alerts, intelligent tracking systems, and AI-based medication management can help address these challenges, ensuring better healthcare accessibility and improved patient outcomes.

To improve user experience and accessibility, the integration of a customer service chatbot can provide instant support by explaining website functionalities and clearing user doubts. The chatbot can assist visitors in navigating the platform, understanding features, and resolving common queries related to medicine tracking and management. By offering quick and accurate responses, it enhances user engagement, reduces confusion, and ensures a smoother interaction with the website. This AI-driven solution streamlines communication, allowing users to maximize the benefits of the platform efficiently.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Gulbakshi Dharmale et al.[1] proposed a speech-based medicine intake tracker and healthcare assistant named Vita Health. It serves the patients about their medicine dosage quantity and time in the form, of voice note that read aloud the name of medicine.

According to S. Gangopadhyay [2], effective doctor-patient communication plays a crucial role in improving treatment adherence and patient satisfaction. The study analyzed various factors influencing these interactions and provided strategies to enhance communication effectiveness in medical settings.

M. Andersson et al. [3] explored physician-pharmacist collaboration and its impact on reducing drug-related problems (DRPs). Their systematic review demonstrated that structured communication between healthcare professionals significantly decreased the incidence of DRPs, highlighting the importance of pharmacist-physician coordination in medication management.

L. Thompson [4] examined pharmacist-patient interactions and emphasized the necessity for pharmacists to develop better communication skills. The study analyzed multiple interventions, including role-playing and video-based training, showing that improved communication leads to better patient health outcomes.

A. R. Basri et al. [5] investigated the role of digital media in doctor-patient communication. Their findings suggested that digital communication platforms enhance accessibility, responsiveness, and patient satisfaction, underlining the growing importance of technology in healthcare interactions.

Dheemanth Manur et al. [6] suggests a diagnostic conversation by utilizing ai to better identify the illness before a doctor’s appointment and include specific knowledge regarding the disease.

A. Fadhil [7] proposed a chatbot Roborto, to create an engaging interactive and intelligent environment for patients and assist in positive lifestyle modification. They describe the health, technical and behavioural approaches to the problem of medication non-adherence and propose a diagnostic and decision support tool.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

A. System Overview

The Medicine Tracker System is an efficient and secure platform designed to streamline medication management, appointments, and communication among Suppliers, Doctors, Pharmacists, and Patients. It ensures role-based access control, allowing each user to interact with relevant features while maintaining data security. Suppliers manage the supply chain and inventory, Doctors handle prescriptions and appointments, Pharmacists track stock and expiry alerts, and Patients receive medication reminders and consult doctors. The system integrates automated medicine tracking to prevent wastage and ensure compliance with health regulations by notifying stakeholders about soon-to-expire medicines. Additionally, an AI-powered chatbot assists users with medicine availability, prescriptions, and appointment scheduling, reducing manual support dependency. By enhancing security, efficiency, and accessibility, the Medicine Tracker System promotes better medication adherence, minimizes expired medicine risks, and improves healthcare services for all stakeholders.

B. System Architecture

Figure 1:Medicine tracker system architecture

Figure 1 illustrates the Medicine Tracker System's multi-tier architecture, ensuring secure and efficient healthcare management. It provides role-based access for Suppliers, Doctors, Pharmacists, and Patients, enabling login, registration, and dashboard functionalities. The backend manages medicines, appointments, authentication, and notifications while interacting with a secure database for storing medical records. An AI-powered chatbot enhances user support by handling customer service queries.

C. Modules

- User Module

Manages authentication and role-based access control, ensuring that users such as Pharmacists, Suppliers, Doctors, and Patients can interact with the system according to their permissions.

- Supplier And Pharmacist Module

Enables suppliers to update stock availability and pharmacists to manage medicines by adding, updating, and tracking expiry details while sending alerts for medicines nearing expiry.

- Doctor Module

Allows doctors to verify medicine expiry details before prescribing and provides access to patient medication history to ensure safe prescriptions.

- Doctor-Patient Communication Module

Facilitates communication between doctors and patients by sending alerts for expired or soon-to-expire medicines and providing prescription recommendations.

- Chatbot Module

Assists users by answering queries related to medicine expiry tracking, system functionalities, and navigation, with a planned upgrade to an AI-based chatbot using NLTK for improved interactions.

- Database Management Module

Securely stores system data, including user roles and medicine details, while implementing Row-Level Security (RLS) to ensure controlled access and data integrity.

IV. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

A. System Design

- Use Case Diagram

Figure 2: Use Case Diagram

Figure II represents the workflow of role-based interactions in the Medicine Tracker System, where Suppliers, Pharmacists, Doctors, and Patients communicate with the admin for managing medicine supplies, appointments, and schedules. The admin oversees supplier details, verifies appointments, and approves time tables, ensuring seamless coordination among all stakeholders.

B. Implementation Details

- Frontend Technologies

The front-end of the Medicine Tracker system is developed using HTML, CSS, JavaScript, JSON, and Node.js, providing an interactive and responsive user interface. HTML and CSS ensure a structured and visually appealing layout, while JavaScript enhances user interactivity with dynamic content updates. JSON is used for efficient data exchange between the front-end and back-end, ensuring seamless communication. Node.js, with its asynchronous capabilities, helps in handling server-side interactions, improving the overall performance of the web application. These technologies were chosen to create a user-friendly, scalable, and responsive interface.

- Backend Technologies

The backend is built using Supabase, Express.js, and Python, ensuring a robust and scalable infrastructure. Supabase, an open-source alternative to Firebase, provides a PostgreSQL database with built-in authentication and real-time capabilities. Express.js, a lightweight and flexible Node.js framework, facilitates efficient API development, enabling smooth interaction between the front-end and database. Python is used for specific backend functionalities, particularly in chatbot development and AI-based interactions. Together, these technologies ensure seamless data flow, fast processing, and secure communication between the user interface and the database.

- Security Mechanisms

Security is implemented using Supabase's authentication system, supporting email/password login, OAuth, and multi-factor authentication (MFA) for enhanced protection. Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) ensures that different user roles (pharmacists, doctors, suppliers, and patients) have appropriate access permissions, preventing unauthorized modifications. Row-Level Security (RLS) further restricts access at the database level, ensuring privacy and data integrity. Secure API endpoints, HTTPS encryption, and protection against common vulnerabilities such as SQL injection, Cross-Site Scripting (XSS), and Cross-Site Request Forgery (CSRF) safeguard sensitive user data and system interactions.

- Database Management

Data is managed using Supabase, which provides a PostgreSQL-based backend with built-in authentication, role-based access control, and real-time database updates. Row-Level Security (RLS) is enforced to ensure that users can only access data relevant to their role, maintaining privacy and security. Data storage techniques focus on efficient indexing and optimized queries to handle large-scale medicine expiry tracking and user interactions while ensuring minimal latency in data retrieval.

V. RESULTS

Medicine Tracker system overcomes these limitations by introducing role-based access for Suppliers, Pharmacists, Doctors, and Patients, ensuring collaborative medicine expiry management. Unlike existing apps, it enables suppliers and pharmacists to update stock and expiry details while allowing doctors to verify medicine safety before prescribing. The integrated AI-powered chatbot enhances user support, and Supabase with RLS ensures secure and structured data management. These improvements make the system more efficient, secure, and scalable for real-world applications.

VI. CONCLUSION

Medicine tracker plays a vital role in ensuring proper medication management, improving adherence, and enhancing health outcomes. By providing a structured approach to tracking dosages and schedules, it helps patients, caregivers, and healthcare providers maintain accurate records and reduce the risks of missed or incorrect doses. It also fosters consistency, particularly for individuals with chronic conditions, by offering reminders and monitoring progress, ultimately improving treatment efficacy. Additionally, healthcare professionals benefit from a comprehensive medication history, enabling informed decisions and reducing adverse drug interactions.

Advancements in technology have further improved medicine tracking through digital apps, AI-powered reminders, and real-time monitoring, making medication management more efficient. AI-driven trackers can predict adherence challenges, provide personalized interventions, and enhance doctor-patient communication by offering accurate medication records. This fosters better trust, cooperation, and engagement in healthcare decisions. As medicine tracking systems continue to evolve, they will further reduce medication errors, improve adherence, and contribute to better healthcare outcomes worldwide.

VII. FUTURE SCOPE

The Medicine Tracker can be enhanced by integrating advanced AI-powered chatbots for personalized assistance and predictive analytics to detect adherence patterns. Future developments may include IoT-enabled smart medicine dispensers for automated dosage tracking and blockchain for secure medical data sharing. Expanding the system to support multilingual interfaces and voice recognition can improve accessibility.

REFERENCES

- [1] Gulbakshi Dharmale, Shreenidhi Karjagi, Babita Sonare, Karan Kavatage, Pranav Kul, Harshal Kotalwar, “Vita Health – A Complete Healthcare System”, 2023.
- [2] S. Gangopadhyay, “The Impact of Doctor-Patient Communication on Treatment Adherence and Patient Satisfaction” *Journal of Medical and Dental Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 9, pp. 87-90, 2023.
- [3] M. Andersson, J. Melhus, and J. M. Mölstad, “Collaboration Between Clinical Pharmacists and Physicians to Reduce Drug-Related Problems: A Systematic Review” *BMC Health Services Research*, vol. 22, no. 8505, pp. 1-12, 2022.
- [4] L. Thompson, “Improving Pharmacist-Patient Communication: The Key to Better Health Outcomes” *Pharmacy Times*, vol. 30, no. 5, pp. 45-50, 2023.
- [5] A. R. Basri, S. Kurniawan, and M. Z. Akbar, “The Role of Digital Media in Enhancing Doctor-Patient Communication” in *Proc. Int. Conf. Innovation, Sci., Technol., Educ., Children, Health (ICISTECH)*, pp. 1-8, 2023.
- [6] Dheemanth Manur, Chandan Gowda, Mohammed Firaaz Farook, Sharaschandra M Desai, “Doctor Patient Assistance System Using Artificial Intelligence”, 2021.
- [7] A. Fadhil, “A Conversational Interface to Improve Medication Adherence: Towards AI Support in Patient's Treatment” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1803.09844*, 2018.

QUADRAPED SPIDER ROBOT FOR SURVEILLANCE

Anantha Krishnan K B
Electronics and Communication
engineering
John Cox CSI Institute of Technology
Thiruvananthapuram, India
ananthakrishnankb23@gmail.com

Sibi S
Electronics and Communication
engineering
John Cox CSI Institute of Technology
Thiruvananthapuram, India
line 5: email address or ORCID

Jofna Joseph
Electronics and Communication
engineering
John Cox CSI Institute of Technology
Thiruvananthapuram, India
line 5: email address or ORCID

Abstract— Quadraped spider robot for surveillance is a four-legged spider-inspired robot equipped with various algorithms for versatile locomotion and interactive functionalities, including camera surveillance. Quadra Spider's movement capabilities extend beyond basic walking to include agile navigation through challenging terrains, such as rough and uneven surfaces, which makes it perfect for camera surveillance. We demonstrate the robot's exceptional agility and stability through extensive testing, ensuring that it can traverse a diverse array of environments with efficiency and reliability. Beyond basic locomotion, the robot exhibits additional capabilities like camera surveillance and object detection. Energy efficiency is a critical consideration in robotic systems. To address this, we will conduct comprehensive power consumption tests and incorporate power chargeable silicon batteries into Quadra Spider's design. This feature ensures prolonged operation and minimizes the need for frequent recharging, making the robot practical for extended use in emergency situations for surveillance.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the realm of advanced robotics, innovation continues to push boundaries and redefine what's possible. One such groundbreaking development is the quadruped spider robot, designed especially for surveillance applications. This sophisticated piece of technology combines the agility and versatility of a spider with the precision and intelligence of modern robotics, making it an invaluable asset in various surveillance scenarios.

The quadruped spider robot stands out due to its unique design, which mimics the locomotion and stability of a spider. With four robust and flexible legs, this robot can navigate challenging terrains with ease, from rough outdoor landscapes to complex indoor environments. Its ability to move swiftly and steadily across different surfaces allows it to access areas that traditional wheeled or tracked robots might struggle with. This exceptional mobility ensures that the robot can conduct thorough surveillance in diverse settings, be it urban environments, remote locations, or confined spaces.

At the core of the quadruped spider robot's functionality is its advanced sensor suite. Equipped with the high-definition cameras, the robot can capture detailed visual data and map its surroundings in real-time. These sensors provide a comprehensive view of the environment, enabling the robot

to detect and track objects or individuals with precision. The integration of artificial intelligence algorithms further enhances its capabilities, allowing the robot to analyze the collected data, identify patterns, and informed decisions autonomously.

One of the primary applications of the quadruped spider robot is in security and surveillance. Its ability to operate discreetly and cover vast areas makes it an ideal choice for monitoring public spaces, critical infrastructure, and private properties. In situations where human presence might be risky or impractical, the robot can serve as a reliable alternative, conducting surveillance tasks without drawing attention. Moreover, its advanced sensor systems can detect anomalies, such as unauthorized intrusions or unusual activities, and alert human operators in real-time, ensuring swift and appropriate responses.

Beyond security, the quadruped spider robot has significant potential in search and rescue operations. In disaster-stricken areas where accessibility is a major challenge, the robot can navigate through rubble and debris, locating survivors and assessing damage. The real-time data transmission capability ensures that rescue teams receive up-to-date information, enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of their efforts.

The quadruped spider robot can also find applications in environmental monitoring and research. Its ability to transverse diverse terrains allows scientists to gather data from remote or hazardous locations, contributing to studies on wildlife, ecosystems, and climate change. By equipping the robot with specialized sensors, researchers can monitor environmental parameters such as temperature, humidity, and air quality, facilitating a deeper understanding of our planet.

II. BLOCK DIAGRAM

Fig 1. Block diagram

The block diagram illustrates a system designed to control twelve servos using an Arduino microcontroller and communicate with a mobile app via a Wi-Fi module, integrating an ESP32 camera for video streaming. This setup is useful in applications requiring remote control and real-time video feedback, such as in robotics, home automation, or surveillance systems.

The Arduino Microcontroller is the core component of the system, responsible for controlling the twelve servos labeled Servo 1 to Servo 12. Each servo can be programmed to perform specific movements based on the instructions received from the Arduino. The microcontroller uses Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) signals to control the position, speed, and direction of each servo. This allows for precise and coordinated movements, crucial in applications like robotic arms, animatronics, or automated systems.

The Wi-Fi Module is connected to the Arduino, enabling wireless communication between the microcontroller and a mobile app. This module allows the Arduino to receive commands from the mobile app and send data back to it. The Wi-Fi module ensures that the system can be controlled remotely, providing flexibility and ease of use. Users can issue commands from their mobile devices, making it convenient to operate the system from a distance.

Two instances of the Mobile App are depicted in the diagram. One instance interacts with the Wi-Fi module to send control signals to the Arduino, enabling users to operate the servos remotely. The other instance receives a video stream from the ESP32 Camera, which is also part of the system. The ESP32 camera captures real-time video footage and streams it to the mobile app, providing visual feedback. This feature is particularly useful in surveillance applications, allowing users to monitor environments remotely.

In summary, the block diagram represents an integrated system that combines servo control, wireless communication, and video streaming capabilities. By using an Arduino microcontroller, Wi-Fi module, and ESP32 camera, the system can be used for various remote-controlled applications, offering precision, flexibility, and real-time feedback. This setup is ideal for projects that require complex motor control and visual monitoring.

III. CIRCUIT DIAGRAM

Fig 2. Circuit Diagram

This circuit diagram presents a comprehensive system involving an Arduino Nano (Rev3.0), multiple servo motors,

a Bluetooth module, and an ESP32-CAM, segmented into two main parts for clarity.

Part 1: Servo Motors Control

- **Arduino Nano (Rev3.0):** At the core of this setup is the Arduino Nano, a compact yet powerful microcontroller that manages the operations of all connected components.
- **Servo Motors (J1 to J12):** This system integrates twelve servo motors, divided into two sets. The first set, J1 to J6, connects to the analog pins A0 to A5 on the Arduino Nano, while the second set, J7 to J12, connects to the digital pins D2 to D7. Each servo has three connections: a pulse (signal) wire, a power wire connected to the 5V rail, and a ground wire. These connections allow the Arduino to control the position of each servo motor by sending PWM signals to the pulse pins.

Part 2: Communication and Imaging

- **Wi-Fi Module (Bluetooth Mate Silver):** This module enables wireless communication between the Arduino and a mobile app. The TX and RX pins of the Bluetooth module are connected to the RX and TX pins of the Arduino Nano, respectively, allowing bidirectional data transmission. The CTS and RTS pins of the Bluetooth module are tied to the 5V power supply and ground, ensuring proper operational voltage levels.
- **ESP32-CAM:** The ESP32-CAM module, equipped with a camera, enables real-time video streaming. It is connected to the Arduino Nano, with its 5V and ground pins linked to the 5V power and ground rails. Additional pins (IO12, IO13, IO14, IO15, IO2, IO4) connect to various digital pins on the Arduino Nano, facilitating control over the camera's functions and data transmission.
- **Power Supply:** The entire system is powered by a 5V power supply, distributed across the circuit via power and ground rails. These rails ensure all components receive the necessary power for operation.

System Functionality

Fig 4. Two-way joint

Fig 5. Spider legs

Fig 6: Main Framework

Fig 7: Joint with main framework

This integrated setup leverages the Arduino Nano's capability to control multiple servos, enabling complex movements and operations. The Bluetooth module adds the advantage of remote control, allowing users to operate the system wirelessly via a mobile app. The ESP32-CAM provides visual feedback by streaming video to the app, enabling real-time monitoring and control.

Applications

Such a system is ideal for robotics, automation, and remote surveillance applications. It can be used in projects requiring precise motor control, remote operation, and real-time video feedback, such as robotic arms, automated vehicles, or security surveillance systems.

IV. 3D PRINT RENDERS

Fig 8: Main Framework

V. OUTPUT

Fig 9: Top & Front view

Fig 10. Bottom View

VI. ADVANTAGES

Mobility and Agility: Quadruped spider robots can navigate a wide variety of terrains, including uneven ground, rocky surfaces, and obstacles.

Stability: The design of quadruped robots provides a low center of gravity and a robust structure, enhancing their stability.

Versatility: These robots can be equipped with a wide range of sensors and tools, making them adaptable to various tasks.

Remote Operation: Quadruped spider robots can be operated remotely, which is crucial in hazardous situations.

Energy Efficiency: With their optimized movement patterns and ability to adjust their gait according to terrain, quadruped robots can be more energy-efficient than other types of robots.

Real-Time Data Collection: Equipped with various sensors, quadruped robots can collect and transmit data in real time. This capability is essential in applications like environmental monitoring or search and rescue.

VII. CONCLUSION

The quadruped spiderbot robot project effectively demonstrated the potential of a mobile, remotely controlled robotic platform with live video streaming capabilities. Using an Arduino microcontroller to coordinate 12 servos, the robot achieved stable and flexible movement. The addition of a Wi-Fi module enabled wireless control through a custom mobile

app, allowing users to send real-time commands, while the ESP32 CAM provided live video streaming for remote monitoring. These capabilities highlight the spiderbot's versatility, offering possible applications in scenarios where human access is challenging, such as search and rescue, environmental inspection, and exploration. Throughout the project, we faced challenges in balancing mechanical stability with control precision, optimizing servo performance, and maintaining reliable wireless communication. Each solution implemented, from calibration techniques to app interface improvements, helped refine the robot's performance. Overall, this project laid the groundwork for further advancements in low-cost, multipurpose robotic systems. Future enhancements could focus on developing more advanced movement algorithms, adding sensors for environmental feedback, and optimizing energy efficiency to extend operational duration. This project underscored the spiderbot's adaptability and potential in various fields, proving its capabilities as an affordable, customizable platform for robotics applications.

REFERENCES

- [1] W.K.Huang, J.Xiao, F.Zeng, P.Lu, G.Lin, W.Hu, X.Lin, and Y.Wu, "A quadruped robot with three-dimensional flexible legs," *Sensors*, 21(14), 2021, pp 1-18/
- [2] Y.Shi, S.Li, M.Guo, Y.Yang, D.Xia, and X.Luo, "Structural design, simulation and experiment of quadruped robot," *Applied Sciences*, 11(22), 2021, pp. 1-19.
- [3] Semini, V. Barasuol, J. Goldsmith, M. Frigerio, M. Focchi, Y. Gao, and D. G. Caldwell, "Design of the Hydraulically Actuated, TorqueControlled Quadruped Robot HyQ2Max," *IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics*, 22(2), 2017, pp. 635-646.
- [4] D. Ayaklı Robotlar İçin Hidrolik Tahrikli Bir, M. Kalyoncu, M. Arif Sen, and V. Bakircioglu, "Bacak Geliştirilmesi-Development of a Hydraulically Actuated Leg for Quadruped Robots View project Inverse Kinematic Analysis Of A Quadruped Robot," *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, 6(9), 2017, pp. 285-189. *Journal of Engineering Sciences Vol 15 Issue 05, 2024 ISSN:0377-9254.*
- [5] C. G. Darwin, and S. Claudio, "Development of the Light weight Hydraulic Quadruped Robot MiniHyQ," In: 2015 IEEE International Conference on Technologies for Practical Robot Applications (TePRA), 2015, pp.1-6.
- [6] B. Sandeep, and P. Tamil Selvan, "Design and Development of an Autonomous Quadruped Robot," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 1012(1), 2021, pp. 1-20.
- [7] S. Rajesh Babu, K. Senthil Kumar, G. Sabari Narayanan, R. Raja, K. Anbazhagan, and H. Yasar Sathab, "Design and conception of Arduino based quadruped robot," In: *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 2021, pp. 1-6.
- [8] J. Kim, T. Kang, D. Song, and S. J. Yi, "Design and control of a open source, lowcost, 3dprinted dynamic quadruped robot," *Applied Sciences*, 11(9), 2021, pp. 1-18.
- [9] C. Yan, K. Shi, H. Zhang, and Y. Yao, "Simulation and analysis of a single actuated quadruped robot," *Mechanical Sciences*, 13(1), 2022, pp. 137-146.
- [10] P. Biswal, and P. K. Mohanty, "Development of quadruped walking robots: A review," *AinShams Engineering*.

REAL TIME SIGN LANGUAGE CONVETER

Boby Shibu Thomas
Department of Computer Science and
Engineering,
Johncox memorial institute of technology
kannammoola,Thiruvananthapuram,India 695033

bobyshibhu10th@gmail.com

Sai Krishna U.S.
Department of Computer Science and
Engineering,
Johncox memorial institute of technology ,
kannammoola,Thiruvananthapuram,India 695033

saikichuhh@gmail.com

Sidharth V.
Department of Computer Science and
Engineering,
Johncox memorial institute of technology,
kannammoola,Thiruvananthapuram,India 695033

bosssidharthv@gmail.com

Jeslin B.S.
Department of Computer Science and
Engineering,
Johncox memorial institute of technology,
kannammoola,Thiruvananthapuram,India 695033

jeslinbright@gmail.com

Mrs. Sreelakshmi A.
Assistant Professor,
Department of Computer Science and
Engineering,
Johncox memorial institute of technology,
kannammoola,Thiruvananthapuram,India 695033
srilaxmi1610@gmail.com

***Abstract* : Hearing and speech impairments significantly impact an individual's ability to communicate, often creating barriers to social interaction, education, and employment. To bridge this communication gap, Sign Language Translators play a crucial role in enabling effective interaction between individuals with hearing or speech impairments and the broader society. Leveraging image processing and machine learning techniques, these translators enhance accessibility and inclusivity. This paper aims to develop a robust model for sign language translation, ensuring greater accuracy and efficiency. Ultimately, our goal is to provide an accessible and scalable communication solution that can be widely adopted across diverse communities.**

Keywords: Image Processing, Machine Learning, Assistive Technology, Sign Language Translation, Gesture Recognition, Computer Vision, Convolutional Neural Networks(CNNs).

I. INTRODUCTION

According to a research report by WHO, it was estimated that around 1.5 billion people suffer from hearing loss, out of which 430 million people (5% of the global population) suffer from disabling hearing loss. It was also found that around 34 million children suffer from deafness.

Additionally, around 30% of individuals over 60 suffer from hearing loss.

Furthermore, it was concluded that 80% of the people who suffered from disabling hearing loss live in low- and

middle-income countries, which makes their access to treatment and rehabilitation facilities limited and difficult [1].

Machine learning is one of the branches of AI that enables computers to learn and develop progressively from information recognized and collected from patterns in data. This technology allows machines to make predictions and solve problems independently, acting based on past experiences. Machine learning is essential for automating tasks like calculations, data processing, and pattern recognition, using training data to improve accuracy and efficiency.

Figure 1: WHO Infographic on rise of hearing loss

The various forms of communication involve verbal and non-verbal communication, where verbal communication involves spoken or written words to convey messages, while non-verbal communication relies on gestures, expressions and body language. Individuals with hearing impairments often use sign language to communicate, but there is a significant communication barrier with those who do not understand sign language.

Our project, the Sign Language Detector, aims to bridge this gap by translating sign language gestures into English, making it easier for hearing individuals to communicate with the deaf and mute.

Machine Learning plays a huge role in this project, particularly in image acquisition and image processing using a camera-based system that captures and analyzes sign language gestures in real-time. It predicts outcomes by processing images or videos, enabling smooth

communication between sign language users and non-users.

II. PREVIOUS WORKS

Several research studies have been done on Sign Language Translators utilizing machine learning algorithms.

A study by Ankit Ojha et al. (2020) [2] focused on developing a desktop application capable of translating a person's gestures into American Sign Language. The translated text was then converted into audio, enhancing accessibility for communication. The model was trained using a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) algorithm and achieved an impressive accuracy of 95% in translating gestures to text.

The authors of *Real-Time Sign Language Recognition and Translation to Text for Vocally and Hearing Impaired People* (2020) [3] proposed a system utilizing multiple image preprocessing techniques, including a median filter for noise reduction, the Canny operator for edge detection, and Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) for feature extraction. The extracted features were then processed using a Support Vector Machine (SVM) model for classification based on the training data. However, the study found that the histogram-based approach often led to misclassification, limiting its effectiveness to a small set of distinct alphabets or gestures. A key challenge identified was achieving precise differentiation, which largely depended on both input image quality and the algorithm's efficiency.

In a study by Dr. N. Krishnaveni et al. (2024) [4], the authors proposed a system utilizing a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) algorithm to recognize and translate signs and gestures into American Sign Language (ASL). The model was trained on a Kaggle dataset containing 29 classes, including 26 alphabets and 3 special symbols. The system achieved a prediction accuracy of 90.22%, demonstrating its effectiveness in gesture recognition.

In a research study conducted by B. S. Vinay Krishna et al. (2023) [5], the authors proposed a model for translating signs and gestures into Indian Sign Language (ISL) using a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) algorithm. The system integrated image preprocessing, feature extraction, and model training to enhance prediction accuracy.

The authors of *Sign Language Detector using Machine Learning* (2023) [6] developed an

application using the Python Tkinter GUI interface. The system captures user input images via a webcam, utilizing OpenCV and Python for image processing. TensorFlow's Object Detection API was employed to develop the detection models, which were trained over 10,000 steps using 26 labels

In a research study by Nidhin Manoj et al. (2023) [7], the authors proposed a hand gesture recognition device based on Arduino. The system employed flex sensors to accurately capture fine finger movements, with hand gloves enhancing gesture detection precision. Additionally, a gyroscope and an accelerometer were integrated to minimize input errors caused by unintended movements.

III. PROPOSED WORK

Developing a Sign Language Translator comprises of several steps performed in sequential order. The procedures involved in designing such a system is given below:

1. Data Collection: The first step involves gathering a comprehensive and diverse dataset of sign language gestures, including images and videos that capture fine details such as slight variations in hand movements, positions, and motion patterns. Data can be sourced through original recordings, webcam images, and pre-existing datasets. Accurate data collection is crucial, as it ensures a precise understanding of the meaning associated with each gesture, ultimately enhancing the effectiveness of the recognition model

Figure 2: American Sign Language

Figure 3: Indian Sign Language

2. Data Preprocessing: After collecting the images, data preprocessing is performed to prepare them for analysis. OpenCV is used to standardize the dataset by resizing images to a consistent format (300x300 pixels) and normalizing pixel values to enhance model performance. The dataset is then divided into training, validation, and test sets, ensuring a balanced representation of all signs in each subset for optimal learning and evaluation.

Figure 4: Data Preprocessing

3. Model Development: Once the data is collected and preprocessed, the next step is to develop a sign language recognition model by selecting an appropriate architecture. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are widely used for image classification due to their ability to capture spatial hierarchies essential for recognizing complex hand gestures. TensorFlow and Keras can be utilized to construct and train the model. Additionally, transfer learning can be considered as an option to improve accuracy and performance by leveraging pre-trained models, which can also help reduce the training time.

Figure 5 : CNN Model Architecture

4. Model Training : Once the model is developed, it undergoes training using the collected dataset. This process involves compiling the model with an appropriate loss function, such as categorical cross-entropy, and an optimizer like Adam. The training dataset is used to adjust model parameters, while performance is continuously monitored using the validation set to prevent overfitting and ensure generalization..

Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architectures often have numerous layers that improve the model's ability to capture features. A typical structure has the following layers:

- i Conv2D:** This layer uses convolutional filters to extract spatial information from the input data, including edges, textures, and patterns.
- ii Batch Normalization:** Normalizes the activations from the preceding layer, which accelerates convergence and stabilizes training.
- iii ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit):** Adds nonlinearity to the network, enabling it to learn complex patterns.
- iv MaxPooling2D:** Reduces the dimensionality of feature maps by selecting the highest value in a grid, keeping important information while reducing computation.
- v Dropout:** Randomly deactivates a subset of neurones during training to prevent overfitting and improve the model's generalizability.
- vi Flatten:** Converts the multi-dimensional feature maps into a one-dimensional vector before feeding into the fully connected layers.
- vii Dense:** Determines the final mapping between learnt features and output classes.
- viii Softmax:** Used in the last layer of multi-class classification to generate a probability distribution across the classes.

These layers and technologies serve as the foundation for a robust CNN architecture, assuring great accuracy and reliability in gesture recognition.

Figure 6 : Image Processing using CNN

5. Model Evaluation: After training, the model is evaluated to assess its effectiveness in recognizing sign language gestures. This evaluation is conducted using a test dataset and focuses on key performance metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score.

Additionally, a confusion matrix is generated to analyze classification results, helping to identify misclassifications and areas for improvement. This assessment provides valuable insights into the model's strengths and limitations, guiding further refinements for enhanced performance.

6. Gesture Recognition: After model validation, real-time hand gesture recognition is implemented. This process involves using the trained model along with OpenCV to capture video frames from a camera in real time. Each frame is analysed by the CNN model to detect hands and recognize movements accurately. A feedback mechanism ensures immediate output, converting the user's gestures into meaningful letters. This real-time recognition system enhances both accuracy and user experience, making communication more seamless and efficient.

7. User Interface Development: Designing a user-friendly interface is essential to ensuring the accessibility of the Sign Language Translator. The interface is developed using Tkinter, providing an intuitive and interactive experience for users. The main page allows users to select between American Sign Language (ASL) and Indian Sign Language (ISL), enhancing system flexibility. Additionally, the interface supports key functionalities such as video input for image capture and real-time user feedback, ensuring a seamless and efficient user experience.

Figure 7: Architecture Diagram

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Our "Real-Time Sign Language" system utilizes a webcam to capture user input and employs advanced hand

detection algorithms to translate signs instantly. Designed for inclusivity, it supports both **American Sign Language (ASL)** and **Indian Sign Language (ISL)**, allowing users to choose their preferred language before interaction. The system leverages a **Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)** to process the captured input, ensuring accurate and efficient sign recognition and translation.

The system processes images and detects hands in real time using OpenCV. To guarantee precise sign classification and recognition, the CNN model is constructed and trained using TensorFlow and Keras.

With an impressive **95.6% accuracy rate**, **Real Time Sign Language** ensures **reliable recognition and translation** for users of both **ASL and ISL**. Its **intuitive user interface** allows seamless transitions between the two sign languages, enabling **personalized and effortless communication**. This adaptability **expands accessibility**, making the system a powerful tool for fostering **inclusive and effective interactions**.

Figure 8: Working Model

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we present the implementation of a **Real-Time Sign Language Translator** that accurately translates **signs and gestures** into speech or text. Our research demonstrates that the **Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model** delivers the highest accuracy in recognizing and interpreting hand gestures.

The primary goal of this study was to develop a **reliable and intuitive application** that bridges the communication gap between the **deaf community and the general public**. Designed to support both **American Sign Language (ASL) and Indian Sign Language (ISL)**, the system enhances accessibility for users worldwide.

With a user-friendly interface, the translator facilitates seamless communication, promoting inclusivity and adaptability across different sign languages. This innovation holds an immense potential to empower deaf individuals and improve global accessibility in daily interactions

VI. FUTURE SCOPE

Sign language translators have immense potential for future advancements, driven by **cutting-edge machine learning algorithms**. The accuracy and efficiency of sign recognition can be significantly enhanced through the integration of **deep learning techniques**, enabling more precise translation of complex gestures and expressions.

The future of sign language translation technology is filled with immense possibilities for innovation and inclusivity. Expanding the system to support multiple sign languages from different regions will make it more universal, breaking communication barriers worldwide. Integrating real-time sign language translation into video calling platforms can enhance digital interactions, ensuring accessibility during virtual meetings. Additionally, embedding this technology into public systems such as customer kiosks, medical facilities, and educational institutions can greatly improve communication in essential services. The adaptation of sign language translation into wearable technology, such as smartwatches, AR glasses, and gesture-recognition gloves, will further enhance real-time

accessibility in daily life. Moreover, advancements in deep learning and Natural Language Processing (NLP) will improve the

system's ability to understand context, ensuring greater accuracy and fluency in translations. By embracing these advancements, sign language translation technology can reshape accessibility standards and foster a more inclusive society.

VII. REFERENCES

- [1] WHO, World Health Organisation; [<https://www.who.int/news-room/factsheets/detail/deafness-and-hearing-loss>]
- [2] C. Sun, T. Zhang, B. K. Bao, C. Xu and T. Mei, "Discriminative exemplar coding for sign language recognition with kinect", IEEE Transactions on Cybernetics, vol. 43no. 5, pp. 1418-1428, 2013,
- [3] W. C. Hall, "What You Don't Know Can Hurt You: The Risk of Language Deprivation by Impairing Sign Language Development in Deaf Children", Maternal and Child Health Journal, pp. 1-5, 2017,
- [4] R. C. Dalawis, K. D. R. Olayao, E. G. I. Ramos and M. J. C. Samonte, "KinectBased Sign Language Recognition of Static and Dynamic Hand Movements", Eighth International Conference on Graphic and Image Processing, pp. 1022501-1022501,
- [5] Suharjito Ricky, Anderson Fanny, Wiryana Meita, Chandra Ariesta and Gede Putra Kusuma, "Sign Language Recognition Application Systems for Deaf-Mute People: A Review Based on Input-Process-Output", 2nd International Conference on Computer Science and Computational Intelligence 2017 ICCSCI 2017, 3-14 October,

- [6] Vannesa Mueller, Amanda Sepulveda and Sarai Rodriguez, The effects of baby sign training on child development In:Early Child Development and Care, vol. 184, no. 8, pp. 1178-1191, 2014,
- [7] . S. Chen, C. M. Fu and C. L. Huang, "Hand gesture recognition using a realtime tracking method and hidden Markov models", Image and vision computing, vol.21, no. 8, pp. 745-758, 2003
- [8] Svendsen, B.; Kadry, S. Comparative Analysis of Image Classification Models for Norwegian Sign Language Recognition. *Technologies* **2023**, *11*, 99.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/technologies11040099>
- [9] Alsharif, B.; Altaher, A.S.; Altaher, A.; Ilyas, M.; Alalwany, E. Deep Learning Technology to Recognize American Sign Language Alphabet. *Sensors* **2023**, *23*, 7970.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/s23187970>

Remote controlled lifejacket for drowning prevention

Devika V M
Electrical and Electronics Engg. Dept.
John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of Technology
Trivandrum, Kerala, India
devudo893@gmail.com

VaishnaviSK
Electrical and Electronics Engg. Dept.
John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of Technology
Trivandrum, Kerala, India
vaishnavisk60@gmail.com

Abstract—This project presents a life jacket which is used for the rescuing of drowning person which can be operated remotely. This main components of the life jacket comprises the motor section for the movement of this device in the water and the robotic grabbing arm section for the rescuing of the person. This device is operated by the operator through a mobile device which is connected through a GSM module which enables remote control of this device. Energy efficiency is a critical consideration in robotic systems. To address this, we will conduct comprehensive power consumption tests and incorporate power chargeable silicon batteries into its design. This feature ensures prolonged operation and minimizes the need for frequent recharging, making the robot practical for extended use in emergency situations for surveillance. Also this robot device serves as a lifesaver in places where someone drowning and no one can physically go there.

I. INTRODUCTION

Drowning is a critical issue worldwide, leading to numerous fatalities each year. Traditional life jackets, while effective, often lack the advanced features needed to significantly improve survival rates in urgent situations. The development of a remote-controlled life jacket with robotic arms offers a ground-breaking solution to enhance water safety and rescue operations. This innovative technology aims to provide rapid and precise assistance to individuals in distress, ensuring their safety until further help arrives.

A remote-controlled life jacket with robotic arms combines the essential flotation capabilities of a conventional life jacket with advanced robotics and remote control technology. The primary feature of this jacket with advanced robotics and remote control technology. The primary feature of this life jacket is its ability to be controlled remotely, allowing rescuers to guide the guide the jacket towards the drowning person with precision. Equipped with GPS technology, the life jacket can be accurately tracked and navigated in real-time, ensuring that it reaches the individual in need without delay.

The inclusion of robotic arms in the life jacket enhances its functionality. These arms are designed to extend and grasp the individual, providing a secure hold and preventing them from slipping away. The robotic arms are equipped with sensors that detect the person's position and adjust accordingly to maintain a firm grip. This feature is particularly useful in situations where the person is unconscious or unable to hold onto the life jacket themselves. By ensuring a secure hold, the robotic arms prevent the individual from drifting away and reduce the risk of secondary drowning.

The implementation of this advanced life jacket technology represents a significant advancement in drowning prevention and water safety. Traditional life jackets, while essential, often require the individual to remain conscious and

capable of holding on. In contrast, the remote-controlled life jacket with robotic arms provide active assistance, ensuring that the individual is securely held and continuously monitored. This proactive approach greatly enhances the chances of survival, particularly in critical situations where every second counts

Furthermore, the development of this technology highlights the potential for further innovations in water safety and rescue operations. Further advancements could include the integration of additional features such as automated deployment systems, enhanced sensor capabilities, and improved communications interfaces. These enhancements would further increase the effectiveness and efficiency of rescue operations, ultimately saving more lives.

Hence, the remote-controlled life jacket with robotic arms represents a trans-formative development in water safety technology. By combining advanced robotics, remote control capabilities, and comprehensive monitoring system, this innovative life jacket offers a powerful tool for preventing drowning and ensuring the safety of individuals in distress. As technology continues to evolve, the potential for further advancements and applications of this life-saving device remains vast, paving the way for a safer future in water environments.

II. BLOCK DIAGRAM

A. Proposed system

Block diagram of proposed system shown in figure 1. The block diagram represents a sophisticated system comprising a user interface, GSM modules, a micro-controller unit (MCU), motor drivers, motors, water level sensors, and a power supply. This configuration illustrates how these components interconnect and interact to form a cohesive system for remote monitoring and control. At the core of the system lies the MCU, which serves as the primary control unit, orchestrating the operations of all other components. Positioned centrally in the diagram, the MCU receives data from various inputs, processes this information, and sends commands to execute the required actions.

Starting from the power supply, it is depicted as the source for the MCU, ensuring that the entire system remains operational. This power supply provides the necessary voltage and current to the MCU and other connected components, stabilizing their performance. The MCU, being the brain of the system, is responsible for processing input data and generating output commands. It receives data from GSM modules, which are essential for wireless communication, enabling remote control and monitoring.

Figure.1. Block diagram of proposed system

To the left of the MCU, one GSM module is connected to a user interface or app. This connection is crucial for allowing users to interact with the system remotely. The user interface sends commands to the GSM module, which then transmits these commands to the MCU. Conversely, the MCU sends status updates and data back to the user interface through the GSM module, ensuring bidirectional communication. This setup allows for real-time monitoring and control of the system, enhancing its responsiveness and flexibility.

Below the MCU, a motor driver is depicted, receiving command data from the MCU. The motor driver is a critical component responsible for controlling the motors based on the commands it receives. It acts as an intermediary between the MCU and the motors, translating the low-power signals from the MCU into high-power signals that can drive the motors. The motors, situated at the bottom of the diagram, are the actuators that perform the physical tasks required by the system, such as moving components or pumping water.

The diagram illustrates the data flow and command signals between these components, highlighting their roles within the system. The GSM modules enable remote communication, the water level sensors provide crucial data for decision-making, and the motor driver ensures precise control of the motors. Together, these components form a robust system capable of real-time monitoring and control.

In summary, this block diagram represents a well-integrated system architecture where a user interface communicates with an MCU via GSM modules. The MCU processes data from water level sensors and sends commands to motor drivers, which control the motors. The power supply provides the necessary power for the MCU, this setup allows for remote monitoring and control of the system, making it suitable for applications that require real-time data acquisition and actuation based on sensor inputs. The central role of the MCU in coordinating the activities of the system and the importance of GSM modules in enabling remote control and monitoring are clearly highlighted in this diagram.

III. CIRCUIT DIAGRAM

The circuit diagram illustrates a remote-controlled system, likely part of a life-saving device such as a motorized life jacket for drowning prevention. At its core, the system is powered by a 7.4 V 18650 battery pack, ensuring a stable energy for the components, with an 8.4 V charging unit included for recharging. The Arduino board functions as the central microcontroller, responsible for processing inputs and

executing commands. It receives signals via a Bluetooth module (such as HC-05 or HC-06), enabling wireless communication between the device and a remote controller, likely a smartphone or dedicated remote.

Figure.2. circuit diagram

To facilitate movement, the system incorporates a motor driver module (such as L298N) shown in fig 2, which regulates power distribution to two DC motors. These motors play a crucial role in propulsion, allowing the life-saving device to move in water and reach a drowning victim efficiently. The wiring connections in the diagram suggest that the motor driver is interfaced with both the Arduino and the battery pack, ensuring seamless control of motor operations.

This design (fig.2) is indicative of a remote-controlled aquatic rescue system, where the user can guide the device toward a person in distress. The Bluetooth module enables wireless operation, making it possible to control the movement of the motors remotely. By integrating these components, the system enhances water safety, offering a rapid response solution for drowning prevention in emergency situations.

IV. FLOW CHART

Fig.3 describes a rescue operation utilizing a device controlled via an app. The process begins with the system being set up and initialized. Once all components are functioning, the system assesses whether a person is in danger. If no danger is detected, the process ends. However, if there is a confirmed danger, the operation moves forward.

At this point, the rescuer uses the application to communicate and provide commands to the device. The device begins navigating toward the location where the distressed individual might be. Upon reaching the area, it actively searches for the person in need. If the person is not found, the device continues its search until success.

When the person is located, the device prepares its mechanical arm for action. The arm is activated to securely rescue the individual. After ensuring the person is safe, the device initiates its return journey, transporting the individual back to safety. Once the person is delivered to a secure

location, the operation concludes, demonstrating the efficiency and precision of the rescue process.

This structured approach highlights the integration of technology in ensuring safety during emergencies.

Figure.3. Flow chart

V. HARDWARE COMPONENTS

5.1 Arduino UNO

In Fig.4 shows the component Arduino which is popular micro-controller board based on the ATmega328p. It features 14 digital I/O pins, 6 analog inputs, and operates at 5V. It's programmable via the Arduino IDE, which simplifies coding. The board can be powered via USB or an external power supply. With its versatility and ease of use, it's ideal for a wide range of electronic project, from beginner's experiments to complex prototype.

A. Working

The Arduino UNO is a micro-controller board based on the ATmega328p chip, designed for creating digital devices and interactive projects. Powered via USB, an AC-to-DC adapter, or a battery, it offers 14 digital I/O pins (6 with PWM output) and 6 analog input pins, allowing versatile interaction with various sensors and actuators. The board's 16 MHz quartz crystal ensures precise timing operations, while the onboard USB port facilitates programming and communication with a computer. Features a reset button for convenient troubleshooting, the Arduino UNO is known for its ease of use, making it an ideal platform for learning electronics and prototyping innovative solutions.

B. Technical Information

- Micro-controller: Atmega328P
- Operating Voltage: 5V
- Input Voltage (recommended): 7-12 V
- Digital I/O Pins: 14 (6 PWM Outputs)
- Analog Input Pins: 6
- Flash memory: 32 KB (0.5 KB used by boot-loader)
- SRAM: 2KB

- EEPROM: 1KB
- Clock speed: 16 MHz
- USB port: For Programming and communication
- ICSP Header: For direct programming of the micro-controller
- Reset Button: To reset the micro-controller

Figure.4.Arduino UNO

C. Features

1. Micro-controller: ATmega328P, providing the core processing power.
2. USB Interface: Facilitates programming and serial communication with a computer, making it easy to upload code and monitor output.
3. Clock speed: 16 MHz quartz crystal, providing the timing for operations and ensuring accurate execution of instructions.
4. Cross-Platform compatibility: The Arduino IDE works on Windows, mac-OS and Linux, making it accessible to a wide range of users.

D. Applications

1. Prototype and Development: Ideal for creating and testing new electronic projects before scaling up.
2. Robotics: Controls motors, sensors and actuators in robots, enabling automation and intelligent behavior.
3. Home automation: Manages lighting, security systems, thermostats, and other home appliances for smart home setups.
4. Wearable Technology: Powers devices like fitness trackers, health monitors and other portable gadgets.

5.2 Motors

A brush-less DC motor (BLDC) is an electric motor driven by direct current (DC) electricity, which is shown in fig 6.2 with an electronically controlled commutation system instead of mechanical brushes. Unlike traditional brushed motors, BLDC motors use electronic controllers to switch the current in the windings, producing a smooth, efficient rotation. This design offers several advantages: higher efficiency, longer lifespan due to the lack of brush wear, lower maintenance requirements, and quieter operation. BLDC motors are widely used in applications requiring high reliability and performance, such as in electric vehicles, drones, and industrial automation. Their precision and durability make them a preferred choice for many modern applications.

A. Working

1. Structure: Consists of a stator with windings and a rotor with permanent magnets.
2. Electronic Commutation: Uses an electronic controller to switch the current in the stator windings.
3. Position sensing: Hall Effect sensors or similar devices detect the rotor position and provide feedback.
4. Magnetic Field Creation: The controller switches current in the windings, generating a rotating magnetic field.

B. Technical information

- Rated Speed: 1000 rpm
- Voltage: Typically operates between 7.2 V to 12 V (2-3 Li-Poly or 6-10 Ni-Cd/NiMH cells).
- Power: Maximum power output around 150 W.
- Torque: Produces torque suitable for small drones and light weight applications.
- Protection Grade: IP65 (Dust and water resistant)

C. Features

- High efficiency: Typically around 80-85%, reducing energy consumption and heat generation.
- Low maintenance: No brushes to wear out, leading to a longer lifespan and less maintenance.
- High torque: Capable of producing significant torque, suitable for various applications.
- Compact design: Lightweight and compact, making it ideal for space-constrained applications.
- Quiet Operation: Operates more quietly compared to brushed motors due to the lack of mechanical contact.

D. Applications

1. Drones and UAVs: Used for propulsion due to their high torque and efficient power consumption, enabling longer flight times and better maneuverability.
2. Robotics: Powers robotic arms, wheels, and joints, providing precise control and movement.
3. Model aircraft: Used in automated systems such as blinds, doors and security cameras, requiring reliable and quiet motors.
4. Industrial Automation: Drives conveyor belts, actuators, and other machinery in manufacturing and assembly lines.

5.3 Servo motor

In fig.5 shows a servo motor which is a rotary actuator that allows precise control of angular or linear position, velocity, and acceleration. It consists of a motor coupled with a sensor for position feedback. The controller adjusts the motor's position by sending signals to the motor and uses feedback from the sensor to ensure accurate movement. Servo motors are known for their high efficiency and precision, making them ideal for applications such as robotics, CNC machinery, and automated manufacturing. They are often used where precise and repeatable motion is required.

A. Working

- Power Supply: Operates within a voltage range of 4.8V to 8.4V.

- Torque: Delivers a torque of 25kg/cm (approximately 250 Nm).
- Control Signal: Uses Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) signals to control the position, speed, and direction.
- Feedback Mechanism: Equipped with sensors (like potentiometers or encoders) to provide real-time feedback on the motor's position and speed.
- Controller: The controller processes the feedback signals and adjusts the motor's output to achieve the desired position or speed.
- High Torque Output: Capable of handling heavy loads and providing precise control even under high-stress conditions.
- Applications: Commonly used in robotics, industrial machinery, and automation systems where high torque and precision are essential.

B. Technical information

- Model: DS3225MG
- Torque: 25 kg/cm (approximately 250 Nm)

- Rotation Angle: 180 degrees (some models offer up to 270 degrees)

Figure.5. Servo motor

- Operating Voltage: 4.8V to 8.4V
- Motor Type: Brush-less DC motor or Core less motor
- Gear Type: Stainless steel and aluminum gears
- Frequency: 50-333Hz
- Weight: Around 60 grams
- Size: 40 x 20 x 40.5 mm
- Current Consumption: Typically around 1-2A depending on load and speed
- Feedback Mechanism: Equipped with sensors for position feedback
- Applications: Robotics, RC vehicles, industrial machinery, and Arduino projects

C. Features

- High Torque: Delivers up to 25 kg/cm (approximately 250 Nm) of torque, ideal for heavy-duty applications.
- Wide Operating Voltage: Functions within a voltage range of 4.8V to 8.4V, providing flexibility in various power scenarios.
- Durable Gears: Equipped with stainless steel or aluminum gears, ensuring longevity and robust performance.
- Rotation Angle: Typically offers a rotation range of 180 degrees, with some models extending up to 270 degrees.
- Feedback Mechanism: Utilizes sensors like potentiometers or encoders for accurate position feedback.
- High Precision: Provides precise control over position, speed, and acceleration, essential for applications requiring high accuracy.

- **Low Noise:** Designed to operate quietly, minimizing noise during operation.
- **Fast Response:** Quick response time to control signals, ensuring smooth and efficient operation.
- **Heat Dissipation:** Built-in heat sink or cooling features to manage heat effectively during high-load conditions.
- **Lightweight:** Weighs around 60 grams, making it suitable for applications where weight is a consideration.
- **Versatile Applications:** Suitable for robotics, industrial machinery, RC vehicles, and automation systems.

D. Applications

- **Robotics:** Used in robotic arms, joints, and grippers to handle heavy loads and perform precise movements.
- **Industrial Automation:** Powers machinery and equipment that require accurate positioning and heavy-duty performance.
- **RC Vehicles:** Controls steering and throttle in large-scale remote-controlled cars, boats, and airplanes.
- **Drones and UAVs:** Adjusts flaps, landing gear, and camera gimbals in larger drones and unmanned aerial vehicles.
- **CNC Machines:** Drives the axes of computer numerical control machines for precise cutting, milling, and engraving.

5.4 Motor Driver L298n

The L298N motor driver is a widely used module for controlling DC motors and stepper motors which is shown in fig 6.3. It's robust and versatile design. It features a dual H-Bridge configuration, allowing it to control two DC motors or one stepper motor simultaneously. The module operates within a voltage range of 5V to 46V and can handle a current of up to 2A per channel, making it suitable for a variety of applications. With the ability to provide precise speed and direction control using Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) and direction control pins, the L298N ensures efficient motor management. Additionally, the driver includes built-in over temperature protection and a low saturation voltage, which enhances its efficiency and safety. The compact design, complete with a heat sink for improved thermal performance, and a power-on LED indicator, makes the L298N a reliable and convenient choice for robotics, automotive projects, and other applications requiring precise motor control.

A. Working

- **Dual H Bridge Configuration:** Controls two DC motors or one stepper motor independently.
- **Direction Control:** Uses transistors to switch the polarity of the voltage applied to the motors, allowing them to move forward or backward.
- **Speed control:** Employs Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) to regulate the voltage and control the speed of the motors.
- **Voltage range:** Operates between 5V and 46V, accommodating various motor types.
- **Current Handling:** Provides up to 2A of continuous current per channel.
- **Built-In Diodes:** Protects against voltage spikes generated by inductive loads.
- **Over temperature Protection:** Ensures safe operation by shutting down the driver if it overheats.
- **Low saturation voltage:** Reduces power loss and improves efficiency.
- **Compact design:** Includes a heat sink for better thermal performance.

- **Logic input:** Accepts standard TTL logic levels for control signals.
- **Power-On LED Indicator:** Helps in visual debugging and status monitoring.

B. Technical specifications

- **Model:** L298n
- **Driver chip:** Dual H-bridge L298n IC
- **Motor supply voltage:** 4.5V to 46V
- **Logic voltage:** 5V
- **Maximum Output Current:** 2A per channel
- **Maximum power:** 25W

C. Features

- **Dual-H Bridge Configuration:** Allows control of two DC motors or one stepper motor independently.
- **Wide Voltage Range:** Operates from 4.5V to 46 V, accommodating various motor types.
- **High Current output:** Delivers up to 2A continuous current per channel, suitable for powerful motors.
- **Direction Control:** Can change the direction of the motor rotation by altering the polarity.
- **Built-in Diodes:** Provides protection against back EMF voltage spikes.

D.Applications

- **Robotics:** Controls DC motors and stepper motors in robotic arms, mobile robots, and automated systems, providing precise movement and speed control.
- **RC vehicles:** Powers motors in remote-controlled cars, boats, and drones, ensuring responsive and reliable operation.
- **Industrial Automation:** Drives conveyor belts, robotic manipulators, and other machinery, enhancing automation and production efficiency.
- **Prototyping:** Integral part of DIY projects and prototypes, allowing hobbyists to experiment with motorized designs and concepts.

VI. APPLICATION OF FRONT END

Figure.6 App front end

The fig 6 represent the function as a remote controller for operating a lifeboat via bluetooth. It includes features like "BT connect" and "disconnect" allowing users to establish or terminate a bluetooth connection with the lifeboat. The interface has directional arrows –up,down,left,right–for navigating the life boat in various directions. A slider bar offers fine –turned adjustments, possibly for controlling speed or other parameters. Additionally the app has action command buttons like "Hold", Helping Hand, release, which likely correspond to specific life boat operations, such as stabilizing its positions, offering support. Overall the app's design suggests that it is purpose built for emergency or risky operation, enabling precise and remote control of a life boat.

VII. PROTOTYPE

Fig.7. Prototype

1. **The Remote-Controlled Feature:** On the right side of the image, someone is holding a remote control or a tablet, showcasing the ability to operate the device from a distance. This allows rescuers to navigate the life-saving device toward the individual in need without physically entering the water.
2. **Flotation Mechanism:** The bright orange color of the device ensures high visibility in water, and its design focuses on delivering buoyancy to keep the drowning individual afloat until further help arrives shown in fig 7. By integrating remote-control technology, the device enhances both safety and efficiency in water rescue scenarios, making it a practical tool for preventing drowning incidents.

VII. ADVANTAGES

- **Enhanced Rescue Efficiency:** The remote control feature significantly reduces response times in emergencies. Rescuers can accurately direct the life jacket to individuals in distress without having to enter the water themselves. This precision ensures that help reaches the person quickly, which is crucial in life-threatening situations.
- **Improved Safety:** The robotic arms are designed to securely grasp individuals, preventing them from slipping away even if they are unconscious or unable to hold onto the life jacket. This firm hold ensures that the person remains securely attached until further help arrives, reducing the risk of secondary drowning.
- **Real-Time Monitoring:** Equipped with advanced sensors, the robotic arms can adjust their grip based on real-time data, ensuring a firm hold under various conditions. Additionally, the life jacket can transmit vital signs and

location data to rescuers, enabling them to make informed decisions quickly. This continuous monitoring enhances the overall safety and effectiveness of the rescue operation.

- **Versatility in Different Conditions:** The life jacket is designed to operate efficiently in various water environments, including oceans, rivers, and lakes. Its adaptability makes it suitable for a wide range of rescue scenarios, from calm waters to rough seas and flood conditions, ensuring that it can be used in almost any aquatic emergency.

- **Autonomous Operation:** In certain situations, the life jacket can operate autonomously, using GPS coordinates and predefined algorithms to navigate to the person in distress. This feature minimizes the need for human intervention, allowing rescuers to focus on other critical tasks and enhancing the overall efficiency of the rescue operation.

- **Advanced Navigation:** The integration of GPS technology ensures precise location tracking and navigation, allowing the life jacket to reach the target individual quickly and accurately. This advanced navigation capability is crucial in ensuring that help arrives swiftly, particularly in complex or crowded water environments.

- **Continuous Communication:** Real-time communication modules keep rescue teams updated and coordinated, improving the overall strategy and effectiveness of rescue missions. This continuous communication allows for better coordination among team members and ensures that everyone is informed and able to respond promptly to changing conditions.

- **Reduced Risk for Rescuers:** By minimizing the need for human rescuers to enter dangerous waters, the life jacket enhances the safety of rescue personnel. This reduced risk is particularly important in hazardous conditions, such as rough seas or polluted waters, where traditional rescue methods might put rescuers at significant risk.

- **Innovative Technology:** The remote-controlled life jacket with robotic arms represents a significant advancement in drowning prevention, setting new standards for water safety and rescue operations. This innovative approach leverages the latest technology to provide a more effective and reliable solution for saving lives in aquatic environments.

- **User-Friendly Interface:** The life jacket typically comes with a user-friendly controller or mobile app, making it easy for rescue personnel to operate the system with minimal training. This intuitive interface ensures that the life jacket can be used effectively even by those with limited technical expertise, enhancing its overall accessibility and usability.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The development of a remote-controlled life jacket with robotic arms marks a significant milestone in the realm of water safety and rescue operations. This innovative project successfully integrates cutting-edge technologies to address the critical issue of drowning, which remains a leading cause of accidental death worldwide. By merging the high-buoyancy flotation capabilities of traditional life jackets with advanced robotic assistance and remote control, this project offers a comprehensive and effective solution for enhancing water rescue efforts.

The remote-controlled life jacket is designed to provide rapid and precise assistance to individuals in distress, even in challenging and hazardous environments. The incorporation of robotic arms equipped with sensors and actuators allows for a secure grip on the individual, preventing them from slipping away, regardless of their physical condition. This feature is particularly crucial in scenarios where the person may be unconscious or unable to hold onto the life jacket themselves. The robotic arms' flexibility and strength ensure they can adapt to various body sizes and conditions, providing reliable support in all situations.

One of the standout features of this life jacket is its remote-control capability, which enables rescuers to operate it from a distance using a handheld controller or a mobile app. This remote operation is facilitated by GPS technology, ensuring accurate location tracking and navigation. The communication modules integrated into the life jacket enable real-time data transmission between the life jacket and the rescue team, allowing for continuous monitoring of the individual's condition. This real-time feedback is invaluable for making informed decisions during the rescue operation and ensuring the individual's safety.

The project involved several stages, from design and development to testing and refinement. The design phase focused on creating a robust and ergonomic life jacket capable of supporting the weight of the robotic arms and the individual. During the development phase, the integration of electronic components, sensors, and actuators was completed, followed by the programming of control algorithms for remote operation. The testing phase involved conducting trials in controlled environments to evaluate the life jacket's performance and make necessary adjustments. These rigorous testing procedures ensured the life jacket met the highest standards of safety and reliability.

In conclusion, the remote-controlled life jacket with robotic arms represents a significant advancement in drowning prevention technology. It addresses the limitations of traditional life jackets by providing remote control and robotic assistance, ensuring rapid and secure rescue operations. The real-time monitoring capabilities further enhance its effectiveness, allowing rescuers to continuously assess and respond to the individual's condition. This innovative device has the potential to save countless lives, making water activities safer for everyone. As technology continues to evolve, the remote-controlled life jacket with robotic arms sets a new standard in water safety and rescue operations, paving the way for future advancements and applications in maritime industries, water sports, and disaster response scenarios. This project exemplifies the power of integrating advanced technology with practical applications to create life-saving solutions. And reliable solution for saving lives in water environments.

IX. FUTURE SCOPE

The future scope of the remote-controlled life jacket with robotic arms is expansive and promising, poised to transform water safety and rescue operations significantly. This innovative technology addresses critical gaps in traditional life-saving methods, providing a more efficient, precise, and

adaptable solution for drowning prevention. As this project evolves, several key areas offer potential for further development and application.

Firstly, advancements in autonomous control and artificial intelligence will enhance the life jacket's capabilities. By incorporating machine learning algorithms, the life jacket can learn from various rescue scenarios, improving its decision-making processes and responsiveness over time. This will enable the device to operate more independently, reducing the need for constant human supervision and intervention. Enhanced autonomy also means the life jacket can be deployed in more challenging and hazardous environments, such as rough seas or flood zones, where human rescuers might be at risk.

Integration with broader emergency response networks is another crucial area for future development. By connecting the life jacket with other rescue and emergency systems, such as drones, boats, and emergency services, a more coordinated and efficient response can be achieved. This interconnected approach ensures that real-time data from the life jacket, including GPS coordinates and vital signs, is instantly available to all responders, facilitating quicker and more informed decision-making.

The potential for expanding the range of applications is significant. Beyond individual rescues, the life jacket can be utilized in large-scale maritime operations, such as offshore drilling platforms, cruise ships, and fishing vessels, where rapid response to emergencies is critical. Additionally, the technology can be adapted for use in recreational water activities, enhancing safety measures for swimmers, surfers, and kayakers. It can also be instrumental in disaster response scenarios, providing essential support in floods and other water-related disasters.

Future research and development efforts could focus on improving the durability and robustness of the life jacket, ensuring it can withstand extreme conditions and prolonged use. Advancements in material science and battery technology will further enhance the device's performance and reliability. Moreover, ongoing user feedback and field testing will be invaluable in refining the design and functionality, ensuring the life jacket meets the diverse needs of various users.

Overall, the remote-controlled life jacket with robotic arms holds immense potential for revolutionizing water safety and rescue operations. As technology continues to advance, this innovative project will undoubtedly set new standards in drowning prevention, offering a safer, more efficient, and reliable solution for saving lives in water environments.

REFERENCES

- [1]"Smart Life Saver Jacket" by Vasanthakumar M, Ravishankar N, Moulidharan, April2020.
- [2]"Controlling robot arm using Kinet"by Asim Turiaqi, Ammar Ashour, May 2019.
- [3]" An intelligent Life Jacket System Based on OneNET" by Kaixuan Wang, Kexuan Zhao, Mingyi Su, Jin Qi, Yuqing Hou, Sheng Tang, April 2021.

- [4]"Self-heating inflatable lifejacket using gas generating agent as energy source" by Zhiyue Han, Wenjie Wang, Zhiming Du, Yupeng Zhang, Yue Yu, June 2021.
- [5]"Design, Analysis and Fabrication of Remote-Controlled Life Saving Buoy" by Saurabh Kathole, Tushar Galphade, Shubham Sonavane, and Shardul Patne, August 2021.
- [6]"Remote Robot Control with Low-cost Robotic Arms and Human Motions" by Jordan Fogg, Zeyu Deng, Emory Meursing, Long Huang, Huaxia Wang, and Chen,Septmeber 2022.
- [7]"Gesture Control Robotic Arm" by Hardik Sharma and Vikas Baghel,June 2020.
- [8]"International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews: Remote Control of Robotic arm using RF" by Bhagyashri Bake, Robit Andani, SHubhangi Pawar, Tanuja Masti, Mr.Sujay Gejji, May 2024.
- [9]Design, Analysis and Fabrication of Remote-Controlled Life Saving Buoy" by Surabh Kathole, Tushar Galphade, Shubham Sonavane, Shardul Patne, August 2021.
- [10]Robotics in Disaster Response: Enhancing search and rescue operations by Mugo Moses, September 2024.

Seashell-Infused Permeable Pavement With Polyester Fiber Strengthening

Adithyan.R, Ahimdas.S.B, Annie Johniya, Gowri.R.Kutty

Civil Engineering dept.

John Cox Memorial C.S.I Institute Of Technology

Trivandrum, India

Abstract- Permeable pavement is an innovative approach to urban infrastructure that allows water to pass through its surface, reducing stormwater runoff, minimizing flooding, and aiding groundwater recharge. The project determines the effectiveness of seashell in percentage replacement of 10%, 20% and 30% by weight of coarse aggregates and polyester fiber by 1% and 2% in enhancing strength, the filtration efficiency and clogging resistance of permeable concrete.

The results of the project shows that the compressive strength decreases slightly with seashell inclusion but it was increased to a great extent when the polyester fiber increased. The tensile and flexural strengths are increased from 10% to 20% percentage of seashell addition and decreases beyond that percentage. Optimum percentage of seashell was identified as 20%. Even though the slump value decreases with seashell, the polyester fiber increases it to a great extent and exhibits medium workability. The permeability increases with seashell addition but the increased polyester fiber slightly reduces the permeability and exhibits better permeability than normal permeable concrete. The amount of solids present in the water passing through it decreases with the addition of polyester fiber and seashell in permeable concrete.

Keywords- *Seashells; Polyester Fibers; Compressive Strength; Flexural Strength; Tensile Strength; Permeability; Total Solids; Permeable Concrete.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Permeable pavement is an innovative approach that allows water penetration, aiding

ground water recharge, reducing stormwater runoff and flood. However, these are made mainly from natural aggregates. Excessive dependence of the this may leads to depletion of earth resources. Some Limitations includes causes clogging due to dirt, debris etc, reducing its ability to allow water infiltration. Lack in strength, so unsuitable for high-traffic areas and of higher Initial Costs. May not perform well in areas with poorly draining soils or on steep slopes. On the other hand, a new technology in permeable pavement is incorporation of materials like seashells and polyester fibers to enhance the performance and sustainability.

Seashell-natural by product of the seafood industry, as a partial substitute of aggregate, providing excellent porosity and structural stability. Calcium carbonate in seashells can help neutralize acidic rainwater as it filters through the permeable pavement. As water percolates through the seashell aggregate, the shells can help filter out pollutants, such as heavy metals and excess nutrients, improving the quality of water that penetrates into the groundwater system. They are Cost-Effective, improved stormwater management, helps in distributing loads more evenly, increasing the pavement's load-carrying capacity, promote sustainability and add strength reducing cracks and deformations.

Polyester Fibers are derived from recycled plastics, are added to improve the pavement to enhance properties. It improve the tensile strength of the pavement, it can withstand heavier loads and reduce the risk of cracking, particularly in high-traffic areas. Polyester fibers helps in resisting rutting. This ensures that the pavement maintains a smooth surface Prevents clogging and degradation and are UV resistant. Freeze thaw resistance and are high temperature resistance. They are resistant to water and environmental

degradation, which helps the pavement resist damage from moisture. This contributes to a longer lifespan. Lower long-term costs and less disruption for users.

The main objectives are- To study the effect of adding different percentages of seashell and polyester fibers to determine the percentage which gives the maximum strength as compared to normal permeable concrete. To investigate the increase in permeability of seashell infused permeable concrete with polyester fibers. To study the increase in filtration capacity of seashell and polyester fiber permeable concrete.

II. SPECIMEN PREPARATION AND TESTING

A. Materials

1. Seashells

Seashells that were commonly used oyster, clam, and scallop shells due to their availability and high calcium content. The seashells are placed in a large container and rinse them thoroughly with fresh water to remove loose sand, dirt, and salt. Placed the shells in a sturdy bag crush them by using a hammer to the size of coarse aggregates. Sieve the crushed seashell into the desired size.

Fig. 1 Seashell

2. Polyester Fibers

Polyester fiber is collected from a trader, which is a textile and mattress industry. The sorted fibers are cleaned to remove any impurities, dirt, or residues. The cleaned polyester is shredded into smaller, uniform pieces to facilitate further processing. The shredded material is dried to remove any moisture that could affect the binding process.

3. Cement and Aggregate

Ordinary Portland cement is used. Cement acts as the binding agent in the concrete mix. Coarse aggregates passing through 20mm sieve and retained in 4.75mm sieve is used as coarse aggregate. Water is essential for mixing, influencing workability and hydration and it also facilitate mixing process. The main physical properties of aggregates [Table 1].

Table 1 Physical properties of aggregates

Properties	Unit	Crushed shell aggregates	Crushed limestone aggregates
Bulk density	g/cm ³	0.93	1.26
Density	g/cm ³	2.77	2.56
Inter-granular porosity	%	66.42	51.17
Water absorption	%	12.05	2.8

B. Mix Composition and Specimen Preparation

The mix design is developed by considering the desired properties of the concrete mix. The M20 concrete is use in this concrete mix. The seashell replaces the coarse aggregate by different percentages (10%, 20% and 30%). The polyester fiber is added by 1% and 2%. The control mix were prepared without adding seashell and polyester fiber. The water-cement ratio is 0.35. The mix proportioning for M20 grade concrete is used for the work. It is designed as per IS 10262:2019 standards. Began with mixing the cleaned and crushed seashells with aggregates and mix thoroughly.

Portland cement was added to the dry mix. Gradually introduced the polyester fiber into the mix and ensured that fibers are dispersed evenly to prevent clumping. Required amount of water was added while continuously mixing to ensure the uniform blend. Formwork was set up as per the required dimensions and shape. Cubes of 150mm×150 mm, beams of 500mm×150mm×150mm and cylinders of 300mm×150mm were prepared. Pour the mix in formwork and compact it thoroughly. The concrete samples were cured by placing them in the water tank. Curing lasts for 28 days.

C. Tests Procedure

1. Workability Test

The slump test is a method for measuring the workability of concrete. It measures the consistency of fresh concrete before it sets. It is carried out in slump cone of height 30 cm, top diameter 10 cm and bottom diameter 20 cm. The concrete is placed in 3 layers and each layer is well compacted. Measure the slump value.

2. Compressive Strength Test

The test specimens of 150 mm cubes is casted and tested at the desired age (7 and 28 days). This test is carried out in the compression testing Machine. Applied a compressive load at a steady rate and Recorded the maximum load and then calculated the compressive strength.

Fig 2 Compressive strength Test

3. Flexural Strength Test

The flexural strength test measures the ability to resist bending forces without failing. It is carried out in a test specimen of 150mm×150mm×500mm beam. After curing, placed the specimen on a three-point bending test setup in a Universal testing machine. Applied a load until failure occurred and calculated the flexural strength.

$$\text{Flexural strength} = Pl/bd^2$$

P = Maximum load applied to the beam

l = Support length

b = width of the beam

d = failure point depth

Fig3 Flexural Strength Test

4. Splitting Tensile Strength Test

Splitting tensile strength test is carried to measure the tensile strength of the concrete, which is determined by applying compressive strength along the length of cylinder. Test is carried out in 150mm×300mm cylinder. After curing, tested the specimen at 7, 28 days in a universal Testing Machine and load is applied along the diameter. Failure point is recorded and calculated the load. Apply the load continuously without shock at a rate of 10 to 15 tons/minutes until the specimen fails. Finally, note down the breaking load (P).

$$\text{Split Tensile Strength} = 2P/\pi dl$$

P = Load applied

d = diameter of specimen

l = length of specimen

Fig 4 Split Tensile Strength Test

5. Permeability Test

Permeability tests measure the ease with which liquid can penetrates into the concrete. Water Permeability Test is conducted to measure permeability of concrete. The side of the cylindrical concrete sample was sealed and a pipe is connected to keep the constant water

head. Water is poured into the sample by keeping constant head of 2 cm and recorded the time taken by 2L water passing through it.

Coefficient of Permeability is calculated using the following formula: K

$$K = QL / tA\Delta h$$

Where,

K = Darcy's Coefficient of Permeability (cm/s)

Q = Volume of water in cm³

L = Length of the test sample in centimetres

t = Elapsed time in seconds

Δh = Applied pressure head in centimetres of water

A = Area of the test sample in cm² ($\pi d^2/4$)

Fig 5 Permeability Test

6. Total Solids Test

Total solids are measured by weighing the amount of solids present in a known volume of sample. This is done by weighing a China dish, filling it with a known volume of 20 ml, evaporating the water in an oven and completely drying the residue, and then weighing the China dish with the residue. The total solids concentration is equal to the difference between the weight of the China dish with the residue and the weight of the dish without it. The residue in the dish is then scrapped and measured the weight of the dish along with the scrapped residue. Since the residue is so light in weight, the lab will need a balance that is sensitive to weights. The measurement of total solids cannot be done in the field. The sample collected is then filtered through the cylindrical sample instead of a filter paper. Then repeat the same procedure of testing unfiltered water. Calculated the total solids, total dissolved solids, total fixed solids, total suspended solids and total volatile solids.

Fig 6 Total Solids Test

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Fresh Concrete

Table 2 Slump Test

Mix	Slump value (mm)
Normal Concrete	100
10% seashell 1% polyester concrete	80
10% seashell 2% polyester concrete	95
20% seashell 1% polyester concrete	65
20% seashell 2% polyester concrete	85
30% seashell 1% polyester concrete	60
30% seashell 2% polyester concrete	70

Fig 7 Slump Value vs percentage of Seashell and Polyester fiber

Fig 8 Slump value vs percentage of seashell & 2% polyester fiber

The table presents slump values for various concrete mixes, including normal concrete and concrete modified with different percentages of seashell and polyester. Normal concrete exhibits the highest slump value of 100 mm, suggesting it has the best workability among all tested mixes. When 10% seashell is introduced into the concrete, the slump value decreases to 80 mm with 1% polyester fiber but increases to 95 mm with 2% polyester fiber. This indicates that increasing the polyester fiber content enhances workability, nearly restoring it to that of normal concrete. As the seashell content increases to 20%, the slump value further decreases, recording 65 mm for 1% polyester fiber and 85 mm for 2% polyester fiber. This suggests that while polyester helps improve workability, a higher proportion of seashell reduces it significantly. The trend continues with 30% seashell content, where the slump value drops to 60 mm with 1% polyester fiber and 70 mm with 2% polyester fiber, the lowest among all mixes. However, all the mixes contain medium workability which is desirable for the permeable concrete.

B. Mechanical Properties

1. Compressive Strength

The results indicate that seashell replacements tend to reduce compressive strength, with higher replacement levels leading to greater reductions since seashell increases the porosity and void ratio. However, increasing polyester fiber content helps mitigate these losses, especially at lower seashell percentages since polyester fiber is

crack resistance and balances the increased void ratio.

Table 3 Compressive Strength

Mix	7 days	28 days
Normal concrete	8.44	12.35
10% seashell 1% polyester concrete	6.83	11.00
10% seashell 2% polyester concrete	8.00	11.65
20% seashell 1% polyester concrete	6.39	9.75
20% seashell 2% polyester concrete	7.50	11.20
30% seashell 1% polyester concrete	5.95	9.30
30% seashell 2% polyester concrete	6.52	10.68

Fig 9 Compressive Strength vs percentage of seashell & 1% polyester fiber

Fig 10 Compressive Strength vs Percentage of seashell & 2% polyester fiber

2. Tensile Strength

From this analysis, it is evident that the inclusion of both seashells and polyester fibers positively impacts the tensile strength of concrete. Tensile strength increases with seashell since the crushed seashells increased the bond between cement and aggregates. It increases with polyester fiber since polyester

fiber acts as bridging cracks and thus improving tensile strength.

Table 4 Tensile Strength

Mix	7 days	28 days
Normal concrete	0.63	1.05
10% seashell 1% polyester concrete	0.65	1.25
10% seashell 2% polyester concrete	1.27	2.08
20% seashell 1% polyester concrete	1.73	2.65
20% seashell 2% polyester concrete	1.96	3.18
30% seashell 1% polyester concrete	1.43	2.31
30% seashell 2% polyester concrete	1.67	2.70

Fig 11 Tensile strength vs percentage of seashell & 1% polyester fiber

Fig 12 Tensile Strength vs Percentage of Seashell & 2% Polyester Fiber

Higher percentages of polyester fibers and seashells generally lead to improved tensile performance, with the most substantial gains observed in the 20% seashell and 2% polyester fiber mix. This suggests an optimal balance between seashell replacement and polyester fiber reinforcement, significantly

enhancing concrete's tensile strength properties.

3. Flexural Strength

The flexural strength increases with seashell since the crushed seashell increases the bond between cement and aggregates. Also, it increases with polyester fiber since polyester fiber acts as bridging cracks and thus improves flexural strength. Overall, the data indicate that incorporating seashells and polyester fibers enhances flexural strength, with the most effective improvement observed at 20% seashell replacement with 2% polyester fiber reinforcement. However, beyond a certain threshold (30% seashell replacement), the benefits seem to slightly diminish.

Table 5 Flexural Strength

Mix	7 days	28 days
Normal concrete	3.5	4.75
10% seashell 1% polyester concrete	4.25	5.90
10% seashell 2% polyester concrete	5.7	7.48
20% seashell 1% polyester concrete	6.32	8.72
20% seashell 2% polyester concrete	6.68	9.57
30% seashell 1% polyester concrete	6.02	8.37
30% seashell 2% polyester concrete	6.39	9.28

Fig 13 Flexural Strength vs percentage of seashell & 1% polyester fiber

Fig 14 Flexural strength vs percentage of seashell & 2% polyester fiber

Fig 15 Coefficient of permeability vs percentage of seashell & 1% polyester fiber

4. Permeability Test

The data suggests that incorporating seashells increases the permeability of concrete and making it more porous due to the shape and configuration of seashells. However, polyester fiber plays a crucial role in reducing this effect by reducing the void ratio. But coefficient of permeability is still higher than normal concrete which is desirable for permeable concrete. This information is useful in determining the best mix for balancing strength, permeability, and durability in construction materials.

Fig 16 Coefficient of permeability vs percentage of seashell & 2% polyester fiber

Table 6 Coefficient of Permeability

Mix	Coefficient Of Permeability (cm/s)
Normal Concrete	4.24
10% seashell 1% polyester concrete	4.85
10% seashell 2% polyester concrete	4.68
20% seashell 1% polyester concrete	6.17
20% seashell 2% polyester concrete	5.5
30% seashell 1% polyester concrete	6.4
30% seashell 2% polyester concrete	6.0

5. Total Solids Test

Table 7 Total Solids Test

Mix	Total solids (mg/l)	Total Fixed Solids (mg/l)	Total Dissolved Solids (mg/l)	Total Suspended Solids (mg/l)	Total Volatile Solids (mg/l)
Normal Concrete	32000	30500	6500	25500	1500
10% seashell 1% polyester concrete	12000	10500	2500	9500	1500
10% seashell 2% polyester concrete	7500	6500	2000	5500	1000
20% seashell 1% polyester concrete	6500	5500	2000	4500	1000
20% seashell 2% polyester concrete	5000	4000	1500	3500	1000
30% seashell 1% polyester concrete	6000	5000	1500	4500	1000
30% seashell 2% polyester concrete	4500	4000	1500	3000	500

IV CONCLUSION

Waste recovery is now a favorable solution for technical and economic reasons. The purpose of this study is the valuation of uses of marine co-product, like seashells, to produce an eco-material that responds to the environmental problem. The experimental study focused on the idea of replacing natural aggregates with recycled shell aggregates in different percentage (10%, 20% and 30%) and studied their influence on the properties of pervious concrete. The addition of the mix in lower percentages has helped to improve the strength of the concrete. It was concluded that the permeable concrete gives the maximum strength when the coarse aggregates is replaced by 20% seashell and 2% polyester fiber added to the mix.

- It was concluded that the permeability of the permeable concrete increases with increase in the percentage of seashell and it is balanced by some extend with the increase in polyester fiber content.
- It was concluded that the amount of solid content in the water which is filtered through the permeable concrete decreases significantly with the increase in the percentages of seashell and polyester fiber and thus increases the quality of water.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We express our sincere gratitude to Ms. Nithya Susan Joseph, Assistant Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, for her invaluable guidance and support. We also extend our thanks to Mrs. Cera Shalom and Mrs. L. Sreeletha for their assistance, and to Dr. Anshad A.S for permitting us to carry out our project at John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of Technology. Finally, we are grateful to our faculty, parents, friends, and everyone who contributed to the successful completion of our project.

REFERENCES

- [1] Boutouil M., Ngyuyen D.H., Sebaibi N., Leleyter L. and Baraud F.(2013). "Volatization of seashell by-products in pervious concrete pavers", *Construction and building Materials*, Vol.49, pp. 151-160, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2013.08.017>

Fig 17 Amount of solids vs percentage of seashell & 1% polyester fiber

Fig 18 Amount of solids vs percentage of seashell & 2% polyester fiber

The solid content decreases with increase in seashells since crushed seashell trapped the pollutants due to the rough structure and thus water quality increases. It also increases with increase in polyester fiber since it traps the debris and sediments through its mesh like formation ensuring the water can infiltrate through the concrete and thus it prevents clogging of permeable concrete. The reduction in total solids, particularly suspended and fixed solids, could have implications for the material's porosity and permeability. Permeable concrete is designed to allow water to pass through, and incorporating seashells and polyester fibers might influence its filtration capacity, strength, and durability.

The data suggests that higher seashell and polyester content lead to lower total solid concentrations, which could indicate increased porosity. However, the drop in total fixed solids may also suggest a reduction in structural integrity, potentially affecting the load-bearing capacity of the concrete. Additionally, the decline in volatile solids implies a decrease in organic content, which might reduce biodegradation risks and enhance the material's longevity.

- [2] Kumar P.M and Sai V.J.(2019). “Experimental analysis of durability of pervious concrete by using crushed seashells”, *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, Vol.6, <https://www.irjet.net/archives/V6/i9/IRJET-619343.pdf>
- [3] Melais F.Z., Dorbani K., Arabi N. and Achoura D.(2023). “The use of marine shells as aggregates in pervious concretes”, *Geomaterials and Environment Laboratory*, pp. 76-91, <https://doi.org/10.32047/CWB.2023.28.2.2>
- [4] Nguyen D.H., Sebaibi N., Boutouil M., Leleyter L. and Baraud F.(2023). “The Use of Seashell By-Products in Pervious Concrete Pavers”, *Engineering and Technology*, Vol.7, <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/260120431>
- [5] Olivia M., Mifshella A.A. and Darmayanti L.(2015). “Mechanical properties of seashell concrete”, *The 5th International Conference of Euro Asia Civil Engineering Forum*, pp.760–764, <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0/>
- [6] Sangeetha P., Annamalai V.E. and Kaythry P.(2023). “Durability studies on concrete with partial replacement of cement and coarse aggregates by seashell waste”, *Materials Today: Proceedings*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2023.12.009>
- [7] Sha F., Zhang S., Sun X., Fan G., Diao Y., Duan X., Qiao A. and Wang H.(2024). “Mechanical performance and pore characteristics of pervious concrete”, *Case studies in Construction Materials*, Vol.21, <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.cscm.2024.e03674>
- [8] Tabatabaeian M., Khaloo A. and Khaloo H.(2019). “An innovative high-performance pervious concrete with polyester and epoxy resins”, *Construction and Building Materials*, Vol.228, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2019.116820>
- [9] Xie N., Akin M. and Shi X.(2019). “Permeable Concrete Pavements: A review of environmental benefits and durability”, *Journal of cleaner Production*, Vol.210, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.11.134>

Smart Garbage Management System

Abhishek R Sen, Anandu B Vijay, Sivani Bhadra

Mrs. TINI S RUSSEL (ASST. PROFESSOR ECE)

Department of Electronic And Communication Engineering, JCMCSIIT, Kannammoola

Abstract— Smart Garbage Management System monitors the garbage bins and informs about the level of garbage collected in the garbage bins via a web page. Ultrasonic sensors are placed over the bins to detect the garbage level and compare it with the garbage bins depth. In addition, we also have weight sensors attached below the garbage bins. Thus, the system sends over the internet the level of fill of the garbage bins as well as the weight of the fill of the garbage bins. The advantage of this combo sensing is that the garbage bin lifting weight can also be known by the authorities. If the garbage bin is not filled up, but still the weight of fill has reached the limit of what the garbage lifting vehicles can pick up, the vehicles can be immediately driven towards that bin for evacuation. IoT or the Internet of Things refers to a network of linked physical objects which can interact and share data among themselves without any human interference. The system makes use of AVR family microcontroller, LCD screen, Wi fi modem for sending data and a buzzer. Atmega328 microcontroller-based device monitors the garbage continuously. Ultrasonic sensors track the level of the garbage. Here two sensors are used to monitor two garbage bins. A Weighting sensor module (HX711) is used to calculate garbage bin weight. LCD screen is used for garbage level display. Wi-Fi module (ESP8266) uploads all data to the website.

Keywords — Weight cell, Ultrasonic Sensor, Arduino Uno, ESP8266, LCD Display, Buzzer

I. INTRODUCTION

The principle of IoT can be applied in every industry in the modern world. Waste management has been the major issue as well as the task in most of the cities so that they inculcate the best way of waste disposal method. Today in most of the public places there are no proper method is followed because we cannot monitor the dustbins manually. Introduction to smart garbage management system using sensor and weight cell for real time data processing, this data will have a optimization method to know the various applications such as saving money, saving fuel and importantly less time. One of the main concerns with our cities are the waste management which impacts the health and environment of our society. The garbage bins are built with the sensory module that is the ultrasonic sensors, that continuously monitors the best possible levels of garbage monitoring system. Any moment the garbage level passes over the critical level/red line that crosses the limits that is usually written in the code. The system then generates the notification to the monitoring panel so that they can collect the waste from the bins, which also enables you to save the fuel, fleet and labor maintenance costs. IOT based garbage monitoring system is very effective in it's way which will help in keeping the cities clean. The concern is not just about keeping the cities clean, but also reducing the man work for the cleanliness concepts in the areas, dump yards, factories.

II. EXISTING SYSTEM

In the existing system, if the bin is empty, the garbage is collected on the daily regular basis by the municipal staff. As we see several times in the public places the garbage bins are full due to the regular rise in the waste. Because of this, the garbage is shrinking and producing the bad odor that tends to cause air pollution and spread disease. That can cause the damage to human health. Finding garbage bin location is also one of the tasks especially for new driver. GPS facility had been introduced to find the location and clean the dustbins to overcome the aforementioned problem. Disadvantages of the existing systems is i) It requires more human resource to run the system. ii) The system is totally manual. iii) High costs. iv) It spreads bad smell and may cause illness to human beings. v) Unhygienic Environment and look of the city.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The system proposed focuses on the process of waste collection. It reduces the consumption of time, and is an automated process. The bin's status is continuously monitored, and the notification is sent via the web site to the designated authority. The advantages of the proposed systems are i) Real time information of the dustbins. ii) Intelligent service management. iii) Improves the quality of the environment. iv) Cost management and the improvement of the capital.

IV. HARDWARE

Arduino Uno, Ultrasonic Sensor, Load cell, HX711 module, Wi-Fi module, LCD Display, Buzzer

A. Arduino Uno

The ATmega328 Controller is an open-source controller board based on the Arduino.cc ATmega328 microchip controller. The board is equipped with sets of digital and analog input / output (I/O) pins that can be interfaced with different boards (shields) for expansion and other circuits. The board has 14 digital pins, 6 analog pins and is programmable via a type B USB cable with the Arduino IDE (Integrated Development Environment). It can be powered by a USB cable or by an external 9 Volt battery, but it accepts voltages between 7 and 20 volts. It's similar with Arduino Nano and Leonardo, too. Distributed under a Creative Common Attribution Share-Alike 2.5 license, the hardware reference design is available on the Arduino website. The ATmega328 comes pre-programmed with a boot loader that enables new code to be uploaded to it without using an external hardware programmer.

B. Ultrasonic Sensor

Ultrasonic sensor HC-SR04 uses sonar to measure distance to an item. This provides excellent non-contact range detection with high precision and an easy to use kit with

reliable readings. It comes complete with module ultrasonic transmitter and receiver. The time between the signal being transmitted and received allows us to know the distance of an object.

C. Load cell

A load cell is defined as a "weight measuring system needed for electronic scales that display weights in Figure its." However, load cell is not limited to weight measurement in electronic scales. Load cell is a passive transducer or sensor translating the force exerted into electrical signals. They are also called "load transducers". The only load cells that predominate, however, are the load cells based on strain gages. The reason why strain gage-based load cells are broadly adopted is their characteristics:- Small size compared to other load-cell types. Long operating life due to lack of moving parts or other friction-causing components. Ease in production due to small number of components.

D. HX711 (Weighthing Sensor Module)

Weight Sensor Module is based on HX711, which is a 24-bit analog-to - digital precision converter designed to interface directly with a bridge sensor for weight scale and industrial control applications. HX711 not only has a few simple functions compared to other chips, it also includes high integration, rapid response, immunity and other features. The lower chip ds the electronic scale costs, while improving performance and reliability at the same time.

E. Wi-Fi Module (ESP8266)

The ESP8266 Wi-Fi Module is a self-contained SOC with built-in TCP / IP protocol stack that can provide connectivity to your Wi-Fi network to any microcontroller. The ESP8266 will host an application or discharge all Wi-Fi networking functions from another device processor. The ESP8266 Wi-Fi module is a low cost component with which manufacturers make module microcontroller wirelessly networkable. Wi-Fi module ESP 8266 is a system-on-a-chip with 2.4GHz range capabilities. It uses a RISC CPU of 32 bit, running at 80MHz. It is based on the TCP / IP (Transfer control protocol). This is the most critical component in the system because it conducts the IOT operation. It has ROM booting 64 kb, RAM instruction 64 kb, RAM data 96 kb. Wi-Fi device performs IOT operation by sending data from an energy meter to a website that can be accessed via IP address. The TX, RX pins link with the Arduino microcontroller's 7 and 8 pins.

F. Liquid Crystal Display (LCD)

The word LCD stands for liquid crystal display. It is one type of electronic display module used in a wide range of applications such as various circuits & devices such as cell phones, calculators, computers, television sets, etc. Such displays are chosen for light-emitting diodes and seven segments in multi-segment configurations. The main benefits of using this module are inexpensive; simply programmable, animations, and the display of custom characters, special and even animations, etc., is not limited. A 16 LCD has two registers like the register of data and the register of commands. The RS (register select) is primarily used to switch between registers. When the set of the register is '0' it is known as the register of commands. Similarly, it is known as the data register when the register set is '1.'

V. IMPLEMENTATION

IoT garbage monitoring with weight sensing is very simple and real time. The project consist of:-

- Atmega328 microcontroller-based device which monitors the garbage continuously.
- Ultrasonic sensors which track the level of the garbage. Two sensors are used to monitor two garbage bins.
- A Weighing sensor module that is used to calculate garbage bin weight.
- LCD screen for garbage level display.
- Wi-Fi module for uploading all data to the website.

The Wi-Fi module is attached to the pre-program SSID and to the PASSWORD at device initialization. The user must set the SSID and PASSWORD to either router or mobile hotspot. During the Wi-Fi connection, the system also calculates the garbage bin height and record all the bins height. After that the system starts monitoring all the garbage levels. Also for better performance the Wi-Fi connection is established over and over again for each time of garbage monitoring. All the monitoring data is sent over the website so that the person concerned or the municipal officer can see the level of garbage from anywhere. The machine automatically plays the buzzer when each garbage bin is full and turns the led on and it constantly sounds the buzzer until the garbage level goes down.

VI. BLOCK DIAGRAM

VII. FLOW CHART

VIII. CONCLUSION

This project work is implementing a smart garbage management system using Ultrasonic Sensor, Weight Sensor, Microcontroller, and Wi-Fi. This system ensures dustbins will be cleaned soon when the level of garbage reaches its maximum. If the dustbin is not cleaned in a reasonable period,

the record shall be submitted to the higher authority which may take appropriate action against the contractor concerned. This program also helps track the false reports and therefore can eliminate corruption in the overall system of management. This reduces the total number of garbage collection vehicle trips and thus reduces the overall costs associated with the garbage collection. In the end, it helps to preserve cleanliness in society. The smart garbage management system therefore allows collection of the garbage more efficient.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We are grateful to the Department of Electronics and Communication, JCMCSIIT, Kannammoola for inspiring the project.

REFERENCES

- [1] Jose M. Gutierrez and Michael Jensen, "Smart Waste Collection System Based on Location Intelligence", 2015.
- [2] Parkash and Prabu, "IoT based waste management for smart city" Dept. of Embedded System Design, NIELIT, February 2016.
- [3] Sanket Dharme and Vaibhav, "IoT based intelligent Bin for smart cities" Dept. Of Electrical engineering, SKN institute of technology, May 2020.
- [4] Darshan Suthar and Mathin Ahmed, "IoT Based Garbage Monitoring System and Notification Application" Sri Dharmasthala institute of technology, May 2023.
- [5] Manab Kr. Das and Saikat Mondal, "IoT Based Intelligent Smart Bin for Garbage Monitoring based on Real-Time Data Analysis" Dept. of Computer application and science, IEM-Kolkata, June 2023.

SMART MEDICINE BOX

Abhijay A. S., Aishwarya baburaj S., Nandana B. S., Vishnu Varma
Department of Computer Science and Engineering John Cox Memorial
CSI Institute of Technology, Kerala, India

Abstract—An advanced medicine box monitoring, analysis and control system is proposed in this paper. The latter design is based on a smart and safe medical box that assists patients in taking their pills treatment on time. Two main functionalities characterize this system: safety which assures the well-being of the patient and the good functioning of the system by duplicating the electrical components and the security that helps keeping the medication out of the reach of the children by automatically locking the medical box whenever the patient takes his pills. This system can also be monitored by the patient parents as it will be linked to a phone application. This application will be used to configure the medical box by calculating the weight of each pill, setting the schedule of medical intake, alarming the user of the number of remaining pills, generating alarms whenever the patient does not take the required number of pills or doesn't take them at all, and so on. This system was implemented and tested by more than 50 patients who were taking several medication types (each one of them takes one medication only) and were using different mobile phone. The overall results were very acceptable with a faulty alarm generation below 3%..

Keywords—*Medicine box monitoring, Phone application, alarm, Electrical components*

I. INTRODUCTION

As the population ages, the number of elderly individuals managing chronic health conditions is on the rise. Many of these conditions require regular medication, which can become complex due to multiple prescriptions. Irregular medication intake and medication errors—such as taking the wrong pill or missing doses—can lead to severe health complications, increased hospitalizations, and even mortality. Adhering to prescribed medication regimens is critical for managing chronic illnesses, preventing complications, and ensuring quality of life. Effective strategies to promote adherence can significantly improve health outcomes and reduce healthcare costs. Advancements in technology have led to the development of smart medication management systems, such as smart pillboxes. These devices are designed to remind users about their medications, track adherence, and ensure that the right pills are taken at the right times. Features often include alarms, visual indicators, and connectivity with mobile apps for easy management. The integration of technology into medication management represents a proactive approach to addressing the challenges

faced by elderly individuals, promoting independence, and enhancing their overall health and well-being.

II. Literature Survey

In recent years, several approaches have been explored to enhance medicine Box. IoT-based smart medicine box is to assist patients, particularly the elderly, in managing their medication effectively by providing timely reminders for medication intake. It aims to ensure that patients take their medicines at the correct times and in the prescribed quantities, thereby reducing the risk of missed doses. The system also tracks medication adherence by recording dosages taken and missed, which can be monitored by caregivers or family members. By enabling patients to manage their medications independently, the smart medicine box promotes autonomy and alleviates the burden on family members. Ultimately, the device seeks to improve health outcomes and enhance the quality of life for individuals who require regular medication. The advent of technology has revolutionized healthcare, and the development of smart devices has significantly impacted patient care. One such innovation is the smart medicine box, a device designed to enhance medication adherence, particularly for elderly individuals and those with complex medication regimens. This paper will explore the design and implementation of a smart medicine box that addresses the challenges associated with medication adherence. By incorporating features like automated dispensing, timely reminders, and remote monitoring, this device aims to improve patient outcomes and reduce the burden on caregivers. The following sections will delve into the specific design considerations, technical implementation, and potential benefits of this smart medicine box.

III. OBJECTIVES

Develop a reliable reminder system that ensures elderly users take their medications on time, reducing the risk of missed doses or incorrect usage. Create a user-friendly design that accommodates the needs of individuals with visual impairments and cognitive challenges, making it easy for them to interact with the device. Enable family members to program the pillbox remotely, allowing them to customize

medication schedules and monitor adherence without being physically present. Implement alarm and LED indicators that offer clear and intuitive reminders for medication times, ensuring users can easily understand when to take their pills. Integrate a notification system that alerts family members or caregivers if a dose is missed, allowing for timely intervention and support. Design an engaging and motivating experience for users, fostering a sense of independence and responsibility in managing their medications. Use materials and components that are safe, durable, and easy to clean, ensuring the pillbox can withstand daily use in various environments. Implement a feedback mechanism that allows users and caregivers to provide input on the device's functionality, leading to ongoing enhancements and better user satisfaction.

IV. SCOPE

The scope of this topic is creating an Arduino-based programmable pillbox tailored for elderly individuals and those with visual impairments. Recognizing the challenges these users face in managing their medications, the device will incorporate multiple compartments to organize pills designated for different times of the day. This structure will facilitate easy access and reduce confusion, ultimately helping users adhere to their prescribed medication schedules. In addition to physical organization, the pillbox will feature auditory alarms and LED indicators to provide timely reminders, ensuring that users take the correct medications at the right times. A user-friendly programming interface will allow family members to set and adjust medication schedules conveniently, fostering a supportive environment that enhances the overall user experience. This feature aims to empower both users and caregivers, promoting collaboration in medication management. Furthermore, the project will include tracking functionalities to monitor medication adherence, allowing users and caregivers to access reports on medication-taking behaviors. While the primary focus is on the pillbox, future enhancements could explore integration with a mobile application for remote management and notifications. User testing and feedback will play a crucial role in the development process, ensuring the final product effectively meets the needs of the target population and can potentially expand to include additional health monitoring features.

V. PROPOSED SYSTEM

A Smart Medicine Box is a system designed to help individuals manage their medications in a more efficient, accurate, and convenient manner. It is especially beneficial for elderly people, individuals with chronic conditions, or anyone who needs to take multiple medications daily. The pillbox integrates both hardware and software components, ensuring a seamless user experience. At the core is the microcontroller, which serves as the central processing unit, managing all functions such as timing, reminders, and user inputs. The pillbox features three distinct compartments designed to hold medications, each programmed for different times of the day. To alert users, auditory signals are provided via a buzzer or speaker, complemented by LED indicators that visually signal

when it's time to take medications. User interaction is facilitated through buttons or sensors that allow for easy programming and confirmation of medication intake. The device is powered by a reliable source, such as batteries or a USB connection, ensuring continuous operation. In terms of software, the device is programmed using the microcontroller, where the code governs timing, alarms, and user interactions. The user interface is designed to be simple and intuitive, allowing family members to easily input medication schedules.

A tracking system is incorporated into the software, enabling the logging of medication-taking behaviors and the generation of reports that can be shared with caregivers and healthcare providers. This combination of hardware and software elements ensures that the pillbox is both functional and user-friendly. This pillbox begins with a needs assessment, gathering input from potential users and caregivers to identify specific requirements and challenges in medication management. This is followed by the design and prototyping phase, where initial models are created and tested for functionality and usability. Iterative testing involves engaging users to provide feedback, allowing for continuous refinement of both hardware and software components. Once the design is finalized, the implementation phase includes training users and caregivers on how to effectively set up and use the pillbox. Finally, ongoing monitoring and evaluation will be conducted post-deployment to assess adherence rates and user satisfaction, informing any further enhancements to the device.

medications. A servo motor controls the compartment doors, unlocking them upon successful user authentication. The system is powered by a 6U power supply, ensuring stable performance. The system is designed using an ESP32 microcontroller, which controls all primary functions, including facial recognition, alarms, and compartment access. The medicine box consists of three bins with multiple sub-compartments, each designated for specific medications.

B. Facial Recognition & Authentication

To enhance security, the system employs biometric authentication via facial recognition. Authorized users register their facial data, which is stored in a database. When a user attempts to access medication, the system captures their facial image, processes key features, and matches it against the stored database. If authenticated, the corresponding compartment door unlocks; otherwise, access is denied, and the attempt is logged. Security is a major aspect of the Smart Medicine Box, achieved through facial recognition authentication. During the initial setup, the system registers the faces of authorized users (patients and caregivers) and stores their facial features in a database.

C. Time-Based Scheduling & Alerts

Medication schedules are set through a web application, which allows users or caregivers to configure reminders. The ESP32 continuously monitors the system clock, and when the scheduled time arrives, it triggers an alarm system consisting of a buzzer and LED indicators. The LED corresponding to the correct compartment lights up, guiding the user to take their medication. The system follows a time-based medication schedule, set up through a web application. The user or caregiver inputs the required medication time, bin selection, and dosage details into the application.

D. Web Application for Monitoring & Control

The web-based interface enables remote tracking of medication history. Caregivers can check whether medication was taken on time or missed, ensuring adherence. The application also logs all facial recognition attempts for security purposes. The web-based interface provides users with complete control over medication schedules and access records.

E. Auto-Lock & Security Measures

Once the user retrieves their medication, the system automatically locks the compartment to prevent unauthorized access. The system also maintains a history log of medication access and alerts to enhance monitoring. To enhance security, the system includes an auto-lock feature that engages after medication retrieval.

F. Power Management & Connectivity

The system runs on a 6U power supply, ensuring stable operation for all components, including the ESP32, servo motors, LED indicators, and alarm system. Since it operates through a hotspot connection between the medicine box and a laptop, it does not rely on external internet sources, making it more reliable in remote areas.

VII. RESULTS

The system demonstrates high performance in identifying authorized users, achieving an impressive accuracy of 95%, precision of 96%, and recall of 95%, with a balanced

F1-score of 95.5%. It offers secure facial recognition access, automated LED and buzzer reminders, and a web application for scheduling and tracking purposes.

Confusion Matrix - Smart Medicine Box

Additionally, the system is equipped with LED indicators for compartment activation and integrates ESP32, servo motors, and a buck converter. It boasts a 94% successful access rate, 97% timely alert efficiency, and maintains a low false recognition rate of 4%. This combination of features ensures a robust and efficient solution. The system demonstrates high performance in identifying authorized users, achieving an impressive accuracy of 95%, precision of 96%, and recall of 95%, with a balanced F1-score of 95.5%. It offers secure facial recognition access, automated LED and buzzer reminders, and a web application for scheduling and tracking purposes. Additionally, the system is equipped with LED indicators for compartment activation and integrates ESP32, servo motors, and a buck converter. It boasts a 94% successful access rate, 97% timely alert efficiency, and maintains a low false recognition rate of 4%. This combination of features ensures a robust and efficient solution.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The Arduino-based programmable pillbox represents a significant advancement in medication management for elderly and visually impaired individuals. By integrating user-friendly features such as automated reminders, visual and auditory alerts, and sensor-based tracking, this system addresses the critical challenges of medication adherence. The thoughtful design, both in hardware and software, ensures that users can easily navigate their medication schedules with minimal assistance, promoting greater independence and safety. Moreover, the inclusion of data logging and optional connectivity features allows caregivers to monitor adherence in real time, fostering a collaborative approach to health management. This solution not only enhances the quality of life for its users but also provides peace of mind for caregivers.

and family members. Overall, the programmable pillbox is a practical and innovative tool that leverages technology to support better health outcomes, demonstrating the potential of smart systems in everyday life.

REFERENCES

- [1] Akshaya.C , Jayasowmiya.J , Kanchana.P , Raja.J, ‘Smart Medicine Box’ International Journal of Engineering Research in Computer Science and Engineering (IJERCSE) Vol 6, Issue 7, page no.125-128, July 2019

- [2] Anandhapadmanaban .S, Ashifa .A, Sanjay Kumar .S, Suryalakshmi .R, ‘ A Smart Medicine Box for Medication Management using IoT’ Journal of Xi'an University of Architecture & Technology, Volume XII, Issue V, page no.1169- 1173, 2020

- [3] Deepak Bhatt, Shantanu Verma, Ghongade R.B,’ Smart Medicine Box’, International Journal of Industrial Electronics and Electrical Engineering, ISSN(p): 2347-6982, ISSN(e): 2349-204X Volume-6, Issue-3, page no.47-50, Mar.-2018

- [4] Diao Salama Abdul Minaam MohamedAbd-ELfattah, ‘Smart drugs: Improving Healthcare using Smart Pill Box for Medicine Reminder and Monitoring System’ Elsevier B.V 20 page no 444-456, November 2018

Smart Vision: An AI-Based Assistive Device for Visually Impaired People

Alvina S, Anjana S, Anisha L.S, Angel S

From John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of Technology

Affiliated to APJ Abdul Kalam Technological University

Abstract— Visually impaired individuals face numerous challenges in their daily lives, necessitating assistive technology for enhanced mobility and independence. This paper presents an AI-powered wearable assistive device, Smart Vision, designed to provide real-time object recognition, text reading, facial and emotion detection, and obstacle avoidance. The device integrates deep learning, computer vision, and sensor-based technologies to offer auditory feedback, enabling users to perceive their surroundings effectively. Experimental validation using real-world scenarios demonstrates the system's accuracy in recognizing objects, detecting obstacles, and facilitating social interaction.

Keywords— Assistive technology, Computer vision, Deep learning, Object recognition, Visually impaired, Wearable devices

I. INTRODUCTION

Millions of visually impaired individuals worldwide encounter difficulties in performing daily tasks, including identifying objects, reading printed text, and navigating safely. Traditional assistive tools such as white canes and braille books offer limited functionalities, whereas AI-driven solutions provide real-time, dynamic assistance. This paper proposes Smart Vision, a compact and energy-efficient wearable device that leverages deep learning and embedded systems to enhance accessibility for visually impaired individuals.

II. RELATED WORK

Several AI-based assistive technologies have been developed, including deep learning-based object recognition systems, smart glasses, and speech-to-text tools. While previous systems primarily relied on cloud processing, Smart Vision incorporates an edge-based computing approach using a Raspberry Pi, ensuring real-time responses and privacy.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

A. System Overview

The Smart Vision device comprises a high-resolution camera for image capture, ultrasonic sensors for obstacle detection, a microphone for voice commands, and a Raspberry Pi for local AI processing. The system provides real-time feedback through a speaker or headphones.

B. Hardware Components

1. Camera Sensor – Captures real-time images for object recognition and OCR.
2. Ultrasonic Sensors – Detects obstacles and estimates distance for safe navigation.
3. Processing Unit – A Raspberry Pi is used for executing deep learning algorithms.
4. Microphone – Captures voice commands and aids in emotion detection.
5. Speaker/Headphones – Provides real-time auditory feedback to the user.
6. Power Supply – Rechargeable battery for extended operational time.

C. Software and AI Models

The device utilizes multiple deep learning models, including:

- YOLO (You Only Look Once) for object detection.
- FaceNet for facial recognition.
- CNN-based models for emotion detection.
- Tesseract OCR for text recognition.
- Text-to-Speech (TTS) for multilingual voice output.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Object and Text Recognition

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) such as YOLO and SSD are employed for real-time object detection. Optical Character Recognition (OCR) extracts text from captured images, allowing users to read printed and handwritten text through audio feedback.

B. Facial and Emotion Recognition

FaceNet is used for facial recognition to identify familiar individuals, while CNN-based models analyze facial expressions to interpret emotions. This helps users better engage in social interactions.

C. Obstacle Detection and Navigation

Ultrasonic sensors continuously scan the user's surroundings to detect obstacles and provide real-time feedback via audio or haptic signals. Signal filtering techniques ensure precision in obstacle identification.

D. Multilingual Voice Assistance

A multilingual TTS engine allows users to receive feedback in their preferred language. Users can customize voice settings such as speech speed and volume for an enhanced experience.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

A. Testing Conditions

The system was evaluated under various conditions, including different lighting environments, indoor and outdoor settings, and moving object scenarios.

B. Performance Metrics

- Object Recognition Accuracy: 89% on a dataset of commonly encountered objects.
- OCR Efficiency: 85% for printed text; lower accuracy for handwritten text.
- Obstacle Detection: 92% accuracy for large objects; struggles with small obstacles.
- Response Time: 150ms for real-time processing.

C. User Feedback and Real-World Testing

Blind and visually impaired users tested the device, providing feedback on usability and performance. Key observations include:

- Improved mobility and confidence in navigation.

- Effective social interaction through facial recognition.
- Need for enhancements in recognizing small or moving obstacles.

Functionality	True Positive (TP)	False Positive (FP)	False Negative (FN)	True Negative (TN)
Object Recognition	80	10	15	95
Face Recognition	45	7	5	50
Emotion Detection	40	6	9	52
Obstacle Detection	90	8	12	85

VI. CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS

A. Environmental Variability

The performance of object recognition and OCR is affected by lighting conditions, shadows, and object occlusions.

B. Processing and Latency Issues

High-resolution image processing requires significant computational power, which can lead to delays. Optimizing deep learning models is essential to maintain real-time performance.

C. Battery Life and Power Management

As a wearable device, power efficiency is critical. Future versions need optimized hardware to extend battery life without compromising processing speed.

D. Cost and Accessibility

The cost of high-performance sensors and embedded processors may limit widespread adoption. Efforts are needed to reduce costs while maintaining functionality.

VII. FUTURE WORK

A. Enhanced Object Detection

Incorporating AI-driven depth perception and LiDAR technology could improve obstacle detection accuracy.

B. Handwriting Recognition

Future improvements in OCR technology will enhance the recognition of handwritten text.

C. Gesture-Based Interaction

Adding gesture recognition capabilities will enable users to interact with the device more intuitively.

D. Cloud Connectivity for Continuous Learning

Although the current version operates offline, future models could integrate cloud-based learning to improve recognition accuracy over time.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Smart Vision presents a significant advancement in assistive technology by providing a comprehensive AI-powered solution for visually impaired individuals. Its capabilities in object recognition, facial detection, emotion analysis, and real-time navigation offer improved mobility and social interaction. While current limitations exist, ongoing enhancements in AI, sensor technology, and power efficiency will further refine this assistive device, making it more reliable and accessible.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We express our sincere gratitude to our project guide, Mrs. Padma Priya S. Babu, for her invaluable guidance and continuous support. We extend our thanks to the Department of Computer Science at John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of Technology for providing the necessary resources and encouragement. Special thanks to our families and friends for their unwavering support and motivation throughout this project.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Teles, M. Cagy, F. Silva, "Deep Learning-Based Wearable Assistive System for Visually Impaired People," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 12345-12357, 2019.
- [2] A. Hartman, V. Nandikolla, "Efficient Multi-Object Detection and Smart Navigation for Visually Impaired," in *Proc. IEEE Conf. Assistive Tech*, 2020.
- [3] D. J. D'Souza, S. Srivastava, "MedGlasses: AI-Based Wearable Drug Recognition System," *IEEE Trans. Med. Imaging*, vol. 39, no. 6, pp. 1103-1115, 2021.

[4] S. Modi, D. Mevawala, "Computer Vision-Based Assistance System for the Visually Impaired," *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 5678-5689, 2022.

[5] M. Amur, S. Kesavan, "CNN-Based Object Recognition for Visually Impaired," in *Proc. IEEE Symp. AI Assistive Tech*, 2023.

[6] D. Sri, R. Kanuri, "Artificial Intelligence for Visually Impaired Individuals," *IEEE Transactions on Human-Machine Interaction*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 345-360, 2024.

SMART WHEELCHAIR

Anurenjana Pradeep, Gouri B S,

Joslien Jeromias, Reshma S

From John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of Technology

Affiliated to APJ Abdul Kalam Technological University

Abstract— This paper presents an IoT-enabled smart wheelchair designed to enhance mobility and independence for individuals with disabilities. The system integrates multiple control mechanisms, including eye-blink detection and pressure sensors, allowing intuitive, hands-free wheelchair navigation. Obstacle detection, fall detection, and health monitoring are incorporated, with real-time data transmitted to a mobile application for remote monitoring and control. This project aims to improve safety, efficiency, and ease of use for wheelchair users.

Keywords— Smart Wheelchair, IoT, Eye-Blink Sensor, Pressure Sensor, Obstacle Detection, Fall Detection, Vital Sign Monitoring.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, assistive technologies have made remarkable strides in improving the quality of life for individuals with disabilities. One such innovation is the IoT-enabled smart wheelchair, designed to provide enhanced mobility, autonomy, and safety for users with severe physical impairments. Traditional wheelchairs, whether manual or joystick-controlled, pose significant challenges for individuals with limited motor function. The development of an intelligent wheelchair system that responds to eye blinks, breath patterns, and involuntary movements offers a transformative solution for those unable to use conventional controls.

This project introduces a sensor-based smart wheelchair that leverages blink sensors, air pressure sensors, gyroscopes, and accelerometers to interpret user intent and automate navigation. The system is specifically designed for individuals with conditions such as quadriplegia, cerebral palsy, or neuromuscular disorders, who cannot operate traditional mobility aids. By utilizing real-time IoT connectivity, the wheelchair not only enhances movement but also incorporates health monitoring, fall detection, and emergency alert mechanisms.

The integration of an ESP32 microcontroller, MAX30100 pulse oximeter, and ultrasonic obstacle detection ensures a secure and intelligent environment for the user. The wheelchair also includes live video streaming via an ESP32-CAM module, allowing caregivers to monitor the user's surroundings remotely. Furthermore, the system is designed with energy efficiency in mind, optimizing power consumption for prolonged battery life.

Despite significant advancements in smart wheelchair research, existing solutions often lack comprehensive multi-sensor integration. Many are either gesture-controlled, voice-operated, or joystick-dependent, making them unsuitable for individuals with severe mobility impairments. Our proposed model bridges these gaps by offering hands-free navigation, automatic fall detection, and real-time biometric tracking, ensuring both safety and independence.

This paper explores the architecture, methodology, advantages, and limitations of the proposed system while highlighting potential future enhancements such as AI-driven navigation, BCI (Brain-Computer Interface) integration, and solar-powered charging. The ultimate goal is to develop a cost-effective, scalable, and adaptive assistive mobility solution for those who need it the most.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The smart wheelchair is built around an ESP32 microcontroller, which serves as the processing unit for user input and sensor data. The primary components include:

- Eye-Blink Sensors & Pressure Sensors: Detect and interpret user commands.
- Ultrasonic Sensors: Identify obstacles and prevent collisions.
- Accelerometer & Gyroscope: Detect falls and sudden movements.
- MAX30100 Pulse Oximeter: Monitor heart rate and blood oxygen levels.
- ESP32-CAM Module: Stream live video to the mobile application.

These components work together to ensure safe and efficient navigation.

III. METHODOLOGY

The IoT-enabled smart wheelchair is designed to assist individuals with severe mobility impairments by integrating multiple sensor technologies, real-time data processing, and IoT connectivity. The system operates based on user eye blinks, breath patterns, and involuntary hand movements, eliminating the need for conventional joystick-based controls. The methodology consists of several key components, including sensor integration, data processing, real-time communication, and safety mechanisms.

1. Sensor Integration & Data Acquisition

The core functionality of the smart wheelchair relies on multiple sensors to interpret user input and ensure safety. The primary sensors and their roles include:

- i. **Blink Sensor (Eye-Blink Detection for Navigation):**
A non-invasive infrared (IR) sensor detects voluntary eye blinks. A left-eye blink held for 2 seconds commands the wheelchair to move left. A right-eye blink held for 4 seconds moves the wheelchair right. The sensor differentiates between involuntary blinks and intentional commands using pattern recognition algorithms.
- ii. **Air Pressure Sensor (Breath-Controlled Motion):**
A pressure sensor embedded in spectacles detects controlled inhalation and exhalation. Inhaling above a threshold moves the wheelchair forward. Exhaling beyond a threshold moves it backward. The system calibrates individual breathing patterns to avoid false triggers.

iii. Ultrasonic Sensors (Obstacle Detection):

Placed at the front and sides, ultrasonic sensors continuously scan for obstacles. If an object is detected within a predetermined safe distance, the system automatically halts movement to prevent collisions. The system generates real-time alerts in the mobile app for caregivers.

iv. MPU6050 Accelerometer & Gyroscope:

The MPU6050 sensor, placed in a smartwatch worn by the user, monitors hand orientation and sudden movement shifts. A tilt beyond a predefined threshold (left, right, or downward) is recognized as a fall event. Upon detection, an automated emergency alert is sent to caregivers through the IoT-enabled mobile app.

v. MAX30100 Pulse Oximeter (Health Monitoring)

The pulse oximeter continuously tracks heart rate and SpO₂ levels. If vital signs exceed predefined danger thresholds, an emergency alert is triggered.

vi. ESP32-CAM Module (Live Video Streaming)

The ESP32-CAM is mounted on the wheelchair to provide real-time surveillance. The live feed can be accessed via a mobile app, enabling caregivers to monitor the user remotely.

2. Data Processing & Decision-Making Algorithms :

The data from multiple sensors is processed in real time to ensure accurate decision-making. The processing steps include:

i. Signal Acquisition & Preprocessing

Raw data from blink sensors, breath sensors, and accelerometers is collected. Noise filtering algorithms eliminate false signals (e.g., unintentional eye blinks, accidental hand movements).

ii. Feature Extraction & Classification :

The system extracts specific movement patterns (e.g., blink duration, breath intensity).

iii. Command Execution & Movement Control :

The ESP32 microcontroller processes inputs and translates them into motor control signals. Based on the interpreted user intent, the wheelchair moves in the corresponding direction. If obstacles or fall events are detected, movement is halted, and emergency alerts are triggered.

3. IoT Connectivity & Mobile App Integration :

The IoT-enabled mobile application serves as the central interface for caregivers and users. It provides:

- Real-time wheelchair location tracking
- Live health monitoring
- Emergency alerts & fall detection notifications
- Remote-controlled wheelchair operation
- Live video streaming for situational awareness

The mobile app communicates with the wheelchair via Wi-Fi and MQTT protocols, ensuring low-latency data transmission.

4. Safety & Emergency Response Mechanism :

To enhance user security, the system includes:

- If a fall is detected, an emergency alert is sent caregivers with the exact location of the incident.

- The mobile app provides emergency call functionality to seek immediate assistance.
- Obstacle Avoidance & Collision Prevention
- Ultrasonic sensors prevent the wheelchair from moving too close to obstacles.
- If an obstacle is detected, the system automatically stops the wheelchair.
- Battery Management & Power Optimization
- The system monitors battery levels and notifies users when charging is required.
- Low-power modes extend battery life when the wheelchair is idle.

5. Implementation & Testing

The smart wheelchair prototype undergoes rigorous testing to ensure its functionality and reliability. The key testing phases include:

- Accuracy Testing for Blink & Breath Sensors :
- The system is tested with different users to refine threshold values for navigation commands.
- Fall Detection Sensitivity Analysis :
- The MPU6050 sensor is tested for various involuntary movements to minimize false alarms.
- Obstacle Avoidance & Navigation Testing :
- The wheelchair is placed in different environments to ensure smooth navigation without collisions.
- IoT Communication & Mobile App Reliability :
- The system is tested under different network conditions to ensure real-time data synchronization.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

The system was rigorously tested for accuracy, response time, and reliability. Results showed:

- Eye-Blink & Pressure Sensor Accuracy: 87%
- Obstacle Detection Success Rate: 91%
- Fall Detection Response Time: <1s
- Vital Sign Monitoring Accuracy: 89%
- Remote Control Responsiveness: Near-instantaneous

These findings confirm the effectiveness of the system in practical applications.

V. LITERATURE REVIEW

The development of smart wheelchairs has evolved significantly with technological advancements. Several research efforts have contributed to the integration of IoT, AI, and sensor-based control systems to improve mobility for individuals with disabilities. Below are some key studies relevant to this project:

1. Brain-Computer Interface (BCI) IoT Healthcare Wheelchair (2017)

Authors: Ariel Teles, Maurício Cagy, Francisco Silva
This study introduced a Brain-to-Thing Communication (BTC) system, enabling wheelchair users to control devices

through their EEG signals. The system allows seamless interaction with smart environments, improving user autonomy. However, challenges include high hardware costs and signal processing complexities

2. Gesture-Controlled Wheelchair Using Accelerometer Sensors (2018)

Authors: Ravi Kumar, Manish Singh

This system employs accelerometer-based gesture recognition for movement control. It is an affordable alternative to joystick-controlled wheelchairs. However, hand tremors and accidental movements can impact accuracy

3. IoT-Based Smart Wheelchair for Health Monitoring (2019)

Authors: Divya Jennifer D'Souza, Sanket Srivastava

The proposed wheelchair integrates MAX30100 pulse oximeters for SpO₂ and heart rate monitoring. The system also alerts caregivers via a mobile app. However, the reliance on Wi-Fi connectivity poses limitations in areas with weak signals

4. Autonomous Wheelchair with Obstacle Avoidance (2021)

Authors: Siddhant Pawar, Yogesh Kanade

This research focuses on line-following technology combined with ultrasonic sensors for autonomous navigation in hospital environments. The system ensures collision-free movement but struggles with dynamic environments and requires pre-set paths

5. Voice-Controlled Smart Wheelchair with Safety Features (2022)

Authors: Dr. Pushpa D, Vijayalakshmi K

This work integrates speech recognition modules with IoT-based real-time monitoring. The system is particularly useful for users with limited upper-body mobility, but background noise interference affects voice recognition accuracy

6. AI-Based Smart Wheelchair with Fall Detection (2023)

Authors: Diviya Sri, Ravi Kumar Kanuri

This study proposes a fall detection system using MPU6050 accelerometers. The system provides emergency alerts via IoT, but false positives remain an issue, requiring adaptive AI filtering.

V. CONCLUSION

The IoT-enabled smart wheelchair is a transformative assistive technology designed to provide individuals with severe mobility impairments greater independence, safety, and ease of use. By integrating blink and breath sensors, ultrasonic obstacle detection, fall detection using accelerometers, and real-time health monitoring, the system ensures hands-free navigation and enhanced security for users who cannot operate traditional

wheelchairs. The addition of an IoT-connected mobile application further improves caregiver monitoring and emergency response, making it a comprehensive mobility solution.

Unlike conventional mobility aids, this smart wheelchair eliminates the need for joystick-based or voice-controlled systems, making it ideal for users with quadriplegia or neuromuscular disorders. The fall detection mechanism, which triggers an automated emergency alert, ensures timely assistance in critical situations. Additionally, live video streaming, health monitoring via a pulse oximeter, and remote control features add further layers of security and accessibility.

While the system offers numerous advantages, some challenges remain, such as sensor accuracy under different environmental conditions and dependence on stable internet connectivity for IoT features. Future enhancements may include AI-driven navigation, 5G integration, Brain-Computer Interface (BCI) control, and solar-powered charging, further improving efficiency and usability.

In conclusion, this intelligent wheelchair system bridges the gap between mobility and technology, ensuring that individuals with severe physical disabilities can move independently and safely. With continued innovation, such smart assistive devices have the potential to significantly improve the quality of life for millions worldwide.

VI. FUTUREWORK

The development of smart wheelchairs is continuously evolving. Future work on this project will focus on enhancing navigation intelligence using AI and machine learning algorithms. Additional improvements may include energy-efficient power management, 5G connectivity for low-latency control, and the incorporation of alternative user control methods, such as brain-computer interfaces (BCI).

VII. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to express their gratitude to the faculty and staff of John Cox Memorial CSI Institute of Technology for their guidance. Special thanks to our project advisor, Mrs. Sharika B.C., for her invaluable support.

REFERENCES

- [1] Teles, A., Cagy, M., & Silva, F. (2017). "Using Brain- Computer Interface and IoT for Smart Wheelchair Control." *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems & Rehabilitation Engineering*.
- [2] Kumar, R., & Singh, M. (2018). "Gesture Recognition for Smart Wheelchair Navigation." *IEEE Sensors Journal*.
- [3] D'Souza, D. J., Srivastava, S., & Prithika, R. (2019). "IoT-Based Smart Wheelchair for Health Monitoring." *International Conference on Biomedical Engineering*.

- [4] Pawar, S., Kanade, Y., & Singh, H. (2021). "Autonomous Wheelchair with AI-Based Navigation." *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*.
- [5] Pushpa, D., & Vijayalakshmi, K. (2022). "Voice-Controlled Wheelchair: IoT Integration and Safety Features." *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*.
- [6] Sri, D., & Kanuri, R. K. (2023). "Fall Detection and Emergency Alert System for Smart Wheelchairs." *IEEE Transactions on Mechatronics*.
- [7] Chen, Y., & Wu, X. (2023). "Deep Learning-Based Smart Wheelchair for Healthcare Applications." *Journal of Medical Internet Research*.
- [8] Gupta, A., & Raman, S. (2024). "Sensor-Based Mobility Aids: A Review of Assistive Technologies." *IEEE Access*.

Stabilization Of Marine Clay Using Banana Fibre And Alkaline Activators

Abin Raj.T.P, Anto.P.R, Roshni.S.S, Saniya.S.M

Civil Engineering dept.

John Cox Memorial CSI Institute Of Technology

Trivandrum, India

Abstract— Marine clay is a type of clay found in coastal regions around the world. Vast deposits of marine clay soil are typically linked with poor engineering properties, such as low shear strength, high compressibility and low permeability. Most of the areas in Kerala have marine clay deposits. These types of soil mainly posed a significant challenge and problems in designing, construction of building and infrastructure. Recent development now a day is concerned with obtaining better performance of stabilization by reducing the usage of cement based binder with a minimal environmental cost. Alkaline activation (AA) has grown as one of the binders that were introduced as a replacement of cement due to the environmentally friendly materials and low emission of carbon dioxide. Many past studies have reported on the effectiveness of the AA as the soil stabilizer. Which significant in the improvement of the soil strength as well as filling the voids inside the soil. Natural fiber has also been used as a mixture in the soil to improve the behavior of the soils since it is locally available and reduces the cost of work. In this study we are analyzing the potential of banana fiber and alkaline activator as a sustainable alternative to conventional marine clay stabilization. The study explores the effects of adding varying percentages of banana fiber (0.5%, 1%, 1.5%, 2%, 2.5%) and alkaline activator (3%, 7%, 10%) on the soil. By conducting standard proctor compaction test, unconfined compressive strength (UCC) test, and California bearing ratio (CBR) test.

The results of the study show that the addition of banana fiber and alkaline activator significantly improves the engineering properties of marine clay. Optimal performance observed at 2% for banana fiber and 7% dosage of alkaline activator by dry weight of the soil. The addition of optimum percentage banana fiber and alkaline activator improves the workability during

compaction. The combined addition of banana fiber and alkaline activator gives maximum unconfined compressive strength, bearing capacity and workability than separate addition of banana fiber and alkaline activator.

Keywords— soil stabilization; banana fibre; marine clay; alkaline activator

I. INTRODUCTION

Soil stabilization is a critical process in geotechnical engineering, aimed at improving the physical and mechanical properties of soil to enhance its performance in construction and infrastructure projects. Vast deposits of marine clay soil are typically linked with poor engineering properties such as low shear strength, high compressibility and low permeability. Traditional stabilization methods often rely on chemical additives or synthetic materials, which can have negative environmental impacts. Ordinary Portland cement (OPC) is a common hydraulic binder that has been widely used in geotechnical applications to improve the mechanical properties of soils, such as shear strength and compressibility. However, the production of 1 tonne of OPC releases about 0.7–1.1 tonnes of carbon dioxide. Producing OPC also releases Nitric Oxide (NO_x), which is one of the factors of the greenhouse effect and acid rain. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in sustainable and eco-friendly alternatives for soil stabilization.

The stabilization of marine clay using banana fibre and an alkaline activator represents a promising approach to improving the geotechnical properties of this often problematic soil type. Marine clay, typically characterized by its high compressibility, low shear strength, and susceptibility to significant volume changes under loading, poses challenges in civil engineering applications.

Stabilizing such soils is essential for enhancing their load-bearing capacity and durability in construction projects, especially in coastal or reclaimed land areas. In recent years, there has been increasing interest in the use of natural fibres as reinforcement materials due to their eco-friendliness, availability, and renewable nature. Banana fibre, in particular, is an abundant natural fibre that has shown potential for improving the mechanical properties of soils when used in combination with an alkaline activator. Alkaline activators, such as sodium hydroxide or potassium hydroxide, work by altering the chemical structure of the clay, promoting the formation of cementations compounds that bind the soil particles more tightly. When combined with banana fibres, these activators help to enhance the soil's tensile strength, reduce shrinkage, and increase its overall stability. The fibres act as a reinforcement material, providing additional strength and flexibility to the soil matrix, thereby improving its resistance to shear stress and reducing its tendency to undergo excessive deformation. This method not only improves the structural performance of the soil but also offers a sustainable alternative to traditional soil stabilization techniques, minimizing environmental impacts while utilizing agricultural waste products.

The synergy between banana fibres and alkaline activators thus presents an innovative solution for enhancing the engineering properties of marine clay, making it a viable option for various geotechnical and infrastructural applications.

II. OBJECTIVES

- To investigate the engineering properties of banana fibre on marine clay stabilization.
- To investigate the engineering properties of alkaline activator on marine clay stabilization.
- To investigate the engineering properties of both banana fibre and alkaline activator on marine clay stabilization.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

A. Materials

a. Soil

Marine clay is the soil type chosen to stabilize in this study, which is to be collected from surroundings of Vellayani Lake in Thiruvananthapuram district on the coastal lowlands of Kerala. The main components of marine

clay include microcrystalline minerals such as chlorite, illite, kaolinite, quartz, mica and halloysite materials.

Fig.1 Marine clay

Marine clay is a type of fine-grained sedimentary soil originating from marine environments, such as ocean floors, estuaries, coastal areas, and deltas. It is characterized by high water content, low shear strength, high compressibility, low permeability, and high sensitivity to changes in water content. Marine clay can be classified into three types: soft clay, firm clay, and hard clay, depending on its consolidation state. Compositionally, marine clay consists of fine-grained minerals, organic matter, carbonates, and silicates. Marine clay poses significant challenges due to its instability, low bearing capacity, high settlement, and environmental concerns. However, various stabilization techniques can mitigate these issues, including preloading, cement deep mixing, lime stabilization, geosynthetics, and electro osmotic consolidation.

b. Banana fibre

The banana fibres are hydrophilic (water absorbing) in nature which can be changed to hydrophobic (water resistant) by treatment for use as reinforcing material. Banana fibres were drawn from pseudo-stem, has gained attention in various engineering applications due to its unique properties.

Presently, fibre has also been used as a mixture in the soil to improve the behaviour of the soils. However, the focus nowadays is on environmental and sustainability awareness which is more likely to involve natural fibre that is used as reinforcement in the soil matrix.

Fig. 2 Banana fibre

Many past researches have conducted a test by including different types of fibre such as geo- fibre, jute, nylon, sisal fibre, kenaf fibre, palm fibre and many other types of fibre at different types of soil. They concluded that inclusion of the fibre in the soil increased the ductility, compressive strength, and moisture content, and reduced the maximum dry density of soil, increased tensile strength and enhanced the strength of the California Bearing Ratio (CBR). Banana fibre, obtained from the pseudo-stems of banana plants, represents a promising candidate for soil reinforcement due to its abundance, low cost, and favourable mechanical properties. Annually, millions of tonnes of banana plant waste are generated globally, presenting an opportunity for value-added utilization in civil engineering applications. The incorporation of banana fibre into soil stabilization techniques not only addresses waste management issues but also aligns with the principles of sustainable development in construction practices.

c. Alkaline activator

i. Alkaline activator

Alkali Activator, consisting of NaOH and Na₂SiO₃, was used as geopolymer-forming material. This is because sodium cations are more suitable when dealing with silica-alumina elements than silica-alumina elements only. Furthermore, incorporating sodium hydroxide and sodium silica can be an effective activator to increase the strength properties. NaOH and Na₂SiO₃ were provided as a solid form. Both materials are used in a 1:1 ratio to support the cementitious level of high calcium fly ash.

Fig.3 Na₂SiO₃ and NaOH

ii. Fly ash

Fly ash (FA) is a pulverized solid formed after burning coal in thermal power plants, which is a waste, and if left untreated will have a negative impact on the environment, and recycling, and its disposal will waste a lot of energy and money. Fly ash

is used as the precursor material for the geopolymerisation process. Fly ash contains silica and alumina, which can react with the alkaline activator to form a stable cementitious gel. Fly ash is often available at a lower cost than traditional cementitious materials.

Fig.4 Fly ash

B. Methodology

a. Collection of marine clay

Marine clay was collected from surroundings of Vellayani Lake in Thiruvananthapuram district. It is then dried under sunlight.

b. Index properties of marine clay checked

The test conducted for identify marine clay are:

- Specific gravity
- Moisture content
- Plastic limit
- Liquid limit
- Particle size distribution

c. Preparation of alkaline activator

Alkaline activator is prepared as a combination of NaOH, Na₂SiO₃ and fly ash. Alkaline activator consists of 15% NaOH, 15% Na₂SiO₃ and 70% fly ash. In order to keep the same units in NaOH, Na₂SiO₃ and fly ash we added it in solid form.

d. Test performing

i. Proctor compaction test

The Proctor Compaction Test is a laboratory procedure used to determine the optimal moisture content at which a soil type will achieve its maximum dry density. This test is commonly used in geotechnical engineering to assess the suitability of soils for construction purposes.

Fig .5 Proctor compaction test

ii. California bearing ratio test

The California Bearing Ratio (CBR) test is a penetration test used to evaluate the strength and bearing capacity of soil, primarily for designing pavements and road structures. The CBR test measures the ability of the soil to withstand traffic loads and is used to determine the quality of subgrade soil for use in roads, airstrips, and other pavement-related projects.

Fig .6 CBR test

iii. Unconfined compressive strength test

The Unconfined Compressive Strength (UCS) test is a widely used method for determining the compressive strength of soils, particularly cohesive soils like clays and silts. The test is simple and provides crucial information for understanding the bearing capacity and stability of soils in engineering projects. It is also an important test for assessing the strength of rock-like materials such as soft rocks or weak bedrock.

Fig .7 UCS test

e. Test conducted with varying percentage of banana fibre

The soil is mixed with 0.5%, 1.0%, 1.5%, 2.0% and 2.5% of banana fibre by dry weight of soil. Proctor compaction test, UCS test, and CBR test were conducted for each percentage of banana fibre. The following procedure was used for sample preparation. The required amount of air-dried soil was weighed and placed in a mixing bowl. The calculated quantity of banana fibres was added to the soil. The soil and fibres were thoroughly mixed by hand to ensure uniform distribution. Water was added to achieve the desired moisture content, and the mixture was further blended.

f. Test conducted with varying percentage of alkaline activator

The soil is mixed with 3%, 7% and 10% of alkaline activator by dry weight of soil. Proctor compaction test, UCS test, and CBR test were conducted for each percentage of alkaline activator. The method of mixing alkaline activator was carried out manually. The mixture consisted of 70% fly ash and 30% alkali activator by weight of geopolymer. Each percentage was 3%, 7%, and 10% of the dry weight of the soil. The soil was mixed with 70% fly ash and alkaline activator sequentially, starting with 15% NaOH, then 15% Na₂SiO₃. In order to keep the same units in NaOH, Na₂SiO₃ and fly ash, we chose to add it in solid form. The weighed NaOH and Na₂SiO₃ were dissolved in water. After waiting for the exothermic reaction to finish, the solution was mixed with the soil. The mixing steps were according to previous studies with optimal mixing methods. During this stage, water was added to meet the optimum moisture content.

g. Test conducted with optimum percentage of banana fibre and varying percentage of alkaline activator

The soil is mixed with 2.0% (optimum percentage) of banana fibre and varying percentage of alkaline activator by dry weight of soil. Proctor compaction test, UCS test, and CBR test were conducted for optimum percentage of banana fibre and varying percentage of alkaline activator. The soil was mixed with of optimum percentage of banana fibre by dry weight of the soil and 3%, 7% and 10% of alkaline activator by dry weight of soil with an appropriate water content. The usage of optimum percentage of banana fibre was considered based on the studies states that for gaining the maximum strength as well as workability it is the most suited percentage.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The soil sample (Marine clay soil) was tested to obtain its index properties and confirming that the collected soil is marine clay. Then the clay was blended with different proportions of banana fibre, alkaline activator and both banana fibre and alkaline activator to get their variation in strength properties and optimum dosages. The variations in properties of soil sample were studied. The test results are as follows.

A. Index properties of marine clay

Table 1 Index properties of untreated marine clay

Parameter	Values
Moisture content	76.47%
Specific gravity	2.4
Particle size distribution	Clay-59% Sand-14% Silt-27%
Plastic limit	33.33%
Liquid limit	66.66%
Plasticity index	33.33%

B. Proctor compaction test on banana fiber

Table 2 Proctor compaction test results on banana fiber

Fibre content %	Maximum dry density (g/cc)	Optimum moisture content(%)
0	1.76	16.12
0.5	1.45	17.94
1	1.42	18.78
1.5	1.39	21.84
2	1.29	23.77
2.5	1.16	25

Fig. 8 Maximum dry density and optimum moisture content vs fiber content

From the test results it's clear that maximum dry density starts to decrease upon the increase of banana fiber and optimum moisture content starts to increase upon the addition of banana fiber.

C. UCS test and CBR test on banana fiber

Table 3 UCS test and CBR test results on banana fibre

Fibre content (%)	UCS (Kg/cm ²)	CBR value
0	0.219	27.17
0.5	0.268	52.75
1	0.378	70.60
1.5	0.898	81.26
2	1.616	86.18
2.5	1.414	74.59

Fig. 9 UCS vs fiber content

Fig. 10 CBR Value vs fiber content

Table 3 provides the UCS and CBR test results while adding different percentage of banana fiber. Figure 9 and 10 indicates increasing of UCS and CBR up to optimum dosage of banana fiber which is 2% banana fiber by dry weight of the soil. After that it starts to decrease.

D. Proctor compaction test on alkaline activator

Table 4 Proctor compaction test results on alkaline activator

Alkaline activator (%)	Maximum dry density (g/cc)	Optimum moisture content (%)
3	1.686	20.81
7	1.792	18.84
10	1.8	14.285

Fig. 11 Maximum dry density and optimum moisture content vs alkaline activator

Table 4. indicates the results of proctor compaction test when the marine clay soil is mixed with different percentages of alkaline activator by dry weight of the soil. From the figure 11 it is clear that maximum dry density starts to increase and optimum moisture content starts to decrease upon the addition of alkaline activator.

E. UCS test and CBR test on alkaline activator

Table 5 Unconfined compressive strength test and CBR test results on alkaline activator

Alkaline activator (%)	UCS (Kg/cm ²)	CBR Value
3	0.280	69.93
7	0.914	128.41
10	0.217	72.61

Fig. 12 Unconfined compressive strength vs alkaline activator

Fig. 13 CBR Value vs alkaline activator

Table 5 indicates the results of UCS test and CBR test when the marine clay soil is mixed with different percentages of alkaline activator by dry weight of the soil. From the figure 12 and 13 it is clear that up to 7% addition of alkaline activator by dry weight of the soil unconfined compressive strength value and CBR value increases further addition of alkaline activator reduces unconfined compressive strength and CBR value Optimum dosage of alkaline activator is 7% by dry weight of the soil.

F. Proctor compaction test on optimum percentage of banana fiber and alkaline activator

Table 6 Proctor compaction test results on banana fiber and alkaline activator

%	Maximum dry density (g/cc)	Optimum moisture content (%)
2% banana fibre (BF)&3%alkaline activator (AA)	1.696	19.106
2% banana fibre &7%alkaline activator	1.64	20
2% banana fibre (BF)&10% alkaline activator (AA)	1.54	22.76

Fig 14 Maximum dry density and optimum moisture content vs optimum percentage of banana fiber and varying percentage of alkaline activator

Table 6 indicates the results of proctor compaction test when the marine clay soil is mixed with different percentages of alkaline activator and optimum percentage of banana fiber by dry weight of the soil. From the figure 14 it is clear that maximum dry density starts to decrease and optimum moisture content starts to increase upon the addition of alkaline activator.

G. UCS test and CBR test optimum percentage of banana fiber and alkaline activator

Table 7 Unconfined compressive strength test and CBR test results on banana fiber and alkaline activator

%	UCS (Kg/cm ²)	CBR value
2% banana fiber & 3% alkaline activator	0.328	95.91
2% banana fiber & 7% alkaline activator	1.986	134.67
2% banana fiber & 10% alkaline activator	0.256	112.04

Fig.15 Unconfined compressive strength vs 2% of banana fibre and varying percentage of alkaline activator

Fig.16 CBR Value vs 2% of banana fibre and varying percentage of alkaline activator

Table 7 indicates the test results of UCS test and CBR test when the marine clay soil is mixed with different percentages of alkaline activator and optimum dosage of banana fiber by dry weight of the soil. From the figure 15 and 16 it is clear that up to 7% addition of alkaline activator and 2% addition of banana fiber by dry weight of the soil increases the UCS value and CBR value further addition of

alkaline activator reduces UCS value and CBR value. Optimum dosage was 7% alkaline activator and 2% banana fiber by dry weight of the soil.

V. CONCLUSION

The experimental investigations done so as to bring out the effect of stabilization of marine clay soil using banana fibre, alkaline activator and both banana fibre and alkaline activator gave a good result. From the series of tests conducted on marine clay soil mixed with various percentages of banana fibre, alkaline activator and both banana and alkaline activator and their corresponding results, following conclusions are obtained

- The addition of banana fiber significantly improves the unconfined compressive strength and bearing capacity of marine clay, with optimal performance observed at 2% fiber content by dry weight of the soil.
- The addition of banana fiber decreases the maximum dry density and increases the optimum moisture content of the marine clay, improves workability during compaction.
- The addition of alkaline activator improves the unconfined compressive strength and bearing capacity of marine clay, with optimal performance was observed at 7% dosage of alkaline activator by dry weight of the soil.
- The addition of alkaline activator increases the maximum dry density and decreases the optimum moisture content of the marine clay, reduces the workability during compaction.
- The combined addition of optimum percentage banana fiber and alkaline activator increases the bearing capacity and the unconfined compressive strength of marine clay, with optimal performance observed at 2% fiber content and 7% alkaline activator by dry weight of the soil.
- The addition of optimum percentage banana fiber and alkaline activator decreases the maximum dry density and increases the optimum moisture content of the marine clay, improves the workability during compaction.
- The combined addition of banana fiber and alkaline activator gives maximum unconfined compressive strength, bearing capacity and workability than separate addition of banana fiber and alkaline activator.

VI. REFERENCE

[1] Alam S., and AlselamiN.A. (2024), “Geotechnical properties of fly ash blended expansive soil : a review”, *Civil*

engineering journal, Vol 10, <https://dx.doi.org/10.23991/CEJ-SP2024010-06>

[2] Kamaruddin F.A., Nahazanan H, Huat B.K and AnggrainiV(2020), “Improvement of marine clay soil using lime and alkaline activation stabilized with inclusion of treated coir fibre”, *Applied science*, Vol 10, pp. 2129, doi:10.3390/app10062129

[3] Kumar M., Hussan, Vikas K., Prasad S. and UpadhyayR.K., (2023) “An experimental study on stabilization of clayey soil reinforced with banana fiber”, *Education administration :theory and practice*, Vol 29, pp. 1587-1597, <https://kuey.net/10.53555/kuey.v29i4.6523>

[4] Muntaha M., FitriR.H.A., Wahyuni F. and Tajunnisa Y. (2023),”The use of alkaline activators with high calcium fly ash as soft clay stabilization materials”, *International journal of GEOMATE*”, Vol 25, pp.9-7, <https://doi.org/10.21660/2023.109.3286>

[5] Qamar W., Khan A.H., Rehman Z., and Masoud Z. (2022), “Sustainable application of wool-banana bio-composite waste material in geotechnical engineering for enhancement of elastoplastic strain and resilience of subgrade expansive clays”, *Sustainability*, Vol 14, pp. 13215, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142013215>

[6] Turan C., Javadi A.A., Vinai R. and Russo G. (2022), “Effects of fly ash inclusion and alkali activation on physical, mechanical and chemical properties of clay”, *Materials*, Vol 15, pp.4628, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma15134628>

[7] Wang H., Liu T., Yan C. and Wang J. (2023), “Expansive soil stabilization using alkaliactivated fly ash”, *Processes*, Vol 11, pp. 1550, <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr11051550>

STUDY OF EFFECTS OF PARTIAL REPLACEMENT OF COARSE AGGREGATE USING ALUMINIUM SCRAP

Aiswarya L, Aswathy S, Darshik S S, L Sreelatha, Cera Shalom
UG Students – Final Year, Associate Professor & HOD, Associate Professor
Department of Civil Engineering JCM Institute of Technology, Kannammoola, Trivandrum, India

Abstract: -A lot of research is happening around the world for the treatment of waste. Many waste materials will be used as the raw materials in many industries. This will decrease the negative effect on the environment and be helpful for the establishment of secondary and tertiary industries. But after the advancement in technology this scrap and the waste can be used as a raw material for many other industries. The current study considers the utilization of recycled aluminium waste in producing concrete and gives out the information on utilizing a scrap of aluminium in the concrete as a replacement for Coarse aggregate. This paper also seeks to reduce the natural aggregates that we get from blasting and crumbling down. The research has been performed to develop an environment-friendly solution to utilize waste from the aluminium industry which is partially replacing coarse aggregates by 10, 20 and 30 % in the Concrete. The Compressive and Flexural strength of the Concrete is determined and computed with the Nominal Concrete

Keywords: Aluminium scrap, Cement and Aggregates.

1. INTRODUCTION

Aluminium scrap, generated from various industrial processes, poses significant environmental concerns due to its non-biodegradable nature and potential toxicity. Utilizing aluminium scrap as a partial replacement for coarse aggregate in concrete can help reduce waste disposal issues and conserve natural resources.

High demands for raw materials such as natural aggregate due to the rapid increase of population and construction development has caused a heavy exploitation of the natural resources. Continuous of natural aggregate quarrying produced issues like damaging the environment and depleting fast, causing a shortage in natural aggregate. Thus, comprising the Negative environmental effect of aluminum scrap and the depletion of natural aggregate, make use of scrap aluminum as a partial mixture replacement in concrete has foreseen to end up the appreciably powerful solution for the issues. The development of aluminium scrap aggregate as construction materials are important to both the construction and aluminium recycling industry as it is essential to preserves our depleting natural resource.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Following are the research works conducted on concrete with various alternatives as partial to full replacement for coarse aggregate.

Ahmed et al. (2022) study investigates the utilization of aluminum and iron residues as partial replacements for fine aggregate in concrete, aiming to assess their effects on the mechanical properties of the resulting concrete mix. The mix proportions used were 1:2:3 for dry components, with a water/cement ratio of 0.45. It highlights the environmental significance of recycling industrial waste, particularly in the context of construction and demolition debris, which is often underutilized. The findings reveal that incorporating iron residues into concrete enhances both compressive strength and tensile strength, especially at lower replacement ratios, indicating their beneficial role in improving concrete performance.

Kumar et al. (2024) The study investigates the partial replacement of coarse aggregates in concrete with soft drink bottle caps, aiming to assess the impact on compressive and split tensile strength. A total of four replacement percentages were tested: 0%, 5%, 10%, and 15%. The compressive strength results indicated a decrease with increasing replacement. Similarly, the split tensile strength showed a decline.

Muhammed et al. (2020) The study investigates the feasibility of using aluminum caps as a partial replacement for coarse aggregates in concrete, focusing on its effects on compressive, split tensile, and flexural strengths over curing periods of 7, 14, and 28 days. The conclusions drawn from the study indicate that the compressive strength, split tensile strength, and flexural strength of concrete with aluminum caps are relatively close to those of normal concrete, but a 15% replacement leads to a significant reduction in strength.

Narayanan et al. (2020) The research focused on the utilization of aluminium caps as a partial replacement for coarse aggregates in concrete, addressing the increasing costs and demand for construction materials while promoting eco-friendly practices. The concrete mix design employed was M20, adhering to IS:10262-1982 standards, and involved four variations: a control mix without replacement, and mixes with

15%, 20%, and 25% replacement of coarse aggregate with aluminum caps. The study revealed that the compressive strength of concrete with 15% aluminium caps increased gradually over the curing period, demonstrating the potential benefits of this replacement. However, as the percentage of aluminium caps increased beyond 15%, a notable decrease in compressive strength was observed, indicating that there is an optimal limit for replacement.

Paktiawal et al. (2021) The study investigates the use of aluminum dross waste and low-density polyethylene (LDPE) as partial replacements for cement in M60 grade concrete, with varying percentages of aluminum dross (2%, 4%, 7%, and 12%) and LDPE (3.5%, 7%, 12.5%, and 21%) as additives. The study concluded that the addition of aluminum dross and LDPE affects the workability and expansion of concrete, with higher aluminum content leading to increased expansion due to hydrogen gas formation. Non-destructive tests indicated variations in compressive strength and durability, highlighting the potential of using these waste materials in concrete production while also addressing environmental concerns.

Sabarish et al. (2021) The study investigate the effects of looped-end aluminium fibers on the mechanical properties of concrete, specifically focusing on split tensile and compressive strength. Using locally available aluminium scrap wires with a diameter of 0.96 mm and an aspect ratio of 50, various grades of concrete (M20, M30, M40) were tested with fibre volume fractions of 0, 0.5, 1, 1.5, and 2%. The mix designs for M20 and M30 included specific quantities of coarse and fine aggregates, cement, and water, with M20 having a water/cement ratio of 0.55 and M30 at 0.45. The results indicated that the addition of aluminium fibres improved both compressive and splitting tensile strengths, with optimal performance observed at a 0.5% fibre volume fraction. The study concluded that looped-end aluminium fibres significantly enhance the strength properties of concrete, with the peak compressive strength achieved at 0.77% fibre volume concentration, suggesting further research is needed to validate the predictive equations developed for strength assessment.

3. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

3.1 MATERIALS

3.1.1 CEMENT

Cement acts as the binder material, a substance used in construction that adheres to sets and hardens the material for proper binding. Its powdered form consists of limestone and clay, blended with sandstones and water. It achieves strength through chemical reaction with water. Cement when mixed with mineral fragments and water, binds the particles into a whole compact. Cement is the most important and costliest ingredient of concrete. Ordinary Portland cement of 53 grade confirming to requirements of IS: 12269 – 1987.

Table 1: Test results of cement

SL NO	PROPERTIES	VALUE
1	Specific gravity	3.15
2	Standard consistency	34%
3	Initial setting time (in minutes)	48
4	Final setting times (in minutes)	600
5	Fineness	10.0

3.1.2 FINE AGGREGATE

Fine aggregate, commonly known as sand, is a key component in concrete and mortar production. It consists of small particles that pass through a 4.75 mm sieve and typically includes materials such as natural sand or crushed stone M sand confirming to grading zone II of IS 383-1970 is used as fine aggregates.

Table 2: Test results of fine aggregate

SL NO	PROPERTIES	VALUE
1	Specific gravity	2.51
2	Fineness modulus	2.94
3	Water absorption	0.52%
4	Effective size(D ₁₀)	0.21 mm
5	Uniformity coefficient (D ₆₀ /D ₁₀)	5.320

3.1.3 COARSE AGGREGATE

Coarse aggregate is a critical component of concrete and consists of larger particles that typically range in size from 4.75 mm to 20 mm or larger. It includes crushed stone, gravel, or recycled concrete. Coarse aggregate provides bulk and structural integrity to concrete, contributing to its overall strength and stability. It also helps reduce shrinkage and cracking. Coarse aggregates of 20mm according to IS:383-1970 are used.

Table 3: Test results of coarse aggregate

SL NO	PROPERTIES	VALUE
1	Water absorption	1.5%
2	Fineness modulus	3.96
3	Bulk density	1.3KN/mm ²
4	Specific gravity	2.8

3.1.4 ALUMINIUM SCRAP

Aluminum scrap refers to discarded aluminum materials that are recovered and recycled for reuse, coming from various sources such as manufacturing processes, construction activities, and consumer products. When incorporated into concrete as a coarse aggregate, aluminum scrap brings several significant benefits. One of the primary advantages is weight reduction; because aluminum is lighter than traditional aggregates like gravel or crushed stone, it contributes to the creation of lightweight concrete. This lightweight characteristic can lead to savings in transportation costs and foundation requirements, making it particularly beneficial in large construction projects. Additionally, aluminum scrap enhances the durability and corrosion resistance of concrete, which can extend the lifespan of structures and reduce maintenance needs over time. The incorporation of aluminum can also improve thermal properties, leading to better energy efficiency in buildings.

Beyond these material benefits, using aluminum scrap in concrete plays a vital role in waste reduction. It diverts substantial amounts of aluminum waste from landfills, alleviating the pressure on waste management systems and mitigating environmental issues associated with landfill use, such as soil degradation and methane emissions. This practice fosters a circular economy by transforming waste materials into valuable resources, reducing the demand for virgin raw materials, and encouraging more efficient recycling initiatives. Overall, the use of aluminum scrap in concrete not only enhances its physical properties but also supports sustainable construction practices, minimizing environmental impact and conserving natural resources in the process.

3.2 MIX DESIGN

M30 Grade concrete ratio = 1:0.75:1.5

Quantity of materials,

Total cement needed = 161.764kg

Total fine aggregate needed=121.323kg

Total coarse aggregate needed=206.08kg

Total aluminium scrap needed = 36.398kg

3.3 CONCRETE MIXING

The measured quantity of cement and fine aggregates shall be mixed until the dry mixture is thoroughly blended and uniform in colour. The coarse aggregate is then added and mixed thoroughly. The water is then added, and the entire batch mixed until the concrete appears to be homogenous and has the desired consistency. A control mix is prepared at first to compare it with the partially replaced aluminium scrap concrete.

Fig 1: Mixing of concrete

3.4 CASTING

The mixed concrete is then cast in cubes of 150mm × 150mm × 150mm in size, the beam of 100mm × 100mm × 500mm, and a cylinder of 150mm diameter and 300mm height. All the cast specimens were demoulded after 24 hours and were placed in a curing tank for a period of 7,14 and 28 days of curing. 3 cubes,3 beams, and 3 cylinders for 0%, 10%, 20%, 30% replacement of cement is casted for 7,14 and 28 days of curing. Therefore, total 36 specimens are casted.

Fig 2: Casting of specimens

3.5 CURING

Concrete curing is the process of maintaining adequate moisture in concrete within a proper temperature range in order to aid cement hydration at early ages. All the casted specimens are demoulded after 24 hours and placed in curing tanks for 7 to 28 days. The essential parameters that are considered during the curing process is moisture, heat and time.

Fig 3: Curing of specimens

3.6 TESTING AND RESULTS

3.6.1 COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH

The compressive strength of the concrete is determined using the compression testing machine. For this test cubes of 150mm × 150mm × 150mm are used.

$$\text{Compressive Strength} = \frac{\text{Maximum load applied}}{\text{Area of specimen}}$$

Fig 4: Cube under compression testing machine

3.6.2 SPLIT TENSILE STRENGTH

The split tensile test of concrete is determined using the universal testing machine. For this test cylinders of 300mm height and 150mm diameter are used.

$$\text{Split tensile strength} = \frac{2P}{\pi dl}$$

where,

P = Load applied(N)

d = diameter of specimen(mm)

l = length of specimen(mm)

Fig 5: Cylinder under universal testing machine

3.6.3 FLEXURAL STRENGTH

The flexural strength of the concrete can be determined using the universal testing machine. For this test beams of 100×100×500mm are used.

$$\text{Flexural strength} = \frac{Pl}{bd^2}$$

where,

P = Maximum load applied (N)

l = Span(mm)

b = Width of the beam(mm)

d = failure point depth(mm)

Fig 5: Beam under universal testing machine

Table 4 Compressive strength values

% Replacement of Aluminium scrap	Compressive strength (MPa)		
	7 days	14 days	28 days
0	27.55	30.4	43.55
5	24.44	26.66	38.66
10	21.77	25.33	32.44
15	19.55	23.55	30.22

Table 5 Split tensile strength values

% Replacement of Aluminium scrap	Split tensile strength (MPa)		
	7 days	14 days	28 days
0	27.55	30.4	43.55
5	24.44	26.66	38.66
10	21.77	25.33	32.44
15	19.55	23.55	30.22

Table 6 Flexural strength values

% Replacement of Aluminium scrap	Flexural strength (MPa)		
	7 days	14 days	28 days
0	27.55	30.4	43.55
5	24.44	26.66	38.66
10	21.77	25.33	32.44
15	19.55	23.55	30.22

4.CONCLUSION

It is concluded that,

1. The optimum percentage replacement of aluminium scrap to attain the maximum strength is found in 20% replacement of aluminium scrap.
2. While comparing the hardened properties of control concrete and normal concrete it is found that the hardened properties increased in aluminium scrap replaced concrete mix in 10% and 20%. But the value decreases at 30% replacement.
3. By using aluminium scrap it is found that it is an effective waste management practice.

The 20% mix consistently demonstrates the highest flexural strength across all curing periods, while the 30% mix performs the weakest. The 10% mix offers strength comparable to the normal mix, making it a viable alternative.

The 20% mix consistently demonstrates the highest split tensile strength across all curing periods, showing significant improvement over the normal mix. The 10% mix also performs well, closely following the 20% mix, making it a strong contender in terms of tensile strength. In contrast, the 30% mix consistently shows the weakest performance, indicating that higher replacement percentages lead to a reduction in tensile strength. Overall, the 20% mix proves to be the most effective in enhancing tensile strength, while the 30% mix exhibits the least favorable results.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We are deeply indebted to our guide and project coordinator Mrs. Cera Shalom, Assistant Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, for her excellent guidance, positive criticism and valuable comments. We are greatly thankful to Mrs. L Sreeletha, Head of Civil Engineering Department and Dr.Anshad A S for permitting us to carry out our project at John Cox Memorial CSI Institute Of Technology. Finally, we are thankful to our parents for their support in connection with the project. Gratitude may be extended to all well-wishers and friends who directly and indirectly contributed to the successful completion of our project.

REFERENCES

[1] Ahmed A.H., Madallah A.M., and Mattar M.R.(2022).“Enhancing of Concrete Properties by Using Aluminium and Iron Residues as a Partial Replacement of Fine Aggregate”, *International Journal of Scientific Research & Engineering Trends*, <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/363717161>.

[2] Kumar V.P., Reddy V.H.K., Likhitha P., Krishna Y.S., Sriram N., Babu N.P., and Kopuri N.G.A.K.M(2024).“An Experimental Study on Partial Replacement of Coarse Aggregates with Soft Drink Bottle Caps in Concrete”, *International Journal of Scientific Research &*

- [3] Muhammed E., Yohannan T.A., Varghese A.S., and Thomas T.M.(2020).“Replacement of Coarse Aggregate in Concrete with Aluminium Caps”, *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology* Vol. 9, issue 7.
- [4] Narayanan S.R., Kumar R.M., Kumar S.C., and Manju.S(2020).“ Experimental Study on Behaviour of Concrete with the Partial Replacement of Aluminium Caps” *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology* Vol.7, issue 6.
- [5] Paktiawal A., and Alam M.(2021).“An experimental study on effect of aluminum composite panel waste on performance of cement concrete”, *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asej.2020.07.024>.
- [6] Sabarish S., Sabapathy Y.K., Nithish C.N.A., Ramasamy S.M., and Krishna.G.,(2021). “Experimental study on strength properties of aluminium fibre reinforced concrete”, *Journal of King Saud University – Engineering Sciences* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jksues.2019.12.004>.

UNDER WATER IMAGE CORRECTION, ENHACEMENT AND RECOGNITION USING DEEP LEARNING

ABHIRAM V.M. Department of Computer Science and Engineering John Cox Memorial CSI
Institute of Technology, Kerala, India

Abstract—The paper, "A Detailed Understanding of Underwater Image Enhancement using Deep Learning," reviews state-of-the-art techniques in underwater image enhancement, with a particular focus on deep learning approaches that tackle the significant challenges posed by underwater environments. These challenges include issues like light scattering, color distortion, and reduced visibility, which affect crucial tasks in marine engineering and aquatic robotics, such as object recognition and environmental sensing. The authors categorize enhancement techniques into three primary approaches: model-free, model-based, and deep learning-based, with an emphasis on the advantages of deep learning. Among the deep learning techniques, Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) such as FUNIE-GAN, Fusion GAN, and Spiral GAN are highlighted for their capacity to automatically correct color, adjust contrast, and remove haze, achieving superior image quality compared to traditional methods. These GAN models are trained on large synthetic and real-world datasets, enabling them to accurately map distorted images to enhanced versions while preserving details. The authors also perform a comparative analysis showing that deep learning methods, especially GAN-based approaches, outperform traditional image restoration techniques in metrics like Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) and Structural Similarity Index (SSIM). The paper concludes by discussing the potential for further research to improve model robustness and effectiveness in various underwater scenarios, emphasizing the transformative impact imaging.

Keywords—GAN, Deep Learning, PSNR, underwater environment.

I. INTRODUCTION

Underwater image processing has gained considerable attention as it plays a vital role in fields like marine engineering, underwater exploration, and environmental monitoring. Capturing high-quality images in underwater environments poses unique challenges, as factors like light absorption, scattering, and suspended particles lead to significant color distortion, low contrast, and hazy effects. As depth increases, red wavelengths are quickly absorbed, leaving images dominated by blue and green hues, while scattered light and particulate matter further degrade visibility. These distortions impede the performance of computer vision tasks, such as object detection, environmental mapping, and species identification, which are critical for tasks like underwater navigation and marine ecosystem analysis. Traditional image enhancement techniques, including model-free and model-based methods, offer limited improvements due to their inability to adapt to the unique optical properties of underwater environments. In response, researchers have increasingly turned to deep learning-based techniques, particularly Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), which have shown

remarkable success in enhancing underwater images. GAN-based models, trained on large datasets of both synthetic and real underwater images, can learn complex mappings that correct color, adjust contrast, and remove haze, resulting in clearer and more accurate images. By addressing these specific underwater imaging challenges, deep learning methods are advancing the capabilities of underwater imaging, providing higher-quality data that supports more precise and reliable marine operations and research.

II. Literature Survey

In recent years, several approaches have been explored to enhance the purpose of using deep learning techniques for underwater image color correction, specifically with a focus on hue preservation, is to improve the clarity and visual accuracy of images captured underwater. Underwater environments present unique challenges, as water absorbs and scatters light in ways that distort colors and reduce visibility. Accurate color correction not only enhances the aesthetic quality of underwater images but also provides more reliable visual data for scientific and industrial applications. This is crucial for fields such as marine biology, underwater archaeology, and environmental monitoring, where preserving natural color hues aids in object recognition, species identification, and environmental assessments. By leveraging deep learning, particularly models tailored to address hue shifts, researchers aim to achieve enhanced image quality that accurately reflects the true underwater scene, which is essential for both scientific accuracy and practical usability in various underwater applications.

III. OBJECTIVES

The objective of the paper is to explore and evaluate advanced underwater image enhancement techniques, particularly focusing on the application of deep learning approaches to overcome the unique visual challenges presented by underwater environments. Given the critical need for high-quality images in applications like marine engineering, underwater robotics, and ecological monitoring, the paper aims to assess the effectiveness of deep learning models in enhancing underwater images that are often degraded by color distortion, low contrast, and haze. Traditional

image processing methods, while useful, struggle with the complex and varying optical characteristics of underwater scenes. Therefore, the paper seeks to investigate how deep learning methods, especially Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), can be comprehensive understanding of their performance on crucial metrics such as Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) and Structural Similarity Index (SSIM). Ultimately, the objective is to highlight how these models enhance the accuracy and reliability of underwater imaging, enabling more effective data collection and analysis in various underwater applications.

IV. SCOPE This study investigates the use of AI technologies, particularly ML and DL, to enhance malware detection techniques. The research encompasses the analysis of malware evolution, from simple pranks to sophisticated attacks orchestrated by organized cybercrime. It aims to develop an efficient and scalable detection algorithm capable of identifying malware on various platforms, including Windows and Android. Statistical analyses will be conducted to identify malware characteristics, which will inform the development of detection tools. Additionally, the study will explore the effectiveness of combining static and dynamic analysis to enhance the accuracy of malware detection. AI-based detection models will be assessed for their ability to adapt to evolving threat landscapes and their robustness in detecting polymorphic and metamorphic malware. Moreover, the study will involve the development of user-friendly interfaces and tools that enable seamless deployment of the proposed system across diverse platforms, ensuring accessibility and usability for enterprises and individuals alike.

V. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Underwater image enhancement using Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) represents a cutting-edge approach to address the unique challenges of underwater imaging. GANs consist of two neural networks: a generator and a discriminator, engaged in a competitive learning process. The generator aims to produce realistic enhancements of underwater images, while the discriminator learns to differentiate between real and generated images. By utilising the innate structure and patterns seen in underwater photos, the generator network is trained to generate aesthetically pleasing enhancements in the context of underwater image enhancement. With the goal of minimising the impacts of backscatter and blurring, as well as enhancing contrast and colour distortion, it creates improved copies of input

underwater photographs. In the meantime, the discriminator network gains the ability to discriminate between real underwater photos and the artificially enhanced ones produced by the generator. Through iterative training, the generator improves its ability to produce high-quality enhancements that closely resemble real underwater scenes, while the discriminator becomes more adept at discerning between authentic and generated images. This adversarial training process leads to the refinement of the generator’s capabilities in capturing the complex characteristics of underwater imagery.

VI. METHODOLOGY

A. Training and Prediction of GANs

In the training phase of a generative adversarial network (GAN), the generator network is iteratively trained using the output of the discriminator to improve its ability to generate more realistic samples, as the gradients of the discriminator are back propagated through the generator to update its parameters, effectively guiding it towards producing synthetic data that can better deceive the discriminator, ultimately leading to the generation of high-quality and coherent samples that closely resemble those from the true data distribution, thus facilitating the adversarial learning process and enhancing the overall performance of the GAN framework..

B. VGG 19

VGG-19 contributes to the computation of perceptual loss, an essential component in the training of GANs for underwater image enhancement. Perceptual loss involves comparing the high-level features extracted by VGG-19 from generated images with those obtained from corresponding real images. Minimizing the discrepancy between these features incentivizes the generator to produce images that not

only deceive the discriminator but also closely resemble authentic underwater images in terms of their perceptual content. This integration of VGG-19 in defining the perceptual loss function promotes the generation of visually convincing and realistic underwater images. Pre-trained VGG-19 models are useful for GAN-based underwater picture enhancement applications; these models were first trained on large datasets such as ImageNet. These pre-trained models capture complete visual representations that have been learned in a variety of visual domains. By adjusting or employing these pre-trained models directly within the GAN framework, substantial visual knowledge may be used, which may improve the GAN model's performance and generalisation on underwater picture data. Because of this, VGG-19 is a crucial tool for GAN-based underwater picture enhancement projects. It makes feature extraction, perceptual loss computation, and the use of pre-trained representations easier and more accurate.

C. Pix2Pix

Pix2Pix is a deep learning architecture designed for image-to-image translation tasks within the framework of Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs). It was introduced by researchers at the University of California, Berkeley. Pix2Pix is particularly effective when there exists a paired dataset consisting of input images and corresponding output images. A generator and a discriminator, like to conventional GANs, are the two primary parts of the Pix2Pix model. But Pix2Pix uses a conditional GAN (cGAN) framework, in which training conditions are applied to the generator and discriminator based on input images. Through this conditioning process, the model has the ability to translate images between different domains while maintaining crucial structural and semantic details.

D. EUVP Dataset

The EUVP dataset contains a large collection of paired and unpaired underwater images of poor and good perceptual quality. We used seven different cameras, which include multiple GoPros, Aqua AUV's uEye cameras, low-light USB cameras, and Trident ROV's HD camera, to capture images for the dataset. The data was collected during oceanic explorations and human-robot cooperative experiments in different locations under various visibility conditions. Additionally, images extracted from a few publicly available YouTubeTM videos are included in the dataset. The images are carefully selected to accommodate a wide range of natural variability

VII. RESULTS

We use TensorFlow libraries to implement the FUnIE-GAN model. It is trained separately on 11K paired and 7:5K unpaired instances; the rest are used for respective validation and testing. Four NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1080 graphics cards are used for training; both models are trained for 60K-70K iterations with a batch-size of 8. We now present the experimental evaluations based on a qualitative analysis, standard quantitative metrics, and a user study. We consider two standard metrics [6, 7, 8] named Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) and Structural Similarity (SSIM) in order to quantitatively compare FUnIE-GAN enhanced images with their respective ground truths. The PSNR approximates the reconstruction quality of a generated image x compared to its ground truth y based on their Mean Squared Error (MSE) as follows:

$$\text{PSNR}(x, y) = 10 \log_{10} \frac{255^2}{\text{MSE}(x, y)}. \quad (1)$$

On the other hand, the SSIM [41] compares the image patches based on three properties: luminance, contrast, and structure. It is defined as follows:

$$\text{SSIM}(x, y) = \frac{2\mu_x\mu_y + c_1}{\mu_x^2 + \mu_y^2 + c_1} \frac{2\sigma_{xy} + c_2}{\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + c_2} \quad (2)$$

$$\mu_x \quad \mu_y \quad \sigma_x \quad \sigma_y$$

In Eq. 2, μ_x (μ_y) denotes the mean, and σ_x (σ_y) is the variance of x (y); whereas σ_{xy}

σ_{xy} denotes the crosscorrelation between x and y . Additionally, $c_1 = (255 \times 0.01)^2$ and $c_2 = (255 \times 0.03)^2$ are constants that ensure numeric stability.

VIII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the author compares various deep learning-based underwater image enhancement methods, focusing particularly on the use of Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) to address common challenges like color distortion, underexposure, haze, and scattering in underwater imagery. The methods discussed include Spiral-GAN, Underwater GAN, and other deep learning models such as U-Net, all of which leverage advanced neural networks to restore and enhance underwater images by improving color accuracy, contrast, sharpness, and details. Experimental results, using both paired and unpaired real-world datasets, demonstrate that these deep learning methods significantly outperform traditional image enhancement techniques (e.g., histogram

equalization, DCP) and other machine learning-based approaches in terms of both qualitative and quantitative metrics like PSNR, SSIM, UIQM, and UCIQE. Among these, Spiral-GAN showed superior results with faster processing speeds, making it particularly suitable for real-time applications. The findings underscore the effectiveness of GAN-based models in producing high-quality underwater images, positioning them as a robust solution for real-world underwater imaging challenges.

REFERENCES

- [1]M. J. Islam, Y. Xia, and J. Sattar, "Fast underwater image enhancement for improved visual perception," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 3227–3234, 2020.

- [2]S. Jin, P. Qu, Y. Zheng, W. Zhao, and W. Zhang, "Color correction and local contrast enhancement for underwater image enhancement," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 119 193–119 205, 2022.

- [3] Z. Liang, Y. Wang, X. Ding, Z. Mi, and X. Fu, "Single underwater image enhancement by attenuation map guided color correction and detail preserved dehazing," *Neurocomputing*, vol. 425, pp. 160–172, 2021.

- [4]Y. Wang, J. Guo, H. Gao, and H. Yue, "Uiec²-net: Cnn-based underwater image enhancement using two color space," *Signal Processing: Image Communication*, 116250, 2021.

USAGE OF PHARMACEUTICAL WASTE FOR CLAY STABILIZATION

Manjima M G, Neeraj S S, Vishnu dath S, Sreejith K M, L Sreeletha
UG Students – Final Year & HOD
Department of Civil Engineering JCM Institute of Technology, Kannammoola, Trivandrum,
India

Abstract: - The innovative approach to sustainable clay stabilization by pharmaceutical waste, a significant medical waste, in combination with lime. The proposed method aims to reduce the environmental impact of traditional stabilization techniques while repurposing medical waste. Laboratory experiments were conducted to evaluate the effects of pharmaceutical waste and lime on the geotechnical properties of clay soil. Results show significant improvements in soil strength, durability, and reduced plasticity, meeting the requirements for construction materials. The use of recycled pharmaceutical waste as a sustainable alternative to reduces waste disposal issues. It also demonstrates a viable solution for sustainable clay stabilization, contributing to environmentally friendly construction practices and waste management strategies pharmaceutical waste -assisted clay stabilization offers a novel approach to improving clay soil stability. The technique enhances soil properties, including unconfined compressive strength, shear strength, and durability, while reducing settlement. The Pharmaceutical waste system ensures uniform distribution of stabilizers, minimizes waste and environmental impact, and provides cost-effectiveness. Its adaptability makes it suitable for varied soil conditions, showing promise for geotechnical engineering applications, particularly in sensitive or hard-to-reach environments.

Keywords: *Pharmaceutical waste, clay soil stability*

1. INTRODUCTION

Soil stabilization is a crucial technique in geotechnical engineering to enhance soil strength, durability, and overall performance. In early days mechanical methods of mixing two variants of soil were used to improve the geotechnical properties.

In recent years, researchers have explored alternatives solution of using sustainable materials for soil stabilization, such as waste materials. Pharmaceutical wastes are a good example for waste materials globally.

The careless deposition of these waste in the environment increases the production of pathogenic bacteria's which causes severe diseases to human kind.

Benefits of adding pharmaceutical wastes in soil

Improves the strength of clay

Enhanced durability

Reduced soil shrinkage

Increased soil workability

OBJECTIVES:

To Compare the results of Unconfined compressive strength, Light compaction and Triaxial test of:

Untreated clay.

Untreated clay treated with pharmaceutical waste.

Untreated clay treated with pharmaceutical waste and lime

To determine whether pharmaceutical waste can be used for clay stabilization by comparing the unconfined compressive strength of untreated clay and untreated clay treated with pharmaceutical waste and with lime.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Following is the research works conducted on concrete with various alternatives as partial to full replacement for coarse aggregate.

Hassen et al. (2021) The addition of aluminum composite waste materials into the soft soil would improve the geotechnical properties of the soil by lowering the plasticity and liquid limit of the soil. Which would impart structural stability to the soil

Marik et al. (2023) The process of soil stabilization may be divided into two different categories i.e. chemical, and mechanical methods.

In mechanical approach, two or more soils of different gradations are mixed together to improve the nature of weak soil.

This method results in higher cost and consumes more time.

In order to stabilize the weak soil by overcoming this problem, researchers introduced chemical stabilization. This method was turned out to be more appropriate as a smaller amount of additive added to the soil initiates chemical reactions such as flocculation and agglomeration, cation exchange, and pozzolanic activity, which strengthen the subgrade soil properties.

The calcium silicate hydrate compound will be form when silica is added with soil which improves the engineering properties.

M. S. I. Zaini and M. Hasan (2024) The soft clay soils are low shear strength, poor permeability and high compressibility.

This leads to a bearing capacity failure and excessive settlement to the construction project.

The study investigates the strength enhancement of expansive clay soil using silica fume and lime.

Using standard proctor and unconfined compressive strength the various mix ratios of silica fume and lime are examined (silica fume (SF) (2%, 4%, and 6%) and lime (L) (3%, 6%, and 9%)).

The mixture of silica fume and lime result to a compressive strength of 80.22%.

Marsum et al. (2022) Disinfection of infusion bottles contaminated with bacteria using soil solution was able to reduce the number of bacteria by 98%.

Mixing water with soil was carried out to increase the effectiveness of cleaning bacteria in infusion bottles.

Improper treatment of this waste poses a severe risk of disease transmission such as Contamination of highly infectious agents such as the COVID-19 virus.

Natural clay has antibacterial properties, one of which is based on reduced iron (Fe 2+). Fe 2+ ions can enter the protein structure of bacteria's outer cells and produce hydroxyl radicals that kill bacteria.

N. K. Maha Lakshmi and M. Kumar. (2024) The pandemic and healthcare activities have increased medical waste generation, with 85%.

This project explores recycling medical waste as a soil stabilizer. Plastic flakes and expired tablets (GLIMI DM PLUS is used in treatment of type 2 diabetes) were mixed with soil in varying proportions (0.25-1%) and evaluated through Standard Proctor compaction and California Bearing Ratio tests.

Results show improved soil strength with medical waste addition, but excessive amounts decrease strength.

In standard proctor compaction test the optimum moisture content and maximum dry density observed were 18% and 2.056g/cc respectively which is higher than the natural soil.

The optimum CBR percentage is 4.18 %.

For soil with 1% Expired tablets and 0.5% of plastic flakes which is also higher than natural soil.

3. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

3.1 MATERIALS

3.1.1 PHARMACEUTICAL WASTE

Pharmaceutical waste products refer to materials that are no longer usable or needed in the pharmaceutical or healthcare and need to be disposed safely.

Pharmaceutical waste includes materials like empty pill bottles, syringes, infusion bottles, tablet strips and medical packaging etc. The use of pharmaceutical waste in clay stabilization will improve geotechnical engineering properties of soil for construction purposes.

By using pharmaceutical waste materials, after the sterilization process in the soil improves its engineering properties. This can potentially provide an eco-friendly solution to both waste management and soil stabilization.

3.1.2 BENTONITE CLAY

Bentonite clay is a naturally occurring, fine-grained, absorbent clay formed from volcanic ash. Due to its alkalinity pH, it can neutralize the effect of bacteria, virus and other toxic materials.

3.1.3 CLAY

Clay is a fine-grained earth material composed of minerals, water, and other substances. It's a naturally occurring, plastic, and ductile material when moist, but hardens when heated or dried.

Engineering Properties:

Bearing Capacity: Clay's bearing capacity varies depending on its type, moisture content, and density.

Permeability: Clay's permeability is relatively low, ranging from 10^{-6} to 10^{-9} m/s, making it an effective barrier against water flow.

Compressive Strength: Clay's compressive strength varies from 50 kPa to 500 kPa.

Challenges: Settlement, Water Infiltration, Expansive Behavior.

3.1.4 LIME

Lime is a commonly used additive in soil stabilization, particularly for clayey soils. It stabilizes and improves the soil properties for construction, infrastructure, and environmental applications.

Benefits: Soil pH adjustment, Moisture control, Strength enhancement etc.

Types of Lime: Quicklime (calcium oxide), hydrated lime (calcium hydroxide), lime slurry.

Among these lime categories we used quick lime for our project work.

3.2 METHODOLOGY

3.2.1 SAMPLE COLLECTION

Soil samples for project work was collected clay from different places.

Sample 1-Neyyathinkara, sample 2- Vellayani, and sample 3- Alathoor. Liquid limit test conducted in three samples and graph were plotted.

3.2.2 TESTS FOR DETERMINING INDEX PROPERTIES OF CLAY

Liquid limit

The liquid limit for a clay sample is a measure of the water content at which the clay changes from a liquid-like state to a plastic state. It is an important property in geotechnical engineering, as it helps to classify soils and determine their behavior under different conditions.

Fig 2: Measuring catchment area using total station

X - axis = no. of blows, 1 div=5%

Y - axis =Water content, 1div = 20 blows

The water content corresponding to 25 blows in the graph gives the liquid limit of specimen.

Sample 1 liquid limit = 62%

Sample 3 liquid limit = 41%

Sample 1 has higher liquid limit of 62% as compared to sample 3 with liquid limit 41%. which means that sample 1 is the weakest soil among the collected samples. Hence, we selected sample 1 for hydrometer analysis.

The number of blows of sample 2 is less than 25 hence we couldn't determine the liquid limit graphically. Hence, we rejected sample 2.

Water content

To determine the field water content of collected soil samples.

Table 1 Field water content

Description	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3
Weight of container (w1)	12	10	10
Weight of container + wet soil(w2)	18	16	16
Weight of container + dry soil (w3)	16	14	14
Water content % $\frac{(w2-w3)}{(w3-w1)} * 100$	50	50	50

Hydrometer analysis

To determine the particle distribution of fine-grained soil.

The hydrometer analysis which was conducted on sample 1 helped to determine the particle distribution of the sample. which reveals that sample 1 has a clay size particle of 3.8% and the silt particles of 0.98% and the rest of the particles have particle size less than clay. Hence, we can conclude that sample 1 is a clay soil.

Hence, we selected sample 1 for our project work.

3.2.3 QUANTITY ESTIMATION OF PHARMACEUTICAL WASTE, SELECTED CLAY SAMPLE& LIME

Calculation for quantity of clay needed:

Quantity of clay sample required for compaction = 5kg

Quantity of clay sample required for UCC = 300g

Quantity of clay sample required for Triaxial = 300g

Total clay sample required for 1 set of test =5,600 ~ 6kg

Estimation of pharmaceutical waste and lime required (by weight)

Set 1 (4% pharmaceutical waste + clay)

Clay sample required = 6000g

Quantity of hospital waste required in 4% that is $6000 * 4/100 = 240g$

Set 2 (6% of pharmaceutical waste +clay)

Clay sample required = 6000g

Quantity of hospital waste required in 6% that is $6000 * 6/100 = 360g$

Set 3 (lime 6% +4% pharmaceutical waste+ clay)

Waste = $6000 * 4/100 = 240g$

Lime = $6000 * 6/100 = 360g$

Set 4 (lime 9% + 6% pharmaceutical waste +clay)

Waste = $6000 * 4/100 = 240g$

Lime = $6000 * 9/100 = 540g$

Total quantity of hospital waste
 = 240+360+240+360
 =1200g ~ 2kg

Total quantity of lime required = 360+560
 = 920g ~1kg

3.2.4 STERILIZATION OF PHARMACEUTICAL WASTE

Infusion bottles, tablets strips, collected from several places. The places were David clinic palliyod, sut hospital vattapara, and Gov. Hospital Paraniyam. Materials were sterilized using bentonite clay. Materials dipped into water mixed with bentonite clay. For 1 liters of water 5g (2 table spoon).

Fig:3 pharmaceutical wastes dipped in bentonite

3.2.5 MICROSCOPIC VIEW BEFORE AND AFTER STERILIZATION

Fig:4 Before sterilization

Fig:5 After sterilization

Microscopic view helps to find whether the bacteria present in the pharmaceutical waste is decreased or not. Mixing water with bentonite clay was carried out to increase the effectiveness of cleaning bacteria. The idea of using hospital waste materials, which are typically a non-hazardous after the sterilization process in the soil will improve its engineering properties. We can see the before and after view of pharmaceutical waste using microscope a large amount of change can see in the picture.

3.2.6 CUTTING OF PHARMACEUTICAL SAMPLE

After sterilization materials get dried and cut using sanding machine and knife to make the material into small size for passing through 4.75 mm sieve.

Fig:6 Stripped tablet strips

3.2.6 COMPACTION

To determine the dry density of soil.

DISCUSSION:

Dry density of normal clay = 1.44 g/cc

Dry density of normal clay with 4% pharmaceutical waste
 = 1.47 g/cc

Dry density of normal clay with 6% pharmaceutical waste
 = 1.55 g/cc

Dry density of normal clay with 4% pharmaceutical waste and 6% lime = 1.6 g/cc

Dry density of normal clay with 6% pharmaceutical waste and 9% lime = 1.8 g/cc.

As comparing the test results of the above compaction trials conducted; clay treated with 6% medical waste and 9% lime exhibits a high dry density of 1.8 g/cc.

Percentage of increase in dry density = $\frac{(1.8-1.44)}{1.44} * 100$
 = 25%.

3.2.7 UNCONFINED COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH

The determine the compressive strength of clay.

Sample calculation

$$\text{Area of mold} = (\pi/4) \times 3.8^2 \\ = 11.34 \text{cm}^2$$

$$P \text{ max} = 8.9 \text{kg}$$

$$\text{Initial height of soil specimen} = 7.5$$

$$\text{Final height of soil specimen} = 6.5$$

$$\text{Strain} = \Delta x/x = (7.5-6.5) / 7.5 \\ = 0.13$$

$$\text{Area corrected (Ac)} = A/1-\text{strain} \\ = 11.34/1-0.13 = 13.15$$

$$\text{UCS} = \frac{P_{max}}{A} = 8.9/13.15 \\ = \mathbf{0.67 \text{ kg/cm}^2}$$

DISCUSSION:

Compressive strength of normal clay = 0.67kg/cm²

Compressive strength of normal clay with 4% pharmaceutical waste = 0.81kg/cm²

Compressive strength of normal clay with 6% pharmaceutical waste = 0.77kg/cm²

Compressive strength of normal clay with 4% pharmaceutical waste and 6% lime = 0.94kg/cm²

Compressive strength of normal clay with 6% pharmaceutical waste and 9% lime = 1kg/cm²

As comparing the test results of the above UCC trial conducted clay treated with 6% medical waste and 9% lime exhibits a high compressive strength of 1 kg/cm².

$$\text{Percentage of increase in compressive strength} \\ = ((1-0.067)/0.067) * 100 = 49\%.$$

3.2.8 TRIAXIAL TEST

Determine the cyclic load shear of clay.

DISCUSSION:

Among the above trials of the experiment conducted the clay added with 6% of pharmaceutical waste and 9% lime gives higher cyclic shear strength of 97 KN/m².

$$\text{Percentage increase in shear strength} = 97.6 - 58 / 58 * 100 \\ = 68.2 \%$$

4. CONCLUSION

By comparing the results of UCC test, Compaction test, Triaxial test it is found that clay treated with 6% of pharmaceutical waste and 9% of lime gives the highest compressive strength of 1 kg/m², highest dry density of 1.8g/cc and highest cyclic shear strength of 97.6 KN/m².

1. Percentage increase in compressive strength = 49%
2. Percentage increase in dry density = 25%
3. Percentage increase in cyclic shear strength = 68.2%

Hence, we conclude that pharmaceutical waste can be used as a sustainable additive to clay to improve its geo technical properties like shear strength, compressive strength and dry density.

4. REFERENCES

- [1] Abdulrahman, M. A., & El-Aziz, M. (2021). The effect of local waste aluminum material on the geotechnical properties of soft soil. Journal of Geotechnical Engineering, 45(2), 123-134 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/353083622_The_Effect_of_Local_Waste_Aluminium_Material_on_the_Geotechnical_Properties_of_Soft_Soil

- [2] Marik, S., Ransinchung, G. D. R. N., Singh, A., and Khot P. (2022). "Investigation on use of silica-based additive for sustainable subgrade construction," *Case Studies in Construction Materials* Vol (7). <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2214509522003618>
- [3] Mahaalakshmi, N. K., & Kumar, M. (2023). "Experimental analysis on the stability of the soil using medical waste", *International Journal for Research in Applied Science & Engineering Technology (IJRASET)*, Vol 11(6). <https://www.ijraset.com/research-paper/experimental-analysis-on-the-stability-of-the-soil-using-medical-waste#:~:text=The%20effect%20of%20stabilization%20using,%2C%200.75%25%20and%201%25>.
- [4] Marsum, M., Sunarto, S., Widodo, W., Khayan, K., & Wardoyo, S. (2022). "Waste treatment innovation for infusion bottle using soil solution". https://www.researchgate.net/publication/357004240_Waste_Treatment_Innovation_For_Infusion_Bottle_Using_Soil_Solution
- [5] Zaini M. S. I., Hasan M., Almuaythir, S., and Hyodo, M. (2024). "Experimental investigations on physio-mechanical properties of kaolinite clay soil stabilized at optimum silica fume content using clamshell ash and lime," *Scientific report*, Vol (2). <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-024-61854-1>